

IDENTIFICATION OF MULTI-INPUT MULTI-OUTPUT
STATE-SPACE SYSTEMS: FROM LINEAR
TIME-INVARIANT TO LINEAR
PARAMETER-VARYING MODELS

"Habilitation à Diriger des Recherches"

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Preface

This document gathers the scientific part of the manuscript I submitted to get my "Habilitation à Diriger des Recherches" in 2012. It is a summary of my research activities between 2005 and 2012. As you can notice by reading the title of this document, these activities mainly focused on state space model identification with a specific attention to linear time invariant and linear parameter varying models.

By the way, you may not be familiar with the French academic system and you may not know what an "Habilitation à Diriger des Recherches" is. Let me shortly explain what it means. In France, we have two main permanent positions in universities: "maître de conférences" and "professeur des universités" (which are equivalent to the associate and full professor positions, respectively). These two positions are tenure track positions. The "maître de conférences" position is taken after earning a doctoral degree (after some dedicated administrative steps (we are French, so we love administrative steps...) and the availability of free positions in universities). Once you are a "maître de conférences", if you want to become a "professeur des universités", you must write a sort of second PhD manuscript (the document you can read accompanied with a detailed CV, a description of your administrative and teaching activities and a research project for the next five years or so), then send it to a dedicated examining committee (just like for the PhD degree). This specific process finally comprises a dissertation defense in front of the examination committee. Once you get this degree¹, you can apply for free "professeur des universités" (if there are !-) and, more importantly, you can supervise your own PhD students.

The results gathered in this document would not have been obtained without the involvement and help of co-authors and friends. Thus, I use this opportunity to thank Olivier Prot, Marco Lovera, Stéphane Lecœuche, Edouard Laroche, Thierry Pointot, Régis Ouvrard and Sylvain Lalot for their strong contributions to this document. During these seven years, I also had the chance to work with great PhD students. So, thank you Laurent (Bako), Wafa (Farah),

¹By the way, I got it in 2012.

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Contents

Preface	iii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 System identification: a generic formulation	1
1.2 A brief overview of non-linear system identification	5
1.2.1 Basic idea and model structures	5
1.2.2 Least-squares support vector machine identification of Hammerstein systems	7
1.3 From a non-linear system to a LPV model structure	13
1.4 Outline of the monograph	19
2 Regression techniques for 4SID: an overview	25
2.1 Motivations and problem formulation	25
2.2 Subspace-based identification involving linear regression	29
2.2.1 Construction of a state sequence from past input and past output data	30
2.2.2 Subspace ident. using linear regression for open-loop systems	41
2.2.3 Subspace ident. using linear regression for closed-loop systems	54
2.3 Conclusions	64
3 4SID of parameterized black-box state-space systems	65
3.1 Motivations	65
3.2 Parameterization of LTI black-box state-space systems	67
3.2.1 Problem formulation and related definitions	68
3.2.2 A randomly-generated canonical form for MIMO systems	72
3.3 Application to subspace-based identification	77
3.3.1 Subspace-based identification of a user-defined canoni- cal form	78
3.3.2 Properties and extensions of the propagator method . . .	87

3.3.3	Propagator-based subspace identification and uncertainty domain description	88
3.4	Conclusions	104
4	Identification of parameterized gray-box state-space systems	105
4.1	Motivations and problem formulation	105
4.2	Physically-structured state-space representation and identifiability	108
4.3	Description of the output-error parametric estimation problem .	113
4.4	From a fully-parameterized model to a parsimonious structure .	117
4.4.1	Null-space-based techniques	118
4.4.2	(Un)constrained optimization techniques	126
4.4.3	Simulation examples	133
4.5	Conclusions	152
5	Ident. of SS LPV models: new developments for the local approach	155
5.1	Motivations	155
5.2	LPV SS models: definitions and notations	160
5.3	Identification of LPV SS models from local experiments: an approach using balanced forms	164
5.3.1	Balancing of the identified local models	166
5.3.2	Comments and discussion	170
5.4	Identification of a global LPV SS model from local experimental data: the glocal method	174
5.5	Simulation example	176
5.5.1	Robot manipulator description	178
5.5.2	Non-linear and linearized dynamic models	181
5.5.3	Identification results with the method based on the local balanced forms	186
5.5.4	Identification results with the glocal method	195
5.6	Conclusions	197
A	Appendices	201
A.1	Canonical state-space matrices determination	201
A.2	Proof of Proposition 3.2	203
A.3	Proof of Proposition 3.3	204
A.4	Dynamic model of the flexible two-links arm	205
	Bibliography	211

CHAPTER 1

Introduction

1.1 System identification: a generic formulation

System identification (or experimental modeling) consists in determining a mathematical model of a dynamic system from observed data. In order to reach this goal, the model-based identification procedure is composed of many interconnected steps, as described, *e.g.*, by Ljung in his well-known book dedicated to system identification [Ljung, 1999a]. In brief, system identification involves

- a data set,
- a set of model candidates,
- a rule to determine the model (and its parameters) which fits the data set as well as possible.

Among these three steps, the second one, *i.e.*, the selection of the model structure, is probably the most difficult one. Indeed, estimating the parameters of a model within a given structure from the acquired data is "only an algorithmic problem" which is often not so difficult to solve.

Most of the time, the choice of the model parameterization is guided by prior knowledge (*e.g.*, physical insights and/or laws governing the behavior of the system). According to the quality and the quantity of the information available *a priori*, different colored-coded mathematical models can be handled [Söderström and Stoica, 1989, Ljung, 1999a].

- Gray-box model: mathematical models with a structure determined from physical prior knowledge and containing a number of unknown parameters, parameters which often have a physical meaning. These unknown parameters are estimated from data recorded on the system.

- Black-box model: mathematical models with a structure as flexible as possible (in order to contain the behavior of the real system) without using any physical insights. The parameters of the black-box model are estimated in order to get a final model able to describe/approximate the behavior of the system. Most of the time, the parameters of the estimated model have no physical meaning.

Notice that, in this monograph, no white-box models are considered. On the contrary, the main contributions introduced hereafter will mainly focus on gray and black-box models. A white-box model is indeed an analytical model entirely constructed from prior knowledge and physical insights (by using first principles) [Ljung, 1999a]. Thus, by definition, it does not require any experiments in order to get accurate parameters of the system. Unfortunately, a white-box model is application-dependent and requires full knowledge of the physical laws governing the behavior of the system. In many cases, the studied systems are so complex that it is not possible to get accurate models by using physical insights only. That is the reason why gray-box and black-box models are more and more used in industry in order to build reliable models of complex systems.

To sum up, the main goal of the user of a system identification method is to estimate parameters or unmeasured variables available in a set of dynamic equations which have been determined from the prior knowledge of

- the physical relations (*e.g.*, Newton's or Kirchoff's laws) governing the behavior of the system,
- some measurable parameters and signals of the system,
- the structure of the different parts composing the system to identify.

These dynamic equations relate the inputs and the outputs of the system (as well as its environment) with the help of a vector gathering internal variables (which may vary with time) and several (unknown) parameters. Mathematically, these relations can be described by using the following general formulation [Schön, 2006]

$$\mathbf{f}(\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t), \mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t), \mathbf{y}(t), \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, t) = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

where the dot denotes the differentiation with respect to time, $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ is the vector of inputs, $\mathbf{y}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ is the vector of outputs, $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ is the vector of internal variables and $\boldsymbol{\vartheta} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\vartheta}$ is the vector containing the unknown parameters. All these variables are related dynamically with the help of a possibly non-linear function \mathbf{f} . Eq. (1.1) is called a differential-algebraic equation (DAE) [Kunkel and Mehrmann, 2006]. A DAE gathers [Brenan et al., 1996]

- differential equations modeling, *e.g.*, the dynamic behavior of the system,
- algebraic equations corresponding to constraints (*e.g.*, initial or final conditions), *i.e.*, variables and equations free of derivatives.

Remark 1.1 *Eq. (1.1) can be used to represent the dynamic behavior of many systems. However, it does not describe all of the non-linear systems available in practice [Tóth, 2010]. Indeed, this specific representation assumes a prior selection of a state vector \mathbf{x} as well as a partition of the available measurable data into a set of input signals \mathbf{u} and a set of output signals \mathbf{y} . These specificities reduce the applicability of this parameterization. Notice however that the class of systems satisfying Eq. (1.1) is wide enough to encompass a lot of systems encountered in automatic control.*

This way of describing a non-linear system currently knows an active research effort because of the increasing demand for tools which improve and automate the physical modeling of processes [Gerdin, 2006]. Most of these tools are based on specific object-oriented modeling languages such as¹, *e.g.*, MODELICA [Tiller, 2001, Fritzson, 2004], MAPLESIM or MATLAB-SIMSCAPE. These tools use DAE in order to make the connection of components derived from different physical domains easier. As proved in two recent PhD theses [Gerdin, 2006, Schön, 2006], these tools can simplify the modeling task greatly when they are well-combined with standard identification tools. Interesting from a theoretical point of view (see, *e.g.*, [Brenan et al., 1996], [Oksendal, 2000] or [Kunkel and Mehrmann, 2006] for important definitions and properties related to (stochastic) differential-algebraic equations), the use of DAE can be quite complex in the system identification framework. It is especially true when the equations composing the DAE result in a mixture of variables involved in the differential as well as the algebraic equations. Because of this difficulty, special cases of DAE are often analyzed in the identification framework. For instance, we can cite the semi-explicit DAE or the ordinary differential equation (ODE) with constraints [Hairer and Wanner, 1996, Kunkel and Mehrmann, 2006] defined as follows [Gerdin, 2006]

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t), \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, t) \quad (1.2a)$$

$$\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{y}(t), \mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t), \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, t) = 0 \quad (1.2b)$$

where \mathbf{g} and \mathbf{h} are possibly non-linear functions. When the constraints (1.2b) can be written so that the equations governing the behavior of the system

¹MODELICA is a registered trademark of The Modelica Association. MAPLESIM is a registered trademark of The Waterloo Maple Incorporated. MATLAB-SIMSCAPE is a registered trademark of The Mathworks Incorporated.

satisfy

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t), \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, t) \quad (1.3a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \boldsymbol{\ell}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t), \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, t), \quad (1.3b)$$

the ODE is referred to as a continuous-time state-space form [Gerdin, 2006]. Again, the functions \mathbf{h} and $\boldsymbol{\ell}$ can be non-linear functions, leading to a continuous-time non-linear state-space representation. This monograph will be mainly concerned with this representation.

In the previous set of equations, the signals are continuous-time, *i.e.*, they are defined for all the time points $t \in \mathbb{R}$. When it is necessary, the discrete-time counterpart of Eq. (1.3) is considered

$$\mathbf{x}(k+1) = \boldsymbol{\rho}(\mathbf{x}(k), \mathbf{u}(k), \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, k) \quad (1.4a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(k) = \boldsymbol{\varsigma}(\mathbf{x}(k), \mathbf{u}(k), \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, k) \quad (1.4b)$$

where $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ when the signals are sampled at regular time points T_s and where again the functions $\boldsymbol{\rho}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varsigma}$ can be non-linear functions.

In the parameterizations introduced beforehand, the history of the system is taken into account by the means of the state vector \mathbf{x} . An alternative way of describing the input-output behavior of the system consists in getting rid of the state vector by including the input-output history explicitly into the structure of the representation with the help of past observed inputs and outputs as follows [Sjöberg, 1995, Ljung, 1999a]

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \boldsymbol{\pi}(\{\mathbf{u}\}_1^{t-1}, \{\mathbf{y}\}_1^{t-1}, \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, t) \quad (1.5)$$

where

$$\{\mathbf{u}\}_1^t = \{\mathbf{u}(1), \dots, \mathbf{u}(t)\} \quad (1.6a)$$

$$\{\mathbf{y}\}_1^t = \{\mathbf{y}(1), \dots, \mathbf{y}(t)\} \quad (1.6b)$$

and where $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ is a possibly non-linear function.

As shown in [Sjöberg, 1995, Chapter 3] or in [Verdult, 2002, Appendix], the state-space form (1.3) and the input-output representation (1.5) can be considered and related to each other in a common framework. The main difference between these two structures is linked to the flexibility of the regressors used for the estimation of the unknown parameters. Although the input-output structure (1.5) can describe or approximate "any non-linear system", the state-space representation (1.3) can provide [McKelvey, 1995]

- a more succinct (parsimonious) description of the system with fewer parameters and a lower dimension of the system description,

- a parameterization with a better numerical conditioning of the parameter estimation problem than with the input-output structure (1.5). Notice indeed that a better conditioned parameterization can be obtained with the help of a change of state coordinates basis, even when non-linear state-space structures are involved (see, *e.g.*, [Verdult, 2002, Appendix] for an example).

Most of the developments put forward hereafter will mainly deal with state-space representations, because of, among others, the advantages given beforehand.

According to the structure of the system (and the user's affinities), different algorithms can be used to estimate the parameter vector ϑ in Eq. (1.3) or (1.5). Although many developments are now available in the literature [Nelles, 2000], the problem of identifying non-linear systems is still difficult and "requires a large and active research effort in the next years" [Ljung, 2008]. Indeed, because of the quasi-impossibility of providing a unique method able to deal with all of the non-linear systems, most of the solutions are dedicated to specific classes of non-linear systems such as those described by, *e.g.*, kernels, neural networks, NARMAX or Hammerstein-Wiener structures [Ljung, 1999a, Chapter 5]. Thus, it is unrealistic to give an exhaustive overview of the non-linear system identification techniques. That is the reason why, in Section 1.2, only the basic ideas of non-linear system identification are introduced. The interested reader can have a look at, *e.g.*, [Westwick, 1995, Sjöberg, 1995, Roll, 2003, Enqvist, 2005, Gerdin, 2006, Schön, 2006], for interesting recent references investigating the problem of non-linear system identification more significantly. Notice right now that, in Section 1.3, the problem of non-linear state-space system identification will be addressed more particularly by resorting to the framework of the linear parameter-varying models.

1.2 A brief overview of non-linear system identification

1.2.1 Basic idea and model structures

Most of the developments dedicated to non-linear system identification mainly investigate two connected problems. First of all, the best model structure for the functions h and ℓ in Eq. (1.3), ρ and ς in Eq. (1.4) or π in Eq. (1.5) is looked for. Then, the parameter vector ϑ is calculated by fitting the model

to the data records, for instance with the help of the cost function²

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \|\mathbf{y}(t) - \pi(\{\mathbf{u}\}_1^{t-1}, \{\mathbf{y}\}_1^{t-1}, \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, t)\|_2^2 \quad (1.7)$$

for the input-output models. As said previously, the key problem is often the selection of the model structure, *i.e.*, the choice of the non-linear mappings in Eq. (1.3)-(1.4) or in Eq. (1.5). This problem is generally broken down into two successive steps [Sjöberg, 1995]:

- the choice of the good samples of the past inputs and past outputs,
- the choice of the good non-linear functions \mathbf{h} , ℓ , ρ , ς or π .

The first step is often solved by using equivalent structures as those used for the linear time-invariant systems such as, *e.g.*, the FIR, ARX, ARMAX, BJ, ..., *i.e.*, standard black-box models. In the non-linear framework, these models become [Ljung, 1999a]

- the NFIR model where past inputs are used as regressors,
- the NARX model where past inputs and past outputs are used as regressors,
- the NOE model past inputs and past model outputs are used as regressors,
- etc.

Other choices of regressors are available in [Ljung, 1999a, Chapter 5]. As far as the non-linear mappings \mathbf{h} , ℓ , ρ , ς or π are concerned, most of the techniques dedicated to the identification of non-linear systems aim at decomposing the non-linear map onto a set of *a priori* predefined basis functions $\{\kappa_i\}_{i=1}^n$ with interesting properties such as, *e.g.*, orthogonality, approximation capability, implementation easiness. More precisely, the non-linear mapping³ \wp is rewritten as a function expansion

$$\wp(\phi, \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, t) = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i \kappa_i(\phi) \quad (1.8)$$

where ϕ is the regression vector made up of the regressors and

$$\boldsymbol{\vartheta} = [\alpha_1 \quad \cdots \quad \alpha_n]. \quad (1.9)$$

²For a vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$, $\|\mathbf{x}\|_2^2 = \mathbf{x}^\top \mathbf{x}$.

³ \wp is used as a generic notation for \mathbf{h} , ℓ , ρ , ς or π .

By this way, the parameter vector to estimate is now composed of the coefficients making the combination of the known basis functions $\{\kappa_i\}_{i=1}^n$ and the identification problem consists in estimating these combination parameters. It is interesting to notice that, by knowing the basis functions $\{\kappa_i\}_{i=1}^n$ as well as the regression vector ϕ , the identification problem becomes linear with respect to the unknown coefficients $\{\alpha_i\}_{i=1}^n$. This property allows the estimation of the parameters in a least-squares setting which makes the estimation quite easy (see, *e.g.*, [Tóth, 2010, Chapter 2] for an illustration with orthonormal basis functions).

Many basis functions are available in the literature [Sjöberg, 1995, Ljung, 1999a]. The main differences between the techniques suggested in the literature rely on the choice of these basis functions. We can quote the Volterra expansions, the Fourier series, the wavelet or radial basis networks, etc.

1.2.2 Least-squares support vector machine identification of Hammerstein systems

In order to illustrate the steps composing the standard methods used for non-linear system identification, a particular case is studied in this paragraph. More precisely, a scheme for the identification of single-input-multi-output (SIMO) Hammerstein models is introduced. In the proposed scheme, first the Markov parameters of the system are determined by a least-squares support vector machine regression through an over-parameterization technique. Second, a state-space realization of the system is retrieved by using a (recursive) subspace-based identification method (see [Bako et al., 2009c] for details concerning its recursive implementation). This identification problem deals with discrete-time SIMO Hammerstein state-space systems represented as follows

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}\psi(u(t)) + \mathbf{w}(t) \quad (1.10a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{D}\psi(u(t)) + \mathbf{v}(t) \quad (1.10b)$$

where $\mathbf{y}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$, $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ are the output, the input and the state vectors respectively and $\mathbf{w}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$, $\mathbf{v}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ are white noise vector sequences. Moreover, the system under consideration is assumed to be stable and of known order n_x . $\psi(\bullet)$ is a scalar-valued and smooth non-linear function.

By using these definitions, the considered system identification problem can be formulated as follows: given N consecutive input-output data measurements $\{u(t), \mathbf{y}(t)\}_{t=1}^N$, derive an algorithm able to estimate (recursively) the state-space matrices ($\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}$) and the static nonlinearity ψ of the system in Eq. (1.10) up to a similarity transformation.

To reach this goal, the first step of the developed method consists in writing the output signal $\mathbf{y}(t)$ as a d -step ahead predictive model by using Eq. (1.10). The obtained equation is very similar to a Finite Impulse Response (FIR) model

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}^d\mathbf{x}(t-d) + \sum_{i=0}^d \mathbf{H}_i\psi(u(t-i)) + \underbrace{\sum_{i=1}^d \mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}^{i-1}\mathbf{w}(t-i)}_{\mathbf{e}(t)} + \mathbf{v}(t) \quad (1.11)$$

$\forall t > d$, where d is a positive integer, $\mathbf{e}(t)$ is the equation error and \mathbf{H}_i , defined as

$$\mathbf{H}_i = \begin{cases} \mathbf{D} & \text{if } i = 0 \\ \mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}^{i-1}\mathbf{B} & \text{if } i \geq 1, \end{cases} \quad (1.12)$$

are the so-called Markov parameters and represent the impulse response of the system. These parameters do not depend on the basis of the state-space representation used in Eq. (1.10). Eq. (1.11) amounts to

$$y_s(t) = \mathbf{c}_s^\top \mathbf{A}^d \mathbf{x}(t-d) + \sum_{i=0}^d {}^s h_i \psi(u(t-i)) + e_s(t) \quad (1.13)$$

$s = 1, \dots, n_y$, where $y_s(t)$ is the s th output, \mathbf{c}_s^\top the s th row of the matrix \mathbf{C} and ${}^s h_i$ is the s th row⁴ of \mathbf{H}_i . By assuming that the system has fast dynamics and that d is relatively large, the term $\mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}^d\mathbf{x}(t-d)$ may be considered negligible with respect to the noise term. Then, we get

$$y_s(t) \approx \sum_{i=0}^d {}^s h_i \psi(u(t-i)) + e_s(t). \quad (1.14)$$

Remark 1.2 *When the system does not present fast dynamics, it may be safer to use the observer-augmenting procedure described in [Juang et al., 1993, Phan et al., 1995] instead. This latter algorithm introduces an observer gain in order to set the poles of the resulting system as close to zero as possible so that the accuracy of the previous equation is noticeably improved even for small values of d .*

The next step of the procedure consists in estimating the terms ${}^s h_i \psi(\bullet)$. To do so, the least-squares support vector machine (LS-SVM) regression method developed by J. Suykens [Suykens et al., 2002] is adapted to our identification problem. Recall indeed that neither the parameters \mathbf{H}_i nor the non-linear

⁴In the SIMO case, ${}^s h_i \in \mathbb{R}$.

function $\psi(\bullet)$ are known *a priori*. The LS-SVM regression procedure consists in modeling the non-linearity as

$$\psi(\bullet) = \omega^\top \varphi(\bullet) + \delta \quad (1.15)$$

where $\varphi : \mathbb{R}^{n_u} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_h}$ is a non-linear mapping from the input space to a possibly high (even infinite) dimensional feature space \mathbb{R}^{n_h} , δ is a bias compensator and $\omega \in \mathbb{R}^{n_h}$. Thanks to this parameterization, by assuming that the feature space \mathbb{R}^{n_h} exists, the non-linear function ψ is modeled via a linear function $\omega^\top \varphi(\bullet)$. Unfortunately, the direct application of this basic idea results in a hard non-convex optimization problem as shown, *e.g.* in [Goethals, 2005]. In order to circumvent this difficulty, an over-parameterization associated with a component-wise LS-SVM [Pelckmans, 2005] can be introduced. More precisely, instead of dealing with one vector ω^\top , Pelckmans in [Pelckmans, 2005] suggested introducing several vectors $\omega_{i,s}^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n_h}$, $i \in [1, d]$, so that the non-linear function becomes

$${}^s h_i \psi(\bullet) = \omega_{i,s}^\top \varphi(\bullet) + \delta_{i,s} = \zeta_{i,s}(\bullet). \quad (1.16)$$

In brief, this basic idea consists in substituting a wider class of model for the initial non-linearity (1.15). Notice that this procedure leads to a model class that is not necessarily limited to the description of the Hammerstein systems. However, the resulting problem is easier to solve than the previous one. Then, by introducing Eq. (1.16) into Eq. (1.14), we get

$$y_s(t) = \sum_{i=0}^d \zeta_{i,s}(u(t-i)) + e_s(t) = \sum_{i=0}^d \omega_{i,s}^\top \varphi(u(t-i)) + \delta_s + e_s(t) \quad (1.17)$$

with $\delta_s = \sum_{i=0}^d \delta_{i,s}$, $s = 1, \dots, n_y$, $t = d+1, \dots, N$. By using the component-wise approach, *i.e.*, by introducing a wider class of non-linear models, the optimization problem is easier to solve but its solution is not unique. For any solution $\{\zeta_{i,s}(\bullet)\}_{i=0}^d$ of Eq. (1.17), $\{\zeta_{i,s}(\bullet) + \varepsilon_{i,s}(\bullet)\}_{i=0}^d$ is also a solution for all arbitrary functions $\{\varepsilon_{i,s}(\bullet)\}_{i=0}^d$ satisfying $\forall t = d+1, \dots, N$, $\sum_{i=0}^d \varepsilon_{i,s}(u(t-i)) = 0$. Hence, each function $\zeta_{i,s}$ can only be estimated up to an additive undetermined function term. A standard way to overcome this difficulty is to introduce additional constraints on the $\omega_{i,s}^\top \varphi(\bullet)$ obtained by solving Eq. (1.17) so that the redundancy is removed. In [Goethals et al., 2005], this constraint is chosen as a centering relation over the time window of the measurement points. An alternative way of dealing with this problem, which is more convenient in view of a recursive implementation, is presented in the following.

The LS-SVM constrained optimization problem is based on the cost function (see [Suykens et al., 2002] for details)

$$\mathcal{J}(\boldsymbol{\omega}_{i,s}, e_s(t)) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{s=1}^{n_y} \sum_{i=0}^d \boldsymbol{\omega}_{i,s}^\top \boldsymbol{\omega}_{i,s} + \frac{\eta}{2} \sum_{s=1}^{n_y} \sum_{t=d+1}^N e_s^2(t) \quad (1.18)$$

subject to Eq. (1.17) where η is a regularization parameter and serves as a weight in the cost function to minimize. The relative importance between the smoothness of the solution and the data fitting is governed by this scalar η . In order to apply the Lagrange multipliers method [Boyd and Vandenberghe, 2004], the following Lagrangian is introduced

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\omega}_{i,s}, \delta_s, \alpha_{t,s}, e_{t,s}) &= \mathcal{J}(\boldsymbol{\omega}_{i,s}, e_{t,s}) \\ &- \sum_{s=1}^{n_y} \sum_{t=d+1}^N \alpha_{t,s} \left(\sum_{i=0}^d \boldsymbol{\omega}_{i,s}^\top \boldsymbol{\varphi}(u(t-i)) + \delta_s + e_s(t) - y_s(t) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (1.19)$$

where the $\alpha_{t,s}$ stand for the Lagrange multipliers. The associated Karush-Kuhn-Tucker optimality conditions [Boyd and Vandenberghe, 2004] are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_{i,s}} &= 0 \\ \rightarrow \boldsymbol{\omega}_{i,s} &= \sum_{t=d+1}^N \alpha_{t,s} \boldsymbol{\varphi}(u(t-i)), \quad \forall i = 0, \dots, d \quad \forall s = 1, \dots, n_y \end{aligned} \quad (1.20)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \delta_s} = 0 \rightarrow \sum_{t=d+1}^N \alpha_{t,s} = 0 \quad \forall s = 1, \dots, n_y \quad (1.21)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \alpha_{t,s}} &= 0, \quad \forall t = d+1, \dots, N \quad \forall s = 1, \dots, n_y \\ \rightarrow y_s(t) &= \sum_{i=0}^d \boldsymbol{\omega}_{i,s}^\top \boldsymbol{\varphi}(u(t-i)) + \delta_s + e_s(t) \end{aligned} \quad (1.22)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial e_s(t)} = 0 \rightarrow e_s(t) = \eta^{-1} \alpha_{t,s}, \quad \forall t = d+1, \dots, N \quad \forall s = 1, \dots, n_y. \quad (1.23)$$

Taking into account Eq. (1.20) and Eq. (1.23) in Eq. (1.22) gives

$$y_s(t) = \sum_{i=0}^d \left(\sum_{q=d+1}^N \alpha_{q,s} \boldsymbol{\varphi}^\top(u(q-i)) \boldsymbol{\varphi}(u(t-i)) \right) + \delta_s + \eta^{-1} \alpha_{t,s}. \quad (1.24)$$

At this stage, it is interesting to highlight that, in the previous equation, it is not necessary to define the feature map φ explicitly. Indeed, only its inner product $\varphi^\top(\bullet)\varphi(\bullet)$ is required. This property is often called the kernel trick [Schölkopf and Smola, 2002]. More precisely, the kernel $K(u(q), u(t))$ is defined from $\mathbb{R}^{n_u} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ to \mathbb{R} as $K(u(q), u(t)) = \varphi^\top(u(q))\varphi(u(t))$ and selected hereafter to be, e.g., a Gaussian Radial Basis Function

$$K(u(q), u(t)) = \exp(-\|u(q) - u(t)\|_2^2 / \sigma^2) \quad (1.25)$$

with σ a constant (see [Schölkopf and Smola, 2002] for a discussion dedicated to the kernel functions). Equations (1.21) and (1.24) can be summarized in the following linear equation with the dual parameters of the optimization problem as unknowns

$$\left[\begin{array}{c|c} 0 & \mathbf{1}_M^\top \\ \hline \mathbf{1}_M & \mathbf{\Omega} + \eta^{-1}\mathbf{I}_{M \times M} \end{array} \right] \begin{bmatrix} \delta_s \\ \bar{\alpha}_s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \bar{y}_s \end{bmatrix} \quad \forall s = 1, \dots, n_y, \quad (1.26)$$

where $M = N - d$, $\mathbf{I}_{M \times M}$ is the identity matrix of order M and $\mathbf{\Omega} = (\Omega_{ij}) \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M}$, $\mathbf{1}_M$, $\bar{\alpha}_s$ and $\bar{y}_s \in \mathbb{R}^M$ are defined as

$$\Omega_{ij} = \sum_{m=0}^d K(u(i + d - m), u(j + d - m)) \quad (1.27a)$$

$$\mathbf{1}_M = [1 \quad \dots \quad 1]^\top \quad (1.27b)$$

$$\bar{\alpha}_s = [\alpha_{d+1,s} \quad \dots \quad \alpha_{N,s}]^\top \quad (1.27c)$$

$$\bar{y}_s = [y_s(d+1) \quad \dots \quad y_s(N)]^\top. \quad (1.27d)$$

The solution of Eq. (1.26) is obtained as follows

$$\delta_s = \mathbf{1}_M^\top \mathcal{T}^{-1} \bar{y}_s / \left(\mathbf{1}_M^\top \mathcal{T}^{-1} \mathbf{1}_M \right) \quad (1.28)$$

$$\bar{\alpha}_s = \mathcal{T}^{-1} (\bar{y}_s - \mathbf{1}_M \delta_s), \quad s = 1, \dots, n_y, \quad (1.29)$$

where $\mathcal{T} = \mathbf{\Omega} + \eta^{-1}\mathbf{I}_{M \times M}$. Note that matrix \mathcal{T} is the same for all the components of the output vector because it depends only on the input u through the kernel function K . Obviously, the properties of \mathcal{T} (e.g., its conditioning) are directly related to those of the input.

Once the dual parameters $\alpha_{t,s}$ and δ_s are known, the sought non-linear components can be expressed as

$$\hat{\omega}_{i,s}^\top \varphi(\bullet) = \sum_{t=d+1}^N \alpha_{t,s} K(u(t-i), \bullet) = \bar{\alpha}_s^\top \mathbf{k}_i(\bullet) \quad s = 1, \dots, n_y \quad (1.30)$$

where

$$\mathbf{k}_i(\bullet) = [K(u(d+1-i), \bullet) \ \cdots \ K(u(N-i), \bullet)]. \quad (1.31)$$

It should be noticed that, according to the selected kernel, the LS-SVM solution to the non-linear regression problem is very similar to what is obtained by using the standard techniques of expanding the non-linearity on polynomials or RBF bases. The solution (1.30) is known to be nonsparse, that is to say that some of the terms $\alpha_{t,s}K(u(t-i), \bullet)$ have a very small contribution into the general error reduction and therefore can be removed without a great impact. Some pruning techniques have been developed to make it sparse (see, *e.g.* [de Kruif and de Vries, 2003]) but the current presentation does not address this problem.

It is well-known that the over-parameterization technique may result in an estimate for $\zeta_{i,s}$ which does not satisfy Eq. (1.16) any longer (see, *e.g.*, [Goethals et al., 2005]). This means that the estimates for the components $\zeta_{i,s}$ may not be collinear as they are expected to be. More precisely, the estimate may be corrupted by an unknown additive component $\varepsilon_{i,s}(\bullet)$ such that

$$\sum_{i=0}^d \varepsilon_{i,s}(\bullet) = 0, \forall t = d+1, \dots, N. \quad (1.32)$$

Hence, we have

$$\hat{g}_{i,s} = \hat{\omega}_{i,s}^\top \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\bullet) + \hat{\delta}_{i,s} = {}^s h_i \psi(\bullet) + \varepsilon_{i,s}(\bullet). \quad (1.33)$$

The summation of the above equation along the subscript i results in

$$\sum_{i=0}^d \hat{\omega}_{i,s}^\top \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\bullet) + \hat{\delta}_s = \mu_s \psi(\bullet) \quad (1.34)$$

where $\mu_s = \sum_i {}^s h_i$ is assumed to be nonzero. Note that for any nonzero scalar λ ,

$${}^s h_i \psi(\bullet) = ({}^s h_i \lambda) \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} \psi(\bullet) \right). \quad (1.35)$$

In other words, $\psi(\bullet)$ can only be estimated up to a scalar factor just as the matrices $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ can be determined only up to a similarity transformation. In the light of this remark, the static non-linearity ψ can be arbitrarily set as

$$\hat{\psi}(\bullet) \leftarrow \mu_s \psi(\bullet) \quad (1.36)$$

which leads to

$$\hat{\psi}(\bullet) = \sum_{i=0}^d \hat{\omega}_{i,s}^\top \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\bullet) + \hat{\delta}_s, \quad s = 1, \dots, n_y. \quad (1.37)$$

Because the nonlinearity $\psi(\bullet)$ does not depend on a particular output, it is not worth repeating this estimation for every output because it may increase the computational cost. The nonlinear function $\psi(\bullet)$ can be extracted from the measurements of the input and the ones of a single arbitrary output s or a combination of all the outputs.

From now on, by having access to an estimate of the nonlinearity, the matrices of the system can be computed by using any subspace-based identification method [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1996a, Katayama, 2005, Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007]. The linear system considered hereafter has $\psi(u)$ as the input and the entire output vector \mathbf{y} as the outputs (instead of one component as above). More precisely, the Markov parameters \mathbf{H}_i can be estimated first from the following regression equation

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = [\mathbf{H}_0 \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{H}_d] \begin{bmatrix} \psi(u(t)) \\ \vdots \\ \psi(u(t-d)) \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{e}(t), \quad t = d+1, \dots, N \quad (1.38)$$

as a standard least-squares optimization problem. When this step is completed, all the \mathbf{H}_i terms, $i \in [0, \dots, d]$, *i.e.*, \mathbf{D} , \mathbf{CB} , \mathbf{CAB} , \dots , $\mathbf{CA}^{d-1}\mathbf{B}$ and ψ are known. In the case of a batch implementation, the matrices (\mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C} , \mathbf{D}) can be directly computed from these parameters by using a singular value decomposition. In [Bako et al., 2009c], a recursive scheme which avoids the use of an SVD, which is known to be computationally demanding, is developed. The interested reader can study the aforementioned article.

1.3 From a non-linear system to a linear parameter-varying model structure

As explained previously, most of the methods dedicated to non-linear system identification require an initial decomposition of the non-linear mappings onto a set of *a priori* predefined basis functions. Efficient from a theoretical point of view [Hunter and Korenberg, 1986, Sjöberg, 1995, Schön, 2006], this way of dealing with non-linear systems can have many practical drawbacks. For instance, a crucial point of this approach is the choice of the basis functions. According to the non-linearities involved in the behavior of the system as well as their diversities, no universal solution can be suggested to the user. Most of the time, a trade-off between accuracy and complexity can guide the user to the most efficient solution. In order to circumvent this choice, an alternative and natural way to deal with non-linearity consists in linearizing the dynamics of the system, *i.e.*, by approximating the non-linear model by a linear one. This approach is particularly used when the system works

finally under feedback because, usually, the controller keeps the system working around a fixed operating point for which the linear time-invariant model is a good approximation of the real system. Interesting from a practical point of view because LTI system identification is now a research field full of efficient algorithms [Ljung, 2001], this approach, which is historically prior to the developments resorting to the decomposition of the non-linear mappings onto a set of *a priori* predefined basis functions, can be restrictive because [Shamma, 1996]

- the linear model often gives only a local description of the dynamic behavior of the system,
- specific dynamic behavior can be totally neglected by the linear approximation.

Such drawbacks and restrictions can be tackled by

- estimating one LTI model associated with confidence intervals as well as a sort of a distance between the true system and its LTI approximation [Ljung, 2001],
- handling many equilibrium points and an LTI model for each operating point [Shamma, 1996].

This last approach, which is mainly used in Chapter 5, consists in

- first decomposing the operating range of the system into a number of smaller working regimes where a simple local model can be obtained to describe the behavior of the system around this working point,
- second interpolating the local models by using a (smooth) interpolation function depending on the operating points.

This basic idea is the starting point of many linearization-based approximation methods [Shamma, 1996]. For instance, this approach is used in many papers devoted to linear parameter-varying (LPV) model identification associated with gain scheduling (see [Rugh and Shamma, 2000] for a list of references in the 90's). As shown in [Shamma, 1996] and [Rugh and Shamma, 2000], LPV modeling is historically linked to control engineering where a controller must be designed in order to guarantee a suitable closed-loop performance for a given plant working in different operating conditions. A well-known example of controller design technique using this basic idea is the gain scheduling approach [Rugh and Shamma, 2000]. In gain scheduling, the coefficients of the controller vary according to measurable signals called the

scheduling signals, parameters or variables. By construction, this approach relies on the availability of an accurate LPV model. Such a model is historically obtained from standard linearization-based approximation methods such as, e.g., the Jacobian linearization method [Shamma and Athans, 1990], the state transformation technique [Shamma and Cloutier, 1993, Casella and Lovera, 2008] or the function substitution approach [Marcos and Balas, 2004] (see also [Kwiatkowski et al., 2006] for a technique leading to an automated generation of affine LPV models). The goal of this section is not to present a new overview of these linearization-based approximation methods. An interesting state-of-the-art as well as a comparison of all of these techniques are indeed available, e.g., in [Tóth, 2010, Chapter 7]. However, in order to introduce a first definition of an LPV model description as well as the basis of the identification methods composing the local approach of LPV system identification (see Chapter 5 for a definition), the Jacobian linearization method is going to be quickly described.

Remark 1.3 *The reader must be aware that, in this section, the problem of the existence of an LPV form of the non-linear system is not addressed at all. While the aforementioned linearization-based approximation methods bypass this important problem by considering specific subclasses of LPV representations, "LPV modeling of non-linear systems still deserves attention" [Tóth, 2010, Chapter 7] because, to the author's knowledge, conditions and theorems ensuring the existence of an LPV description for any non-linear system are not available in the literature⁵ yet.*

In the next chapters, a particular attention is payed to the state-space representations. Thus, it is assumed herein that the non-linear system can be represented by the set of equations (1.3) (or (1.4) in the discrete-time domain), i.e.,

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t), \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, t) \quad (1.39a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \boldsymbol{\ell}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t), \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, t). \quad (1.39b)$$

Before describing the linearization method, several definitions must be introduced [Shamma, 1996, Nocedal and Wright, 2006].

Definition 1.1 *Assume that \mathbf{f} is a function from the Euclidean n -space \mathbb{R}^n to the Euclidean m -space \mathbb{R}^m . In terms of components,*

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{bmatrix} f_1(x_1, \dots, x_n) \\ \vdots \\ f_m(x_1, \dots, x_n) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.40)$$

⁵A good formulation of the problem is given in [Tóth, 2010, Chapter 7].

where the x_j , $j \in [1, n]$, are the scalar components of \mathbf{x} and the f_i , $i \in [1, m]$, are the scalar valued functions of \mathbf{f} . Then, the partial derivatives of all these functions (if they exist) can be organized in an m by n matrix, called the Jacobian matrix \mathbf{F}_x of \mathbf{f} , as follows

$$\mathbf{F}_x = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_1} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial f_m}{\partial x_1} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_m}{\partial x_n} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1.41)$$

When \mathbf{f} is continuously differentiable at the point \mathbf{x}_0 , this definition can be useful to approximate the function \mathbf{f} . Indeed, by using the Taylor series expansion of \mathbf{f} , we get

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_0) + \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_0}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0) + \mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (1.42)$$

where the term $\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x})$ stands for the higher order terms. This observation is the basic idea of the linearization-based method introduced hereafter. Notice furthermore that the Jacobian matrix can be extended to a function of several vectors, for instance $\mathbf{f} : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^p \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$. In this case, we can define the Jacobian matrix with respect to each variable.

Because the first developments dedicated to the Jacobian linearization technique assumed the availability of equilibrium points, this concept point must be defined (for the state-space representation (1.39)) [Shamma, 1996, Tóth, 2010].

Definition 1.2 A point $(\mathbf{x}_{eq}, \mathbf{u}_{eq})$ satisfying

$$\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}_{eq}, \mathbf{u}_{eq}) = 0 \quad (1.43)$$

is an equilibrium point for the plant described by the set of equations (1.39).

By using these definitions and by assuming that

- the system (1.39) has a set of equilibrium points $(\mathbf{x}_{eq_i}, \mathbf{u}_{eq_i})$, $i \in [1, q]$,
- the functions \mathbf{h} and ℓ are continuously differentiable,

the multivariable Taylor series introduced beforehand can be applied to the functions \mathbf{h} and ℓ in Eq. (1.39) around each couple $(\mathbf{x}_{eq_i}, \mathbf{u}_{eq_i})$. This calculation leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t), \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, t) &= \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}_{eq_i}(t), \mathbf{u}_{eq_i}(t), \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, t) \\ &+ \mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_{eq_i}, \mathbf{u}=\mathbf{u}_{eq_i}}(\mathbf{x}(t) - \mathbf{x}_{eq_i}) \\ &+ \mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_{eq_i}, \mathbf{u}=\mathbf{u}_{eq_i}}(\mathbf{u}(t) - \mathbf{u}_{eq_i}) + \mathbf{r}_{h_i}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t)) \end{aligned} \quad (1.44a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \ell(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t), \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, t) &= \ell(\mathbf{x}_{eq_i}(t), \mathbf{u}_{eq_i}(t), \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, t) \\ &+ \mathbf{L}_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_{eq_i}, \mathbf{u}=\mathbf{u}_{eq_i}}(\mathbf{x}(t) - \mathbf{x}_{eq_i}) \\ &+ \mathbf{L}_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_{eq_i}, \mathbf{u}=\mathbf{u}_{eq_i}}(\mathbf{u}(t) - \mathbf{u}_{eq_i}) + \mathbf{r}_{\ell_i}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t)) \end{aligned} \quad (1.44b)$$

where \mathbf{r}_{h_i} and \mathbf{r}_{ℓ_i} contain the remainders of higher order. By combining these equations with the dynamic relations (1.39), we get⁶

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{A}_i \mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}_i \mathbf{u}(t) + \boldsymbol{\gamma}_i(t) \quad (1.45a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}_i \mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{D}_i \mathbf{u}(t) + \boldsymbol{\lambda}_i(t) \quad (1.45b)$$

with

$$\mathbf{A}_i = \mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_{eq_i}, \mathbf{u}=\mathbf{u}_{eq_i}} \quad (1.46a)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_i = \mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_{eq_i}, \mathbf{u}=\mathbf{u}_{eq_i}} \quad (1.46b)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\gamma}_i(t) = -\mathbf{A}_i \mathbf{x}_{eq_i} - \mathbf{B}_i \mathbf{u}_{eq_i} + \mathbf{r}_{h_i}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t)) \quad (1.46c)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_i = \mathbf{L}_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_{eq_i}, \mathbf{u}=\mathbf{u}_{eq_i}} \quad (1.46d)$$

$$\mathbf{D}_i = \mathbf{L}_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_{eq_i}, \mathbf{u}=\mathbf{u}_{eq_i}} \quad (1.46e)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\lambda}_i(t) = -\mathbf{C}_i \mathbf{x}_{eq_i} - \mathbf{D}_i \mathbf{u}_{eq_i} + \mathbf{r}_{\ell_i}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t)) + \boldsymbol{\ell}(\mathbf{x}_{eq_i}, \mathbf{u}_{eq_i}, \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, t). \quad (1.46f)$$

Eq. (1.45) is the result of the linearization of the non-linear dynamic system (1.39) around the equilibrium point $(\mathbf{x}_{eq_i}, \mathbf{u}_{eq_i})$. Then, by subtracting the remainder terms $\boldsymbol{\gamma}_i(t)$ and $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_i(t)$ (if they are available) from the signals \mathbf{x} , \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{y} or by simply neglecting them, the set of equations (1.45) becomes

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{A}_i \mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}_i \mathbf{u}(t) \quad (1.47a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}_i \mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{D}_i \mathbf{u}(t) \quad (1.47b)$$

which can be seen as a local LTI states-space model of the system.

This linearization procedure can be performed for each equilibrium point, leading to q sets of state-space matrices $(\mathbf{A}_i, \mathbf{B}_i, \mathbf{C}_i, \mathbf{D}_i)$, $i \in [1, q]$. By having access to these q local models, the behavior of the real non-linear system can be approximated by combining efficiently these local representations. Many solutions of weighted combinations of these local LTI models are available in the literature (see [Murray-Smith and Johansen, 1997] for an overview). Most of them interpolate these local models with specific weightings like, e.g., the well-known Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy membership functions [Babuska, 1998, Nelles, 2000, R. Babuska, 2003]. This characteristic is shared by the linear parameter-varying model description. This approach assumes that the equilibrium points $(\mathbf{x}_{eq_i}, \mathbf{u}_{eq_i})$ are dependent on variables, called the scheduling parameter vector or the scheduling variables $\mathbf{p}(t)$, assumed to be measurable during the use of the system and a (not necessarily *a priori* known) function of the inputs and the state variables, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{p}(t) = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t)). \quad (1.48)$$

⁶Keep in mind that $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}_{eq_i}(t), \mathbf{u}_{eq_i}(t), \boldsymbol{\vartheta}, t) = 0$.

More precisely, a parameter-varying model can be obtained by considering the following interpolated structure

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \underbrace{\sum_{i=1}^q (\mathbf{g}_i(\mathbf{p}(t)) \mathbf{A}_i)}_{\mathcal{A}(\mathbf{p}(t))} \mathbf{x}(t) + \underbrace{\sum_{i=1}^q (\mathbf{g}_i(\mathbf{p}(t)) \mathbf{B}_i)}_{\mathcal{B}(\mathbf{p}(t))} \mathbf{u}(t) + \boldsymbol{\gamma}(t) \quad (1.49a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \underbrace{\sum_{i=1}^q (\mathbf{g}_i(\mathbf{p}(t)) \mathbf{C}_i)}_{\mathcal{C}(\mathbf{p}(t))} \mathbf{x}(t) + \underbrace{\sum_{i=1}^q (\mathbf{g}_i(\mathbf{p}(t)) \mathbf{D}_i)}_{\mathcal{D}(\mathbf{p}(t))} \mathbf{u}(t) + \boldsymbol{\lambda}(t) \quad (1.49b)$$

where

- $\boldsymbol{\gamma}(t)$ and $\boldsymbol{\lambda}(t)$ gather the remainder terms, *i.e.*, weighted combinations of the components of $\boldsymbol{\gamma}_i(t)$ and $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_i(t)$,
- $\mathbf{g}_i(\mathbf{p}(t))$ are user-defined weighting functions satisfying

$$0 \leq \mathbf{g}_i(\mathbf{p}(t)) \leq 1 \quad \sum_{i=1}^q \mathbf{g}_i(\mathbf{p}(t)) = 1. \quad (1.50)$$

By construction, when the system operates around the i th equilibrium point, the weighting $\mathbf{g}_i(\mathbf{p}(t))$ must be close to one.

The LPV modeling framework is interesting compared to the non-linear one because, by construction, the relations between the input, the output and the state signals are linear. However, it is important to notice that [Tóth, 2008, Chapter 7]

- the model (1.49) is a linear parameter-varying state-space model if the terms $\boldsymbol{\gamma}(t)$ and $\boldsymbol{\lambda}(t)$ are removed. This removal can deeply modify the capabilities of the LPV model to approximate the behavior of the real system;
- the parameter-varying model (1.49) can perform badly when it is used away from the equilibrium points. It often happens when the scheduling parameter vector quickly varies during the use of the model [Tóth et al., 2007]. Most of the time, this defect leads to a poor transient performance as shown, *e.g.*, in [Tóth et al., 2007] or in [Shorten et al., 1999];
- this linearization-based approach can be easily extended to points which are not equilibrium points but, *e.g.*, user-defined operating points belonging to a specific operating range of the system. This approach has

been considered in [Leith and Leithead, 1996, Marcos and Balas, 2004]. By construction, the following PV model may lead to a better transient behavior than with a model obtained from the standard linearization-based described beforehand (and based on equilibrium points) if the operating points used for the linearization are well-chosen. Then, the main difficulty of this approach consists in well-choosing these operating points. To the author's knowledge, few contributions addressing this crucial problem can be found in the literature (except, to some extent, in [Pfifer and Hecker, 2008] or in [Khalate et al., 2009]);

- the identification methods known as the local approaches or the multiple model approaches (see [Tóth, 2010] and Chapter 5 for a definition) are inspired by these local linear approximation methods and, by definition, share many advantages and drawbacks with this interpolation technique (see Chapter 5 for a discussion about the characteristics of the local identification procedure).

1.4 Outline of the monograph

This monograph is divided into six chapters including this introduction and appendices. As a whole, these chapters are mainly devoted to the introduction of solutions for the identification of multivariable (non-linear) systems described by state-space representations. More precisely, the following contents are investigated.

Chapter 2: **Regression techniques for subspace-based black-box state-space system identification: an overview.** As illustrated previously, a crucial point of any identification procedure is the selection of the structure of the model. Indeed, the structure of the model must be chosen so that its complexity

- allows a good description of the behavior of the system,
- is not too difficult in order to ensure that the cost function used to assess the quality of the model can be optimized, at least numerically, with a good chance to reach its optimal value.

Thus, a trade-off between flexibility and simplicity of the structure is required. Because, most of the time, it is almost impossible to find a mathematical description of the system corresponding exactly to the true system without involving too complex representations, the model used in system identification is often an approximation of the true description. A standard solution consists in resorting to a linear time-invariant description of the system. Such a choice is limited because, in practice, very few real systems can be considered as

linear and time-invariant (LTI). However, as shown, *e.g.*, by the literature dedicated to the identification techniques used for the tuning of PID controllers [Åström et al., 1993, Leva et al., 2001, Åström and Hagglund, 2005], a (two- or three-parameter) LTI model is often enough to describe the behavior of the system, at least in a specific frequency domain. Interesting results available in [Ljung, 2001, 2002, 2010] also clearly illustrate the role played by the LTI models in system identification and their capability to approximate the behavior of quite complex systems. As claimed by Ljung in [Ljung, 2001], "the LTI identification machinery is always able to deliver an unfalsified linear model with decreasing uncertainty regions as more and more data become available, regardless of the character of the system". Notice also that an LTI model is often preferred to a non-linear one or a time-varying one for a first try because a huge amount of techniques and algorithms are now available in many toolboxes dedicated to system identification. Among all the solutions available in the literature, the subspace-based state-space model identification techniques have proved their efficiency in many practical cases since the beginning of the 90's as illustrated, *e.g.*, in [Verhaegen et al., 1994, Bittanti et al., 1997, Bastogne et al., 1998, Favoreel et al., 2000, Juricek et al., 2001, De Cock et al., 2002, Oku, 2003, De Cock et al., 2006, van Wingerden and Verhaegen, 2009, Bergamasco and Lovera, 2011]. Chapter 2 introduces an overview of these techniques by focusing on their formulation as a least-squares problem. Apart from the article [Qin, 2006], to the Author's knowledge, such a regression formulation is not totally investigated in the books [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1996a, Katayama, 2005, Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007] which can be considered as the references as far as subspace-based identification is concerned. Thus, in Chapter 2, a specific attention is paid to the regression-based techniques used to identify systems working under open-loop as well as closed-loop conditions. The subspace-based identification methods being, in a way, the underlying theme of this monograph, Chapter 2 is also used to introduce the basic mathematical and theoretical tools that are used in the sequel.

Chapter 3: **Subspace-based identification of parameterized black-box state-space systems.** Most of the subspace-based identification algorithms lead to fully-parameterized state-space forms. Interesting in many practical cases because

- all the systems of a given order can be described in a fully-parameterized model structure,
- such a structure removes the structural problems inherent to the standard canonical parameterizations,

this over-flexibility associated with the fact that the standard subspace-based

identification algorithms yield an estimated state-space representation known up to a similarity transformation make these estimation tools difficult to use when dealing, *e.g.*, with multi-models or switched systems because

- the estimated fully-parameterized model is by construction not identifiable,
- it is really difficult to ensure that all the estimated models can be expressed with respect to coherent state coordinates bases.

In order to circumvent these difficulties, Chapter 3 revisits the problem of determining a canonical state-space representation for multivariable systems. More precisely, a method is derived to build a canonical state-space representation directly from data generated by a linear time-invariant system. Contrary to the standard construction methods of canonical parameterizations, the technique developed in this chapter does not assume the availability of any observability or controllability indices. A subspace-based identification algorithm is also introduced to estimate such a canonical state-space parameterization directly from input-output data. Because the subspace-based identification algorithm introduced in this chapter results in a canonical form, the estimated parameters are, by construction, invariants of the system. This structural characteristic makes the determination of the uncertainty domains of the estimated parameters possible, as explained in this chapter. Thanks to this property, a bounded-error approach is introduced in order to characterize the uncertainty domains of the coefficients of the state-space matrices. Simulation examples are included in order to demonstrate the efficiency of the developed methods. This chapter is mainly based on the concepts available in [Mercère and Lovera, 2007, Mercère et al., 2008, Mercère and Bako, 2011, Farah et al., 2012].

Chapter 4: Identification of parameterized gray-box state-space systems. Estimating the order as well as the matrices of a black-box linear time-invariant state-space model is now a relatively easy problem to solve, *e.g.*, by resorting to the standard subspace-based identification algorithms [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1996a, Katayama, 2005, Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007]. However, it is well-known that the estimated state-space matrices obtained thanks to these system identification tools are unique modulo a non-singular similarity transformation matrix. This characteristic could have serious consequences if the system to identify is a real physical system, the parameters of which are of interest. Indeed, if the true system contains physical parameters, then the identified black-box fully-parameterized model could no longer have the physical parameters in a form that can be extracted easily. The question addressed in Chapter 4 then is how to recover the physical parameters once the system has been identified in a fully-parameterized form. Two solutions to this re-structuration problem are more precisely introduced in this chapter.

First, by assuming that a reliable initial fully-parameterized state-space model is available, an algorithm dedicated to non-smooth optimization is introduced in order to transform this initial fully-parameterized model into the structured state-space parameterization of the system to identify. A specific constraint on the similarity transformation between both system representations is added to avoid singularity. Second, the same problem is solved by transforming the bilinear equations arising from the similarity transformation equations as a null-space problem. Extracting the physical parameters then requires the solution of a non-convex optimization problem in a reduced dimensional space. By assuming that the physical state-space form is identifiable and the initial fully-parameterized model is consistent, it is proved that the solution of this optimization problem is unique. Numerical examples highlight the performance of the developed techniques. These results are based on the papers [Prot and Mercère, 2011, Prot et al., 2012].

Chapter 5: Identification of state-space linear parameter-varying models from local experimental data: new developments for the local approach. The former paragraphs have shown that a non-linear system can be efficiently identified by resorting to a decomposition of the whole non-linear functioning domain of the system into many local domains where

- the local behavior of the system is more linear than the global one,
- the system can thus be approximated by a simple but reliable local model.

Such a viewpoint is shared by the gain-scheduling interpolation-based concept used for LPV system identification, also referred to as the local approach. In Chapter 5, the local approach is revisited and two new solutions are formulated by focusing on the question: how to perform the interpolation in a more efficient sense. First, the problem of deriving MIMO parameter-dependent models from data generated by local identification experiments is considered and a numerically sound approach is suggested, based on subspace identification ideas combined with the use of suitable properties of balanced state space realizations. Second, inspired by the discussion available in [Casella and Lovera, 2008], more precisely by the fact that shortcomings of the analytical and experimental methods could be relaxed by combining techniques and ideas originating from both points of view, the second technique, called the glocal method in the sequel, consists in

- resorting to the knowledge available from the study of the non-linear equations governing the system behavior in order to fix the structure of the global LPV model,

- estimating the parameters of this global LPV model by using data acquired locally, *i.e.*, input-output data sets corresponding to different but fixed operating points.

Both techniques are validated by using a simulator of a non-linear flexible robot manipulator designed to attain fast dynamics in order to compensate the heart tissue motion for cardiac surgery. This chapter can be considered as an overview of results developed in [Lovera and Mercère, 2007, Mercère et al., 2011a].

CHAPTER 2

Regression techniques for subspace-based black-box state-space system identification: an overview

2.1 Motivations and problem formulation

A linear time-invariant (LTI) discrete-time (DT) system can always be represented with the help of an LTI DT state-space form

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{w}(t) \quad (2.1a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{v}(t) \quad (2.1b)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ is the state vector, $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ is the input vector, $\mathbf{y}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ is the output vector, $\mathbf{v}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ is the output measurement noise vector and $\mathbf{w}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ is the process noise vector. ($\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}$) are the state-space matrices of the system with appropriate dimensions.

Remark 2.1 *In this chapter, all the developments involve only DT data and DT systems. Thus, $t \in \mathbb{Z}$ and can be related to the sampling period T_s used to acquire the input-output data. Notice however that one of the subspace-based identification algorithms introduced in the following overview has been recently extended in the continuous-time (CT) framework [Bergamasco and Lovera, 2010a,b, 2011].*

In order to estimate the state-space matrices ($\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}$), the standard maximum likelihood methods [Ljung, 1999a] can be used. One example is the well-known output-error approach which is investigated in Chapter 4. However, when the user wants to avoid a difficult non-linear optimization, an interesting alternative consists in resorting to a subspace-based state-space identification (4SID) algorithm [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1996a, Katayama, 2005, Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007]. The subspace-based identification methods have attracted a large interest since the 1990's because, among other things,

- they use reliable and robust numerical tools such as the RQ factorization or the singular values decomposition (SVD) [Golub and Van Loan, 1996],
- they do not require any non-linear optimization scheme,
- they lead to fully-parameterized and well-conditioned black-box state-space forms (for instance a balanced realization [McKelvey, 1994]),
- they can handle multi-input-multi-output (MIMO) systems as easily as single-input-single-output (SISO) systems.

Historically, the first studies [Verhaegen and Dewilde, 1992a,b, Verhaegen, 1993a, 1994, Van Overschee and De Moor, 1994, 1995a, Viberg, 1995] mainly focused on the development of efficient algorithms which yield consistent estimates under different practical conditions and noise properties. This work has led to two main classes of subspace-based identification methods:

- the techniques which retrieve the space generated by the columns of the extended observability matrix from the available input-output data (*e.g.*, the "Multivariable Output-Error State sPace" (MOESP) methods [Verhaegen and Dewilde, 1992a,b, Verhaegen, 1993a, 1994] or the "Instrumental Variable for Subspace State-Space Sytem IDentification" (IV-4SID) methods [Viberg, 1995]),
- the algorithms which estimate the state sequence from the available input-output data (*e.g.*, the "Numerical algorithms for Subspace State-Space SyStem IDentification" (N4SID) [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1994] or the "Canonical Variate Analysis" (CVA) method [Larimore, 1990]).

It is interesting to point out that these methods

- share the same linear algebra tools (RQ factorization and SVD),
- require projection techniques in order to calculate specific subspaces of the system and to fix the state coordinate basis [Peternell, 1995] giving rise to a particular fully-parameterized state-space form, *e.g.*, a balanced realization [Chou and Maciejowski, 1997, Markovsky et al., 2005] or an orthogonal basis for the state-space [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1995b],
- involve model reduction techniques in order to determine the order of the system (especially when the data is corrupted by disturbances).

Interesting from a numerical point of view, these techniques

- are a lot more difficult to study from a statistical point of view than, *e.g.*, the maximum likelihood techniques [Ljung, 1999a],
- make the introduction of prior information about the system into the identification procedure quite complex.

These shortcomings mainly happen because the aforementioned subspace-based identification methods do not minimize explicitly a cost function in order to estimate the state-space matrices. Thus,

- the standard tools dedicated to the statistical analysis of the regression or prediction-based estimates [Ljung, 1999a] are difficult to adapt to this specific framework,
- the techniques incorporating prior knowledge about the process into the optimization problem with the help of constrained equalities or inequalities [Rothenberg, 1973] or via specific probabilistic tools [Peterka, 1981] cannot be used directly with most of the subspace-based identification methods.

In order to adapt the tools used for the statistical analysis of the standard linear regression estimates to the subspace-based identification framework, several researchers have investigated the formulation of the subspace-based identification with the help of specific structured regression models [Paternell et al., 1996, Jansson and Wahlberg, 1996, Bauer and Jansson, 2000]. Initially developed for systems working under open-loop conditions [Ljung and McKelvey, 1996b, Qin and Ljung, 2003b, Qin et al., 2005], this linear regression approach has allowed the development as well as the analysis of some subspace-based identification algorithms for closed-loop data [Ljung and McKelvey, 1996a, Jansson, 2003, Qin and Ljung, 2003a, Jansson, 2005, Lin et al., 2005, Chiuso and Picci, 2005a,b, Houtzager et al., 2009b, Chiuso, 2010]. More recently, this formulation of the subspace-based identification as a linear regression-based problem has been used to incorporate prior information into some subspace-based identification algorithms [Trnka and Havlena, 2007, 2009, Alenany et al., 2010].

The linear regression formulation of the subspace-based identification is introduced thoroughly in this chapter. Open-loop as well as closed-loop operating conditions are respectively considered in Sub-Section 2.2.2 and Sub-Section 2.2.3. To the author's knowledge, such an overview is not available in any book dedicated to subspace-based identification. Notice also that this least-squares interpretation of the subspace-based identification techniques is the basis of the developments introduced in Chapter 3.

Before presenting the basic idea of the regression-based subspace identification, it is important to introduce generic notations which will be used all along this chapter. First, for any vector $\mathbf{r}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r}$, we can define

- the infinite past stacked vector

$$\mathbf{r}^-(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ \mathbf{r}(t-2) \\ \mathbf{r}(t-1) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.2)$$

- the infinite future stacked vector

$$\mathbf{r}^+(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{r}(t) \\ \mathbf{r}(t+1) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.3)$$

- the finite past stacked vector

$$\mathbf{r}_\ell^-(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{r}(t-\ell) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{r}(t-2) \\ \mathbf{r}(t-1) \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{\ell n_r \times 1}, \ell \in \mathbb{N}_*^+ \quad (2.4)$$

- the finite future stacked vector

$$\mathbf{r}_\ell^+(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{r}(t) \\ \mathbf{r}(t+1) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{r}(t+\ell-1) \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{\ell n_r \times 1}, \ell \in \mathbb{N}_*^+. \quad (2.5)$$

By having access to these finite stacked vector¹, the past and future Hankel matrices (resp. $\mathbf{R}_{\ell,M}^-(t)$ and $\mathbf{R}_{\ell,M}^+(t)$) can be deduced as follows

$$\mathbf{R}_{\ell,M}^-(t) = [\mathbf{r}_\ell^-(t) \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{r}_\ell^-(t+M-1)] \in \mathbb{R}^{\ell n_r \times M}, \ell \in \mathbb{N}_*^+, M \in \mathbb{N}_*^+ \quad (2.6)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_{\ell,M}^+(t) = [\mathbf{r}_\ell^+(t) \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{r}_\ell^+(t+M-1)] \in \mathbb{R}^{\ell n_r \times M}, \ell \in \mathbb{N}_*^+, M \in \mathbb{N}_*^+. \quad (2.7)$$

¹By looking closer at the definition of $\mathbf{r}_\ell^-(t)$ and $\mathbf{r}_\ell^+(t)$, it is quite obvious that a single definition could be used because, e.g., $\mathbf{r}_\ell^-(t) = \mathbf{r}_\ell^+(t-\ell)$. However, in order to highlight the fact that $\mathbf{r}_\ell^-(t)$ (resp. $\mathbf{r}_\ell^+(t)$) is composed of past (resp. future) data with respect to the present time index t , two notations are used hereafter. This notion of past and future is indeed standard when subspace-based identification is concerned.

Now, from four matrices \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{D} of appropriate dimensions, the following generic block matrices can be constructed

$$\mathbf{\Omega}_\ell(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) = [\mathbf{A}^{\ell-1}\mathbf{B} \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{A}\mathbf{B} \quad \mathbf{B}], \quad \ell \in \mathbb{N}_*^+ \quad (2.8)$$

$$\mathbf{\Gamma}_\ell(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B}\mathbf{A} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}^{\ell-1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \ell \in \mathbb{N}_*^+ \quad (2.9)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_\ell(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{D} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{C}\mathbf{B} & \mathbf{D} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}^{\ell-2}\mathbf{B} & \dots & \mathbf{C}\mathbf{B} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \ell \in \mathbb{N}_*^+. \quad (2.10)$$

By construction, for $\ell \geq n_x$, $\mathbf{\Gamma}_\ell(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})$ (resp. $\mathbf{\Omega}_\ell(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B})$) is the extended observability (resp. (reversed) controllability) matrix of the system (2.1).

2.2 Subspace-based identification involving linear regression

A quick look at the literature dedicated to the linear regression-based subspace identification [Wahlberg and Jansson, 1994, Jansson and Wahlberg, 1996, Ljung and McKelvey, 1996a, Peternell et al., 1996, Bauer, 2003, Qin, 2006] indicates that most of the least-squares methods for subspace-based identification first try to determine a sequence of the state vector \mathbf{x} . By having access to a reliable state estimate as well as a sufficiently large set of input and output measurements, the identification problem becomes a linear regression problem

$$\varpi(t) = \mathbf{\Theta}\phi(t) + \nu(t) \quad (2.11)$$

where

$$\varpi(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}(t+1) \\ \mathbf{y}(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{\Theta} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{C} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \quad \phi(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}(t) \\ \mathbf{u}(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad \nu(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}(t) \\ \mathbf{w}(t) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.12)$$

Second, the parameter matrix $\mathbf{\Theta}$ can be estimated by using a least-squares method. The characteristics of the disturbances \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{w} can also be estimated, in a second step, from the analysis of the residuals.

Remark 2.2 *As soon as the state vector is determined, the coordinate basis of the state-space realization is fixed.*

In this section, the main steps involved in this specific linear regression framework are described in a quite general context. Sub-Section 2.2.1 is more precisely dedicated to the construction of a state sequence from the available input and output data. By knowing this state sequence (as a linear combination of past data), specific multi-step predictors are introduced in Sub-Section 2.2.2 as well as dedicated optimization algorithms (involving certain rank constraints) in order to yield consistent estimates of the state-space matrices \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C} , \mathbf{D} . Because the linear regression techniques studied in Sub-Section 2.2.2 lead to biased estimates when the system to identify operates in closed-loop, a particular attention is paid to techniques efficient under closed-loop operating conditions in Sub-Section 2.2.3.

2.2.1 Construction of a state sequence from past input and past output data

This sub-section is mainly dedicated to this first step of the main linear regression-based subspace identification methods. Different formulations of the state sequence as specific combinations of past inputs and past outputs are more precisely addressed. Notice right now that these combinations will involve unknown matrices such as the state-space matrices of the system (via, *e.g.*, the Markov parameters). These matrices are unknown at this step of the identification procedure. The goal of this section is not to estimate the state but to reformulate it as a combination of known signals in order to simplify the data equations used in Sub-Section 2.2.2 and Sub-Section 2.2.3. The problem of the state-space matrices extraction is indeed investigated in these two aforementioned paragraphs. This state sequence determination phase is only an intermediate step necessary to give rise to linear regression problems.

2.2.1.1 State sequence construction from the Kalman filter

A standard way to construct a state sequence consists in resorting to an observer. An observer is indeed a mathematical tool able to approximate the state vector of a dynamic system from measurements of its inputs and outputs. A standard observer is the Kalman filter. The Kalman filter is a well-known and widely used tool (see, *e.g.*, [Fossen and Perez, 2009, Galleani and Tavella, 2010, Grewal and Andrews, 2010] for recent applications). One of its main use consists in reconstructing the state of a given state-space system in a statistically optimal way [Kalman, 1960, Kalman and Bucy, 1961]. By statistically optimal way, it is meant that the Kalman filter yields an unbiased state estimate $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t)$ (*i.e.* $\mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{x}(t) - \hat{\mathbf{x}}(t)\} = \mathbf{0}$) with² a state error covariance

² $\mathbb{E}\{\bullet\}$ stands for the expected value of the random variable \bullet .

matrix $\mathbb{E}\left\{(\mathbf{x}(t) - \hat{\mathbf{x}}(t))(\mathbf{x}(t) - \hat{\mathbf{x}}(t))^\top\right\}$ as small as possible [Johansson, 1993, Gustafsson, 2000, Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007]. Contrary to a standard Luenberger observer, the Kalman filter takes the disturbances acting on the system into account.

The Kalman filter deals with linear time-varying systems of the form

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = \mathbf{A}(t)\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{w}(t) \quad (2.13a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}(t)\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{D}(t)\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{v}(t) \quad (2.13b)$$

where the process noise \mathbf{w} and the measurement noise \mathbf{v} are assumed to be zero-mean white noises with joint covariance matrix

$$\mathbb{E}\left\{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}(k) \\ \mathbf{w}(k) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}^\top(j) & \mathbf{w}^\top(j) \end{bmatrix}\right\} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}(k) & \mathbf{S}^\top(k) \\ \mathbf{S}(k) & \mathbf{Q}(k) \end{bmatrix} \delta_{kj} \geq 0 \quad (2.14)$$

where $\mathbf{R}(k) > 0$, $\mathbf{Q}(k) \geq 0$ and where δ_{kj} is the Kronecker delta function defined by

$$\delta_{kj} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } k = j \\ 0 & \text{if } k \neq j \end{cases} \quad (2.15)$$

The Kalman filter is a recursive estimator. Most of the time, it is written as a two-step approach where [Welch and Bishop, 2001]

- the first step (usually named the prediction phase) uses the state estimate from the previous time-step in order to calculate an estimate of the state at the current time-step. This predicted state estimate is also known as the *a priori* state estimate because it does not include observation information from the current time-step.
- the second step (usually named the update phase) combines the current *a priori* prediction with current observation information in order to refine the state estimate. This update state estimate is also named the *a posteriori* state estimate.

The DT Kalman filter can be viewed as a cycle where the prediction step and the correction step alternate.

In the following, only the prediction phase is introduced. For more details concerning the DT Kalman filter, see, e.g., [Anderson and Moore, 1990]. This limitation can be justified by the fact that, in the system identification framework considered herein, at best the data up to time $t-1$ are involved to estimate the unknown parameters. Thus, the update phase will not intervene in the following.

The prediction step can be described as follows. By assuming that an estimate $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ of \mathbf{x} is available at time t satisfying

$$\mathbb{E} \{ \mathbf{x}(t) \} = \mathbb{E} \{ \hat{\mathbf{x}}(t) \} \quad (2.16a)$$

$$\mathbb{E} \left\{ (\mathbf{x}(t) - \hat{\mathbf{x}}(t)) (\mathbf{x}(t) - \hat{\mathbf{x}}(t))^\top \right\} = \mathbf{P}(t) \geq 0, \quad (2.16b)$$

the state estimate at time $t + 1$ is given by [Katayama, 2005, Chapter 5]

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t + 1) = \mathbf{A}(t)\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t) + \mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathcal{K}(t) (\mathbf{y}(t) - \mathbf{C}(t)\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t) - \mathbf{D}(t)\mathbf{u}(t)) \quad (2.17)$$

where the Kalman gain \mathcal{K} satisfies

$$\mathcal{K}(t) = \left(\mathbf{S}(t) + \mathbf{A}(t)\mathbf{P}(t)\mathbf{C}^\top(t) \right) \left(\mathbf{R}(t) + \mathbf{C}(t)\mathbf{P}(t)\mathbf{C}^\top(t) \right)^{-1} \quad (2.18)$$

where the state error covariance matrix $\mathbf{P}(t)$ is updated by using the Riccati difference equation

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}(t + 1) = & \mathbf{A}(t)\mathbf{P}(t)\mathbf{A}^\top(t) + \mathbf{Q}(t) - \left(\mathbf{S}(t) + \mathbf{A}(t)\mathbf{P}(t)\mathbf{C}^\top(t) \right) \\ & \left(\mathbf{R}(t) + \mathbf{C}(t)\mathbf{P}(t)\mathbf{C}^\top(t) \right)^{-1} \left(\mathbf{S}(t) + \mathbf{A}(t)\mathbf{P}(t)\mathbf{C}^\top(t) \right)^\top. \end{aligned} \quad (2.19)$$

Furthermore, the conditional expectation of the output signal $\mathbf{y}(t)$, given the input and output data from the infinite past up to time $t - 1$, satisfies

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}(t) = \mathbf{C}(t)\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t) + \mathbf{D}(t)\mathbf{u}(t). \quad (2.20)$$

The developments introduced up until now have handled time-varying systems. As shown in [Katayama, 2005, Chapter 5], when the state-space matrices (\mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C} , \mathbf{D}) as well as the variance matrices (\mathbf{R} , \mathbf{S} , \mathbf{Q}) are time-invariant, Eq. (2.17), (2.18), (2.19) and (2.20) can be adapted for time-invariant systems (see also [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007, Chapter 5] for details). More precisely, by considering that the following assumptions are satisfied,

Assumption 2.1 *The noise terms \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{w} in the LTI state-space representation (2.1) are independent zero-mean white Gaussian noises with finite covariance matrices, i.e.,*

$$\mathbb{E} \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}(k) \\ \mathbf{w}(k) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}^\top(\ell) & \mathbf{w}^\top(\ell) \end{bmatrix} \right\} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{S}^\top \\ \mathbf{S} & \mathbf{Q} \end{bmatrix} \delta_{k\ell} \quad (2.21)$$

where $\delta_{k\ell}$ is the Kronecker delta function (see Eq. (2.15)).

Assumption 2.2 *The LTI state-space system (2.1) is minimal, i.e., the pair (\mathbf{A} , \mathbf{C}) is observable and the pair (\mathbf{A} , $[\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{Q}^{1/2}]$) is controllable.*

the following theorem can be stated [Anderson and Moore, 1990].

Theorem 2.1 *Consider the LTI system (2.1) and assume that the hypotheses 2.1 and 2.2 are satisfied. Then,*

- *the Kalman filter is expressed as*

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t+1) = \mathbf{A}\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathcal{K}(t)(\mathbf{y}(t) - \mathbf{C}\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t) - \mathbf{D}\mathbf{u}(t)), \quad (2.22)$$

- *the error covariance matrix satisfies the Riccati equation*

$$\mathbf{P}(t+1) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{P}(t)\mathbf{A}^\top + \mathbf{Q} - \left(\mathbf{S} + \mathbf{A}\mathbf{P}(t)\mathbf{C}^\top \right) \left(\mathbf{R} + \mathbf{C}\mathbf{P}(t)\mathbf{C}^\top \right)^{-1} \left(\mathbf{S} + \mathbf{A}\mathbf{P}(t)\mathbf{C}^\top \right)^\top, \quad (2.23)$$

- *the Kalman gain matrix $\mathcal{K}(t)$ satisfies*

$$\mathcal{K}(t) = \left(\mathbf{S} + \mathbf{A}\mathbf{P}(t)\mathbf{C}^\top \right) \left(\mathbf{R} + \mathbf{C}\mathbf{P}(t)\mathbf{C}^\top \right)^{-1}, \quad (2.24)$$

- *the conditional expectation of the output signal $\mathbf{y}(t)$ is expressed as*

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}(t) = \mathbf{C}\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t) + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{u}(t). \quad (2.25)$$

Furthermore, for any symmetric initial condition $\mathbf{P}(0) > \mathbf{0}$,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathbf{P}(t) = \mathbf{P} > \mathbf{0} \quad (2.26)$$

where \mathbf{P} satisfies

$$\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{P}\mathbf{A}^\top + \mathbf{Q} - \left(\mathbf{S} + \mathbf{A}\mathbf{P}\mathbf{C}^\top \right) \left(\mathbf{R} + \mathbf{C}\mathbf{P}\mathbf{C}^\top \right)^{-1} \left(\mathbf{S} + \mathbf{A}\mathbf{P}\mathbf{C}^\top \right)^\top. \quad (2.27)$$

Moreover, this matrix \mathbf{P} is unique and the deduced Kalman gain matrix \mathcal{K} defined as

$$\mathcal{K} = \left(\mathbf{S} + \mathbf{A}\mathbf{P}\mathbf{C}^\top \right) \left(\mathbf{R} + \mathbf{C}\mathbf{P}\mathbf{C}^\top \right)^{-1} \quad (2.28)$$

ensures that the matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{A} - \mathcal{K}\mathbf{C}$ satisfies

$$\lambda_{\max}(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}) < 1 \quad (2.29)$$

where $\lambda_{\max}(\mathbf{A})$ denotes the eigenvalue of \mathbf{A} of maximum modulus.

In this time-invariant framework, the Kalman filter induces two important consequences as far as system identification is concerned.

- First, by following the lines of [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1996a, Appendix A.5, pp. 207–210], the (non-steady-state) Kalman filter can be written as a linear combination of past inputs, past outputs and an initial state estimate through the following theorem (see also [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1994])

Theorem 2.2 *Given $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(0)$, $\mathbf{P}(0)$, samples of the input and output signals on the time range $[0, t]$, i.e., $\{\mathbf{u}(k)\}_{k=0}^t$ and $\{\mathbf{y}(k)\}_{k=0}^t$ and all the matrices $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ as well as the variance matrices $(\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{S}, \mathbf{Q})$, then the Kalman filter state $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t)$ can be written as*

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{x}}(t) = & (\mathbf{A}^t - \Delta_t \Gamma_t(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})) \hat{\mathbf{x}}(0) + \Delta_t \mathbf{y}_t^-(t) \\ & + (\Omega_t(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) - \Delta_t \mathbf{H}_t(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})) \mathbf{u}_t^-(t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.30)$$

where $\Omega_t(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_u t}$ is the (reversed) extended controllability matrix of the system, where $\Gamma_t(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C}) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y t \times n_x}$ is the extended observability matrix of the system, where $\mathbf{H}_t(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y t \times n_u t}$ is a Toeplitz matrix defined as in Eq. (2.10) and where $\Delta_t \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_y t}$ can be defined by the following recursive formula

$$\Delta_t = [(\mathbf{A} - \mathcal{K}(t-1)\mathbf{C})\Delta_{t-1} \quad \mathcal{K}(t-1)]. \quad (2.31)$$

The main interest of this theorem is that the state sequence can be related to the past input and output data (and the memory of the system dynamics $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(0)$) with the help of the Kalman filter. As shown hereafter, this relation will lead to a data equation (see Eq. (2.58) or [Viberg, 1995] for a definition) gathering only input and output signals.

- Second, by assuming that the conditions 2.1 and 2.2 are satisfied, the process state-space form (2.1) is equivalent to the innovation form

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathcal{K}\mathbf{e}(t) \quad (2.32a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{e}(t) \quad (2.32b)$$

where \mathcal{K} is the steady-state Kalman filter gain defined in Theorem 2.1 and \mathbf{e} is called the innovation vector [Ljung, 1999a]. More precisely, the innovation vector \mathbf{e} is the part of \mathbf{y} which cannot be predicted from the past data, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{e}(t) = \mathbf{y}(t) - \hat{\mathbf{y}}(t) = \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}(t) - \hat{\mathbf{x}}(t)) + \mathbf{v}(t). \quad (2.33)$$

By construction (see Theorem 2.1), for any realization of \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{w} satisfying Assumption 2.1, a unique matrix \mathcal{K} and a unique vector \mathbf{e} exist such that the representations (2.1) and (2.32) have the same input-output behavior [Haverkamp, 2001]. Notice also that, although the Kalman gain is computed from the matrices $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ as well as the variance matrices $(\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{S}, \mathbf{Q})$ in a complicated manner (see Theorem 2.1), such an innovation form (deduced from Eq. (2.1)) verifies that all the eigenvalues of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{A} - \mathcal{K}\mathbf{C}$ are strictly inside the unit circle when Assumptions 2.1 and 2.2 are satisfied. Indeed [Kailath, 1980],

Lemma 2.1 *Given matrices $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$ and $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_x}$, if the pair (\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C}) is observable, then a matrix $\mathcal{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_y}$ exists such that $\mathbf{A} - \mathcal{K}\mathbf{C}$ is asymptotically stable.*

This property means that the system is strict minimum phase because [Peternell, 1995]

Proposition 2.1 *A stable system represented by the LTI state-space form (2.32) is strict minimum phase if and only if*

$$\lambda_{\max}(\mathbf{A} - \mathcal{K}\mathbf{C}) < 1. \quad (2.34)$$

As shown hereafter, this minimum phase property is really important in order to simplify some equations and is, in a way, the keystone for the recent closed-loop subspace-based identification techniques [Jansson, 2003, Chiuso and Picci, 2005a] (see Sub-Section 2.2.3 for details).

2.2.1.2 State sequence construction from infinite time series

In the previous paragraph, the state sequence (see Eq. (2.30)) has been written as a combination of finite input and output data sets plus a term involving the initial state estimate $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(0)$. This specificity implies that different Kalman filter sequences can be obtained according to the choice or the estimate of the initial state $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(0)$. This characteristic of the Kalman filter estimate (2.30) has given rise to different state-space subspace-based identification algorithms according to the way this initial state sequence is chosen by the user (see, e.g., [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1996a, Algorithms 1 and 2 of Chapter 4] for two major illustrations). Instead of resorting to the memory of the system dynamics $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(0)$, several authors, e.g., Peternell [Peternell, 1995] or Bauer [Bauer, 1998], have chosen to tackle the problem of the state sequence construction by considering infinite input and output time series. The starting

point of this approach is the state-space predictor form defined as [Qin, 2006]

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = \underbrace{(\mathbf{A} - \mathcal{K}\mathbf{C})}_{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}} \mathbf{x}(t) + \underbrace{(\mathbf{B} - \mathcal{K}\mathbf{D})}_{\tilde{\mathbf{B}}} \mathbf{u}(t) + \mathcal{K}\mathbf{y}(t) \quad (2.35a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{e}(t) \quad (2.35b)$$

which is obtained by substituting the innovation term in Eq. (2.32a) for $\mathbf{e}(t) = \mathbf{y}(t) - \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t) - \mathbf{D}\mathbf{u}(t)$. By defining q as the forward shift operator, *i.e.*,

$$q\mathbf{r}(t) = \mathbf{r}(t+1) \quad (2.36)$$

for a signal $\mathbf{r}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r}$, the state equation (2.35a) can be written as follows

$$(q\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}})\mathbf{x}(t) = \tilde{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathcal{K}\mathbf{y}(t). \quad (2.37)$$

Then, by assuming that the gain matrix \mathcal{K} is built so that Proposition 2.1 is satisfied (see Theorem 2.1), we get

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = (q\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}})^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{u}(t) + (q\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}})^{-1} \mathcal{K}\mathbf{y}(t) \quad (2.38)$$

or, in a different way,

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{j-1} \tilde{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{u}(t-j) + \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{j-1} \mathcal{K}\mathbf{y}(t-j) \quad (2.39)$$

by using the Neumann series [Golub and Van Loan, 1996]

$$(q\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} - \mathbf{A})^{-1} = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{A}^{j-1} q^{-j} \quad (2.40)$$

where q^{-1} stands for the backward shift operator. Thus, the state sequence can be constructed from past inputs and outputs, *i.e.*, two full rank matrices $\Omega_{\infty}(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathcal{K}) \in \mathbf{R}^{n_x \times \infty}$ and $\Omega_{\infty}(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \tilde{\mathbf{B}}) \in \mathbf{R}^{n_x \times \infty}$ exist such that

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \Omega_{\infty}(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathcal{K})\mathbf{y}^{-}(t) + \Omega_{\infty}(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \tilde{\mathbf{B}})\mathbf{u}^{-}(t) \quad (2.41)$$

where

$$\Omega_{\infty}(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathcal{K}) = [\cdots \quad \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^2 \mathcal{K} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \mathcal{K} \quad \mathcal{K}] \quad (2.42a)$$

$$\Omega_{\infty}(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \tilde{\mathbf{B}}) = [\cdots \quad \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^2 \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{B}}]. \quad (2.42b)$$

2.2.1.3 Approximated state sequence construction from finite time series

In practice, the user usually does not have access to infinite time series. Therefore, when finite input and output sequences are handled, approximations must be used. In order to introduce these approximations, a reformulation of the model (2.39) as follows is necessary

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}(t) = & \sum_{j=1}^p \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{j-1} \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{u}(t-j) + \sum_{j=1}^p \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{j-1} \mathcal{K} \mathbf{y}(t-j) \\ & + \sum_{j=p+1}^{\infty} \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{j-1} \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{u}(t-j) + \sum_{j=p+1}^{\infty} \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{j-1} \mathcal{K} \mathbf{y}(t-j) \end{aligned} \quad (2.43)$$

where $p \in \mathbb{N}_*^+$ is a user-defined parameter corresponding to the available "past"³ input and output data. By using the compact notations introduced beforehand, Eq. (2.43) can be rewritten as follows

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{\Omega}_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathcal{K}) \mathbf{y}_p^-(t) + \mathbf{\Omega}_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \tilde{\mathbf{B}}) \mathbf{u}_p^-(t) + \mathbf{v}(t) \quad (2.44)$$

where the error term $\mathbf{v}(t)$ is defined as

$$\mathbf{v}(t) = \sum_{j=p+1}^{\infty} \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{j-1} \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{u}(t-j) + \sum_{j=p+1}^{\infty} \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{j-1} \mathcal{K} \mathbf{y}(t-j). \quad (2.45)$$

Thus, given the observations $\mathbf{y}_p^-(t)$ and $\mathbf{u}_p^-(t)$, it is consistent to approximate the state sequence \mathbf{x} as follows

$$\bar{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{\Omega}_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathcal{K}) \mathbf{y}_p^-(t) + \mathbf{\Omega}_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \tilde{\mathbf{B}}) \mathbf{u}_p^-(t). \quad (2.46)$$

It is now important to assess the quality of this linear estimate $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ of the state sequence \mathbf{x} . First, the error term $\mathbf{v}(t) = \mathbf{x}(t) - \bar{\mathbf{x}}(t)$ is orthogonal to $\left[\mathbf{y}_p^{-\top}(t) \quad \mathbf{u}_p^{-\top}(t) \right]^\top$ [Bauer, 2003]. Second, from the system of equations corresponding to the predictor form (2.35) and standard recursions, it can be verified that

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^p \mathbf{x}(t-p) + \mathbf{\Omega}_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathcal{K}) \mathbf{y}_p^-(t) + \mathbf{\Omega}_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \tilde{\mathbf{B}}) \mathbf{u}_p^-(t). \quad (2.47)$$

³For many subspace-based identification algorithms [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1996a, Katayama, 2005, Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007], the present instant is denoted by t . Then, the past data is related to a user-defined integer p corresponding to the time instants $[t-p, \dots, t-1]$. Similarly, a user-defined integer f can be introduced in order to define the future data, *i.e.*, the time instants $[t, \dots, t+f-1]$.

Therefore, again, the state is a linear function of past input and output signals plus a prior value of the state. Furthermore, we can show that [Bauer, 2003]

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathbf{v}(t)\|_2 &= \left\| \mathbf{x}(t) - \mathbf{\Omega}_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathbf{\mathcal{K}})\mathbf{y}_p^-(t) - \mathbf{\Omega}_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \tilde{\mathbf{B}})\mathbf{u}_p^-(t) \right\|_2 \\ &= \left\| \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^p \mathbf{x}(t-p) \right\|_2 \leq \|\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^p\|_F \|\mathbf{x}(t-p)\|_2 \end{aligned} \quad (2.48)$$

where, for a vector $\mathbf{r}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r}$, $\|\mathbf{r}\|_2 = \sqrt{\mathbf{r}^\top \mathbf{r}}$ and, for a real square matrix \mathbf{A} , $\|\mathbf{A}\|_F = \sqrt{\text{tr}(\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A})}$ [Horn and Johnson, 1990]. A direct consequence of this relation combined with the strict minimum phase condition is that the error term

- can be small [Bauer, 2003] for a truncation index p chosen "sufficiently large",
- vanishes when $p \rightarrow \infty$.

Thus, the observer $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ can be viewed as the optimal linear estimate of \mathbf{x} (in the mean-square error sense) given $\mathbf{u}_p^-(t)$ and $\mathbf{y}_p^-(t)$ [Jansson and Wahlberg, 1996, Katayama, 2005]. Notice however that the asymptotic case ($p \rightarrow \infty$) is only of theoretical interest (and is needed to guarantee the consistency of the estimates introduced hereafter (see Sub-Sections 2.2.2 and 2.2.3)) and generally cannot be satisfied in the system identification framework. Hence, in practice, the tuning parameter p must be chosen

- large enough in order to ensure a small error,
- not too large in order to avoid a huge increase of the variance of the parameters when such a model is used for system identification.

A usual trade-off between bias and variance is thus necessary. This trade-off can be properly satisfied by minimizing specific Akaike information criteria such as those suggested, *e.g.*, in [Paternell, 1995, Chapter 6 and 8] or in [Kuersteiner, 2005]. For a lightly damped predictor form (2.35), p must be chosen very large in order to satisfy $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^i = \mathbf{0}$ for $i \geq p$. Such a situation can lead to numerical problems when, *e.g.*, inversion of matrices with a size increasing with p is required. However, it is interesting to point out that the error can be arbitrarily small (even equal to zero) when

- the system to identify is strictly deterministic,
- an observer is introduced in order to create an additional freedom for the optimizer (similar to what was suggested in [Juang et al., 1993, Phan et al., 1995] or more recently in [Houtzager et al., 2009b]).

Both cases are shortly described in the following two paragraphs.

Deterministic system In this paragraph, let us assume that the noise sequences \mathbf{v} , \mathbf{w} and by extension \mathbf{e} are equal to zero, *i.e.*, the system to identify is deterministic. Then, the system dynamics satisfy

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(t) \quad (2.49a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{u}(t). \quad (2.49b)$$

By iterating the state equation (2.49a), it is straightforward that

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{A}^{n_x}\mathbf{x}(t-n_x) + \mathbf{\Omega}_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B})\mathbf{u}_{n_x}^-(t). \quad (2.50)$$

By using combinations of Eq. (2.49a) and (2.49b), it is found that

$$\mathbf{y}_{n_x}^-(t) = \mathbf{\Gamma}_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})\mathbf{x}(t-n_x) + \mathbf{H}_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})\mathbf{u}_{n_x}^-(t). \quad (2.51)$$

Now, by assuming that the system is observable, then

$$\text{rank}(\mathbf{\Gamma}_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})) = n_x \quad (2.52)$$

and the observability matrix has, at least, n_x linearly independent rows. By assuming⁴ that the first n_x rows of $\mathbf{\Gamma}_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})$ are linearly independent, $\mathbf{\Gamma}_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})[1 : n_x, :]$ is a square full rank matrix⁵. Thus, we can write that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}(t-n_x) &= \mathbf{\Gamma}_{n_x}^{-1}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})[1 : n_x, :]\mathbf{y}_{n_x}^-(t)[1 : n_x, :] \\ &\quad - \mathbf{\Gamma}_{n_x}^{-1}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})[1 : n_x, :]\mathbf{H}_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})[1 : n_x, :]\mathbf{u}_{n_x}^-(t). \end{aligned} \quad (2.53)$$

Then, by gathering Eq. (2.50) and (2.53), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}(t) &= \mathbf{A}^{n_x}\mathbf{\Gamma}_{n_x}^{-1}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})[1 : n_x, :]\mathbf{y}_{n_x}^-(t)[1 : n_x, :] + (\mathbf{\Omega}_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) \\ &\quad - \mathbf{A}^{n_x}\mathbf{\Gamma}_{n_x}^{-1}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})[1 : n_x, :]\mathbf{H}_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})[1 : n_x, :])\mathbf{u}_{n_x}^-(t). \end{aligned} \quad (2.54)$$

This last equation shows that the state sequence can be formulated as a linear combination of finite past input time series and finite past output time series without any approximation. An equivalent result, *i.e.*, without approximation, can be obtained for SISO ARX systems as proved in [Wahlberg and Jansson, 1994].

⁴This assumption is satisfied for any observable MISO system. For a MIMO system, the selection of n_x linearly independent rows among the $n_y f$ composing $\mathbf{\Gamma}_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})$ can be made as explained in Section 3.2.2 (see Chapter 3).

⁵ $\mathbf{A}[i : j, k : \ell]$ is the matrix composed of the coefficients present at the intersection of the rows i to j and the columns k to ℓ of the matrix \mathbf{A} .

System with a user-defined observer In the general case, *i.e.*, when MIMO stochastic processes are involved, the state sequence cannot be exactly recovered from finite data sets and approximations such as Eq. (2.46), must be handled. The main problem with the approximation (2.46) is that the error term $v(t) = \mathbf{x}(t) - \bar{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^p \mathbf{x}(t-p)$ indirectly depends on the Kalman gain matrix \mathcal{K} which, by construction,

- is time-invariant only asymptotically,
- is related to the stochastic properties of the system via the matrices \mathbf{Q} , \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{S} defined in Assumption 2.1 and, so, cannot be freely chosen by the user,
- requires to solve a Riccati equation.

These drawbacks make the assertion $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^p = \mathbf{0}$ difficult to verify for a finite tuning parameter p . In order to circumvent this difficulty, a user-defined observer gain $\mathbf{\Lambda} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_y}$ (which exists because the system is observable) is introduced in [Juang et al., 1993] so that the predictor form becomes

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{x}(t) + \tilde{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathcal{K}\mathbf{y}(t) + \mathbf{\Lambda}(\mathbf{y}(t) - \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t) - \mathbf{D}\mathbf{u}(t)) \quad (2.55a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{e}(t) \quad (2.55b)$$

or, more compactly,

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = \underbrace{(\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{C})}_{\check{\mathbf{A}}}\mathbf{x}(t) + \underbrace{(\mathbf{B} - \mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{D})}_{\check{\mathbf{B}}}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathcal{K}\mathbf{e}(t) + \mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{y}(t) \quad (2.56a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{e}(t). \quad (2.56b)$$

Then, it can be shown that this model satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}(t) = & \check{\mathbf{A}}^p \mathbf{x}(t-p) + \mathbf{\Omega}_p(\check{\mathbf{A}}, \mathbf{\Lambda}) \mathbf{y}_p^-(t) \\ & + \mathbf{\Omega}_p(\check{\mathbf{A}}, \check{\mathbf{B}}) \mathbf{u}_p^-(t) + \mathbf{\Omega}_p(\check{\mathbf{A}}, \mathcal{K}) \mathbf{e}_p^-(t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.57)$$

where $\mathbf{e}_p^-(t)$ is defined like, *e.g.*, $\mathbf{u}_p^-(t)$. By comparing the state sequence in Eq. (2.57) with Eq. (2.47), it is interesting to point out that

- the contribution of $\mathbf{x}(t-p)$ can be made arbitrarily small with the observer-predictor form (2.56) by placing the eigenvalues of the matrix $\check{\mathbf{A}}$ in any desired configuration. This can be done with a smaller value of the user-defined parameter p than when the standard predictor form (2.35) is used. Indeed, because the system is observable, the matrix gain $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ can be chosen (by the user) so that the eigenvalues of $\check{\mathbf{A}}$ are assigned arbitrarily, *e.g.*, at the origin (leading to a deadbeat observer [Valcher and Willems, 1999]),

- the state sequence (2.57) involves past input and output signals (via the vectors $\mathbf{u}_p^-(t)$ and $\mathbf{y}_p^-(t)$) as well as past innovation terms $\mathbf{e}_p^-(t)$. As shown hereafter (see Sub-Section 2.2.2), this last term can make the estimation phase more complicated than with the standard predictor form (2.35). Standard optimization methods, such as the extended least-squares algorithm [Söderström and Stoica, 1989, Ljung, 1999a], can be adapted in order to circumvent this difficulty (see [Houtzager et al., 2009b] for details).

Remark 2.3 *When the user-defined integer p is chosen such that $\check{\mathbf{A}}^i = \mathbf{0}$ (or $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^i = \mathbf{0}$) for $i \geq p$, the (non-zero) initial conditions can be neglected. It is then possible to focus on the steady-state solutions.*

2.2.1.4 To sum up

The three previous paragraphs have introduced different ways to express the state sequence of the LTI state-space system (2.32). By having access to this state sequence, the second step of the linear regression-based subspace identification methods addresses the estimation of the state-space matrices ($\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}$) and possibly the Kalman gain \mathcal{K} (up to a similarity transformation) given realizations $\{\mathbf{u}(t)\}_{t=1}^N$ and $\{\mathbf{y}(t)\}_{t=1}^N$ of the input and output signals on a finite but sufficiently wide time horizon N . This problem is investigated in Sub-Section 2.2.2 and 2.2.3. More precisely, solutions dedicated to open-loop systems are first described⁶ in Sub-Section 2.2.2. Extensions to systems operating in closed-loop are then introduced in Sub-Section 2.2.3.

2.2.2 Subspace-based identification using linear regression for systems operating in open-loop

For $f \in \mathbb{N}_*^+$ a user-defined integer⁷, the starting point of most of the subspace-based identification methods available in the literature is the following data equation [Viberg, 1995]

$$\mathbf{y}_f^+(t) = \mathbf{\Gamma}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{H}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})\mathbf{u}_f^+(t) + \mathbf{H}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathcal{K}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{I}_{n_y})\mathbf{e}_f^+(t). \quad (2.58)$$

Because this sub-section is dedicated to the identification of systems working in open-loop, the following assumptions will be satisfied hereafter.

⁶This overview can be considered as a combination of results available mainly in [Peterzell, 1995, Bauer, 2003, 2005]. Notice that Bauer also surveyed the most relevant asymptotic properties of the subspace estimators in [Bauer, 2003, 2005].

⁷Most of the equations introduced hereafter are accurate for any value of f . However, for rank constraint reasons, it is assumed that f is chosen such that $f \geq n_x$.

Assumption 2.3 *The system represented by the LTI state-space form (2.32) is (asymptotically) stable, i.e.,*

$$\lambda_{\max}(\mathbf{A}) < 1. \quad (2.59)$$

Assumption 2.4 *The system represented by the LTI state-space form (2.32) is strict minimum phase, i.e.,*

$$\lambda_{\max}(\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{K}\mathbf{C}) < 1. \quad (2.60)$$

Assumption 2.5 *The noise terms \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{w} are zero-mean and statistically independent of the input \mathbf{u} . By extension, the innovation \mathbf{e} is zero-mean and statistically independent of the input \mathbf{u} .*

2.2.2.1 Unconstrained least-squares solutions

The central idea of the regression-based techniques is to substitute the approximation (2.47) (or (2.57)) for the state sequence \mathbf{x} in Eq. (2.58). More precisely, after straightforward manipulations of the matrices involved in Eq. (2.47) (or Eq. (2.57)) and Eq. (2.58), the combination of Eq. (2.47) (or Eq. (2.57)) and Eq. (2.58) leads to the following compact equation [Paternell et al., 1996, Jansson and Wahlberg, 1998, Qin, 2006]

$$\mathbf{y}_f^+(t) = \underbrace{\Gamma_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})\Omega_p(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B})}_{\mathbf{L}_{f,p}} \mathbf{z}_p^-(t) + \underbrace{\mathbf{H}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})}_{\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u}} \mathbf{u}_f^+(t) + \mathbf{n}_f^+(t) \quad (2.61)$$

where

$$\mathbf{z}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y}(t) \\ \mathbf{u}(t) \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y+n_u} \quad (2.62)$$

and, by extension, $\mathbf{z}_p^- \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_u+n_y)p}$ and where \mathcal{A} , \mathcal{B} and $\mathbf{n}_f^+(t)$ are defined as follows

$$\mathcal{A} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \quad \mathcal{B} = [\mathbf{K} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{B}}] \quad (2.63)$$

$$\mathbf{n}_f^+(t) = \underbrace{\mathbf{H}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{I}_{n_y})}_{\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,e}} \mathbf{e}_f^+(t) + \Gamma_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^p \mathbf{x}(t-p) \quad (2.64)$$

when Eq. (2.47) is used or

$$\mathcal{A} = \check{\mathbf{A}} \quad \mathcal{B} = [\mathbf{A} \quad \check{\mathbf{B}}] \quad (2.65)$$

$$\mathbf{n}_f^+(t) = \mathbf{H}_f^{ol,e} \mathbf{e}_f^+(t) + \Gamma_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})\check{\mathbf{A}}^p \mathbf{x}(t-p) + \Gamma_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})\Omega_p(\check{\mathbf{A}}, \mathbf{K})\mathbf{e}_p^-(t) \quad (2.66)$$

when Eq. (2.57) is favored. Furthermore, by assuming that

- the assumptions 2.2, 2.4 and 2.5 are satisfied,
- the user-defined integer p and f are chosen at least greater than or equal to n_x and sufficiently large to ensure that the following assumptions are satisfied

Assumption 2.6 *The matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ is nilpotent of degree p , i.e., $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^i = \mathbf{0}$ for $i \geq p$,*

Assumption 2.7 *The matrix $\check{\mathbf{A}}$ is nilpotent of degree p , i.e., $\check{\mathbf{A}}^i = \mathbf{0}$ for $i \geq p$,*

then

- the terms $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^p \mathbf{x}(t-p)$ and $\check{\mathbf{A}}^p \mathbf{x}(t-p)$ are negligible,
- the noise term $\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,e} \mathbf{e}_f^+(t)$ is uncorrelated with $\mathbf{z}_p^-(t)$ as well as $\mathbf{u}_f^-(t)$,
- the following geometric properties are satisfied [Jansson and Wahlberg, 1998, Bauer, 2005]

$$\text{rank}(\mathbf{L}_{f,p}) = n_x \quad (2.67a)$$

$$\text{col}(\mathbf{L}_{f,p}) = \text{col}(\mathbf{\Gamma}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})) \quad (2.67b)$$

where $\text{col}(\bullet)$ is the space generated by the columns of \bullet .

These latter structural properties could be taken into account for the subspace estimation step.

Before describing several subspace-based identification algorithms developed to estimate the subspaces $\mathbf{L}_{f,p}$ and $\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,e}$ (under constraints), the data equations introduced must be slightly modified. More precisely, given input and output data on a finite but sufficiently wide time horizon, future and past Hankel matrices of the signals involved in Eq. (2.61) can be defined⁸ (see Eq. (2.7) for an explicit definition) and the vector data equation (2.61) becomes the matrix data equation⁹

$$\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ = \mathbf{L}_{f,p} \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- + \mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u} \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ + \mathbf{N}_{f,M}^+ \quad (2.68)$$

with $\mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_u+n_y)f \times M}$. This matrix data equation lies at the core of the subspace-based identification idea and the dedicated algorithms [Bauer, 2005].

⁸ M is defined in a way to be compatible with the full number of input-output measurements.

⁹The time index is dropped when this index is not necessary for the understanding of the equations.

Remark 2.4 *In this chapter, it has been chosen to work with Hankel matrices. This choice is shared by many standard subspace-based identification methods [Viberg, 1995, Van Overschee and De Moor, 1996a, Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007]. Recently, rather than working with (infinite) Hankel matrices, a stochastic framework based on specific Hilbert spaces of random variables generated by the signals involved in the identification problem has been considered by Bauer [Bauer, 2003, 2005], Chiuso and Picci [Chiuso and Picci, 2002, 2003] and Katayama [Katayama, 2005] (to cite only the main contributions). By doing so, a new geometric interpretation of the subspace-based identification approach can be suggested (see, e.g., [Chiuso and Picci, 2005a, Katayama, 2005] for important details concerning the definitions and the notations involved in this stochastic framework). As claimed in [Chiuso and Picci, 2002], "the stochastic realization theory lies at the ground of the subspace-based identification". Such a stochastic setting has indeed several advantages. First, it can be really beneficial for the derivation of some asymptotic properties of the subspace estimators [Bauer, 2003]. Indeed, as shown by Chiuso in most of his contributions [Chiuso and Picci, 2004a,c, Chiuso, 2007b, 2010] dedicated to the subspace-based identification, a generalization of the well-established theory for time-series can be performed in the subspace-based identification framework (with exogenous inputs) thanks to the close link between the stochastic realization theory and several geometric tools involved in subspace-based identification. Most of the steps used in the standard subspace-based identification methods as well as some linear algebra tools (e.g., the oblique projection) can be viewed as sampled versions of certain operations used in the stochastic realization theory [Chiuso and Picci, 2002]. Second, from a practical point of view, the use of vector equations (instead of matrix equations) can be convenient when, e.g., huge data sets are involved or missing values as well as outliers are present in the data sets. Some of these benefits have been highlighted in [Bauer, 1998, 2003]. These interesting theoretical and practical properties can be translated into the sampled data matrix framework considered hereafter by noticing that an Hilbert space related to a zero-mean random variable \mathbf{r} (used in the stochastic realization theory) can be replaced by the row space of $\mathbf{R}_{p,M}^-$ and $\mathbf{R}_{f,M}^+$ (see [Katayama, 2005] for details).*

As claimed previously and shown, e.g., in [Houtzager et al., 2009b], the estimation of the matrices $\mathbf{L}_{f,p}$ and $\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u}$ from Eq. (2.68) is more or less complex according to the state sequence approximation used in the regression problem. Indeed, according to the use of Eq. (2.47) or Eq. (2.57) in Eq. (2.58), two different noise terms can be deduced (see Eq. (2.64) and Eq. (2.66)). Now, when Assumption 2.6 and Assumption 2.7 are satisfied, the noise terms (2.64) and (2.66) differ from the presence of a past innovation stacked vector \mathbf{e}_p^- . The problem with this noise contribution is that \mathbf{e}_p^- can be correlated with the past output data involved in \mathbf{z}_p^- . Thus, a standard least-squares opti-

mization applied to Eq. (2.68) with $\mathbf{N}_{f,M}^+$ built from Eq. (2.66) will lead to biased estimates. In order to circumvent this difficulty, the application of the well-known extended least-squares technique [Ljung, 1999a] or a dedicated instrumental variable method [Söderström and Stoica, 1989] can be considered. For instance, a recursive extended least-squares algorithm is suggested in [Houtzager et al., 2009b] for systems operating in closed-loop. Because the aforementioned estimation schemes can be viewed as well-established extensions of the ordinary least-squares, the rest of this section will only focus on the linear problem (2.68) involving

$$\mathbf{n}_f^+(t) = \mathbf{H}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathcal{K}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{I}_{n_y})\mathbf{e}_f^+(t) \quad (2.69)$$

as the residuals. The reader interested by the extended least-squares approach is advised to study [Houtzager et al., 2009b] and the references therein.

By recalling that this vector \mathbf{n}_f^+ (and by extension the residual matrix $\mathbf{N}_{f,M}^+$) is uncorrelated with \mathbf{z}_p^- and \mathbf{u}_f^+ , a natural way to estimate the matrices $\mathbf{L}_{f,p}$ and $\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u}$ consists in minimizing the least-squares cost function

$$V(\mathbf{L}_{f,p}, \mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u}) = \left\| \mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{L}_{f,p} & \mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \\ \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix} \right\|_F. \quad (2.70)$$

This criterion measures the quality of the prediction of the future outputs $\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+$ from a linear combination of the past input and output data $\mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^-$ and the future inputs $\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+$ [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1996a]. Many solutions (and several alternative versions) are available in the literature [Peterzell et al., 1996, Jansson and Wahlberg, 1996, Qin and Ljung, 2003a] in order to solve such a least-squares regression. The main steps composing these contributions are summed up in the following. The interested reader can study [Bauer, 2005, Qin, 2006] and the references cited in these articles in order to complete this brief overview.

Remark 2.5 *In the following, several (constrained) least-squares estimates are introduced. Only theoretical solutions for these least-squares optimization problems are given. The efficient implementation of these solutions is not addressed in this manuscript. A reliable implementation of a least-squares algorithm requires the use of robust numerical tools such as, e.g., the RQ factorization. The interested reader can study, e.g., [Söderström and Stoica, 1989, Chapter 4], [Golub and Van Loan, 1996] or [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007, Chapter 2] for details about the computational aspects.*

Ordinary least-squares solutions A standard way to minimize the cost function (2.70) consists in using an ordinary least-squares estimate [Pternell et al., 1996]

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p} & \hat{\mathbf{H}}_f^{ol,u} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \\ \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix}^\top \left(\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \\ \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \\ \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix}^\top \right)^{-1} \quad (2.71)$$

because, under open-loop conditions,

$$\lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{M} \mathbf{N}_{f,M}^+ \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ & \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \end{bmatrix}^\top = \mathbf{0}. \quad (2.72)$$

This solution requires that

$$\text{rank} \left(\lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \\ \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \\ \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix}^\top \right) = n_u(p + f) + n_y p. \quad (2.73)$$

This rank constraint can be satisfied under mild conditions on the input signals \mathbf{u} acting on the system (see [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007, Lemma 9.9] for details). Alternatively, because the knowledge of $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_f^{ol,u}$ can be useless for the extraction of the state-space matrices estimates, this least-squares problem can be broken down into two steps [Pternell et al., 1996, Jansson and Wahlberg, 1996]:

- elimination of the forced response by applying an orthogonal projection of the row space of $\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+$ onto the complement of the row space of $\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+$, *i.e.*,

$$\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp = \mathbf{L}_{f,p} \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp + \mathbf{N}_{f,M}^+ \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \quad (2.74)$$

where¹⁰

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp = \mathbf{I}_{M \times M} - \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \left(\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+{}^\top \right)^{-1} \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+{}^\top. \quad (2.75)$$

This projection requires that the matrix $\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+$ has full row rank [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007],

- estimation of the subspace $\hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p}$ via a least-squares solution

$$\hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p} = \mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^-{}^\top \left(\mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^-{}^\top \right)^{-1}. \quad (2.76)$$

¹⁰This projection can be computed in a stable and efficient way by using a RQ factorization [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007].

By straightforward calculations, it can be shown that both solutions (2.71) and (2.76) lead to the same estimate of $\mathbf{L}_{f,p}$.

As usual in the subspace-based identification framework, several authors have suggested other solutions to the least-squares problem (2.70) by introducing different weighting matrices pre-multiplying and/or post-multiplying the solutions described beforehand. Bauer addresses this problem in [Bauer, 2005] and undertakes a comparison of the main techniques developed during the 1990's.

By recalling that the noise term $\mathbf{N}_{f,M}^+$ is equal to $\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,e} \mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+$, the residuals are not white. Thus, the least-squares estimators introduced previously are not minimum variance unbiased estimators. If an optimal estimator is sought, the standard solution for this correlation problem consists in resorting to a global least-squares method. This technique requires a prior estimate of the covariance matrix of the residuals and is, by construction, iterative. According to the studies available in [Paternell, 1995, Paternell et al., 1996], such an iterative solution can slightly improve the quality of the estimates of the state-space matrices computed from $\hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p}$. However, to the author's point of view, because the estimation of $\mathbf{L}_{f,p}$ is only an intermediate step, the use of a more complicated algorithm (than a standard least-squares one) should be restricted to the regression problems handling the observer-predictor form (2.56) and the matrix $\check{\mathbf{A}}$. Notice indeed that the residuals considered up until now are theoretically equal to $\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,e} \mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+ + \mathbf{\Gamma}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C}) \check{\mathbf{A}}^p [\mathbf{x}(t-p) \cdots \mathbf{x}(t+M-p-1)]$. As shown in [Houtzager et al., 2009b], verifying Assumption 2.6 in order to ensure an unbiased estimation requires to choose a large value¹¹ for the integer p . Now, it is well-known that increasing the value of p leads to an increase of the estimate variance. Thus, the development of an algorithm able to yield a minimum variance unbiased estimator for an estimation problem characterized by estimates with a large variance seems to be not so essential. This variance problem should be less annoying with the observer-predictor form (2.56) because the user controls the dynamic of $\check{\mathbf{A}}$.

Remark 2.6 *At this stage, it is interesting to emphasize the link between this approach and the standard subspace-based identification algorithms such as the MOESP class of methods [Verhaegen and Dewilde, 1992a,b, Verhaegen, 1993a, 1994, Chou and Verhaegen, 1997] or the N4SID algorithms [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1996a].*

First, let us consider the PO-MOESP algorithm [Verhaegen, 1994]. For this algorithm, a dedicated RQ factorization is introduced in order to apply an orthogonal projection as well as an instrumental variable. More precisely, the following

¹¹With the simulation example considered in [Houtzager et al., 2009b], the past window is at least three times larger with $\check{\mathbf{A}}$ than with \mathbf{A} .

RQ

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \\ \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \\ \mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{11} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{R}_{21} & \mathbf{R}_{22} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{R}_{31} & \mathbf{R}_{32} & \mathbf{R}_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Q}_1 \\ \mathbf{Q}_2 \\ \mathbf{Q}_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.77)$$

is considered where $\mathbf{R}_{11} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u f \times n_u f}$, $\mathbf{R}_{21} \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_u+n_y)p \times n_u f}$, $\mathbf{R}_{31} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y f \times n_u f}$, $\mathbf{R}_{22} \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_u+n_y)p \times (n_u+n_y)p}$, $\mathbf{R}_{32} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y f \times (n_u+n_y)p}$ and $\mathbf{R}_{33} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y f \times n_y f}$ are lower triangular matrices and $\mathbf{Q}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u f \times M}$, $\mathbf{Q}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{k p \times M}$ and $\mathbf{Q}_3 \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y f \times M}$ are orthogonal matrices. Then, by straightforward calculations, it can be shown that [Viberg, 1995]

$$\mathbf{R}_{32} \mathbf{Q}_2 = \mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \left(\mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \right)^{-1} \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp. \quad (2.78)$$

By comparing this equation with Eq. (2.76), it is obvious that

$$\mathbf{R}_{32} \mathbf{Q}_2 = \hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p} \mathcal{W}_r \quad (2.79)$$

with the weighting matrix $\mathcal{W}_r = \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp$. This equality can be summarized algebraically as follows

$$\text{col}(\mathbf{R}_{32}) = \text{col}(\hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p}). \quad (2.80)$$

Therefore, in addition to sharing the same mathematical tools¹², both methods are deeply correlated from a theoretical point of view.

Second, by defining the oblique projection of the row space of $\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+$ along the row space of $\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+$ on the row space of $\mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^-$ as follows¹³ [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1996a, Chapter 1]

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ / \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- &= \mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \left(\mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \right)^\dagger \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \\ &= \mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \left(\mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \right)^{-1} \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \end{aligned} \quad (2.81)$$

if $\mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp$ has full row rank, it is obvious that this oblique projection can be directly related to the least-squares solution (2.76). Indeed, by knowing the estimate $\hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p}$, the optimal prediction (in the least-squares sense) of the future

¹²Keep in mind that a least-squares minimization involves RQ factorizations.

¹³•[†] stands for the Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse of the matrix • [Golub and Van Loan, 1996].

Hankel matrix from the past input and output data satisfies

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{\mathbf{Y}}_{f,M}^+ &= \hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p} \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \\
 &= \mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^{-\top} \left(\mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^{-\top} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \quad (2.82) \\
 &= \mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ / \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^-
 \end{aligned}$$

i.e., is exactly equal to the oblique projection of the row space of $\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+$ along the row space of $\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+$ on the row space of $\mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^-$. This observation is the main step of the combined deterministic-stochastic subspace-based identification procedure developed by Van Overschee and De Moor and known as the N4SID algorithm [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1996a, Chapter 4]. This observation is also the core of the Conditional Canonical Correlation Analysis algorithm developed by Katayama and explained in [Katayama, 2005, Chapter 10] (see Eq. (10.23)) as well as the recent Chiuso's developments and extensions to the systems operating in closed-loop (see [Chiuso and Picci, 2003, 2005a] for details concerning the importance of the oblique projection in stochastic realization theory).

2.2.2.2 Constrained least-squares solutions

Although the solutions (2.71) and (2.76) are asymptotically reliable and accurate [Peternell, 1995, Chapter 7], they suffer from drawbacks the user must be aware of. Most of them are listed in [Bauer, 2003]. The most important ones are probably the following ones.

- These solutions often require to fix a quite large past window in order to satisfy Assumption 2.6. Thus, in practice, with a finite value of p , biased estimates are generally obtained.
- They do not take into account the rank constraint $\text{rank}(\mathbf{L}_{f,p}) = n_x$ as well as the Toeplitz structure of $\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u}$. Indeed, the least-squares solutions (2.71) and (2.76) are full rank matrices.

While the bias problem¹⁴ cannot be solved theoretically without imposing $p \rightarrow \infty$, the rank constraint as well as the structure of $\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u}$ can be taken into account in the least-squares optimization.

¹⁴The reader must remember that using an observer-predictor form can be a solution to solve this problem because, by choosing the observer gain $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ correctly, Assumption 2.7 can be satisfied with a small value of p .

Improvements for the calculation of $\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u}$ As far as the Toeplitz structure of $\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u}$ is concerned, three main solutions are available in the literature [Paternell et al., 1996, Shi, 2001, Qin and Ljung, 2003b].

The first one is based on a rewriting of the least-squares problem (2.70) by applying the vectorization operator [Golub and Van Loan, 1996] in order to remove the zero entries in the Toeplitz matrix $\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u}$. More precisely, by vectorizing Eq. (2.68) and by using standard properties of this operator, it holds that

$$\text{vec}(\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+) = \left(\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \\ \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix} \otimes \mathbf{I} \right) \text{vec} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{L}_{f,p} & \mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u} \end{bmatrix} \right) + \text{vec}(\mathbf{N}_{f,M}^+). \quad (2.83)$$

Then, a matrix $\mathbf{\Pi}$ (composed of zeros and ones) can be constructed such that [Paternell et al., 1996]

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{\Pi} \text{vec}(\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{D} & \mathbf{CB} & \dots & \mathbf{CA}^{f-2}\mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix}) \\ = \text{vec} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{D} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{CB} & \mathbf{D} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{CA}^{f-2}\mathbf{B} & \dots & \mathbf{CB} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.84)$$

The combination of both previous equations leads to a constrained least-squares estimate which can be solved by using dedicated tools (see [Paternell et al., 1996] for details).

The second solution, also available in [Paternell et al., 1996], is based on a two-step procedure. By assuming that estimates of $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ are available (for instance by using the ordinary least-squares approach introduced beforehand), estimates of the Markov parameters composing the Toeplitz matrix $\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u}$ can be constructed and, by extension, an estimate of $\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u}$ can be built. Then, the matrix $\mathbf{L}_{f,p}$ can be estimated by knowing $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_f^{ol,u}$ from the least-squares criterion

$$\bar{V}(\mathbf{L}_{f,p}) = \left\| \mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ - \hat{\mathbf{H}}_f^{ol,u} \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ - \mathbf{L}_{f,p} \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \right\|_F. \quad (2.85)$$

In order to improve the estimation, this iterative technique can be repeated many times. As shown in the simulation examples of [Paternell, 1995], this approach is efficient and does not require many runs to yield accurate estimates.

The third technique, initially introduced in [Qin and Ljung, 2003b], is a parallel reformulation of the least-squares problem. This reformulation allows the suppression of the non-causal terms which appear in the matrix data

equation. In order to see this feature, let us consider the following block-wise decompositions

$$\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ = \begin{bmatrix} {}^1\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \\ {}^2\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \\ \vdots \\ {}^f\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ = \begin{bmatrix} {}^1\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \\ {}^2\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \\ \vdots \\ {}^f\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.86a)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u} = \begin{bmatrix} {}^1\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u} \\ {}^2\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u} \\ \vdots \\ {}^f\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u} \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{L}_{f,p} = \begin{bmatrix} {}^1\mathbf{L}_{f,p} \\ {}^2\mathbf{L}_{f,p} \\ \vdots \\ {}^f\mathbf{L}_{f,p} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.86b)$$

with ${}^i\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u \times M}$, ${}^i\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times M}$, ${}^i\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_{uf}}$ and ${}^i\mathbf{L}_{f,p} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times (n_u + n_y)p}$, $i \in \{1, f\}$. Then, for each $i \in \{1, f\}$,

$${}^i\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ = {}^i\mathbf{L}_{f,p}\mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- + {}^i\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u}\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ + {}^i\mathbf{N}_{f,M}^+. \quad (2.87)$$

When we look closer at $\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u}$, it is obvious that

$$\begin{bmatrix} {}^1\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u} \\ {}^2\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u} \\ \vdots \\ {}^f\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{D} & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{CB} & \mathbf{D} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{CA}^{f-2}\mathbf{B} & \cdots & \mathbf{CB} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.88)$$

Thus, the last columns of ${}^i\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u}$ are all composed of zeros except for ${}^f\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u}$. By taking into account this characteristic, Eq. (2.87) becomes¹⁵

$${}^i\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ = {}^i\mathbf{L}_{f,p}\mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- + \underbrace{[\mathbf{CA}^{i-2}\mathbf{B} \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{CB} \quad \mathbf{D}]}_{{}^i\bar{\mathbf{H}}_f^{ol,u}} \begin{bmatrix} {}^1\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \\ {}^2\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \\ \vdots \\ {}^i\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix} + {}^i\mathbf{N}_{f,M}^+, \quad i \in \{1, f\} \quad (2.89)$$

by removing the terms which involve the zero-block matrices of $\mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u}$. The corresponding input signals $({}^{i+1}\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+, \dots, {}^f\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+)$ are future signals with

¹⁵For $i = 1$, ${}^i\bar{\mathbf{H}}_f^{ol,u} = \mathbf{D}$.

respect to ${}^i\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+$. Thus, when a fully-parameterized Toeplitz matrix is considered, the matrix data equation (2.68) contains non-causal terms. The approach based on Eq. (2.89) excludes these non-causal terms and, in a way, makes the model "more identifiable". As previously, the matrices ${}^i\mathbf{L}_{f,p}$ and ${}^i\bar{\mathbf{H}}_f^{ol,u}$ can be estimated for $i \in \{1, f\}$ from Eq. (2.89) as a least-squares problem, the solution of which is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} {}^i\hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p} \\ {}^i\hat{\mathbf{H}}_f^{ol,u} \end{bmatrix} = {}^i\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \\ {}^1\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \\ {}^2\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \\ \vdots \\ {}^i\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix}^\dagger \quad (2.90)$$

where \bullet^\dagger stands for the Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse of the matrix \bullet [Golub and Van Loan, 1996]. Finally, by stacking all the estimates ${}^i\hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p}$ and ${}^i\hat{\mathbf{H}}_f^{ol,u}$ for $i \in \{1, f\}$, we get $\hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_f^{ol,u}$.

Remark 2.7 *All these solutions yield estimates with a smaller asymptotic variance in comparison with the ordinary least-squares estimates obtained in Paragraph 2.2.2.1 [Peternell, 1995].*

Improvements by using a rank constraint Up until now, the rank constraint $\text{rank}(\mathbf{L}_{f,p}) = n_x$ has not been taken into account during the estimation procedure. Now, when the aforementioned least-squares algorithms are employed, full rank estimates $\hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p}$ are generated. In order to incorporate this prior restriction, a singular value decomposition of $\hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p}$ can be used. More precisely,

$$\mathbf{W}_l \hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p} \mathbf{W}_r = [\mathbf{u}_s \quad \mathbf{u}_n] \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_s & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \Sigma_n \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_s^\top \\ \mathbf{v}_n^\top \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.91)$$

where \mathbf{W}_l and \mathbf{W}_r are weighting matrices chosen by the user in order to allow the construction of various estimates (see [Bauer, 2005] for a discussion about this problem). Herein, Σ_s contains the n_x largest singular values of $\mathbf{W}_l \hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p} \mathbf{W}_r$. Thus, we get

$$\hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p} = \mathbf{u}_s \Sigma_s \mathbf{v}_s^\top. \quad (2.92)$$

This SVD combined with the unconstrained regression introduced previously is a reduced rank regression approach [Bauer, 2003].

Remark 2.8 *Again, in relation to the comments made in Paragraph 2.2.2.1, the SVD (2.91) can be related to the SVD of \mathbf{R}_{32} applied in the PO-MOESP algorithm [Verhaegen, 1994] in order to extract the extended observability subspace.*

2.2.2.3 Extraction of the state-space matrices

In the literature, many solutions are available to extract the state-space matrices from the subspaces estimated beforehand [Bauer, 2005, Qin, 2006]. Again, two main basic ideas can be emphasized, the other developments being adapted versions of these main techniques. The first class of techniques aims at constructing a state sequence from $\hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p}$ and the past data. The second one tries to extract the observability subspace from $\hat{\mathbf{L}}_{f,p}$. Both are quickly described in the following.

State subspace approach As shown in Sub-Section 2.2.1, the state sequence can be related to past input and past output signals with the help of $\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])$ as follows

$$\bar{\mathbf{x}}(t) = [\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathcal{K}) \ \Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \tilde{\mathbf{B}})] \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y}_p^-(t) \\ \mathbf{u}_p^-(t) \end{bmatrix} = \Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}]) \mathbf{z}_p^-(t). \quad (2.93)$$

By getting back to the definition of $\mathbf{L}_{f,p}$, it is obvious that a rank n_x estimate of $\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])$ can be obtained from the SVD of $\mathbf{L}_{f,p}$ (see Eq. (2.91)). Indeed,

$$\hat{\Omega}_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}]) = \Sigma_s^{1/2} \mathbf{V}_s^\top \mathbf{W}_r^{-1}. \quad (2.94)$$

Thus, from $\hat{\Omega}_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])$, we can approximate the state sequence as follows

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \hat{\Omega}_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}]) \mathbf{z}_p^-(t). \quad (2.95)$$

This procedure can be adapted to get an accurate estimate of $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t+1)$ by using a shifted estimated state sequence [Bauer, 2003]. Alternatives have been suggested, *e.g.*, in [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1996a] or more recently in [Chiuso and Picci, 2004c]. For instance, the approach developed by Van Overschee and De Moor, which is based on specific non-steady state Kalman filters, relies on two different initial state vectors for $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t)$ and $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t+1)$ leading to unbiased estimates. See [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1994] and the discussion available in [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1996a, Chapter 4] for details. Now, by having access to $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t)$ as well as $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t+1)$, the state-space matrices can be estimated in one step from the least-squares fitting

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{A}} & \hat{\mathbf{B}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{C}} & \hat{\mathbf{D}} \end{bmatrix} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}} \sum_{k=1}^N \left\| \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{x}}(k+1) \\ \mathbf{y}(k) \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{C} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{x}}(k) \\ \mathbf{u}(k) \end{bmatrix} \right\|_2^2. \quad (2.96)$$

This least-squares estimation leads to consistent parameters when the length of the data set used for this linear regression tends to infinity. A two-step procedure is also available in the literature (see, *e.g.*, [Ljung and McKelvey, 1996a]).

Observability subspace approach By using the SVD (2.91) differently, the observability subspace $\text{range}(\Gamma_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C}))$ can be recovered. Indeed,

$$\hat{\Gamma}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C}) = \mathcal{W}_l^{-1} \mathcal{U}_s \Sigma_s^{1/2}. \quad (2.97)$$

Then, from $\hat{\Gamma}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})$, the matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{C} can be extracted as follows

$$\hat{\mathbf{C}} = \hat{\Gamma}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})[1 : n_y, :] \quad (2.98a)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{A}} = \hat{\Gamma}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})[n_y + 1 : \text{end}, :] \left(\hat{\Gamma}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})[1 : (f-1)n_y, :] \right)^\dagger. \quad (2.98b)$$

Finally, the matrices \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{D} can be estimated from the linear regression [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007]

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \left[\sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbf{u}^\top(\tau) \otimes \hat{\mathbf{C}} \hat{\mathbf{A}}^{t-\tau-1} \quad \mathbf{u}^\top(t) \otimes \mathbf{I}_{n_y \times n_y} \right] \begin{bmatrix} \text{vec}(\mathbf{B}) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbf{D}) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.99)$$

The aforementioned solutions can be viewed as the standard techniques used to extract the state-space matrices ($\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}$) from an estimate of the observability subspace. Many alternatives are suggested in the literature [Verhaegen, 1994, Van Overschee and De Moor, 1996a, Lovera, 1997, Delgado et al., 2004]. An interesting guideline is also available in [Chiuso and Picci, 2001].

Remark 2.9 *Again, according to the way the state-matrices ($\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}$) are estimated, many solutions can be put forward for the estimation of the Kalman gain \mathcal{K} . Basically, two main families can be pointed out. The first one resorts to dedicated Riccati equations and can be related to the stochastic realization theory. The second one relies on a residual technique, i.e., the Kalman gain \mathcal{K} is estimated from the variance of the residuals resulting from the least-squares problem (2.96). The interested reader can consult [Ljung and McKelvey, 1996a, Chiuso and Picci, 2001, Bauer, 2003, 2005, Qin, 2006] and the references therein for the most popular solutions. See also [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007, Chapter 9] for a method which leads to a guaranteed stabilizing estimate of \mathcal{K} .*

2.2.3 Subspace-based identification using linear regression for systems operating in closed-loop

In many situations, the data set used to identify the process must be collected under closed-loop conditions (see Fig. 2.1). Such an experimental procedure can be required for safety reasons (an unstable plant that requires control for instance) but also in order to maintain the quality of the production during the identification. Notice also that, in identification for control

Figure 2.1: Block diagram of a system \mathcal{S} operating in closed-loop with a controller \mathcal{C} .

[Van den Hof et al., 2009], interesting results (sometimes better than under open-loop conditions) can be obtained when the system works in closed-loop (linearization of the behavior of the plant, reduction of the tests duration, less restrictive excitation conditions, ...) [Gevers, 1997, 2006, Bombois et al., 2006, Barenthin et al., 2008].

As far as subspace-based identification for closed-loop systems is concerned, most of the standard algorithms have problems and give biased estimates when the data is collected in closed-loop (see [Ljung and McKelvey, 1996a, Lemma 1] for a proof). The problem inherent to the standard subspace-based identification algorithms under closed-loop conditions can be highlighted by considering again Eq. (2.61), *i.e.*, the vector data equation

$$\mathbf{y}_f^+(t) = \mathbf{L}_{f,p} \mathbf{z}_p^-(t) + \mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u} \mathbf{u}_f^+(t) + \mathbf{n}_f^+(t). \quad (2.100)$$

When the data is collected in open-loop, the noise term \mathbf{n}_f^+ and the future stacked input vector \mathbf{u}_f^+ are uncorrelated. Thus, in the open-loop framework, this least-squares-based problem can lead to unbiased estimates as shown previously in Sub-Section 2.2.2. When the system works in closed-loop, this property is no more satisfied because the feedback introduces a correlation between the input and the noise. Thus, biased estimates are obtained when open-loop MOESP [Verhaegen and Dewilde, 1992a,b, Verhaegen, 1993a], CVA [Larimore, 1990] or N4SID [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1994] algorithms are used with closed-loop data. The first attempts devoted to the closed-loop subspace-based identification have consisted in extending the MOESP or N4SID algorithms

- by modifying the instrumental variable used to decrease the noise effect [Verhaegen, 1993b, Chou and Verhaegen, 1997],
- by resorting to the prior knowledge available on the controller in order to adapt the open-loop N4SID algorithm with closed-loop data [Van Overschee and De Moor, 1997].

Interesting from a practical point of view, the contributions till the middle of the 1990's can be viewed as extensions of the standard open-loop methods. Recent developments have improved the performance of the subspace-based identification algorithms under closed-loop conditions [Ljung and McKelvey, 1996a, Jansson, 2003, Qin and Ljung, 2003a, Jansson, 2005, Chiuso and Picci, 2005a, Qin et al., 2005, Chiuso, 2007a, 2010]. Most of these techniques share the same basic idea and can perform similarly with closed-loop as well as open-loop data. These techniques can be classified as members of the direct approach class (see [Katayama, 2005, Chapter 11] for a definition of the standard classification of the closed-loop methods). Indeed, they practically ignore the existence of the feedback loop and try to estimate the transfer of the plant directly from the signals \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{y} (see Fig. 2.1). As highlighted by the studies available, e.g., in [Lin et al., 2005, Chiuso, 2006, Qin, 2006], these techniques

- use high-order ARX models (HOARX) at least in one step of the procedure,
- rewrite or modify the vector data equation (2.100) in order to uncorrelate the input signals and the noise term.

Three of them (the innovation estimation method (IEM) [Qin and Ljung, 2003a], the state-space ARX (SSARX) technique [Jansson, 2003] and the prediction-based subspace identification (PBSID) [Chiuso, 2007a] are introduced in the following of this sub-section. They can be considered as the best recent contributions for subspace-based closed-loop system identification and are at the heart of the main developments concerning subspace-based identification for LTI systems till the 2000's [Qin, 2006, Chiuso, 2007b, 2010].

Remark 2.10 *In the sequel, we will mainly focus on the PBSID_{opt} algorithm, i.e., the optimized version of the PBSID algorithm [Chiuso, 2007b]. However, because most of the theoretical developments and properties verified by this optimized algorithm have been initially proved for the un-optimized prediction-based subspace identification algorithm or the Whitening Filter Algorithm (WFA) [Chiuso and Picci, 2005a], the acronym PBSID will be mainly used in the following. These algorithms mainly differ from the way they are implemented. They are indeed asymptotically equivalent [Chiuso, 2007a,b, 2010].*

Because it is considered in the following that the system works in closed-loop, three conditions commonly used for the direct closed-loop state-space system identification are adopted hereafter.

Assumption 2.8 *The external excitation¹⁶ $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}_2 + \mathcal{C}(q^{-1})\mathbf{r}_1$ (see Fig. 2.1) is a zero-mean sequence*

¹⁶Most of the time, the signal \mathbf{r}_1 is fixed equal to zero for simplification.

- uncorrelated with the process noise \mathbf{w} and the measurement noise \mathbf{v} ,
- sufficiently persistently exciting [Söderström and Stoica, 1989, Ljung, 1999a].

Up until now, no assumption has been made concerning the correlation between the input \mathbf{u} and the noise sequences \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{w} . The good excitation property of the external excitation \mathbf{r} ensures that the input sequence \mathbf{u} has sufficient excitation in order to excite correctly the dynamics of the system to identify (see [Söderström and Stoica, 1989, Ljung, 1999a, Willems et al., 2005, Bombois et al., 2006] for a general discussion concerning the persistency of excitation).

Assumption 2.9 *The feedback loop contains at least one sample delay.*

Physically, Assumption 2.9 implies that the system or the controller has no direct feed-through. Theoretically, Assumption 2.9 ensures the identifiability of the transfer function of the plant \mathcal{S} (see [Gevers and Anderson, 1981, 1982] for a discussion about this property and the following consequences). Furthermore, it guarantees that the innovation sequence¹⁷ $\mathbf{e}(j)$ and the input $\mathbf{u}(k)$ are uncorrelated $\forall j \geq k$ [Lin et al., 2004].

Assumption 2.10 *The closed-loop system (see Fig. 2.1) is asymptotically stable.*

2.2.3.1 The innovation estimation method

As said previously, the main problem with closed-loop data is the correlation of the future inputs with the past output measurements or the past noise. Indeed, this correlation makes the traditional subspace-based identification methods biased. In order to bypass this difficulty, the innovation estimation method (IEM) [Qin and Ljung, 2003a] iteratively pre-estimates the past innovation sequence. Then, by using this estimate, the observability subspace can be extracted.

The starting point of the IEM is (again) the matrix data equation

$$\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ = \mathbf{L}_{f,p} \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- + \mathbf{H}_f^{ol,u} \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ + \mathbf{N}_{f,M}^+ \quad (2.101)$$

where (see Sub-Section 2.2.2.1)

$$\mathbf{N}_{f,M}^+ = \mathbf{H}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathcal{K}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{I}_{n_y}) \mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+ \quad (2.102)$$

and

$$\mathbf{H}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathcal{K}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{I}_{n_y}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n_y \times n_y} & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{C}\mathcal{K} & \mathbf{I}_{n_y \times n_y} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}^{f-2}\mathcal{K} & \cdots & \mathbf{C}\mathcal{K} & \mathbf{I}_{n_y \times n_y} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.103)$$

¹⁷Remember that the innovation sequence is a stationary zero-mean white noise process.

By resorting again to the row-block partitioning of (2.101) introduced in Paragraph 2.2.2.2, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
{}^i\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ &= \mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}^{i-1}\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])\mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- \\
&\quad + [\mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}^{i-2}\mathbf{B} \ \dots \ \mathbf{C}\mathbf{B}] \begin{bmatrix} {}^1\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \\ \vdots \\ {}^{i-1}\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{D} \ {}^i\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \\
&\quad + [\mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}^{i-2}\mathcal{K} \ \dots \ \mathbf{C}\mathcal{K} \ \mathbf{I}_{n_y \times n_y}] \begin{bmatrix} {}^1\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+ \\ \vdots \\ {}^i\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix}, \quad i \in \{1, f\}. \quad (2.104)
\end{aligned}$$

By looking closer at this equation, it is interesting to stress that the innovation matrix $\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+$ can be partitioned into two parts (corresponding to the past innovation $[{}^1\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+ \ \dots \ {}^{i-1}\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+]^\top$ and the future innovation ${}^i\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+$ respectively) thanks to the structure of the matrix $\mathbf{H}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathcal{K}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{I}_{n_y})$, *i.e.*,

$$\begin{aligned}
[\mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}^{i-2}\mathcal{K} \ \dots \ \mathbf{C}\mathcal{K} \ \mathbf{I}_{n_y \times n_y}] \begin{bmatrix} {}^1\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+ \\ \vdots \\ {}^i\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix} &= \\
[\mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}^{i-2}\mathcal{K} \ \dots \ \mathbf{C}\mathcal{K}] \begin{bmatrix} {}^1\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+ \\ \vdots \\ {}^{i-1}\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix} &+ {}^i\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+, \quad i \in \{1, f\}. \quad (2.105)
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, when $\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{0}$, by having access to an estimate of ${}^k\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+$, $k < i$, an unbiased estimate of $\mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}^{i-1}\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])$ can be calculated from closed-loop data through a straightforward linear regression because the future innovation ${}^i\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+$ is uncorrelated with $\mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^-$, ${}^k\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+$ and ${}^k\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+$, $k < i$, even under closed-loop conditions.

As said previously, this procedure requires the availability of an accurate estimate of ${}^k\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+$, $k < i$. To get this estimate, a multi-stage least-squares algorithm is suggested in [Qin and Ljung, 2003a]. The starting point is Eq. (2.104) for $i = 1$ with $\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{0}$, *i.e.*,

$${}^1\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ = \mathbf{C}\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])\mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^- + {}^1\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+ \quad (2.106)$$

which is a VARX¹⁸ (Vector Auto-Regressive with eXogenous inputs) model. In spite of the feedback, ${}^1\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+$ is uncorrelated with $\mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^-$. Thus, an unbiased

¹⁸A VARX model is similar to a high-order ARX model when SISO systems are handled.

estimate of $\mathbf{C}\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])$ can be obtained from closed-loop data as a least-squares estimate

$$\widehat{\mathbf{C}\Omega}_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}]) = {}^1\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^{-\dagger} \quad (2.107)$$

and a least-squares estimate of the innovation process is

$${}^1\hat{\mathbf{E}}_{f,M}^+ = \mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ - \widehat{\mathbf{C}\Omega}_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}]) \mathbf{Z}_{p,M}^-. \quad (2.108)$$

Then, by knowing ${}^1\hat{\mathbf{E}}_{f,M}^+$, unbiased estimates of $\mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])$ and ${}^2\mathbf{E}_{f,M}^+$ can be calculated from Eq. (2.104) for $i = 2$. This procedure is repeated iteratively for $i = 1$ to f . Finally, from the least-squares estimates of $\mathbf{C}\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])$, $\mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])$, ..., $\mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}^{f-1}\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])$, we can reconstruct

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C} \\ \mathbf{C}\mathbf{A} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}^{f-1} \end{bmatrix} \Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}]) = \Gamma_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C}) \Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}]). \quad (2.109)$$

As a final step, the observability subspace can be extracted through a weighted singular value decomposition (see Paragraph 2.2.2.2 for details). By knowing an accurate estimate of $\Gamma_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})$, the state-space matrices can be obtained by following the techniques described in Paragraph 2.2.2.3 .

2.2.3.2 Closed-loop subspace-based identification with Markov parameter pre-estimation

Although the previous technique is developed to deal with closed-loop data, the IEM can have numerical problems when unstable systems are handled [Lin et al., 2005, Chiuso and Picci, 2005a]. This drawback is mainly due to the direct use of the state matrix \mathbf{A} in Eq. (2.101) and, more problematic when unstable systems are involved, \mathbf{A}^i . In order to circumvent this difficulty, Jansson [Jansson, 2003, 2005], then Chiuso and Picci [Chiuso and Picci, 2005a,b], suggested using a predictor form instead of an innovation form of the system. More precisely, we consider

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{x}(t) + \tilde{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathcal{K}\mathbf{y}(t) \quad (2.110a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{e}(t) \quad (2.110b)$$

where

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{A} - \mathcal{K}\mathbf{C} \quad (2.111a)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{B}} = \mathbf{B} - \mathcal{K}\mathbf{D}. \quad (2.111b)$$

Indeed, as shown previously, one of the advantages of this form is that $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ can be constrained to be (exponentially) stable by fixing the gain \mathcal{K} correctly so that the eigenvalues of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ are as close to zero as possible (see, again, Assumption 2.6)

By iterating the equations composing Eq. (2.110), we get the vector data equation

$$\mathbf{y}_f^+(t) = \Gamma_f(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathbf{C})\mathbf{x}(t) + \underbrace{\mathbf{H}_f(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \tilde{\mathbf{B}}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})}_{\mathbf{H}_f^{cl,u}} \mathbf{u}_f^+(t) + \underbrace{\mathbf{H}_f(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathcal{K}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{0})}_{\mathbf{H}_f^{cl,y}} \mathbf{y}_f^+(t) + \mathbf{e}_f^+(t). \quad (2.112)$$

From the same set of equations, we know that

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^p \mathbf{x}(t-p) + \Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{B}}]) \mathbf{z}_p^-(t). \quad (2.113)$$

Then, with Assumption 2.6, similarly to the open-loop case, the contribution of $\mathbf{x}(t-p)$ can be neglected and the vector data equation (2.112) becomes

$$\mathbf{y}_f^+(t) = \Gamma_f(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathbf{C})\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{B}}]) \mathbf{z}_p^-(t) + \mathbf{H}_f^{cl,u} \mathbf{u}_f^+(t) + \mathbf{H}_f^{cl,y} \mathbf{y}_f^+(t) + \mathbf{e}_f^+(t) \quad (2.114)$$

with standard notations. Under closed-loop conditions, the future innovation \mathbf{e}_f^+ is correlated with the future stacked vectors \mathbf{y}_f^+ and \mathbf{u}_f^+ . In order to circumvent this difficulty, M. Jansson (who followed the work of Peternell on the CCA algorithm [Peternell, 1995]) was actually the first to suggest estimating the Toeplitz matrices $\mathbf{H}_f^{cl,u}$ and $\mathbf{H}_f^{cl,y}$ in a first phase, then using these estimates in order to circumvent this correlation problem [Jansson, 2003]. This basic idea is also shared by the PBSID algorithm developed by Chiuso [Chiuso, 2007a] (see Paragraph 2.2.3.2). The similarity between these two algorithms is not restricted to this common step. Indeed, as proved in [Chiuso, 2006, 2007a], the SSARX algorithm and the PBSID one (as well as its initial version named the Whitening Filter Algorithm (WFA) [Chiuso and Picci, 2005a]) are asymptotically equivalent [Chiuso, 2006, 2007a].

In both cases, specific matrices involved in the estimation problem are built from estimates of \mathbf{D} , $\mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^k\mathbf{B}$ and $\mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^k\mathcal{K}$, $k = 0, \dots, f-2$. These Markov parameters can be calculated from the one-step-ahead VARX model defined as [Chiuso, 2007a]

$$\mathbf{y}(t|t-1) = \sum_{i=0}^{\ell} \tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{\mathbf{u}(t-i)} \mathbf{u}(t-i) + \sum_{i=1}^{\ell} \tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{\mathbf{y}(t-i)} \mathbf{y}(t-i) \quad (2.115)$$

where ℓ is a user-defined truncation index and $\mathbf{y}(t|t-1)$ is the predicted output at time instant t which uses the inputs from t to $t - \ell$ and the outputs from $t - 1$ to $t - \ell$. Again, this finite order long ARX model causes misspecifications and bias when the index ℓ is too small. Raising its value a lot can lead to a prohibitive increase of the variance of the estimated matrices. Thus, a trade-off between bias and variance is necessary. It is interesting to point out that, when Assumption 2.6 is verified, the truncation index can be chosen equal to p which leads to a null truncation error. Furthermore, with this assumption, the relation between this predictor and the Markov parameters is straightforward by substituting Eq. (2.46) for \mathbf{x} in Eq. (2.110b). More precisely [Chiuso and Picci, 2005a],

$$\tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{\mathbf{u}(t-i)} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{D} & \text{if } i = 0 \\ \mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{i-1}\tilde{\mathbf{B}} & \text{if } i > 0 \end{cases} \quad (2.116a)$$

$$\tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{\mathbf{y}(t-i)} = \mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{i-1}\mathcal{K}. \quad (2.116b)$$

As proved in [Chiuso, 2007a, Theorem 4.3], when Assumptions 2.1, 2.2, 2.6, 2.8 and 2.9 are satisfied, consistent estimates of the Markov parameters of the system can be provided from the predictor (2.115) even with closed-loop data. Again, like in the open-loop framework, Assumption 2.6 is necessary to ensure that the truncation error term omitted in Eq. (2.115) is equal to zero.

Remark 2.11 *When a sufficiently large amount of data is available, the estimation of the aforementioned Markov parameters can be performed by minimizing the following least-squares cost function*

$$\left\| \begin{matrix} \mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \\ \mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^- \end{matrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{\mathbf{y}(t-\ell)} & \cdots & \tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{\mathbf{u}(t-1)} & \tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{\mathbf{u}(t)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Y}_{\ell,M}^- \\ \mathbf{U}_{\ell,M}^- \\ \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix} \right\|_F^2 \quad (2.117)$$

or, written differently,

$$\left\| \begin{matrix} \mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \\ \mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^- \end{matrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{\ell-1} [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}] & \cdots & \mathbf{C} [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}] & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Z}_{\ell,M}^- \\ \mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \end{bmatrix} \right\|_F^2 \quad (2.118)$$

where the involved regressors are defined in Paragraph 2.2.2.2. This cost function is, up to the value of the index ℓ , the one used in the first step of the IEM algorithm (see Eq. (2.107)). Thus, basically, apart from the algorithmic implementation, the main difference between the IEM and the PDSID-like algorithms only rests on the use of $\Gamma_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})$ instead of $\Gamma_f(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathbf{C})$.

By having access to accurate estimates of \mathbf{D} , $\mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^k\mathbf{B}$ and $\mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^k\mathbf{K}$, $k = 0, \dots, f-2$, the SSARX and the PBSID algorithms mainly¹⁹ differ from the way these estimates are used in the following steps. See also [Chiuso, 2007a, Remark 4.5] for a thorough discussion about the main differences between the PBSIDopt and the SSARX algorithms.

Remark 2.12 *The reader can see that this basic idea is inspired by the work of Peternell [Peternell, 1995] with his CCA algorithms [Peternell et al., 1996]. The link with the VARX one-step ahead predictor model suggested in [Ljung and McKelvey, 1996a] is also obvious.*

The state-space ARX algorithm From the estimates of $\mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^k\mathbf{B}$, $\mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^k\mathbf{K}$ and \mathbf{D} , $k = 0, \dots, f-2$, estimates of $\mathbf{H}_f^{cl,u}$ and $\mathbf{H}_f^{cl,y}$ can be formed. Then, it can be written that

$$\underbrace{\mathbf{y}_f^+(t) - \hat{\mathbf{H}}_f^{cl,u}\mathbf{u}_f^+(t) - \hat{\mathbf{H}}_f^{cl,y}\mathbf{y}_f^+(t)}_{\mathbf{s}_f^+(t)} = \Gamma_f(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathbf{C})\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathbf{K} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])\mathbf{z}_p^-(t) + \mathbf{e}_f^+(t). \quad (2.119)$$

Because \mathbf{e}_f^+ and \mathbf{z}_p^- are uncorrelated, this equation can be viewed as a low rank linear regression problem for the estimation of $\Gamma_f(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathbf{C})\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathbf{K} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])$. Many algorithms are available to perform this optimization. For instance, a least-squares minimization can be carried out in order to get an estimate of $\Gamma_f(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathbf{C})\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathbf{K} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])$. Then, a (weighted) SVD can be used in order to extract the extended observability subspace. Instead of resorting to such a least-squares approach, M. Jansson suggests performing a canonical correlation analysis (CCA) on $\mathbf{s}_f^+(t)$ and $\mathbf{z}_p^-(t)$. More precisely, the following SVD is used²⁰

$$\hat{\mathbf{R}}_{\mathbf{s}_f^+ \mathbf{s}_f^+}^{-1/2} \hat{\mathbf{R}}_{\mathbf{s}_f^+ \mathbf{z}_p^-} \hat{\mathbf{R}}_{\mathbf{z}_p^- \mathbf{z}_p^-}^{-1/2} = [\mathbf{u}_s \quad \mathbf{u}_n] \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_s & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \Sigma_n \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_s^\top \\ \mathbf{v}_n^\top \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.120)$$

and the CCA estimate of $\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathbf{K} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])$ is given by

$$\hat{\Omega}_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathbf{K} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{B}}]) = \mathbf{v}_s^\top \hat{\mathbf{R}}_{\mathbf{z}_p^- \mathbf{z}_p^-}^{1/2}. \quad (2.121)$$

¹⁹As claimed by Chiuso in [Chiuso, 2007b], the PBSID algorithm can be viewed as a geometrical version of the SSARX algorithm.

²⁰The aforementioned sample correlation matrices are defined as $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_{\mathbf{q}\mathbf{g}}(t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \mathbf{q}(t)\mathbf{g}^\top(t)$.

By having access to $\hat{\Omega}_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])$, the estimated state sequence satisfies

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \hat{\Omega}_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])\mathbf{z}_p^-(t) \quad (2.122)$$

from which the state-space matrices of the system can be estimated by a linear regression as it was introduced in Paragraph 2.2.2.3.

Remark 2.13 *A slightly different implementation of the SSARX algorithm is put forward in [Jansson, 2005]. A three step procedure is more precisely considered, involving the idea of the "one step correction method" of [Werner and Jansson, 2004]. See [Jansson, 2005] for details.*

The prediction-based subspace identification algorithm Instead of resorting to the estimates of $\tilde{\mathbf{G}}_f$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_f$, the key idea of the prediction-based subspace identification (PBSID) algorithm consists in observing that the product of the state and the extended observability matrix is given by

$$\Gamma_f(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathbf{C})\mathbf{x}(t) = \Gamma_f(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathbf{C})\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])\mathbf{z}_p^-(t). \quad (2.123)$$

If this product can be estimated, the extended observability subspace as well as the state sequence can be extracted by solving a low rank optimization problem. To do so, an estimate of $\Gamma_f(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathbf{C})\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}])$ must be available. As shown by Chiuso in [Chiuso, 2007a], this block-matrix can be constructed from the Markov parameters obtained from the least-squares solution of the optimization problem (2.118). Indeed, it is obvious that

$$\begin{aligned} & \Gamma_f(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathbf{C})\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}]) \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{p-1}[\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}] & \mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{p-2}[\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}] & \cdots & \mathbf{C}[\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}] \\ \mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^p[\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}] & \mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{p-1}[\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}] & \ddots & \mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}[\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}] \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{f+p-2}[\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}] & \cdots & \cdots & \mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{f-1}[\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}] \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (2.124)$$

where the block-matrices composing this equation are solutions of the least-squares regression (2.118). Furthermore, under Assumption 2.6, the former matrices become upper block triangular matrices, *i.e.*,

$$\begin{aligned} & \Gamma_f(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \mathbf{C})\Omega_p(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, [\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}]) \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{p-1}[\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}] & \mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{p-2}[\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}] & \cdots & \mathbf{C}[\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}] \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{p-1}[\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}] & \ddots & \mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}[\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}] \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{C}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{f-1}[\mathcal{K} \ \tilde{\mathbf{B}}] \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (2.125)$$

when f is chosen equal to p . By recalling Eq. (2.123), an estimate of the state sequence can be computed from a dedicated weighted SVD from which the state-space matrices of the system can be estimated.

Remark 2.14 *The former description can be viewed as a sketch of the PBSID algorithm, really close to the PBSIDopt algorithm [Chiuso, 2007a]. Different versions of this algorithm are available in the literature. The interested reader can study, e.g., [Chiuso and Picci, 2005a, Chiuso, 2007a, 2010] for more details. For instance, a recent study [Houtzager et al., 2009b] deals with the PBSID algorithm with the help of a Vector Auto-Regressive Moving Average with exogenous inputs (VARMAX) model. By using this model (instead of a VARX (see Eq. (2.115))), Assumption 2.6 can be satisfied with a lower value of the user-defined parameter p (see Paragraph 2.2.1.3 and the discussion about Assumption 2.7 for details). Many details are now available in [Houtzager, 2011] and really good and reliable implementations of the corresponding subspace-based identification algorithms can be downloaded from Delft Center for Systems and Control under the generic name PBSIDToolbox [Houtzager, 2010]. As claimed by the authors of this toolbox, "the Predictor-Based Subspace Identification Toolbox enables you to perform a batch or recursive identification (in open-loop and closed-loop) of LTI/LPV/Hammerstein/Wiener systems".*

2.3 Conclusions

In this chapter, an overview of the main regression-based subspace identification techniques has been introduced. More precisely, a specific attention has been paid to their algorithmic structures, their common points and their differences. Thus, it has been shown that, whatever the operating conditions (open-loop or closed-loop), several subspace identification schemes can be derived from similar least-squares problem formulations. All these regression-based techniques share indeed the idea of approximating the state sequence of the system with past input and output data. Basically, they mainly differ from the way this state sequence is technically approximated. By following this general idea, it has been highlighted that the most efficient least-squares subspace-based identification techniques rely on a state sequence approximation derived from a reformulation of the well-known innovation form into the predictor-form. Said differently, it has also been shown that, for open-loop and closed-loop systems, the main and well-known subspace-based identification algorithms can all be interpreted as prediction-based subspace algorithm or, at least, involve a prediction step.

CHAPTER 3

Subspace-based identification of parameterized black-box state-space systems

3.1 Motivations

As shown in the former chapter, subspace-based identification can be considered as a really good alternative to the standard prediction-error techniques [Ljung, 1999a] when a fully-parameterized state-space form is looked for. Interesting from a numerical point of view [McKelvey, 1995], a fully-parameterized model, by construction, over-parameterizes the model and, as a direct consequence, makes the model non-identifiable, *i.e.*, the input-output behavior of the system can be represented by, at least, two different parameter sets. From a practical point of view, such a flexibility in the fully-parameterized structure is translated into the n_x^2 elements of the similarity transformation which parameterizes the equivalence class. In other words, the estimated state-space representation is known up to a similarity transformation. This fact, which has no consequences if the user is only looking for a black-box mathematical description of the input-output behavior of the system, can be really annoying when

- multi-models or hybrid systems are considered because the sub-models must be described with respect to coherent bases [Petreczky, 2006, Bako et al., 2009c],
- uncertainty domains [Ljung, 1999a] of the estimated parameters of the state-space matrices are looked for because, for such model quality measurements, invariants of the system are favored. Notice indeed that a system identification algorithm should deliver an accurate nominal model but also a confidence region around the model, *i.e.*, a measurement of the distance between the model and the true (non-linear) system.

In order to give answers to the aforementioned issues, a specific technique is introduced hereafter to build as well as to identify a parameterized black-box state-space form for multi-inputs-multi-outputs (MIMO) systems. Contrary to the developments suggested in Chapter 4, the parameterized state-space form delivered hereafter is not obtained from prior knowledge about the system to identify. A specific and user-defined canonical form for black-box MIMO state-space realizations is indeed suggested in the sequel. One of the main interest of the following developments turns out to be that no Kronecker index is required [Kailath, 1980] but a randomly-generated vector is used to build a user-defined similarity transformation. As proved in the following, the deduced canonical form has the minimal number of parameters and is globally identifiable for any linear time-invariant (LTI) discrete-time minimal MIMO system with a non-derogatory [Horn and Johnson, 1990] state matrix. Interesting from a theoretical point of view, this canonical form has also the advantage to be identifiable directly from an input-output data set with the help of a particular subspace-based identification algorithm. This characteristic, presented more precisely in Section 3.3, induces several interesting practical properties. First, prior knowledge of the state-space matrices of the system is not required to get the final state-space canonical form. Notice indeed that the methods based on the Kronecker index (see [Kailath, 1980] for a state-of-the-art) require the availability of the observability or controllability matrix. Second, because the method provides a model described in a canonical form, the problems related to the multiplicity of possible bases used to represent the system in the state-space are circumvented. Finally, as shown in Section 3.3, the developed approach does not use any singular value decomposition (SVD) generally required in subspace-based identification. Notice indeed that the basis of the estimated realization is often chosen during the extraction of the observability or state subspace via a singular value decomposition. Interesting for its numerical robustness, the SVD is computationally intensive and technically hard to update recursively, thus making its use for online identification a fastidious task [Verhaegen and Deprettere, 1991]. On the contrary, because the developed approach is mainly based on several (modified) least-squares minimizations, it can be adapted for the online identification of MIMO linear time-varying systems [Mercère and Lovera, 2007, Mercère et al., 2008, Houtzager et al., 2009a].

In order to introduce this new parameterization of MIMO state-space systems, this chapter is organized as follows. Section 3.2 is dedicated to the description of the state-space canonical form, *i.e.*, the way it is obtained and described as well as its main properties. The use of this parameterization in the identification framework is presented in Section 3.3. More precisely, a dedicated subspace-based identification algorithm is described in Sub-Section 3.3.1

with the specificity to give access to the canonical form introduced in Section 3.2 directly from a set input-output data without requiring any initial state-space realization of the system. Among all the properties and extensions (available in the literature) related to this specific parameterization (see Sub-Section 3.3.2 for details), a particular attention is paid to the description of the uncertainty domain of the parameter estimates in Sub-Section 3.3.3. Several numerical examples are introduced in Section 3.3 in order to illustrate the performance of the developed approach. Section 3.4 concludes this chapter.

3.2 Parameterization and canonical forms of linear time-invariant black-box state-space systems

The parameterization of LTI dynamic systems and the determination of canonical forms are subjects which widely interested the automatic control community in the 1960's, the 1970's and the 1980's [Kalman, 1963, Silverman, 1966, Luenberger, 1967, Denham, 1974, Kailath, 1980, Guidorzi, 1989]. The canonical forms are of importance mainly because they provide a unique parameterization of the studied system in the model set. This property can be exploited in the system identification framework because the canonical forms generally give rise to an identifiable model structure. This property can be really useful when the parameters of the model are estimated by optimizing particular cost functions (such as the sum of squared errors [Ljung, 1999a]) because an injective parameterization leads to a unique minimum in the parameter space [McKelvev, 1995]. They are also a convenient starting point for some control design problems (see, *e.g.*, the pole placement with Ackermann's formula [Kailath, 1980]). Then, they can be useful for a one-to-one correspondence with particular matrix fraction descriptions of LTI systems [Kailath, 1980]. Indeed, the parameters of the canonical forms can have a direct interpretation as particular coefficients of the transfer functions. Finally, it is interesting to notice that the increasing need of relevant and accurate model parameterizations for systems described by linear time-varying [R. Guidorzi and R. Diversi, 2003], linear parameter-varying [Tóth, 2008] or switched linear structures [Petreczky, 2006, Bako et al., 2009b] has triggered a recent surge of interest in linear canonical forms.

Initially developed for single input systems, most of the methods developed in the 1960's have been extended for MIMO systems. The basic idea of the methods developed for MIMO systems mainly consists in selecting particular structural indices, sometimes corresponding to the Kronecker index [Denham, 1974, Kailath, 1980], so that specific vectors, generally extracted from the observability or controllability matrix of the system, are gathered into a full rank square matrix in order to be used as a similarity transformation (see

also, e.g., [Ljung, 1999a, Appendix 4A]).

The parameterization of multivariable systems is still considered as a difficult problem, especially when MIMO minimal forms are required [Ljung, 1999a]. This challenge is related to the fact that a bijective parameterization does not exist when both the input and the output dimensions are greater than one. That is the reason why the family of techniques based on the Kronecker index were introduced in the 1960's [Kailath, 1980]. Notice that the parameterization of MIMO systems is still studied in fields such as system identification [McKelvey, 1995, Ribarits, 2002, Petreczky, 2006] even if solutions to get canonical forms are available in the literature. Indeed, the determination of the model structure has a strong impact on the model accuracy and deeply affects the numerical properties of the identification algorithms [McKelvey, 1995], especially when a non-linear optimization is performed. Furthermore, the techniques developed until now to get canonical forms require the availability of an accurate realization of the state-space form of system and do not start from the I/O data directly. This additional step should be avoided when the identification of the system is concerned. Increasing the number of steps in an identification procedure can indeed lead to an increase of the variance of the estimates.

In this section, the problem of the determination of canonical forms for MIMO state-space systems is revisited. Instead of using the standard tools based on the Kronecker index, a new technique, depending on a user-defined similarity transformation, is put forward. As shown in Section 3.3, this approach will be adapted in the identification framework. This characteristic makes this technique really appealing from a practical point of view.

3.2.1 Problem formulation and related definitions

The starting point of the procedure described hereafter is the following description of the input-output relation of the system

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(t) \quad (3.1a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{u}(t) \quad (3.1b)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ is the state vector, $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ is the input vector and $\mathbf{y}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ is the output vector. Up until now, the term parameterization has been used without being defined mathematically. Basically, a parameterization of a model is a mapping from the parameter vector θ to a set of equations describing the system and involving the parameters included in θ . First, such a simple description can be translated as follows [Glover and Willems, 1974]

Definition 3.1 A parameterization π of the state-space form (3.1) of order n_x is a mapping defined as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \pi : \Theta \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta} &\longmapsto \mathbb{R}^{n_x(n_x+n_u+n_y)+n_un_y} \\ \theta &\longmapsto \begin{bmatrix} \text{vec}(\mathbf{A}(\theta)) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbf{B}(\theta)) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbf{C}(\theta)) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbf{D}(\theta)) \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

where $(\mathbf{A}(\theta), \mathbf{B}(\theta), \mathbf{C}(\theta), \mathbf{D}(\theta))$ are the state-space matrices structured by the vector θ , Θ is a subset of \mathbb{R}^{n_θ} and $\text{vec}(\bullet)$ is the vectorization tool [Horn and Johnson, 1990].

This definition is a description of the way the elements of the matrices $(\mathbf{A}(\theta), \mathbf{B}(\theta), \mathbf{C}(\theta), \mathbf{D}(\theta))$ are formed from the parameter vector θ . In recent contributions [McKelvey, 1995, Peternell, 1995, Ribarits, 2002], the definition of π is preferentially related to the transfer function $\mathbf{G}(q)$ defined by

$$\mathbf{G}(q) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \mathbf{g}_k q^{-k} \quad (3.3)$$

where q stands for the forward shift operator and \mathbf{g}_k , $k \in [0, \infty[$ are the coefficients of the impulse response of the system. It is well-known that both representations are indeed related by the equation

$$\mathbf{G}(q) = \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{C}(q\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} - \mathbf{A})^{-1}\mathbf{B} \quad (3.4)$$

Thus, we can define the parameterization π as follows [McKelvey, 1995, Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007]:

Definition 3.2 Consider $\mathcal{R}_{n_x}^{n_y \times n_u}$ the set of all $n_y \times n_u$ proper rational transfer functions with real coefficients and a degree at most equal to n_x . Then, a parameterization π of the state-space form (3.1) of order n_x is a mapping defined as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \pi : \Theta \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta} &\longmapsto \mathcal{R}_{n_x}^{n_y \times n_u} \\ \theta &\longmapsto \mathbf{G}(q, \theta) \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

where Θ is a subset of \mathbb{R}^{n_θ} and where $\mathbf{G}(q, \theta) = \mathbf{D}(\theta) + \mathbf{C}(\theta)(q\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} - \mathbf{A}(\theta))^{-1}\mathbf{B}(\theta)$ with $(\mathbf{A}(\theta), \mathbf{B}(\theta), \mathbf{C}(\theta), \mathbf{D}(\theta))$ the state-space matrices structured by the vector θ .

Whatever the definition, the mapping π should be surjective, that is to say, for every $\tau \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x(n_x+n_u+n_y)+n_un_y}$ (resp. $\mathbf{G}(q) \in \mathcal{R}_{n_x}^{n_y \times n_u}$), a parameter vector $\theta \in \Theta$ exists such that $\pi(\theta) = \tau$ (resp. $\pi(\theta) = \mathbf{G}(q)$). For instance, a fully-parameterized state-space form is surjective [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007].

In system identification, it can also be required that the mapping π is injective, that is to say, to every point in $\mathbb{R}^{n_x(n_x+n_u+n_y)+n_u n_y}$ (resp. $\mathcal{R}_{n_x}^{n_y \times n_u}$), at most one point exists in Θ . Indeed, with an injective mapping, we can uniquely identify a model from its input and output data. While the surjectivity property is often not difficult to satisfy, determining an injective mapping is not an easy task [McKelvey, 1995]. Resorting to canonical forms can be a solution when the user needs a black-box injective mapping, for instance when the prior knowledge about the system is reduced to its order. Indeed, as shown in Chapter 4, the parameterization as well as the identification of structured models obtained from prior knowledge and physical considerations must be performed differently than with black-box models. Thus, in the current chapter, only black-box state-space models will be handled.

The canonical forms were thoroughly studied in the 1960's, the 1970's and the 1980's [Kalman, 1963, Silverman, 1966, Luenberger, 1967, Denham, 1974, Kailath, 1980, Guidorzi, 1989]. An interesting presentation of the main canonical forms as well as a comparison of the topological and the geometrical properties of these canonical forms with other parameterizations such as the fully-parameterized representation or the data driven local parameterization is available in [Ribarits, 2002]. Hereafter, only a short overview of the main definitions and properties is given. The interested reader can refer to [Kailath, 1980, Hannan and Deistler, 1988, Ribarits, 2002] and the references therein for more details.

First, in order to define accurately what a canonical form is, the concept of equivalence relation must be introduced [Kailath, 1980, Section 6.7.3]

Definition 3.3 *Let \mathcal{F} be a set and $\#$ a binary relation on \mathcal{F} . $\#$ is called an equivalence relation if and only if for all x, y and $z \in \mathcal{F}$, the following properties hold true*

- reflexivity: $x\#x$,
- symmetry: if $x\#y$, then $y\#x$,
- transitivity: if $x\#y$ and $y\#z$, then $x\#z$.

For instance, if \mathcal{F} is a set of square matrices, we can introduce, for arbitrary but non-singular matrices \mathbf{T} , all matrices similar to $\mathbf{A} \in \mathcal{F}$ of the form $\mathbf{T}^{-1}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{T}$ and, by extension, $\mathbf{A}\#\mathbf{T}^{-1}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{T}$. Then, the following definition holds [Guidorzi, 1989],

Definition 3.4 *Let $\#$ be an equivalence relation on \mathcal{F} . A subset \mathcal{E} of \mathcal{F} is called a set of canonical forms for $\#$ if every $x \in \mathcal{F}$ is equivalent under $\#$ to one and only one element of \mathcal{E} . This element is the canonical form of x .*

This notion of uniqueness is what is looked for in system identification.

Remark 3.1 *The previous definitions can be illustrated when sets of state-space models are involved. For that, let us consider a state-space form $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ as well as a similarity transformation \mathbf{T} such that*

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{TAT}^{-1} \quad \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{TB} \quad \mathbf{C} = \mathbf{CT}^{-1} \quad \mathbf{D} = \mathbf{D}. \quad (3.6)$$

Then, $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ is a canonical form if and only if this form is similar to all pairs $\{\mathbf{SAS}^{-1}, \mathbf{SB}, \mathbf{CS}^{-1}, \mathbf{D}, \det(\mathbf{S}) \neq 0\}$.

The main difficulty with canonical forms is their determination. Basically, the determination of a canonical form amounts to find a state-space form $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ similar to all pairs $\{\mathbf{SAS}^{-1}, \mathbf{SB}, \mathbf{CS}^{-1}, \mathbf{D}, \det(\mathbf{S}) \neq 0\}$. In the literature, many schemes have been suggested (see, e.g., [Kailath, 1980, Chapter 6] or [Tóth, 2008, Chapter 2]). By starting with Luenberger's works in the 1960's [Luenberger, 1967], important contributions were gathered in Volume 19, Issue 6 of the IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control Special Issue on System Identification in 1974. In fact, the determination of a canonical form is quite easy when single-input-single-output controllable and/or observable systems are handled (see [Tóth, 2008, Chapter 2] for an illustration). When MIMO systems are considered, the description of a canonical form is a lot more complicated. This is generally achieved by introducing a finite set of integers, gathered in an index often called a Kronecker index, which uniquely describes the set of canonical forms. For instance, the Echelon state-space forms [Bauer, 1998, Ribarits, 2002] are based on the selection of the first linearly independent rows of a specific Hankel matrix corresponding to a given transfer function. More generally, the Kronecker index is chosen so that specific vectors, often extracted from the observability or the controllability matrix of the system, are gathered into a full rank square matrix in order to be used as a similarity transformation. According to the way the Kronecker index is selected, a different canonical form can be obtained (see [Glover and Willems, 1974] for a discussion about this issue). Thus, the involved parameterization of the canonical form is totally dependent on the chosen Kronecker index and, more particularly, is uniquely described in terms of this index [Glover and Willems, 1974]. That is the reason why, most of the time, the parameterization attaching the free parameters to the transfer functions (similar to Definition 3.2) is indexed by the Kronecker index α (see [Bauer, 1998, Chapter 2] or [Ribarits, 2002, Chapter 4] for examples).

As claimed previously, most of the techniques for the selection of the Kronecker index are based on multiple rank tests in order to get a sufficiently large set of independent vectors used, in a second step, as a similarity transformation [Kailath, 1980]. In Sub-Section 3.2.2, a new method is introduced

to build a state-space canonical form for MIMO systems. Contrary to the standard approaches, no Kronecker index is required but a randomly-generated vector is used to build a user-defined similarity transformation. As proved in the following, the deduced canonical form has the minimal number of parameters and is globally identifiable for any LTI discrete-time minimal MIMO system with a non-derogatory [Horn and Johnson, 1990] state matrix. As shown in Section 3.3, this structure can be obtained directly from a sufficiently large data set acquired on the system to identify with the help of a particular subspace-based identification algorithm. This characteristic avoids the prior knowledge of the state-space matrices of the system in order to get the final state-space canonical form.

3.2.2 A randomly-generated canonical form for MIMO systems

3.2.2.1 Basic idea and construction

Inspired by the standard techniques dedicated to the construction of canonical forms, the basic idea of the developed approach consists in building a similarity transformation \mathbf{T} such that the corresponding similar state-space representation is expressed into a minimal and identifiable canonical form. Instead of using the famous Kronecker index, a new user-defined set of indices is introduced hereafter. In this chapter, the starting point of the procedure is a realization $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ of the linear system (3.1). The construction of a canonical form directly from the input and output data of the system (3.1) is postponed until Section 3.3. For this specific realization, let us define the extended observability matrix $\mathbf{\Gamma}_f$ of the system as follows

$$\mathbf{\Gamma}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C}) = [\mathbf{C}^\top \quad \dots \quad (\mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}^{f-1})^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y f \times n_x} \quad (3.7)$$

where f is a user-defined index such that $f \geq n_x$. Then, by assuming that the system is observable, it holds that $\mathbf{\Gamma}_f$ has, at least, n_x linearly independent rows. The goal of this paragraph is to show how a set of n_x linearly independent vectors can be extracted from $\mathbf{\Gamma}_f$ in order to be used as a similarity transformation. When MISO observable systems are considered, the first n_x rows of $\mathbf{\Gamma}_f$ are linearly independent and the choice is clear because the square matrix composed of these vectors has full rank. This particular similarity transformation is well-known and leads to the observability canonical form [Kailath, 1980]. In the MIMO case, the problem is slightly more difficult. Indeed, when multi-output systems are considered, there is no way to ensure that the first n_x rows of $\mathbf{\Gamma}_f$ are linearly independent or that the entire dynamics of the system is observable from one particular output. Instead of resorting to the standard Kronecker index, the following proposition is intro-

duced in order to investigate the selection procedure of suitable rows in the observability matrix

Proposition 3.1 *By assuming that the MIMO system (3.1) is observable and the matrix \mathbf{A} is non-derogatory, by introducing $\boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top = [\kappa_1 \ \kappa_2 \ \cdots \ \kappa_{n_y}]$, $\boldsymbol{\kappa} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n_y}$, a vector generated randomly from a uniform distribution, it holds with probability one that*

$$\text{rank}(\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C})) = n_x. \quad (3.8)$$

Proof 3.1 *See Proof of Proposition 1 in [Bako et al., 2009b].*

First, this proposition is based on a quite unusual assumption: the state matrix \mathbf{A} is non-derogatory. We recall from [Horn and Johnson, 1990] that

Definition 3.5 *A matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is non-derogatory if and only if any of the following equivalent conditions is satisfied.*

- \mathbf{A} is similar to a companion matrix.
- The characteristic polynomial of \mathbf{A} equals its minimum polynomial, where both polynomials are taken to be unitary.
- A vector $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ exists such that the matrix $[\mathbf{v}, \ \mathbf{A}\mathbf{v}, \ \dots, \ \mathbf{A}^{n-1}\mathbf{v}]$ is full rank.
- For any eigenvalue λ of \mathbf{A} , $\dim(\ker(\mathbf{A} - \lambda\mathbf{I}_n)) = 1$.

These equivalent statements have a number of implications in linear system theory. For example, it can be observed that any linear observable MISO (or controllable SIMO) system has a non-derogatory \mathbf{A} -matrix. If an n -order linear system has n distinct poles, then its \mathbf{A} -matrix (taken from any minimal realization) satisfies the non-derogatory property. Some systems which have poles with multiplicities greater than one can be realized with a state-space realization such that the \mathbf{A} -matrix is non-derogatory. On the contrary, a system having at least a double pole and realized by a representation with a diagonalizable \mathbf{A} -matrix cannot be represented by a realization with a non-derogatory \mathbf{A} -matrix.

Second, Proposition 3.1 states that, by choosing a randomly-generated vector (independently of the state-space matrices of the system), the square matrix $\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C})$ can be used as a similarity transformation \mathbf{T} . Before describing the corresponding equivalent representation, let us focus on the role played by $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$. For this purpose, let us introduce the following auxiliary output y_a defined as

$$\mathbf{y}_a(t) = \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{y}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_y} \kappa_i y_i(t) \quad (3.9)$$

where y_i is the i th output of the system, *i.e.*, as a linear combination of the outputs of the system. Then, we have

$$\mathbf{y}_a(t) = \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t) + \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{D}\mathbf{u}(t). \quad (3.10)$$

This relation shows that, under the conditions given in Proposition 3.1, all the dynamics of the system are observable from \mathbf{y}_a . The use of this random vector $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ requires a modification of the initial state-space matrices in order to take into account this auxiliary output. To reach this goal, let us introduce a square matrix $\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_y}$ defined as the identity matrix with one row equal to $\boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top$ (numbered row k_o in the following). For instance, for $k_o = 1$, \mathbf{K} is defined as follows

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} \kappa_1 & \kappa_2 & \cdots & \kappa_{n_y} \\ 0 & 1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.11)$$

Notice that k_o is a user-defined parameter and can be fixed arbitrarily. Then, the application of this matrix \mathbf{K} to the output equation (3.1b) leads to a modified output vector $\bar{\mathbf{y}}$ satisfying

$$\bar{\mathbf{y}}(t) = \mathbf{K}\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{u}(t)) = \bar{\mathbf{C}}\mathbf{x}(t) + \bar{\mathbf{D}}\mathbf{u}(t) \quad (3.12)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{y}}$, $\bar{\mathbf{C}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{D}}$ are obtained from \mathbf{y} , \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{D} respectively by substituting the k_o th row with \mathbf{y}_a , $\boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C}$ and $\boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{D}$ respectively. Then, the similarity transformation $\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C})$ can be applied to the state-space matrices $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \bar{\mathbf{C}}, \bar{\mathbf{D}})$ leading to the following transformed matrices (see Appendix A.1 or [Mercère and Bako, 2011] for the calculations)

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{T}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 1 \\ -\alpha_0 & -\alpha_1 & -\alpha_2 & \cdots & -\alpha_{n_x-1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.13a)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} b_{11} & b_{12} & \cdots & b_{1n_u} \\ b_{21} & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & b_{(n_x-1)n_u} \\ b_{n_x1} & \cdots & b_{n_x(n_u-1)} & b_{n_x n_u} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.13b)$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{K}\mathbf{C}\mathbf{T}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{c}_1^\top \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{c}_{n_y}^\top \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{with } \mathbf{c}_{k_o}^\top = \mathbf{e}_1^\top, \quad (3.13c)$$

$$\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{K}\mathbf{D}, \quad (3.13d)$$

where \mathbf{c}_ℓ^\top , $\ell \in [1, n_y]$ is the ℓ th row of \mathbf{C} , \mathbf{e}_1^\top is a row vector that has 1 as its first entry and 0 everywhere else and α_j , $j \in [0, n_x - 1]$, are the coefficients of the characteristic polynomial of the \mathbf{A} -matrix [Horn and Johnson, 1990].

3.2.2.2 Parameterization properties

The procedure introduced beforehand leads to a form $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ with interesting properties listed in the following.

- First, the parameterization is uniquely characterized by the n_y values κ_i generated by the user.
- Second, the developed scheme gives access to a parameterization with $n_x(n_u + n_y) + n_u n_y$ parameters. Indeed, the matrices of the system are parameterized by

$$\boldsymbol{\theta}_\kappa = \begin{bmatrix} -\alpha_0 & \cdots & -\alpha_{n_x-1} & b_{11} & \cdots & b_{n_x n_u} & c_{11} & \cdots & c_{1 n_x} \\ \cdots & c_{(k_o-1)1} & \cdots & c_{(k_o-1)n_x} & c_{(k_o+1)1} & \cdots & c_{(k_o+1)n_x} \\ \cdots & c_{n_y 1} & \cdots & c_{n_y n_x} & d_{11} & \cdots & d_{n_y n_u} \end{bmatrix}^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_x(n_u+n_y)+n_u n_y) \times 1} \quad (3.14)$$

where b_{ij} , $c_{\ell i}$, $\ell \neq k_o$, and $d_{\ell j}$, $i \in [1, n_x]$, $j \in [1, n_u]$, $\ell \in [1, n_y]$, are respectively the components of \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{D} that are not restricted to zero or one *a priori*. $n_x(n_u + n_y) + n_u n_y$ is the dimension of the class of rational causal $n_y \times n_u$ transfer functions of fixed McMillan degree n_x [Ribarits, 2002]. Thus, the parameterization (3.13) has the minimal number of parameters.

- Third, the structure (3.13) is globally identifiable (see [Ljung, 1999a] and Chapter 4 for a discussion about this property). More particularly, the following proposition holds

Proposition 3.2 *The state-space model structure defined by Eq. (3.13) is globally and locally identifiable at $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ if and only if $(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))$ is controllable.*

Proof 3.2 *See Appendix A.2 or [Mercère and Bako, 2011].*

- Finally, this procedure gives rise to a canonical form for the class of minimal state-space LTI MIMO systems satisfying
 - (i) the order of the system is known *a priori*,

- (ii) $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ is minimal,
- (iii) the matrix \mathbf{A} is non-derogatory.

In order to prove this property, the sets \mathcal{E} and \mathcal{F} introduced in Definition 3.4 must be specified. To reach this goal, let us define

$$\Sigma = \left\{ (\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}), \mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}, \mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_u}, \right. \\ \left. \mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_x}, \mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_u} : \text{As. (ii)-(iii) are satisfied} \right\}. \quad (3.15)$$

Then (see [Guidorzi, 1989])

Theorem 3.1 *The binary relation $\#$ defined over Σ by*

$(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}) \# (\bar{\mathbf{A}}, \bar{\mathbf{B}}, \bar{\mathbf{C}}, \bar{\mathbf{D}})$ if and only if a nonsingular matrix $\mathbf{T} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$ exists such that $\bar{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{TAT}^{-1}$, $\bar{\mathbf{B}} = \mathbf{TB}$, $\bar{\mathbf{C}} = \mathbf{CT}^{-1}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{D}} = \mathbf{D}$

is an equivalence relation.

By turning now to the system (3.1) (which is assumed to be in Σ), consider a vector $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ satisfying $\text{rank}(\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C})) = n_x$ where the matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{C} are taken from any minimal realization of the system (3.1) in Σ . The existence of such a vector follows from Proposition 3.1. By using a so-defined vector $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$, the following subsets of Σ can be defined

$$\mathcal{F}_{\boldsymbol{\kappa}} = \left\{ (\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}) \in \Sigma : \text{rank}(\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C})) = n_x \right\}, \quad (3.16)$$

$$\mathcal{E}_{\boldsymbol{\kappa}} = \left\{ (\mathbf{TAT}^{-1}, \mathbf{TB}, \mathbf{CT}^{-1}, \mathbf{D}) : \right. \\ \left. (\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}) \in \mathcal{F}_{\boldsymbol{\kappa}} \text{ with } \mathbf{T} = \Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C}) \right\}. \quad (3.17)$$

Notice that $\mathcal{E}_{\boldsymbol{\kappa}} \subset \mathcal{F}_{\boldsymbol{\kappa}} \subset \Sigma$. Moreover, the following proposition can be stated.

Proposition 3.3

- (i) *The set $\mathcal{E}_{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}$ is a set of canonical forms for $\#$ over $\mathcal{F}_{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}$.*
- (ii) *The set $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{D})$ having the form given in Eq. (3.13) is equal to*

$$\{(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{K}\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{K}\mathbf{D}) : (\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}) \in \mathcal{E}_{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}\}. \quad (3.18)$$

Here, \mathbf{K} is a matrix function of $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ and is defined as in Section 3.2.2.1.

Proof 3.3 See Appendix A.3 or [Mercère and Bako, 2011].

Remark 3.2 This parameterization has geometrical properties which are close to those satisfied by the Echelon form [Ribarits, 2002]. For instance, just like the Echelon form, as soon as the vector κ is generated, the parameterization of $(\mathcal{A}(\theta_\kappa), \mathcal{B}(\theta_\kappa), \mathcal{C}(\theta_\kappa), \mathcal{D}(\theta_\kappa))$ is quite trivial because it only inserts unknown parameters at the correct position imposed by κ . A comparative study of these two parameterizations should be undertaken in order to complete the study introduced previously with a specific attention to the topological properties of this randomly-generated canonical parameterization (see [Ribarits, 2002, Chapter 4] for an interesting analysis of the Echelon form).

3.3 Application to subspace-based identification

In addition to their numerical robustness, the subspace-based identification techniques are often used in practice (at least, at a first attempt to get a reliable black-box model) because, by construction,

- they directly lead to fully-parameterized state-space forms,
- they only require one structural parameter (the McMillan degree n_x of the system) which can be estimated during the identification procedure.

Thus, by dealing with fully-parameterized models, the difficult problem of the model structure selection is circumvented. Unfortunately, the introduction of n_x^2 extra degrees¹ of freedom makes the parameterization non-injective. Structurally speaking, these n_x^2 extra degrees of flexibility are translated into the n_x^2 elements of the similarity transformation which parameterizes the equivalence class. This similarity transformation introduces a structural flexibility in the model structure. Interesting from a numerical point of view, such a flexible structure makes

- the introduction of prior knowledge complex,
- the statistical analysis of the estimates quite complicated,
- the determination of the estimated parameter uncertainty domain very difficult.

¹When a fully-parameterized state-space model is considered, we have $n_x^2 + n_x(n_u + n_y) + n_u n_y$ free parameters. On the contrary, an identifiable state-space model has, at worst, $n_x(n_u + n_y) + n_u n_y$ parameters.

In fact, all these problems can be related to a single one: the multiplicity of possible bases used to represent the system in the state-space. In addition to the aforementioned issues mainly related to the statistical theory underlying subspace-based model identification, this multiplicity of possible bases can have strong impact when, for instance, multi-models or switched systems [Paoletti et al., 2007] are handled. With such systems, it is essential that all the local models are expressed with respect to the same state basis coordinates in order to be linked in the final step of the identification procedure. Thus, in order to circumvent the problems mentioned previously, the development of a subspace-based identification algorithm able to result in a state-space form in a fixed state basis could be an interesting breakthrough.

As shown in Section 3.2, a canonical form can be extracted from an available state-space realization by resorting to a user-defined vector κ almost independent of the system under study. Thus, as soon as the vector κ is generated, matrices composed of invariants are available. In this section, this idea is adapted for subspace-based identification. Instead of identifying a fully-parameterized state-space representation, then applying the technique given in Section 3.2, the determination of the canonical form will be explicitly included in a dedicated subspace-based identification algorithm. Notice right now that, contrary to the standard subspace-based identification algorithms, the one introduced hereafter does not use any SVD. The non-use of any SVD can be justified by the fact that, by applying an SVD, the person who uses the standard subspace-based identification techniques has difficulties to fix the basis in which the state-space models are estimated. In fact, this choice is realized during the reduction step (when the order of the system is estimated) and the reproducibility of the basis is difficult to ensure when such a tool is employed.

More precisely, Sub-Section 3.3.1 will show how the parameterization problem highlighted in the previous Section can be solved when system identification is concerned. Sub-Section 3.3.2 will list the main properties and extensions following the use of the propagator for system identification. A particular attention will be paid to the uncertainty domain description of the estimated parameters in Sub-Section 3.3.3.

3.3.1 Subspace-based identification of a user-defined canonical form

In Section 3.2, it has been shown that the use of a user-defined similarity transformation can give access to a parameterization with a minimal number of parameters. This sub-section is devoted to the adaptation of the aforementioned basic idea in the subspace-based model identification framework.

3.3.1.1 Basic idea and construction

In order to simplify the notations and the description, let us assume for the moment that the I/O data is noise-free. The method presented hereafter shares many points with the standard subspace-based identification techniques. More precisely, the starting point is again the following well-known relation [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007]

$$\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ = \Gamma_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{H}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+ \quad (3.19)$$

where, apart from the matrix \mathbf{X} defined as follows

$$\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}(t) \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{x}(t + M - 1)], \quad (3.20)$$

the matrices composing this data equation are defined as in Section 2.1 (see Eq. (2.7), (2.9) and (2.10) for the generic definitions). Like many subspace-based identification methods, the first step of the developed technique consists in applying an orthogonal projection of the row space of $\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+$ onto the complement of the row space of $\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+$

$$\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp = \Gamma_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})\mathbf{X} \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \quad (3.21)$$

where $\mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp$, defined as in Eq. (2.75), is used in order to solve the problem of the unknown matrix $\mathbf{H}_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$.

In a certain way, the subspace-based identification methods are different from each other according to the subspace extracted from the previous equation. Here, the observability subspace is considered. More particularly, the developed method is based on the assumptions that the system is observable and that n_x is known (or *a priori* estimated). By assuming that (\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C}) is observable, we know that $\Gamma_f(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C})$ has, at least, n_x linearly independent rows. The basic idea of the technique described hereafter is to use the matrix composed of these rows as a similarity transformation in order to fix the estimated state-space matrices structure. The main problem is the selection of these n_x rows. For this purpose, Proposition 3.1 is applied. As said previously, this proposition states that the system dynamics are observable from the auxiliary output

$$\mathbf{y}_a(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_y} \kappa_i y_i(t) \quad (3.22)$$

where y_i is the i th output of the system (see Eq. (3.9)). Practically, when κ_j , $j \in [1, n_y]$, are randomly selected, the matrix \mathbf{K} defined in Eq. (3.11) can be introduced to substitute, e.g., \mathbf{y}_a for the first output of the system and to obtain

$$\bar{\mathbf{y}}(t) = \mathbf{K}\mathbf{y}(t). \quad (3.23)$$

Remark 3.3 In this sub-section, to make the notations and the explanations more understandable, the first output is used for the substitution, i.e., $k_o = 1$. The procedure can be adapted when another output is considered.

Then, by using this transformation, Eq. (3.21) becomes

$$\bar{\mathbf{Y}}_{f,M}^+ \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp = \mathbf{\Gamma}_f(\mathbf{A}, \bar{\mathbf{C}}) \mathbf{X} \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \quad (3.24)$$

where

$$\bar{\mathbf{C}} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{c}}_1^\top \\ \bar{\mathbf{c}}_2^\top \\ \vdots \\ \bar{\mathbf{c}}_{n_y}^\top \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{j=1}^{n_y} \kappa_j \mathbf{c}_j^\top \\ \mathbf{c}_2^\top \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{c}_{n_y}^\top \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.25)$$

where \mathbf{c}_j^\top , $j \in [1, n_y]$, are the rows of \mathbf{C} . By noting that $\mathbf{\Gamma}_f(\mathbf{A}, \bar{\mathbf{C}})$ has full column rank, a permutation matrix \mathbf{S} can be introduced in order to reorder the rows of $\mathbf{\Gamma}_f(\mathbf{A}, \bar{\mathbf{C}})$ and to ensure that its first n_x rows are linearly independent. This permutation matrix is defined as follows

$$\mathbf{S} = [\mathcal{I}_1 \quad \cdots \quad \mathcal{I}_{n_y}]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{fn_y \times fn_y} \quad (3.26)$$

where

$$\mathcal{I}_i = [\mathbf{e}_i \quad \mathbf{e}_{i+n_y} \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{e}_{i+(f-1)n_y}] \quad (3.27)$$

with $\mathbf{e}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{fn_y}$ a vector composed of 0 entries and 1 in position i . By using the permutation matrix (3.26), we get

$$\mathbf{S} \mathbf{\Gamma}_f(\mathbf{A}, \bar{\mathbf{C}}) = \mathbf{S} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{c}}_1^\top \\ \mathbf{c}_2^\top \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{c}_{n_y}^\top \\ \bar{\mathbf{c}}_1^\top \mathbf{A} \\ \mathbf{c}_2^\top \mathbf{A} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{c}_{n_y}^\top \mathbf{A} \\ \bar{\mathbf{c}}_1^\top \mathbf{A}^{f-1} \\ \mathbf{c}_2^\top \mathbf{A}^{f-1} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{c}_{n_y}^\top \mathbf{A}^{f-1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{c}}_1^\top \\ \bar{\mathbf{c}}_1^\top \mathbf{A} \\ \vdots \\ \bar{\mathbf{c}}_1^\top \mathbf{A}^{f-1} \\ \mathbf{c}_2^\top \\ \mathbf{c}_2^\top \mathbf{A} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{c}_2^\top \mathbf{A}^{f-1} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{c}_{n_y}^\top \\ \mathbf{c}_{n_y}^\top \mathbf{A} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{c}_{n_y}^\top \mathbf{A}^{f-1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{\Gamma}_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \bar{\mathbf{c}}_1^\top) \\ \mathbf{\Psi} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.28)$$

By construction, $\text{rank}(\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \bar{\mathbf{c}}_1^\top)) = n_x$. Hence, $\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \bar{\mathbf{c}}_1^\top)$ can be used as a similarity transformation \mathbf{T} . Notice right now that this similarity transformation is similar to the one used in Section 3.2.2. Furthermore, the matrix Ψ (see Eq. (3.28)) can be written as a linear combination of $\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \bar{\mathbf{c}}_1^\top)$. Thus, a unique operator $\mathbf{P} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y f - n_x \times n_x}$, named the propagator [Munier and Delisle, 1991], exists such that

$$\Psi = \mathbf{P} \Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \bar{\mathbf{c}}_1^\top). \quad (3.29)$$

Hence, it can be verified that

$$\mathbf{S} \bar{\mathbf{Y}}_{f,M}^+ \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp = \mathbf{S} \Gamma_f(\mathbf{A}, \bar{\mathbf{C}}) \mathbf{X} \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \quad (3.30)$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n_x} \\ \mathbf{P} \end{bmatrix} \Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \bar{\mathbf{c}}_1^\top) \mathbf{X} \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \quad (3.31)$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n_x} \\ \mathbf{P} \end{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{X}} \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \quad (3.32)$$

with $\bar{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{T} \mathbf{X}$. This relation shows that the observability subspace can be described in a particular basis if the propagator can be estimated from I/O signals. Indeed, by assuming that \mathbf{P} is known, it holds

$$\Upsilon_f = \mathbf{S}^\top \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n_x} \\ \mathbf{P} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C} \\ \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A}^{f-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.33)$$

with $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{C} \mathbf{T}^{-1}$ and $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{T} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{T}^{-1}$. Thanks to the similarity transformation $\mathbf{T} = \Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \bar{\mathbf{c}}_1^\top)$, the matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{C} will have the form given in Eq. (3.13).

As far as the estimation of \mathbf{P} is concerned, let us introduce \mathbf{Z} defined by

$$\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{S} \bar{\mathbf{Y}}_{f,M}^+ \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Z}_1 \\ \mathbf{Z}_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n_x} \\ \mathbf{P} \end{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{X}} \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \quad (3.34)$$

where $\mathbf{Z}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times M}$ and $\mathbf{Z}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_y f - n_x) \times M}$. Then, under the assumptions considered until now, a consistent estimate of \mathbf{P} can be obtained from the I/O data by minimizing

$$\|\mathbf{Z}_2 - \mathbf{P} \mathbf{Z}_1\|_F^2. \quad (3.35)$$

By knowing $\hat{\mathbf{P}}$, the matrix $\hat{\Upsilon}_f$ can be built by using Eq. (3.33). Then, by using

the Cayley Hamilton theorem [Horn and Johnson, 1990], we can show that

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n_x} \\ \mathbf{P} \end{bmatrix} (2 : n_x + 1, :) \quad (3.36a)$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 1 \\ -\alpha_0 & -\alpha_1 & -\alpha_2 & \cdots & -\alpha_{n_x-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.36b)$$

$$\mathbf{c}_1^\top = [1 \ 0 \ \cdots \ 0] \quad (3.36c)$$

$$\mathbf{c}_j^\top = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n_x} \\ \mathbf{P} \end{bmatrix} ((j-1)f + 1, :) \text{ for } j \in [2, n_y] \quad (3.36d)$$

where α_j , $j \in [0, n_x - 1]$, are the coefficients of the characteristic polynomial of the \mathbf{A} -matrix. Once \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{C} are known, the matrices \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{D} can be obtained via the linear regression satisfied by the output of the system [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007, Chapter 9]

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \left[\sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbf{u}^\top(\tau) \otimes \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A}^{t-\tau-1} \ \mathbf{u}^\top(t) \otimes \mathbf{I}_{n_y} \right] \begin{bmatrix} \text{vec}(\mathbf{B}) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbf{D}) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.37)$$

Notice that all these calculations have been performed by using the I/O measurements only.

In the case of noisy data, this method can be adapted by introducing an instrumental variable, as proposed, e.g., in the MOESP approach [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007]. The choice of the instruments depends on the properties of the inputs and the disturbances (see [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007, Mercère et al., 2008] for details).

Remark 3.4 *It is well known that the identification of systems represented with the help of standard canonical forms (observability, controllability, ..., see [Kailath, 1980]) may involve numerical difficulties [McKelvey, 1995]. Here, a particular canonical form is extracted from the I/O data via the propagator estimation. This operator is a fully-parameterized matrix estimated by using standard least-squares algorithms. The numerical problem inherent to a direct estimation of canonical forms are then circumvented.*

Remark 3.5 *Contrary to the standard subspace-based identification methods, the \mathbf{A} -matrix estimation is not carried out by using the A -invariance property of the observability subspace (which requires the use of a Moore-Penrose inversion [Horn and Johnson, 1990]) but by a mere matrix extraction. This feature is interesting from a numerical point of view. It only needs the estimation of the first row of the propagator.*

Remark 3.6 *The identification of multivariable canonical state-space representations has been also investigated in [Bako et al., 2008, 2009a]. Again, specific subspace-based identification techniques are introduced. More precisely, in both articles, the subspace-based identification problem is recasted into dedicated least-squares problem involving particular user-defined matrices or vectors. In each case, a canonical state-space representation is finally obtained through a simple construction technique. The developed methods can be regarded as alternatives to the standard subspace-based identification methods particularly in situations where the state coordinates basis needs to be maintained constant with respect to the input-output realization used for the estimation. As shown in [Bako, 2008, Chapter 3], these techniques can be related to the propagator-based approach introduced previously. That is the reason why these methods are not further presented in this manuscript. The author invites the reader to study the aforementioned contributions for more details.*

3.3.1.2 Numerical examples

In this paragraph, numerical properties of the approach presented previously are illustrated briefly. For this purpose, a system of the form (3.1) is considered where \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{D} are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A} &= \begin{bmatrix} -0.26 & 0.53 & -0.41 \\ -0.20 & -0.30 & -0.58 \\ 0.75 & 0.33 & -0.20 \end{bmatrix} & \mathbf{B} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.5374 & -0.1919 \\ -0.6848 & 0.2371 \\ -0.4921 & -0.6571 \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{C} &= \begin{bmatrix} -0.6104 & -0.3235 & -0.2164 \\ -0.5969 & 0.6831 & 0.4208 \end{bmatrix} & \mathbf{D} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.18 & 0 \\ 1.50 & 1.24 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.38)$$

The example (3.38) is intentionally chosen such that the modes of the system are not entirely observable (resp. controllable) from a single output (resp. by using a single input), *i.e.*, for any $i \in \{1, 2\}$, $\text{rank}\{\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{c}_i^\top)\} < n_x$ and $\text{rank}\{\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}^\top, \mathbf{b}_i)\} < n_x$, where \mathbf{c}_i^\top and \mathbf{b}_i refer to the rows of \mathbf{C} and the columns of \mathbf{B} respectively and $n_x = 2$. This simulation example is used to illustrate how the propagator method can be used to obtain a canonical representation such as the one in Eq. (3.13) from (i) an arbitrary state-space realization, (ii) a finite sample of I/O data.

Derivation of a canonical form from an arbitrary realization Finding a canonical realization similar to (3.13) for a linear system is, in the general case, far from being trivial. As already argued, such a realization is obtainable only if the \mathbf{A} -matrix is non-derogatory. The traditional methods [Kailath, 1980] proceed firstly by forming a non-singular matrix of the form $\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{c}_i^\top)$ and then by using it to carry out a state transformation. Given the particular

properties of the above example, this conventional procedure fails herein because none of the matrices of this structure is non-singular. In such a situation, our method makes it possible. Because \mathbf{A} in Eq. (3.38) is non-derogatory, Proposition 3.1 ensures that a vector $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ exists such that $\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C})$ has full rank. Because it is aimed at determining the canonical representation from an available realization $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$, the vector $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ can be chosen easily. For example, it can be verified that $\boldsymbol{\kappa} = [1 \ 1]^\top$ fulfills the desired rank condition. A randomly generated $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ fulfills it as well, with probability one.

Derivation of a canonical form from input-output data Now, it is illustrated how a canonical realization of the type (3.13) can be obtained directly from a finite sample of I/O measurements. To this end, a set of identification data is generated with the realization $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ in (3.38) by assuming that the excitation input is a zero-mean white Gaussian noise with unit variance. Because the focus of this first experiment is just to illustrate the feasibility of the approach, the data can be generated noise-free. 100 simulations are drawn with the entries of $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ generated at random (independently for each run) from a uniform distribution in $[-1, 1]$. The vector is subsequently normalized to the unit euclidean norm. Also, the variance-accounted-for between two signals [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007]

$$\text{VAF}_i = \max \left\{ 1 - \frac{\text{var}(y_i(t) - \hat{y}_i(t))}{\text{var}(y_i(t))}, 0 \right\} \times 100\%, \quad (3.39)$$

$i = 1, 2$, is used to measure the fit between the real output $y(t)$ and the output $\hat{y}(t)$ reconstructed from the identified model. For each I/O simulation, the suggested identification approach is applied with the user-defined parameter $f = 5$. The result of this experiment is that $\text{VAF}_i = 100\%$, $i = 1, 2$, for all the 100 simulations. It demonstrates the efficiency of a randomly generated $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$, at least when the data is noise-free.

Discussion on the choice of $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ As shown previously, with the objective of generating a canonical realization (3.13), the vector $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ can be selected very generically when an arbitrary realization is already available or when noise-free data is collected. However, when the parameterization (3.13) must be obtained directly from noisy data, the choice of $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ may become slightly complicated. One reason why it is difficult is the following. When the output is affected by noise, multiplying the output vector by a matrix \mathbf{K} like in Eq. (3.11) changes the statistical properties of the noise. For example, if this one is initially white, it becomes colored (see Eq. (3.34)) thus making the least-squares estimate $\hat{\mathbf{P}}$ biased. A second reason is that the accuracy of the estimation

may be sensitive to the condition number of the similarity transformation matrix $\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C})$. In order to attenuate the effect of the noise, the so-called instrumental variable method is applied. Similarly as in the PO-MOESP algorithm [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007], the instruments are constructed as concatenated past inputs and outputs.

In order to test the performance of the method in this case, a Monte-Carlo experiment composed of 100 I/O simulations is carried out. The process noise and the output noise are drawn from Gaussian distributions that have zero-mean and covariance matrices proportional to the identity. Both noise covariances are designed so that the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) equals 20 dB for both disturbances. For each simulation, the algorithm is run over 1500 identification data by using a vector $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ generated at random and $f = 5$. The identified model is then validated on a sequence of 2000 data which includes the identification data. The results are displayed in Figure 3.1 in terms of the poles of the estimated models. Together with the VAF, they show that, although $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ has been drawn totally at random for each simulation, almost all the simulations achieve correct estimates. The variance of the estimates provided by our algorithm is larger than with the PO-MOESP algorithm. This observation does not come as a surprise because, for our method, a different $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ is used for each run of the algorithm, thus causing the estimates to fluctuate more. If one² of the best $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ (among the 100 previously generated values) is used, and by performing again a Monte-Carlo simulation, results depicted in Figure 3.2 are obtained. It can be observed from this latter figure that, for the above specified value of $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$, our method (which does not use any SVD) performs as well as the PO-MOESP. Moreover, the PO-MOESP procedure does not provide directly a canonical realization so that extra calculations are required to bring the estimated matrices into a canonical form in case this form is needed. The propagator method produces directly a canonical representation.

A heuristic choice of $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ In practice, it may be interesting to have a more systematic way of finding $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$. This paragraph is intended to provide such an approach. The basic idea of this approach is to select $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ so that it is as correlated as possible to the columns of \mathbf{C} , $\mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}$, \dots , $\mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}^{f-1}$. Unfortunately, in the framework of the previous experiment, these matrices are unknown. Therefore, we propose to select the vector $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ from the available I/O measurements as

$$\boldsymbol{\kappa} = \frac{1}{Mn_y} \sum_{i=1}^f \boldsymbol{\Phi}_i \boldsymbol{\Phi}_i^\top \mathbf{1}_{n_y}, \quad (3.40)$$

² $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ is equal to [0.7203 0.6937] in our experiment.

Figure 3.1: Comparison of the poles of the models estimated by the PO-MOESP algorithm and the propagator method (black circles \circ). The red crosses (+) represent the positions of the true poles. κ is generated for each of 100 runs: $\text{VAF}_1 = 86.52 \pm 0.63$ and $\text{VAF}_2 = 99.08 \pm 0.53$ for the propagator method, $\text{VAF}_1 = 89.47 \pm 0.54$ and $\text{VAF}_2 = 99.19 \pm 0.03$ for PO-MOESP.

Figure 3.2: Comparison of the poles of the models estimated by the PO-MOESP algorithm and the propagator method (black circles \circ). The red crosses (+) represent the positions of the true poles. One κ is used for all the 100 runs: $\text{VAF}_1 = 89.32 \pm 0.53$ and $\text{VAF}_2 = 99.17 \pm 0.03$ for the propagator method, $\text{VAF}_1 = 89.37 \pm 0.52$ and $\text{VAF}_2 = 99.18 \pm 0.02$ for PO-MOESP.

where $\mathbf{1}_{n_y}$ stands for a n_y -length vector of ones. Each matrix Φ_i contains n_y rows and follows from the partition $\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp = [\Phi_1^\top \ \cdots \ \Phi_f^\top]^\top$ of $\mathbf{Y}_{f,M}^+ \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{U}_{f,M}^+}^\perp \in \mathbb{R}^{f n_y \times M}$. That is, κ is taken to be the average of the columns of matrices of the form $\Phi_i \Phi_i^\top$. Running a Monte-Carlo simulation with the choice (3.40) of κ results in the outcome depicted in Figure 3.3. This reveals the efficiency of the propagator method.

Figure 3.3: Comparison of the poles of the models estimated by the PO-MOESP algorithm and the propagator method (black circles \circ). The red crosses (+) represent the positions of the true poles. κ is generated for each of 100 runs: $\text{VAF}_1 = 89.15 \pm 0.60$ and $\text{VAF}_2 = 99.19 \pm 0.02$ for the propagator method, $\text{VAF}_1 = 89.4189 \pm 0.51$ and $\text{VAF}_2 = 99.19 \pm 0.02$ for PO-MOESP.

3.3.2 Properties and extensions of the propagator method

To the author's knowledge, the first introduction of the propagator operator for system identification can be dated from 2003 [Mercère et al., 2003a]. In almost ten years, many developments based on the propagator have been put forward. For instance, we can cite

- the theoretical contributions related to
 - the convergence of subspace-based identification algorithms which use the propagator [Mercère et al., 2004, Mercère and Lovera, 2006, 2007],
 - the structural properties of the estimated state-space representation [Mercère and Bako, 2011],

- the adaptations of the time-invariant contributions to linear time-varying systems through the development of recursive algorithms [Mercère et al., 2003a,b, 2005, 2008, Houtzager et al., 2009a, Bergamasco et al., 2011],
- the extensions to switched linear systems [Bako et al., 2007a, 2009b] as well as Hammerstein systems [Bako et al., 2007b, 2009c],
- many efficient applications in aeronautics [De Cock et al., 2006], energetics [Lalot and Mercère, 2008], computer networks [Tanelli et al., 2008] and wind energy [Houtzager et al., 2012, Farah et al., 2011],
- the recent extension to systems operating in closed-loop [Houtzager et al., 2009a, Farah et al., 2010b, Houtzager et al., 2012].

This wide list of achievements can be mainly explained by the fact that the propagator method leads to a canonical form, *i.e.*, invariants of the system, directly from a sufficiently large I/O data set with the help of a modified subspace-based identification technique involving least-squares optimizations only. Such an algorithmic simplicity developed to get invariants of the system is probably the main interest of this technique. For the sake of brevity, the aforementioned results will not be described into details in the following of this chapter. The interested reader can have access to the corresponding references. However, in order to highlight the benefits of the propagator method, the next section will focus on a particular application of the propagator in the system identification framework: the uncertainty domain description. This problem is indeed difficult to solve with standard subspace-based identification techniques because these methods yield fully-parameterized state-space forms estimated up to a similarity transformation. Therefore, before the propagator operator, when talking about uncertainty domain characterization for subspace-based identification estimates, it was compulsory to consider invariants of the system such as the transfer or the poles of the system [Viberg et al., 1991, Bittanti and Lovera, 2000]. Now, with an easy access to a canonical form, the description of specific statistical properties of the subspace-based identification techniques such as the uncertainty domain determination becomes a lot easier. This solution is more precisely described in the next subsection.

3.3.3 Propagator-based subspace identification and uncertainty domain description

System identification is generally viewed as the initial step of a specific design procedure such as, *e.g.*, the design of a controller or a reliable simulator. Although all the system identification algorithms try to identify consistent and

accurate parameters [Ljung, 1999a], the estimated model is only an approximation of the real process, especially when the system has complex dynamics. In order to deal with this shortcoming, an estimate of the model accuracy is required when a reliable design is looked for. For this purpose, the identification procedure must deliver an accurate nominal model as well as a reliable estimate of the uncertainty associated with the model.

In system identification theory, two main philosophies are adopted to characterize the uncertainty domains. The first one is based on statistical assumptions [Goodwin et al., 1992, Ljung, 1999a]. The techniques sharing this basic idea assume that the disturbances acting on the system are realizations of random variables [Ljung, 1997, 1999b]. Because the information on measurement noises is not often available and/or difficult to verify beforehand [de Vries, 1994], a different characterization way can be considered [Ninness and Goodwin, 1995]. This approach is mainly based on deterministic hypotheses, e.g., on the assumption that the residuals are unknown-but-bounded [Giarré and Milanese, 1997, Giarré et al., 1997]. This basic idea has given rise to a number of techniques usually addressed as bounded-error methods or set membership identification [Walter et al., 1996, Belforte et al., 1990, Huang and Gollamudi, 1995, Ramdani and Poignet, 2006]. The main drawback of this approach is its dependence on the way the bound is determined. Notice indeed that the error affecting the system and its identification comes from two sources (the unmodeled dynamics and the noise affecting the data) which makes the bound determination quite complex in practice. In spite of this shortcoming, a bounded-error approach is considered in this section. As shown hereafter, the problem of the bound determination is solved by using specific cost functions and properties of the residuals. This approach makes the bound determination automatic and user-friendly without being too conservative.

A quick look at the literature dedicated to subspace-based identification shows that very little work has been performed as far as the evaluation of model uncertainty is concerned, mainly because of the complexity of the statistical theory underlying subspace-based model identification. This difficulty is (again) mainly due to the fact that most of the subspace-based identification algorithms lead to consistent estimates of fully-parameterized state-space matrices up to a similarity transformation. This similarity transformation introduces a structural flexibility in the model structure. Interesting from a numerical point of view, this flexibility makes the statistical analysis of the estimates quite complicated and the determination of the estimated parameter uncertainty domain very difficult. Thus, only few results are available in the subspace-based identification framework as far as the evaluation of the model uncertainty is concerned. Viberg [Viberg et al., 1991, 1997] was probably the

first to investigate aspects of specific subspace-based identification techniques from a statistical perspective. This work has led to an explicit formulation of the distribution of the estimated poles. During the 90's, efforts were made in the analysis of the statistical properties of the subspace-based identification methods [Deistler et al., 1995, Jansson and Wahlberg, 1998, Bauer and Jansson, 2000]. Most of them are dedicated to proofs of generic consistency and asymptotic normality of the estimates (see [Bauer, 2005] for an overview of the results available until 2005). Interesting from a theoretical point of view, these studies have resulted in complicated limit distribution expressions which are difficult to use in practice (see [Jansson, 2000] for an interesting example). In order to get approximated solutions, a procedure (based on a bootstrap algorithm [Shao and Tu, 1995]) was developed in [Bittanti and Lovera, 2000] resulting in the evaluation of the standard deviation of the frequency response of the estimated models. Notice that, like in [Viberg, 1995] with the estimated poles distributions, these developments only deal with invariants of the system and do not tackle the challenging problem of describing the uncertainty of the parameters of the estimated state-space matrices. This restriction is directly related to the non-uniqueness of the estimates deduced from singular or eigenvalue decompositions [Bauer et al., 1999, Jansson, 2000]. The most recent developments have been carried out by Chiuso and Picci (see [Chiuso and Picci, 2004a,b,c,d] and more recently [Chiuso, 2010]). In these articles, asymptotic variance expressions for the estimated parameters (of systems working under closed-loop conditions) are available. As claimed by the author in [Chiuso, 2010], asymptotic variance of estimated parameters refers to fixed basis or system invariants such as the transfer function, the poles, ... Again, these asymptotic distributions are quite complex and must be adapted according to the invariants required by the user. All these studies and results share the following two characteristics:

- the asymptotic variances expressions are quite complicated and require approximations to be usable in practice,
- the determination of the confidence intervals for the estimated parameters must be restricted to canonical system quantities because of the non-uniqueness of the parameters calculated by using a singular value or an eigenvalue decomposition.

The propagator method has several interesting properties as far the problem of the uncertainty domain description is concerned. First of all, because this technique mainly resorts to least-squares algorithms, the standard tools developed initially for linear regression problems can be adapted in the MIMO state-space framework considered in this chapter. Furthermore, contrary to the standard subspace-based identification methods, the estimated state-space matrices are

minimally parameterized and expressed in a canonical state-space coordinates basis. Thus, the problem of basis reproducibility inherent to the subspace-based identification framework is circumvented and the uncertainty domain computational load is cut down drastically.

In this chapter, it has been chosen to consider a bounded-error approach in order to determine the uncertainty domain of the parameters composing the estimated matrices $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{D})$. This method assumes that the residuals, *i.e.*, $\varepsilon = \mathbf{y} - \hat{\mathbf{y}}$ (with $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ the estimated outputs), are bounded. A particular ellipsoidal iso-level method suggested in [Baron et al., 2001, Farah et al., 2010a,b] is more particularly adopted. In the following, this bounded-error method is first introduced in a quite general case, *i.e.*, for any linearly parameterized MIMO system. Then, thanks to the propagator method, this approach is applied to determine firstly the $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ parameters uncertainty domains and then the $(\mathcal{B}, \mathcal{D})$ parameters uncertainty domains.

3.3.3.1 General case

Consider the following linear regression

$$\mathbf{y} = \Phi^\top \boldsymbol{\theta} + \mathbf{w} \quad (3.41)$$

where $\mathbf{y}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ is the output vector, $\boldsymbol{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta}$ is the parameters vector, $\Phi(t)$ is the regressor and $\mathbf{w}(t)$ is a stochastic process. In this section, our objective is to determine a domain \mathbb{D} such as the true parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}^0 \in \mathbb{D}$.

When dealing with a model defined by Eq. (3.41), the estimation of the parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ can be performed analytically by minimizing the following least-squares criterion [Ljung, 1999a]

$$\begin{aligned} J(\boldsymbol{\theta}) &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \left(\mathbf{y}(t) - \Phi^\top(t) \boldsymbol{\theta} \right)^\top \left(\mathbf{y}(t) - \Phi^\top(t) \boldsymbol{\theta} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \varepsilon^\top(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \varepsilon(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.42)$$

where $\varepsilon(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{y}(t) - \Phi^\top(t) \boldsymbol{\theta}$ is the prediction error. Furthermore, by considering this least-squares setting and by assuming that³

- the system generating the data is in the model set,
- Φ is asymptotically uncorrelated with \mathbf{w} ,

³The generalized expectation operator [Ljung, 1999a], defined by $\bar{\mathbb{E}}(\bullet(t)) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \mathbb{E}(\bullet(t))$, is introduced to deal with stationary and quasi-stationary signals in a similar way.

- the input signal is sufficiently exciting so that $\bar{\mathbb{E}}(\Phi(t)\Phi^\top(t))$ is not singular,

the estimated parameter vector $\hat{\theta}$ is consistent and has an asymptotically normal distribution, a mean equal to θ^0 and covariance equal to $\lambda\mathbf{Q}_\Phi^{-1}$ where λ is the noise variance and where

$$\mathbf{Q}_\Phi = \bar{\mathbb{E}}\left(\Phi(t)\Phi^\top(t)\right). \quad (3.43)$$

In a different way,

$$\hat{\theta} \in N(\theta^0, \mathbf{Q}_\Phi^{-1}/\lambda) \quad (3.44)$$

where $\hat{\theta}$ is an arbitrary estimate of θ . This property allows the definition of confidence intervals as ellipsoids

$$\mathcal{E}_{\hat{\theta}}(\lambda, \mathbf{Q}_\Phi, \alpha) = \left\{ \hat{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^\theta : (\hat{\theta} - \theta^0)^\top \frac{\mathbf{Q}_\Phi^{-1}}{\lambda} (\hat{\theta} - \theta^0) < \chi_\alpha^2(n_\theta) \right\} \quad (3.45)$$

where α is a user-defined probability level and χ_α^2 is the α -percentile of the χ^2 distribution. This is an ellipsoidal domain centered at θ^0 whose shape is given by \mathbf{Q}_Φ . This approach assumes that $\hat{\theta}$ is asymptotically a random vector with Gaussian distribution and mean value θ^0 . Furthermore, the description of this confidence domain depends on the prior knowledge of the noise variance. The problem with this approach is that getting a reliable estimate of the noise variance can be a difficult task in many practical cases. Hereafter, instead of dealing directly with the noise variance, the characterization of the uncertainty domain is performed by using the information contained in the residuals only. To reach this goal, the developments introduced beforehand must be adapted slightly. To do so, consider the cost function (3.42). Then, it can be seen that [Ljung, 1999a]

$$\begin{aligned} J(\theta) &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \left(\mathbf{y}(t) - \Phi^\top(t)\hat{\theta} \right)^\top \left(\mathbf{y}(t) - \Phi^\top(t)\hat{\theta} \right) \\ &+ (\hat{\theta} - \theta)^\top \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \Phi(t)\Phi^\top(t) \right) (\hat{\theta} - \theta) \\ &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \varepsilon^\top(t, \hat{\theta})\varepsilon(t, \hat{\theta}) + (\hat{\theta} - \theta)^\top \mathbf{R}_\Phi (\hat{\theta} - \theta) \end{aligned} \quad (3.46)$$

where

$$\mathbf{R}_\Phi = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \Phi(t)\Phi^\top(t) \quad (3.47)$$

and where $\varepsilon(t, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}})$ are the residuals. The right hand side of Eq. (3.46) is composed of

- the mean square error of the residuals $\frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \varepsilon^\top(t, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \varepsilon(t, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}})$ (computable),
- the term $(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} - \boldsymbol{\theta})^\top \mathbf{R}_\Phi (\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} - \boldsymbol{\theta})$ which can be related to ellipsoids in \mathbb{R}^{n_θ} centered on $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ whose shape is determined by \mathbf{R}_Φ .

Figure 3.4: Illustration of the ellipsoidal approach.

By following the comments available in [Ljung, 1999c], the idea of the method developed herein consists in determining a reliable confidence level on $J(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ in order to ensure that the aforementioned ellipsoids contain the true parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}^0$. To reach this goal, notice first of all that, when $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \boldsymbol{\theta}^0$, we have

$$(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} - \boldsymbol{\theta}^0)^\top \mathbf{R}_\Phi (\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} - \boldsymbol{\theta}^0) = J(\boldsymbol{\theta}^0) - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \varepsilon^\top(t, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \varepsilon(t, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}). \quad (3.48)$$

Thus, by choosing a confidence level

$$M^2 = J(\boldsymbol{\theta}^0) - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \varepsilon^\top(t, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \varepsilon(t, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \quad (3.49)$$

the real parameter vector is located on the border of the domain \mathbb{D} . Hence, to be sure that $\boldsymbol{\theta}^0 \in \mathbb{D}$, the bound M must be chosen such that (see Fig. 3.4)

$$M^2 > J(\boldsymbol{\theta}^0) - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \varepsilon^\top(t, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \varepsilon(t, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}). \quad (3.50)$$

By construction, whatever the statistical properties of \mathbf{w} ,

$$J(\boldsymbol{\theta}^0) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \mathbf{w}^\top(t) \mathbf{w}(t). \quad (3.51)$$

Consequently, a natural way to choose the confidence level M consists in fixing

$$M^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \mathbf{w}^\top(t) \mathbf{w}(t). \quad (3.52)$$

Because it is difficult to measure \mathbf{w} , fixing the size of the ellipsoid domain by using the information contained in the residuals $\varepsilon(t, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}})$ is suggested. This can be done by noticing that

$$\varepsilon(t, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) = \mathbf{y}(t) - \Phi^\top(t) \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = \mathbf{w}(t) - \Phi^\top(t) (\boldsymbol{\theta}^0 - \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}). \quad (3.53)$$

Then, by defining

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{M}^2 &= \frac{1}{N} \max \sum_{t=1}^N \varepsilon^\top(t, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \varepsilon(t, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \\ &= \frac{1}{N} \max \sum_{t=1}^N \left(\mathbf{w}(t) - \Phi^\top(t) (\boldsymbol{\theta}^0 - \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \right)^\top \times \\ &\quad \left(\mathbf{w}(t) - \Phi^\top(t) (\boldsymbol{\theta}^0 - \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (3.54)$$

and by assuming that Φ is uncorrelated with \mathbf{w} , it comes directly that

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{M}^2 &\leq \frac{1}{N} \max \sum_{t=1}^N \mathbf{w}^\top(t) \mathbf{w}(t) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{N} \max \sum_{t=1}^N (\boldsymbol{\theta}^0 - \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}})^\top \Phi(t) \Phi^\top(t) (\boldsymbol{\theta}^0 - \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}). \end{aligned} \quad (3.55)$$

Furthermore, by assuming that $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ is an unbiased estimate of $\boldsymbol{\theta}^0$, we get

$$\bar{\mathbb{E}} \left\{ \left| \Phi^\top(t) (\boldsymbol{\theta}^0 - \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \right| \right\} = \left| \Phi^\top(t) \right| \bar{\mathbb{E}} \left\{ (\boldsymbol{\theta}^0 - \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \right\} = 0. \quad (3.56)$$

Thus, asymptotically, the mean value of $\varepsilon(t, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}})$ tends to \mathbf{w} . So, \tilde{M} is an unbiased estimate of M if $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ is an unbiased estimate of $\boldsymbol{\theta}^0$. It is worth noticing that, when the estimation is biased, *i.e.*, when $\bar{\mathbb{E}} \left\{ (\boldsymbol{\theta}^0 - \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \right\} \neq 0$, \tilde{M} contains the

error due to the noise \mathbf{w} as well as the modeling error ($\boldsymbol{\theta}^0 - \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$). This property is an interesting advantage for the developed uncertainty domain method. Indeed, these regions allow the quantification of the error due to the noise affecting the output of the system as well as the modeling error. Consequently, the uncertainty domain can be described by using the confidence ellipsoids

$$(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} - \boldsymbol{\theta}^0)^\top \mathbf{R}_{\Phi} (\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} - \boldsymbol{\theta}^0) < \tilde{M}^2 \quad (3.57)$$

with

$$\tilde{M}^2 = \frac{1}{N} \max \sum_{t=1}^N \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^\top(t, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(t, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}). \quad (3.58)$$

Notice again that these confidence intervals only resort to the information contained in the residuals.

From a structural point of view, the developments introduced beforehand only require that the model is described with the help of a linear regression. As shown from Eq. (3.35), \mathbf{P} is a least-squares estimate. Because the matrices \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{C} are directly related to the estimate of \mathbf{P} (see Eq. (3.36) for details), the problem of $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ estimation can be written as a linear regression. Thus, the procedure described beforehand can be extended to the uncertainty domain description of the parameters of the matrices \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{C} . As far as \mathcal{B} and \mathcal{D} are concerned, it has been shown that the output of the system can be expressed linearly with respect to \mathcal{B} and \mathcal{D} (see Eq. (3.37)), *i.e.*, as a linear regression. Thus, all the developments introduced for a model satisfying Eq. (3.41) can be adapted to determine the uncertainty domains of the parameters estimated from the propagator.

3.3.3.2 \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{C} parameter uncertainty domains

The goal of this paragraph is to adapt the approach introduced beforehand to the $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ parameters. As shown in Sub-Section 3.3.1, these parameters are directly extracted from the estimated propagator matrix \mathbf{P} . More precisely, these parameters can be related to specific rows of $\hat{\mathbf{P}}$ as follows⁴

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{P}}(n_x + 1, :) \\ \hat{\mathbf{P}}(f + 1, :) \\ \hat{\mathbf{P}}(2f + 1, :) \\ \vdots \\ \hat{\mathbf{P}}((n_y - 1)f + 1, :) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{A}(n_x, :) \\ \mathbf{c}_1^\top \\ \mathbf{c}_2^\top \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{c}_{n_y}^\top \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.59)$$

⁴The first $n_x - 1$ rows of \mathcal{A} and the first row of \mathcal{C} are only made up of 0 and 1.

This sub-matrix $\widehat{\mathbf{P}}$ can be estimated by minimizing the following cost function

$$\left\| \tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_2 - \widehat{\mathbf{P}} \tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_1 \right\|_F^2 \quad (3.60)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_1$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_2$ are respectively deduced from \mathbf{Z}_1 and \mathbf{Z}_2 in a compatible way with $\widehat{\mathbf{P}}$. By using the vectorization tool and the Kronecker product \otimes [Horn and Johnson, 1990], it can be verified that

$$\text{vec}(\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_2^\top) = \underbrace{\left(\mathbf{I}_{(n_y, n_y)} \otimes \tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_1^\top \right)}_{\Phi_{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}}^\top} \underbrace{\text{vec}(\widehat{\mathbf{P}}^\top)}_{\theta_{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}}} \quad (3.61)$$

which is a linear regression equivalent to Eq. (3.41). In a similar way to Paragraph 3.3.3.1, the uncertainty domain can be described by introducing the following confidence ellipsoid

$$\left(\widehat{\theta}_{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}} - \theta_{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}}^0 \right)^\top \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \left(\Phi_{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}}(t) \Phi_{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}}^\top(t) \right) \right) \left(\widehat{\theta}_{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}} - \theta_{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}}^0 \right) < \tilde{M}_{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}}^2 \quad (3.62)$$

where $\theta_{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}}^0$ is the real parameter vector, where $\widehat{\theta}_{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}}$ is an estimate of $\theta_{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}}^0$ and where the level of iso-criterion curves is fixed as

$$\tilde{M}_{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}}^2 = \frac{1}{N} \max \sum_{t=1}^N \varepsilon_{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}}^\top(t, \widehat{\theta}_{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}}) \varepsilon_{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}}(t, \widehat{\theta}_{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}}). \quad (3.63)$$

3.3.3.3 \mathcal{B} and \mathcal{D} parameter uncertainty domains

As far as the uncertainty domains of the parameters of \mathcal{B} and \mathcal{D} are concerned, a similar approach can be considered by noticing that the matrices \mathcal{B} and \mathcal{D} are estimated by using the least-squares cost function

$$\left\| \mathbf{y}(t) - \left[\sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbf{u}^\top(\tau) \otimes \mathcal{C} \mathcal{A}^{t-\tau-1} \quad \mathbf{u}^\top(t) \otimes \mathbf{I}_{n_y} \right] \theta_{\mathcal{B}, \mathcal{D}} \right\|_2 \quad (3.64)$$

where

$$\theta_{\mathcal{B}, \mathcal{D}} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{vec}(\mathcal{B}) \\ \text{vec}(\mathcal{D}) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.65)$$

Although this cost function is linear with respect to $\theta_{\mathcal{B}, \mathcal{D}}$, the main difficulty associated with this criterion is that the estimated \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{C} matrices are involved explicitly. Thus, in order to determine the uncertainty domains of⁵ \mathcal{B} , it is paramount to take into account the uncertainties related to \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{C} .

⁵Notice that there is no combination between \mathcal{D} and \mathcal{A} or \mathcal{C} .

Straightforward calculations based on first order Taylor series approximations lead to (see [Farah et al., 2012] for details)

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{\mathcal{B}}) &= \mathbf{y}(t) - \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbf{u}^{\top}(\tau) \otimes \mathcal{C} \mathcal{A}^{t-\tau-1} \text{vec}(\mathcal{B}) \\ &\approx \boldsymbol{\eta}(t) - \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbf{u}^{\top}(\tau) \otimes \hat{\mathcal{C}} \hat{\mathcal{A}}^{t-\tau-1} \boldsymbol{\theta}_{\mathcal{B}} \end{aligned} \quad (3.66)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\mathcal{B}} = \text{vec}(\mathcal{B})$ and with

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\eta}(t) &= \mathbf{y}(t) - \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} (t - \tau - 1) \mathbf{u}^{\top}(\tau) \otimes \hat{\mathcal{C}} \hat{\mathcal{A}}^{t-\tau-2} (\hat{\mathcal{A}} - \mathcal{A}) \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\mathcal{B}} \\ &\quad - \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbf{u}^{\top}(\tau) \otimes (\mathcal{C} - \hat{\mathcal{C}}) \hat{\mathcal{A}}^{t-\tau-1} \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\mathcal{B}} \end{aligned} \quad (3.67)$$

where $\hat{\bullet}$ denotes the estimate of \bullet . Thus, the cost function (3.64) can be approximated as follows

$$\left\| \boldsymbol{\eta}(t) - \left[\sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbf{u}^{\top}(\tau) \otimes \hat{\mathcal{C}} \hat{\mathcal{A}}^{t-\tau-1} \quad \mathbf{u}^{\top}(t) \otimes \mathbf{I}_{n_y} \right] \boldsymbol{\theta}_{\mathcal{B}, \mathcal{D}} \right\|_2. \quad (3.68)$$

Again, a linear regression similar to Eq. (3.41) is highlighted and, by following the same lines as in Paragraph 3.3.3.1, we obtain an ellipsoidal confidence interval whose shape is fixed via a threshold $\tilde{M}_{\mathcal{B}, \mathcal{D}}^2$ computed from the residuals $\varepsilon(t, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\mathcal{B}, \mathcal{D}})$.

3.3.3.4 Simulation example

In order to highlight the performance of the method described previously, the following LTI state-space system is used⁶

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -3 & -2 & -1 \\ -1 & -2 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}(t) + \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}(t) \quad (3.69a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{v}(t). \quad (3.69b)$$

Instead of dealing with a standard discrete-time (DT) system, it has been chosen to handle a continuous-time (CT) process notably in order to illustrate

⁶This LTI system comes from one of the demonstration program available in the CONTSID Toolbox [Garnier and Gilson, 2009].

the wide applicability of the developed method. As shown in [Farah et al., 2012], the uncertainty domain description technique as well as the propagator method introduced in Paragraph 3.3.1.1 and 3.3.3.2–3.3.3.3 respectively can indeed be extended to the identification of CT systems. Several subspace-based identification methods dedicated to DT processes have already been extended to the identification of CT systems with success (see, e.g., [Moonen et al., 1991, Van Overschee and De Moor, 1996b, Johansson et al., 1999, Haverkamp, 2001, Bastogne et al., 2001, Ohta and Kawai, 2004, Bergamasco and Lovera, 2011], to name some of the main contributions). Most of these CT subspace-based identification algorithms share the following steps

- rewriting of the well-known data equation (2.58) in the CT framework by using particular filters or convolution tools in order to approximate the I/O signals time-derivatives or to substitute dedicated operators for the Laplace transform,
- adaptation of the DT subspace-based mathematical tools (singular value decomposition (SVD), RQ factorization) to this modified data equation in order to extract the estimated state-space matrices efficiently.

The identification algorithms used hereafter do not depart from this rule. Indeed, instead of being applied on DT data directly, the propagator method as well as the uncertainty domain description technique described previously are simply modified so that they can deal with filtered input and output data (see [Farah et al., 2012] for details). Regarding the filter used to approximate the I/O signals time-derivatives involved in the data equation, it has been chosen to resort to the reinitialized partial moments (RPM) [Ouvrard and Trigeassou, 2011] (see, e.g., [Garnier and Wang, 2008] for an overview of the main contributions concerning this approximation problem). According to the studies available in [Garnier et al., 2003, Mercère et al., 2007], the RPM technique, which can be seen as a linear filter method as well as an integral method, is one of the most efficient approximation technique with the advantage of being not too sensitive to its hyper-parameter.

The identification of the model parameters and their uncertainty description are performed by considering the following identification setup

- a sampling period equal to $T_s = 0.1s$ is chosen,
- the initial state vector is chosen equal to zero,
- a Monte Carlo simulation of size 200 is carried out,
- the same input signal, made up of two independent pseudo random binary sequences of size $N = 1000$, is used for the 200 runs,

- for each run, a discrete-time zero-mean Gaussian noise \mathbf{v} is generated, then added up to the output of the system.

In order to reduce the noise effect, past DT inputs are used as instruments variable, *i.e.*, [Mercère et al., 2007]

$$\Xi = \mathcal{U}_p = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}((k-p)T_s) & \mathbf{u}((k+1-p)T_s) & \cdots & \mathbf{u}((N-p)T_s) \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ \mathbf{u}((k-1)T_s) & \mathbf{u}(kT_s) & \cdots & \mathbf{u}((N-1)T_s) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.70)$$

where $p \geq \frac{n_x}{n_u}$. As proven in [Mercère et al., 2007], such an instrumental variable leads to unbiased estimates when the noise acting on the output of the system satisfies

Assumption 3.1 \mathbf{v} is statistically independent of the input signal \mathbf{u} (open-loop condition).

Assumption 3.2 \mathbf{v} is a measurement noise constant between two samples, *i.e.*,

$$\mathbf{v}(t) = \mathbf{v}(kT_s)$$

for $kT_s \leq t < (k+1)T_s$ where T_s is the sampling period. Furthermore, the sequence $\{\mathbf{v}(t_k)\}$, $t_k = kT_s$, is a zero-mean normally distributed (white or filtered) noise with a finite covariance matrix.

This last assumption (inspired by Johansson's work for CT system identification (see [Johansson, 1994, Johansson et al., 1999] or [Garnier and Wang, 2008, Chapter 10] for details)) can be justified (from a practical as well as a theoretical point of view) by the fact that such a DT form

- is much more flexible than standard CT models (such as, *e.g.*, the Wiener process used in [Haverkamp, 2001]) and easier to implement in the estimation problem,
- can be related to its CT white noise counterpart via its rational spectral density (see [Garnier and Wang, 2008, Section 10.2] for a discussion concerning this property).

Zero-mean white Gaussian noise In this paragraph, a DT white Gaussian noise is added on both outputs such that the signal to noise ratio⁷ (SNR) on both outputs equals 35dB. In order to underline the efficiency of the developed method, a comparison of the estimated poles obtained by using

⁷Herein, $\text{SNR} = 10 \log \left(\frac{P_{y_d}}{P_v} \right)$ where P_{\bullet} is the power of the signal \bullet and where y_d stands for the deterministic part of y .

- a CT version of the propagator method introduced in [Farah et al., 2012]
- the RPM+PIMOESP method developed in [Mercère et al., 2007],

is performed. The RPM+PIMOESP algorithm is an extension of the standard DT PIMOESP algorithm [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007] with filtered I/O data (obtained hereafter by using the RPM filter) (see [Mercère et al., 2007] for details). In both cases, the past and future horizons (resp. p and f) are chosen equal to 4. Fig. 3.5 shows the estimated poles calculated by using the CT propagator method as well as the RPM+PIMOESP method. These plots clearly show that

- the variance of the estimated poles is quite similar in both cases,
- the CT propagator method yields unbiased estimates of the real poles.

Notice that this last comment is supported by the figures available in Tab. 3.1.

Real poles	Propagator method	RPM+PIMOESP
-2	-1.98	-2.09
-0.5 ± 0.866	-0.48 ± 0.790	-0.48 ± 0.801

Table 3.1: Mean values of the estimated poles using the CT propagator method and the RPM+PIMOESP method for a zero-mean white Gaussian noise as output disturbance.

The second step of this simulation analysis consists in studying the uncertainty domains determined by following the approach described previously. Fig. 3.6 and Fig. 3.7 illustrate this analysis. More precisely, on these figures are gathered

- the estimated parameter couple $(\mathcal{A}(3, 1), \mathcal{A}(3, 2))$ (resp. $(\mathcal{B}(1, 1), \mathcal{B}(1, 2))$), (symbolized by the blue cross *),
- the real parameters (red cross \times),
- the mean value of the estimated parameters (black cross +),
- black disks • corresponding to the estimated parameters for which the real parameters are outside of the ellipsoid \mathcal{D} centered in the estimated parameters vector.

Figure 3.5: Estimated pole obtained with the CT propagator method and the RPM+PIMOESP method (o). The real poles of the system are symbolized by the red crosses (+).

A first comparison of the relative position of the black crosses $+$ and the red crosses \times on both figures indicates that the estimates obtained with the CT propagator method are accurate. This observation reinforces the conclusion drawn from the analysis of Fig. 3.5 and Tab. 3.1. Then, by focusing on the black disks \bullet which basically represent the mis-quantification of the uncertainty domain, it is interesting to notice that they are not so numerous. In order to quantify this impression, a failure rate measurement is introduced. This measurement is defined as the percentage of realizations for which the parameters are outside of the domain \mathbb{D} . The failure rate equals 7% for the couple $(\mathcal{A}(3, 1), \mathcal{A}(3, 2))$ and 10% for the couple $(\mathcal{B}(1, 1), \mathcal{B}(1, 2))$. The same order of magnitude is obtained for all of the estimated parameters. These figures show that the developed method performs quite well for this simulation example.

Figure 3.6: Level surfaces of the cost function $J_{\hat{\mathbf{P}}}$. The real parameters are symbolized by a red cross (\times), the estimated parameters by a blue stars ($*$) and the mean value of the estimated parameters by a black cross ($+$). Black discs (\bullet) are finally the mis-quantification of the uncertainty domains.

Zero-mean colored Gaussian noise For this second experimental setup, the disturbance \mathbf{v} is a zero-mean colored Gaussian noise. More precisely, \mathbf{v} is obtained by filtering a zero-mean white Gaussian noise \mathbf{e} by a first order filter, *i.e.*,

$$\mathbf{v}(t) = \frac{1}{1 - 0.8q^{-1}} \mathbf{e}(t) \quad (3.71)$$

such that the signal to noise ratio equals 35 dB. The Monte Carlo identification procedure described previously is again carried out with such a zero-mean

Figure 3.7: Level surfaces of the cost function $J_{\mathcal{B}}$. The real parameters are symbolized by a red cross (\times), the estimated parameters by a blue stars ($*$) and the mean value of the estimated parameters by a black cross ($+$). Black discs (\bullet) are the mis-quantification of the uncertainty domains.

colored Gaussian noise. As illustrated by Tab. 3.2, similar results as those obtained with a zero-mean white Gaussian noise acting on the output of the system are highlighted. As far as the uncertainty domains are concerned, failure rates respectively equal to 7.2% for the couple $(\mathcal{A}(3, 1), \mathcal{A}(3, 2))$ and 10.3% for the couple $(\mathcal{B}(1, 1), \mathcal{B}(1, 2))$ are obtained. Despite this small increase of mis-quantification, we can conclude that the developed approach performs satisfactory even with colored output noise. These good results can be jus-

Real poles	Propagator method	RPM+PIMOESP
-2	-1.97	-2.1
-0.5 ± 0.866	-0.48 ± 0.802	-0.48 ± 0.801

Table 3.2: Mean values of the estimated poles using the CT propagator method and the RPM+PIMOESP method for a zero-mean colored Gaussian noise as output disturbance.

tified by noticing that, when the measured output is filtered through a RPM filter in order to be used by the CT propagator method or the RPM+PIMOESP algorithm, the white noise acting on the system becomes colored. Thus, for a CT subspace-based identification algorithm, the treatment of a colored output noise or a white output noise are almost equivalent. That is also the reason

why the instrumental variable $\Xi = \mathcal{U}_p$ performs well when a zero-mean colored Gaussian noise acts on the outputs of the system.

3.4 Conclusions

In this chapter, a new subspace-based identification method leading to a user-defined parameterized state-space form has been described. More precisely, a method able to build and to estimate a MIMO canonical state-space model directly from data has been introduced. This work is motivated by an important feature of the canonical state-space models: they constitute an identifiable state-space model structure that has the minimum number of independent parameters. The state coordinates basis of such models is set in a particularly simple manner. This last property makes canonical forms very suitable for the identification of systems such as linear parameter-varying systems and switched linear systems where all sub-systems must be described with respect to compatible state coordinates bases. Contrary to the conventional approaches, the suggested method does not require the so-called observability/controllability indexes (or equivalent indices) in order to build canonical forms for multivariable systems. On the contrary, the similarity transformation matrix depends on a user-defined vector κ generated such that $\text{rank}\{\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \kappa^\top \mathbf{C})\} = n_x$. It is interesting to point out that, in the identification framework, this vector can be selected in a heuristic way directly from the I/O data. Because the deduced state-space representation contains a companion matrix for the state matrix, this technique is only usable for minimal systems with a non-derogatory \mathbf{A} -matrix. Notice that this condition is satisfied in many practical cases, *e.g.*, for any linear observable MISO (or controllable SIMO) system, or for MIMO systems with distinct poles. A dedicated subspace-based identification algorithm has been described leading to the canonical realization directly from I/O data. Among all the available extensions and adaptations of this approach in the wide identification framework, a specific attention has been paid to the uncertainty domain description of the estimated parameters. Thanks to the propagator method and the following estimated canonical state-space form, it is indeed possible to describe the uncertainty domains of the estimated parameters by adapting a bounded-error approach. These uncertainty regions allow the quantification of the error due to the noise affecting the outputs of the system as well as the modeling error. The efficiency of the developed methods has been illustrated by using specific simulation examples. These simulation results have highlighted the benefits of our approach in comparison with methods available in the literature.

CHAPTER 4

Identification of parameterized gray-box state-space systems

4.1 Motivations and problem formulation

The previous chapters have been essentially dedicated to the estimation of the state-space matrices of systems described by the following black-box discrete-time state-space form¹

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{w}(t) \quad (4.1a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{v}(t) \quad (4.1b)$$

by using specific subspace-based identification methods. Interesting for their easiness of implementation as well as their numerical robustness, the applicability of the subspace-based identification techniques drops drastically when a physically-based structure of the state-space matrices must be taken into account. By physically-based structure, it is meant that the state-space matrices (\mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C}) depend on unknown parameters (gathered into the vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$) in a specific way, known *a priori* and often derived from the laws of physics governing the behavior of the system, *i.e.*, the state-space forms studied hereafter are gray-box models. If the true system contains physical parameters, then the model estimated with the standard subspace-based identification algorithms no longer contains the physical parameters in a form which makes their extraction easy. From an input/output point of view, the identified model often has excellent performance measures, but as far as the physical interpretation is concerned, the identified model is useless. The question then is, how to recover the physical parameters once the system has been identified in a fully-

¹In this chapter, for the sake of conciseness, because the feed-forward matrix \mathbf{D} is a similarity invariant, only strictly proper systems are considered, *i.e.*, $\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{0}$ without loss of generality. Notice however that most of the following developments can be extended to proper systems.

parameterized form. The goal of this chapter is to introduce techniques (related in a certain manner to the subspace-based identification methods) which can take into account this structural constraint. Contrary to the developments introduced in Chapter 3, the following algorithms are not dedicated to structured canonical black-box models but to gray-box ones, *i.e.*, the structure of the model as well as the resulting state variables have a physical interpretation.

Remark 4.1 *The literature dedicated to the parameterization of the state-space representations is full of structured models (e.g., the output normal form, the tridiagonal form or the standard canonical forms [Kailath, 1980, McKelvey and Helmersson, 1996, Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007] or the parameterizations introduced in Chapter 3). Unfortunately, most of them have no physical meaning. That is the reason why these black-box parameterized state-space forms are not taken into account in the following of this chapter.*

As shown, *e.g.*, in [Maciejowski, 1995, Trnka and Havlena, 2009], it is possible to constraint specific subspace-based identification algorithms (*e.g.*, particular CCA-type algorithms [Trnka and Havlena, 2009]) with prior knowledge such as a requirement of guaranteed stability [Lacy and Bernstein, 2003] or the knowledge of specific time-domain characteristics (static gain, time constant, ...) [Trnka and Havlena, 2009]. However, to the author's knowledge, very few papers are dedicated to the subspace-based identification of systems with non-fully-parameterized structures. We can cite [Massioni and Verhaegen, 2008] for circulant systems, [Lyzell et al., 2009] for the ARMAX model structure or [Hagg et al., 2010] for cascade systems. The difficult incorporation of specific structural information into the subspace-based estimates is mainly related to the fact that most of the subspace-based identification algorithms lead to fully-parameterized state-space models in some unknown coordinate bases, *i.e.*, the estimated matrices are known and unique modulo a non-singular similarity transformation matrix. Thus, in general, the direct application of standard subspace-based identification algorithms cannot be performed if structured state-space models are sought. In order to circumvent this difficulty, two complementary² directions can be followed.

- First, by assuming that reliable and consistent fully-parameterized subspace-based estimates (\mathfrak{A} , \mathfrak{B} , \mathfrak{C}) are available, their conversion into a user-defined structured model ($\mathbf{A}(\theta)$, $\mathbf{B}(\theta)$, $\mathbf{C}(\theta)$) can be tackled. A solution to this problem consists in determining the similarity transformation \mathbf{T} as well as the vector θ satisfying

$$\mathfrak{A}\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{A}(\theta) \quad \mathfrak{B} = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{B}(\theta) \quad \mathfrak{C}\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{C}(\theta) \quad (4.2)$$

²As shown hereafter, the first one can be used to initialize the second one.

where θ is the vector gathering the unknown parameters of the structured model $(\mathbf{A}(\theta), \mathbf{B}(\theta), \mathbf{C}(\theta))$.

- Second, knowing the parameterization of the state-space representation $(\mathbf{A}(\theta), \mathbf{B}(\theta), \mathbf{C}(\theta))$, a direct estimation of the parameter vector θ can be performed by optimizing a performance index such as the following cost function

$$V_N(\theta) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \|\mathbf{y}(k) - \mathbf{y}_m(k, \theta)\|_2^2 \quad (4.3)$$

with respect to θ where $\mathbf{y}(t)$ is the output of the system and $\mathbf{y}_m(t, \theta)$ its model counterpart. According to the definition of the signal $\mathbf{y}_m(t, \theta)$ (the one-step ahead predictor or the simulated outputs of the model), the prediction-error methods [Ljung, 1999a] or the output-error methods [Söderström and Stoica, 1989] can be used to solve this optimization problem. Interesting for the analysis of the accuracy of the estimates, the use of criteria such as $V_N(\theta)$ generally leads to non-convex optimization problems and requires, by extension, non-linear programming for its minimization [Nocedal and Wright, 2006]. Such non-convex optimization problems can often be efficiently solved by resorting to regularized Gauss-Newton methods such as the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm [Marquardt, 1963]. However, in order to ensure that the calculated minimum is the global minimum of the criterion, a reliable initial estimate of the parameter vector θ is mandatory. In order to solve this initialization problem, the idea developed in this chapter consists in using as an initial parameter vector the one estimated by solving the problem related to Eq. (4.2) and described previously.

Thus, the following of this chapter will be mainly dedicated to the problem of the efficient initialization of standard non-linear programming gradient-based algorithms used for the estimation of structured state-space matrices. By efficient, it is meant that the solution of the problem introduced hereafter only needs to be an estimate lying inside the attraction region of the global optimum of $V_N(\theta)$. More precisely, solutions to the following problem will be considered

Problem 4.1 *Consider a linear time-invariant system modeled by a minimal and structured gray-box state-space representation $(\mathbf{A}(\theta), \mathbf{B}(\theta), \mathbf{C}(\theta))$ where the matrices are functions of relatively few unknown parameters gathered into a vector θ . Furthermore, let us assume that a consistent fully-parameterized minimal state-space realization $(\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{C})$ of the system under study is available³. Then,*

³The subspace-based identification techniques [Ljung, 1999a, Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007]

the problem considered hereafter consists in determining uniquely the similarity transformation \mathbf{T} as well as the vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ satisfying

$$\mathfrak{A}\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \quad \mathfrak{B} = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \quad \mathfrak{C}\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}). \quad (4.4)$$

However, before addressing this problem and coming up with solutions available in the literature as well as with new developments, two important points must be discussed. First, in order to avoid misunderstandings in the following of this chapter, the notion of structure used herein must be commented a little more, especially its close link with the notion of identifiability. Second, a short presentation of the output-error method must be delivered in order to introduce important notations, to define its applicability and to stress the importance of a good initial parameter vector. Thus, this chapter is built as follows. Section 4.2 is dedicated to the definition of the identifiability concept and its consequences as far as gray-box state-space model identification is concerned. Section 4.3 sums up the main steps handled by the output error method and points out the reasons why a reliable initial parameter vector is compulsory to ensure that the involved optimization algorithms converge towards the optimal parameter vector. Section 4.4 introduces new developments and solutions for the problem 4.1 stated previously. Concluding remarks are given in Section 4.5.

4.2 Physically-structured state-space representation and identifiability

As it was mentioned previously, the following of this chapter is aimed at identifying structured gray-box LTI state-space systems. In practice, the use of a structured model is often dictated by physical constraints. More precisely, in many practical cases, the structure of the state-space model to identify can be motivated by the physical laws governing the behavior of the system. Because, most of the time, these physical laws lead to continuous-time equations, the deduced state-space representation is continuous-time. Thus, in the following, it will be assumed that the state-space system satisfies the continuous-time (CT) set of equations⁴

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{u}(t) \quad (4.5a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{x}(t). \quad (4.5b)$$

are really good candidates to solve this problem. These algorithms can indeed yield consistent estimates in many different noisy cases.

⁴In order to make a difference between the discrete-time matrices ($\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, $\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, $\mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$) and the continuous-time ones ($\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, $\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, $\mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$), slightly different notations (italic and non-italic) are used.

One of the advantages of this physically-structured model is that the prior knowledge is conveniently used thanks to its parameterization as well as the physical interpretation of the parameters and the resulting state variables. Such a parameterization (with a physical meaning) is particularly important when the values of the estimated parameters are specifically of interest. This is the case, for instance, if the model is dedicated to diagnosis based on parameter change detection. For this problem, the parameters of the model must be uniquely retrieved from the available input-output data. In the identification framework, the property of uniqueness is related to the identifiability of the parameterization. In order to explain this important notion, some definitions must be remembered and introduced (see Chapter 3 and [Ljung, 1999a, Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007]).

Definition 4.1 *A model structure (or parameterization) π is a differentiable mapping from a parameter set $\Theta \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta}$ to a set of models.*

For instance, the model set can be chosen as the set gathering the stable LTI state-space models with a McMillan degree equal to n_x or the set of all $n_y \times n_u$ proper rational transfer functions with real coefficients and a degree at most equal to n_x (see Chapter 3). Then, the notion of identifiability can be defined as follows [Ljung, 1999a]

Definition 4.2 *A model structure π is locally identifiable at $\theta^* \in \Theta$ if a neighborhood $\nu(\theta^*)$ of θ^* exists such that*

$$\bar{\theta} \in \nu(\theta^*) \text{ and } \pi(\bar{\theta}) = \pi(\theta^*) \Rightarrow \bar{\theta} = \theta^*. \quad (4.6)$$

Definition 4.3 *A model structure π is globally identifiable if*

$$\pi(\bar{\theta}) = \pi(\theta^*) \Rightarrow \bar{\theta} = \theta^* \quad (4.7)$$

for almost all $(\bar{\theta}, \theta^*) \in \Theta^2$.

These last two definitions imply that a locally (resp. globally) identifiable structure π is a locally (resp. globally) injective mapping. From a practical point of view, with a globally identifiable structure,

- a unique value of θ represents a unique model [McKelvey, 1995],
- a consistent identification algorithm able to deal with this structure will lead to a unique parameter vector θ asymptotically if the data is informative enough (noise-free data, ...) and if the numerical issues are disregarded [McKelvey, 1998].

Thus, it is quite obvious that dealing with an identifiable parameterization is of prime concern when the structure of the LTI state-space model has been deduced from physical considerations and the resulting sought parameters have a physical interpretation. On the contrary, to the author's point of view, if the values of the estimated parameters are not of interest, fully-parameterized state-space representations should be favored because

- their parameterization is trivial,
- they include all the possible systems of a given order n_x [McKelvey, 1995]
- they can have better numerical sensitivity than several structured parameterization,
- a big amount of dedicated identification algorithms have been developed [McKelvey, 1995, Ljung, 1999a, Gibson and Ninness, 2005, Wills and Ninness, 2008]. In addition to the subspace-based identification algorithms (see [Haverkamp, 2001, Bergamasco and Lovera, 2010a] and references therein for CT subspace-based identification), recent developments [Ribarits, 2002, Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007, Gibson and Ninness, 2005, Wills and Ninness, 2008] based on regularized versions of the Gauss-Newton algorithm have been considered to deal with fully-parameterized state-space representations.

Remark 4.2 *The notion of parameterization introduced in this chapter is slightly different from the one used in Chapter 3. Indeed, herein, the structure of the model is obtained from prior knowledge and results in a specific state sequence. In Chapter 3, black-box models were involved. In addition to this difference of physical meaning for the models, it is interesting to notice that the surjectivity of the mapping π obtained from prior physical knowledge is always satisfied because, by construction, the prior knowledge determines the class of system of interest. Therefore, for the parameterizations studied in this chapter, the injectivity of the mapping is (only) of prime concern.*

Although the following developments can be extended to structured parameterization without physical interpretation (such as specific canonical forms), from now on, it is assumed that the structure of the model $(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))$ has been obtained from physical considerations and that the parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ has a physical meaning. Related to this hypothesis, it can be assumed that

the structure

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}) : \Theta \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta} &\longmapsto \mathbb{R}^{n_x(n_x+n_u+n_y)} \\
 \boldsymbol{\theta} &\longmapsto \begin{bmatrix} \text{vec}(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) \end{bmatrix}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.8}$$

is identifiable at least locally. As a straightforward consequence, the number of parameters to estimate will be, at most, $n_x(n_u + n_y)$ [McKelvey, 1995]. Indeed, it is known that the set of all possible input-output behaviors of LTI systems with n_u inputs, n_y outputs and a McMillan degree n_x is a manifold of dimension $n_x(n_u + n_y)$ [McKelvey and Helmerrsson, 1996, 1997]. Then, as far as the problem of determining the similarity transformation \mathbf{T} as well as the vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ from the set of equations (4.2), the identifiability of the parameterization $(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))$ results in the uniqueness of the solutions $\hat{\mathbf{T}}$ and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$. This important property arises from a combination of results available in [Glover and Willems, 1974] and [Kailath, 1980]. More precisely, the following proposition can be set⁵ (see Theorem 1 in [Glover and Willems, 1974])

Theorem 4.1 *Let us define a parameterization*

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}) : \Theta \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta} &\longmapsto \mathbb{R}^{n_x(n_x+n_u+n_y)} \\
 \boldsymbol{\theta} &\longmapsto \begin{bmatrix} \text{vec}(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) \end{bmatrix}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.9}$$

of the system matrices $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C})$ where Θ is an open subset of \mathbb{R}^{n_θ} and let us assume that the parameterization $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C})(\boldsymbol{\theta})$

- is continuously differentiable on Θ ,
- is minimal.

Then,

1. $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C})(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is locally identifiable at $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \boldsymbol{\theta}^*$ if and only if the mapping

$$\begin{aligned}
 G : \Theta \times GL(n_x) &\longmapsto \mathbb{R}^{n_x(n_x+n_u+n_y)} \\
 (\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T}) &\longmapsto \begin{bmatrix} \text{vec}(\mathbf{T}\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{T}^{-1}) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbf{T}\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{T}^{-1}) \end{bmatrix}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.10}$$

is locally injective at $\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x}$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \boldsymbol{\theta}^*$.

⁵In this proposition, the group $GL(n_x)$ consists of the set of all the $n_x \times n_x$ real matrices whose determinant is non-zero [Horn and Johnson, 1990].

2. if

$$\text{rank}\left(\frac{\partial G(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x})}{\partial(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T})}\right) = r \quad (4.11)$$

for all $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ in the neighborhood $\nu(\boldsymbol{\theta}^*)$ of $\boldsymbol{\theta}^*$, then $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C})(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is locally identifiable at $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \boldsymbol{\theta}^*$ if and only if $r = n_x^2 + n_\theta$ or, equivalently, if and only if

$$\det\left(\mathbf{X}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}^*)\mathbf{X}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^*)\right) \neq 0 \quad (4.12)$$

where

$$\mathbf{X}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} \otimes \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \mathbf{A}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \otimes \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} & \frac{\partial \text{vec}(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \\ -\mathbf{B}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \otimes \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} & \frac{\partial \text{vec}(\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \\ \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} \otimes \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) & \frac{\partial \text{vec}(\mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.13)$$

This Theorem has strong impacts as far as the identifiability notion is concerned. First, from a practical point of view, the item 2 of the theorem introduces the rank test (4.12) of the sparse matrix $\mathbf{X}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ which can be performed before carrying out the identification procedure, more precisely without requiring the availability of the input and output signals. This test is reliable only in a neighborhood of the solution $\boldsymbol{\theta}^*$ which is not available. However, several scenarii can be tested numerically in order to give insights into the possible local identifiability of the structure. Second, from a theoretical point of view, this Theorem is really interesting as far as Problem 4.1 is concerned. In order to highlight this characteristic, let us consider the minimal parameterization $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C})(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ and let us assume that

- this parameterization is locally identifiable at $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \boldsymbol{\theta}^*$,
- a reliable minimal fully-parameterized realization $(\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{C})$ of the system is available,
- a neighborhood $\nu(\boldsymbol{\theta}^*)$ of the point $\boldsymbol{\theta}^*$ can be defined,
- two parameter vectors $\boldsymbol{\theta}_1 \in \nu(\boldsymbol{\theta}^*)$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta}_2 \in \nu(\boldsymbol{\theta}^*)$ are available.

Then, by assuming that $(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1), \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1), \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1))$, $(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_2), \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_2), \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_2))$ and $(\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{C})$ are minimal realizations of the system, according to [Kailath, 1980, Theorem 6.2.4], two unique invertible matrices \mathbf{T}_1 and \mathbf{T}_2 exist such that

$$\mathfrak{A}\mathbf{T}_1 = \mathbf{T}_1\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) \quad \mathfrak{B} = \mathbf{T}_1\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) \quad \mathfrak{C}\mathbf{T}_1 = \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) \quad (4.14a)$$

$$\mathfrak{A}\mathbf{T}_2 = \mathbf{T}_2\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_2) \quad \mathfrak{B} = \mathbf{T}_2\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_2) \quad \mathfrak{C}\mathbf{T}_2 = \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_2) \quad (4.14b)$$

or, equivalently, a unique similarity transformation \mathbf{T} exists such that

$$\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_2)\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) \quad \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_2) = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) \quad \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_2)\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) \quad (4.15)$$

with

$$\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{T}_2^{-1} \mathbf{T}_1 \quad (4.16)$$

and [Kailath, 1980, De Schutter, 2000]

$$\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{\Omega}_r(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_2), \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_2)) \mathbf{\Omega}_r^\top(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1), \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1)) \\ (\mathbf{\Omega}_r(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1), \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1)) \mathbf{\Omega}_r^\top(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1), \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1)))^{-1} \quad (4.17)$$

or

$$\mathbf{T}^{-1} = (\mathbf{\Gamma}_r^\top(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1), \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1)) \mathbf{\Gamma}_r(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1), \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1)))^{-1} \\ \mathbf{\Gamma}_r^\top(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1), \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1)) \mathbf{\Gamma}_r(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_2), \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_2)) \quad (4.18)$$

where r is the minimal order of the system and where

$$\mathbf{\Gamma}_r(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C}) = [\mathbf{C}^\top \quad \dots \quad (\mathbf{C} \mathbf{A}^{r-1})^\top]^\top \quad (4.19a)$$

$$\mathbf{\Omega}_r(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) = [\mathbf{B} \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{A}^{r-1} \mathbf{B}]. \quad (4.19b)$$

Then, according to Theorem 4.1 Item 1, if the model structure is locally identifiable at $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \boldsymbol{\theta}^*$, then the mapping $G(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T})$ is locally injective at $\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x}$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \boldsymbol{\theta}^*$. The injectivity of the function $G(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T})$ results in

$$\mathbf{T} \approx \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} \Rightarrow \mathbf{T}_1 \approx \mathbf{T}_2 \quad (4.20a)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\theta}_1 \approx \boldsymbol{\theta}_2 \approx \boldsymbol{\theta}^* \quad (4.20b)$$

for $\boldsymbol{\theta}_1 \in \nu(\boldsymbol{\theta}^*)$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta}_2 \in \nu(\boldsymbol{\theta}^*)$. Thus, by assuming the local identifiability of the model structure $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C})(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, the uniqueness of the similarity transformation \mathbf{T} and the parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ can be ensured. This property is paramount for the identification problem considered hereafter. Hence, the following assumption will be considered in the sequel

Assumption 4.1 *The minimal parameterization $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C})(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is identifiable at $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \boldsymbol{\theta}^*$ at least locally.*

4.3 Description of the output-error parametric estimation problem

In the field of system identification, the estimation of the parameters of a model often involves a non-convex optimization [Ljung, 1999a, Nocedal and Wright, 2006]. For instance, this is the case with the output-error method

[Söderström and Stoica, 1989] where the goal is to estimate the parameter vector θ related to the state-space model

$$\dot{\chi}(t, \theta) = \mathbf{A}(\theta)\chi(t, \theta) + \mathbf{B}(\theta)\mathbf{u}(t) \quad (4.21a)$$

$$\gamma(t, \theta) = \mathbf{C}(\theta)\chi(t, \theta) \quad (4.21b)$$

from a finite number of samples of the input signals and the output signals of the system (see Eq. (4.5)) $\{\mathbf{u}(t_k), \mathbf{y}(t_k)\}$, $k = [1, N]$, $t_k = kT_s$ where T_s is the sampling period. In Eq. (4.21), a different notation (from the original system (4.5)) is used for the output of the model $\gamma(t, \theta)$ and the state sequence $\chi(t, \theta)$. This difference is introduced in order to highlight the fact that the outputs of the model (4.21) depend not only on the input signal \mathbf{u} but also on the parameter vector θ as well as the initial state.

All along this chapter, it is assumed that the parameterization of the state-space matrices $(\mathbf{A}(\theta), \mathbf{B}(\theta), \mathbf{C}(\theta))$ is known *a priori*. Notice that θ only contains the parameters to estimate. Indeed, these matrices can have parameters which are known *a priori*.

Remark 4.3 *In this chapter, it has been chosen to consider output-error models and techniques only. This choice can be justified as follows [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007]. First, we are only interested in estimating efficiently the deterministic part of the system. No model of the noise term is looked for. Second, the output-error does not require any k -step ahead predictors (as handled by the prediction-error method [Ljung, 1999a]). In a certain way, this feature makes the output-error approach easier. However, it must be noticed that many steps introduced hereafter can be extended to the prediction-error framework.*

By having access to a set of reliable⁶ I/O data, the parameter vector θ can be estimated by minimizing the output-error cost function [Ljung, 1999a]

$$V_N(\theta) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \|\mathbf{y}(t_k) - \gamma(t_k, \theta)\|_2^2 \quad (4.22)$$

with respect to θ where \mathbf{y} is the output of the system and γ the output of the model. Most of the time, the structure of the model (4.21) leads to a non-convex cost function. Thus, an iterative gradient-based search [Boyd and Vandenberghe, 2004] is necessary to optimize $V_N(\theta)$. We can cite the Gauss-Newton method, the steepest descent method or the Levenberg-Marquardt

⁶By reliable, it is meant that the input is persistently exciting and that the length of the data set is sufficient. The problem of optimal input design is not considered in this manuscript. See, e.g., [Wahlberg et al., 2006, Hjalmarsson and Martensson, 2007, Wahlberg et al., 2011], for recent discussions about this problem.

technique (see [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007, Chapter 7] for an interesting overview of these algorithms in the output-error framework). For instance, the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm satisfies

$$\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i+1)} = \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)} - \left(\frac{\partial^2 V_N(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}^\top \partial \boldsymbol{\theta}} \Big|_{\boldsymbol{\theta}=\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)}} + \lambda \mathbf{I}_{n_y \times n_y} \right)^{-1} \frac{\partial V_N(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}} \Big|_{\boldsymbol{\theta}=\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)}} \quad (4.23)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)}$ is the estimate at the iteration i and λ is a positive user-defined parameter tuned so that [Ljung, 1999a]

- the term $\frac{\partial^2 V_N(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}^\top \partial \boldsymbol{\theta}} \Big|_{\boldsymbol{\theta}=\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)}} + \lambda \mathbf{I}_{n_y \times n_y}$ is not singular,
- the optimization algorithm can switch between the Newton method ($\lambda = 0$) and the steepest descent method ($\lambda \gg 1$) according to the distance of the current estimate to the optimal value.

Notice that, by introducing approximations for the Hessian as, e.g.,

$$\frac{\partial^2 V_N(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}^\top \partial \boldsymbol{\theta}} \approx \frac{2}{N} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_N(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}^\top} \right)^\top \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_N(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}^\top} \quad (4.24)$$

we get the Gauss-Newton method [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007] where

$$\mathbf{E}_N(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y}(t_1) - \boldsymbol{\gamma}(t_1, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \\ \mathbf{y}(t_2) - \boldsymbol{\gamma}(t_2, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{y}(t_N) - \boldsymbol{\gamma}(t_N, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.25)$$

Under this assumption, the components of Eq. (4.23), i.e., $\frac{\partial V_N(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}}$ and $\frac{\partial^2 V_N(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}^\top \partial \boldsymbol{\theta}}$, can be calculated by resorting to the simulation of the LTI state-space model [Lee and Poolla, 1996, Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007]

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\chi}}(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\boldsymbol{\chi}(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) + \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{u}(t) \quad (4.26a)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\gamma}(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\boldsymbol{\chi}(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \quad (4.26b)$$

associated with the linear systems for $j \in [1, n_\theta]$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \dot{\boldsymbol{\chi}}(t, \boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \theta(j)} \Big|_{\boldsymbol{\theta}=\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)}} &= \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\chi}(t, \boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \theta(j)} \Big|_{\boldsymbol{\theta}=\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)}} \\ &+ \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \theta(j)} \Big|_{\boldsymbol{\theta}=\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)}} \boldsymbol{\chi}(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) + \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \theta(j)} \Big|_{\boldsymbol{\theta}=\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)}} \mathbf{u}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (4.27a)$$

$$\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\gamma}(t, \boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \theta(j)} \Big|_{\boldsymbol{\theta}=\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)}} = \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\chi}(t, \boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \theta(j)} \Big|_{\boldsymbol{\theta}=\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)}} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \theta(j)} \Big|_{\boldsymbol{\theta}=\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)}} \boldsymbol{\chi}(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \quad (4.27b)$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\theta} = [\theta(1) \ \theta(2) \ \dots \ \theta(n_\theta)]^\top. \quad (4.28)$$

Remark 4.4 *The use of a regularized Gauss-Newton method can be related to the use of non-injective parameterizations [McKelvey, 1994, 1998].*

As iterative algorithms, all the aforementioned gradient-based techniques must be efficiently initialized in order to ensure a consistent final estimation (corresponding to the global minimum of the criterion). In other words, the user must have an initial vector $\theta^{(0)}$ in the domain of attraction of the global optimum of $V_N(\theta)$. When this condition is satisfied, the convergence towards the global minimum of the criterion $V_N(\theta)$ can be guaranteed [Söderström and Stoica, 1989, Ljung, 1999a].

While the subspace-based identification algorithms cannot deal with parameterized state-space models directly, they yield reliable (but not necessarily optimal) fully-parameterized estimates (\mathfrak{A} , \mathfrak{B} , \mathfrak{C}) of the state-space matrices (A , B , C). By having access to this reliable fully-parameterized black-box model (\mathfrak{A} , \mathfrak{B} , \mathfrak{C}), as suggested in [Xie and Ljung, 2002] and [Parrilo and Ljung, 2003], the initialization problem inherent to the output-error methods can be circumvented by transforming the state-space form (\mathfrak{A} , \mathfrak{B} , \mathfrak{C}) into a representation satisfying the structure of ($A(\theta)$, $B(\theta)$, $C(\theta)$). More precisely, by assuming that the system is minimal [Kailath, 1980] and the structure of the model is identifiable [Ljung, 1999a], this problem consists in determining uniquely the similarity transformation T as well as the parameter vector θ satisfying

$$\mathfrak{A}T = TA(\theta) \quad \mathfrak{B} = TB(\theta) \quad \mathfrak{C}T = C(\theta). \quad (4.29)$$

This challenging problem is investigated in the next Section.

Remark 4.5 *It was claimed beforehand that the subspace-based identification algorithm can yield reliable black-box estimates (\mathfrak{A} , \mathfrak{B} , \mathfrak{C}). When dealing with continuous-time state-space matrices ($A(\theta)$, $B(\theta)$, $C(\theta)$), it is compulsory to get continuous-time over-parameterized state-space matrices (\mathfrak{A} , \mathfrak{B} , \mathfrak{C}). In order to get these continuous-time black-box matrices, two solutions can be investigated. First, a standard discrete-time subspace-based identification algorithm [Katayama, 2005] can be used to get a consistent discrete-time model. Then, for instance, the following bilinear transformation can be applied [Datta, 2003]*

$$\mathfrak{A} \leftarrow \frac{2}{T_s} (\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} + \mathfrak{A})^{-1} (\mathfrak{A} - \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x}) \quad (4.30a)$$

$$\mathfrak{B} \leftarrow \frac{2}{\sqrt{T_s}} (\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} + \mathfrak{A})^{-1} \mathfrak{B} \quad (4.30b)$$

$$\mathfrak{C} \leftarrow \frac{2}{\sqrt{T_s}} \mathfrak{C} (\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} + \mathfrak{A})^{-1} \quad (4.30c)$$

in order to get an equivalent continuous-time representation (see also [Sinha, 2000, Garnier and Wang, 2008] for other efficient solutions). Second, a subspace-based identification algorithm dedicated to the continuous-time state-space representations can be used. Recent developments are available in [Haverkamp, 2001, Mercère et al., 2007, Garnier and Wang, 2008, Bergamasco and Lovera, 2011] and the references therein. Notice that this initial continuous-time model must be good enough to be used, after it re-parameterization, as an initial parameter vector for a gradient-based optimization algorithm. Thus, the non-optimality of this initial estimation step is not so restrictive in practice. We only need a reliable initial continuous-time state-space model in the domain of attraction of the global optimum of $V_N(\boldsymbol{\theta})$.

4.4 From a fully-parameterized black-box model to a parsimonious model structure

In the literature dedicated to Problem 4.1, two main families of methods can be highlighted. Historically, the first solutions aimed at calculating the parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and the similarity transformation \mathbf{T} by minimizing the error involved in the set of equations (4.29). More precisely, Xie and Ljung in [Xie and Ljung, 2002] were the first to write down a mathematical solution to this quite complex problem. Unfortunately, as shown in Sub-Section 4.4.2, their solution still uses an iterative algorithm which requires good initial values. This problem was reconsidered by Parrilo and Ljung in 2003. More precisely, it is reformulated as a polynomial optimization problem which avoids an iterative algorithm. Despite its mathematical robustness, this solution is limited to small size matrices (around 20-24 unknown parameters as claimed by the authors). Surprisingly, to the author's knowledge, after these first attempts, it took six years to re-address the initial problem 4.1 [Lyzell et al., 2009, Ramos and Lopes dos Santos, 2010]. However, instead of translating this problem into an (un)constrained optimization one, a new reformulation of the set of equations (4.29) was first suggested in [Lyzell et al., 2009], then extended in [Ramos and Lopes dos Santos, 2010] to a null-space-based problem.

Both approaches are described in the following sub-sections. First (see Sub-Section 4.4.1), the null-space-based methods are introduced, then (see Sub-Section 4.4.2) the techniques involving optimization are put forward. For each case, a short description of the literature dedicated to this physical parameter estimation problem is given, then improvements and general solutions are investigated. Sub-Section 4.4.3 illustrates these developments by using simulation examples.

4.4.1 Null-space-based techniques

Before developing complex solutions for this bilinear problem, it is quite natural to analyze Eq. (4.29) in order to see if this system of equations can be solved directly, *i.e.*, if it is possible to extract from this system of equations a sufficiently large set of equations where the bilinear terms (*i.e.*, involving \mathbf{T} and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$) are absent. Surprisingly, to the author's knowledge, this way of dealing with the aforementioned problem has "only" been studied recently [Lyzell et al., 2009, Ramos and Lopes dos Santos, 2010]. Initially suggested in [Lyzell et al., 2009] and, in a way, generalized in [Ramos and Lopes dos Santos, 2010], the direct solutions consist in analyzing the set of equations (4.29) by using a standard property of the vectorization [Horn and Johnson, 1990]

$$\text{vec}(\mathbf{MNP}) = (\mathbf{P}^\top \otimes \mathbf{M})\text{vec}(\mathbf{N}) \quad (4.31)$$

where \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{N} and \mathbf{P} are matrices with compatible dimensions. Indeed, this mathematical tool leads to

$$(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} \otimes \mathfrak{A})\text{vec}(\mathbf{T}) = (\mathbf{A}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \otimes \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x})\text{vec}(\mathbf{T}) \quad (4.32a)$$

$$(\mathbf{B}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \otimes \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x})\text{vec}(\mathbf{T}) = \text{vec}(\mathfrak{B}) \quad (4.32b)$$

$$(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} \otimes \mathfrak{C})\text{vec}(\mathbf{T}) = \text{vec}(\mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})). \quad (4.32c)$$

This system is composed of $n_x^2 + n_x(n_u + n_y)$ equations. By assuming that the structured matrices $(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))$ have a maximum of $n_x(n_u + n_y)$ parameters, which corresponds to the maximum number of parameters in an identifiable representation of the system [McKelvey, 1995], we have, at worst, as many equations as unknown parameters⁷. This property can be really interesting when dealing with linear systems. Unfortunately, in the general case, the set of equations (4.29) is a bilinear form. As suggested by Lyzell et al. in [Lyzell et al., 2009], the bilinear terms can be avoided when specific structured model are considered, for instance, a SISO observer canonical form

$$\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_1 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & 0 \\ \theta_2 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \theta_{n_x-2} & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \theta_{n_x-1} & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & 0 & 1 \\ \theta_{n_x} & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_{n_x+1} \\ \theta_{n_x+2} \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \theta_{n_x+n_u} \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{C}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.33)$$

Under such conditions, by selecting only the equations involving the state matrices $\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, $\mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, \mathfrak{A} and \mathfrak{C} , Eq. (4.32) becomes

$$\mathbf{\Pi}\text{vec}(\mathbf{T}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_x^2} \\ 1 \\ \mathbf{0}_{n_x-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.34)$$

⁷Keep in mind that the similarity transformation $\mathbf{T} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$ must be estimated as well.

with

$$\mathbf{\Pi} = \begin{bmatrix}
 \mathfrak{A} - \theta_1 \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} & -\theta_2 \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} & -\theta_3 \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} & \cdots & -\theta_{n_x-1} \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} & -\theta_{n_x} \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} \\
 -\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} & \mathfrak{A} & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\
 \mathbf{0} & \ddots & \ddots & & & \vdots \\
 \vdots & & \ddots & \ddots & & \vdots \\
 \vdots & & & \ddots & \ddots & \mathbf{0} \\
 \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \cdots & \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} & \mathfrak{A} \\
 \mathfrak{C} & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\
 \mathbf{0} & \mathfrak{C} & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\
 \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & & & \vdots \\
 \vdots & & \ddots & \ddots & & \vdots \\
 \vdots & & & \ddots & \ddots & \mathbf{0} \\
 \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \mathbf{0} & \mathfrak{C}
 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.35)$$

This system contains $n_x^2 + n_x$ equations⁸. By noticing that the bilinear terms are only present in the first n_x row block, $\text{vec}(\mathbf{T})$, which is composed of n_x^2 unknown parameters, can be estimated from the remaining n_x^2 equations. This solution is computable if the matrix composed of the corresponding n_x^2 rows in $\mathbf{\Pi}$ has full rank. This condition only depends on the state matrices \mathfrak{A} and \mathfrak{C} and can be verified beforehand. This solution can be adapted when the unknown parameters of $\mathbf{A}(\theta)$ lie in one row (see [Lyzell, 2009] for details).

By following the same idea, Ramos and Lopes dos Santos suggested in [Ramos and Lopes dos Santos, 2010] adapting the previous technique by transforming the system of equations (4.32) into a null-space problem. Interesting from a theoretical point of view, the null-space reformulation available in [Ramos and Lopes dos Santos, 2010] is unfortunately limited to specific state-space forms. Thanks to straightforward manipulations of the equations (4.32), the developments suggested in [Ramos and Lopes dos Santos, 2010] can be generalized leading to the following rewriting

$$(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} \otimes \mathfrak{A})\text{vec}(\mathbf{T}) - \text{vec}(\mathbf{T}\mathbf{A}(\theta)) = \mathbf{0} \quad (4.36a)$$

$$\text{vec}(\mathbf{T}\mathbf{B}(\theta)) - \text{vec}(\mathfrak{B}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (4.36b)$$

$$(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} \otimes \mathfrak{C})\text{vec}(\mathbf{T}) - \text{vec}(\mathbf{C}(\theta)) = \mathbf{0}, \quad (4.36c)$$

⁸Remember that $n_y = 1$.

or, in a matrix form

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} (\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} \otimes \mathfrak{A}) & -\mathbf{I}_{n_x^2 \times n_x^2} & \mathbf{0}_{n_x^2 \times n_x n_u} & \mathbf{0}_{n_x^2 \times n_x n_y} & \mathbf{0}_{n_x^2} \\ \mathbf{0}_{n_x n_u \times n_x^2} & \mathbf{0}_{n_x n_u \times n_x^2} & \mathbf{I}_{n_x n_u \times n_x n_u} & \mathbf{0}_{n_x n_u \times n_x n_y} & -\text{vec}(\mathfrak{B}) \\ (\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} \otimes \mathfrak{C}) & \mathbf{0}_{n_x n_y \times n_x^2} & \mathbf{0}_{n_x n_y \times n_x n_u} & -\mathbf{I}_{n_x n_y \times n_x n_y} & \mathbf{0}_{n_x n_y} \end{bmatrix}}_{\text{matrix } \Delta} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \text{vec}(\mathbf{T}) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbf{T}\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbf{T}\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}}_{\text{vector } \boldsymbol{\tau}} = \mathbf{0}_{n_x^2 + n_x(n_u + n_y)}, \quad (4.37)$$

where $\Delta \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x^2 + n_x(n_u + n_y) \times (2n_x^2 + n_x(n_u + n_y) + 1)}$ is composed of known coefficients⁹, while $\boldsymbol{\tau} \in \mathbb{R}^{(2n_x^2 + n_x(n_u + n_y) + 1)}$ gathers the unknown parameters. In order to simplify the notation, the re-definitions $n_\tau = 2n_x^2 + n_x(n_u + n_y) + 1$ and $n_\Delta = n_x^2 + n_x(n_u + n_y)$ will be used.

First, by construction, the matrix Δ is of dimension $(n_x^2 + n_x(n_u + n_y)) \times (2n_x^2 + n_x(n_u + n_y) + 1)$. Thus, by construction, the homogeneous system of equations (4.37) is under-determined. Second, because $\text{rank}(\Delta) \leq n_x^2 + n_x(n_u + n_y)$, from the rank-nullity theorem [Horn and Johnson, 1990], we get

$$\dim(\text{null}(\Delta)) \geq n_x^2 + 1. \quad (4.38)$$

This inequality, more precisely the fact that $\dim(\text{null}(\Delta)) > 1$, makes the determination of the vector $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ quite complicated. The estimation of the null-space can be performed by resorting to a singular value decomposition of Δ . Indeed, for any matrix $\mathbf{M} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ with r non-zero singular values, the null-space of \mathbf{M} is spanned by the right singular vectors corresponding to the $n - r$ zero singular values of \mathbf{M} [Horn and Johnson, 1990]. However, because the null-space of Δ is spanned by more than one vector, the determination of the vector $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ solution of Eq. (4.37) is not an easy task. As shown in [Ramos and Lopes dos Santos, 2010], for some specific state-space forms, different (but model-dependent) matrices Δ can be introduced with a null-space of a smaller dimension. These solutions are obtained

- by manipulating the initial set of equations so that the physical parameters can be extracted in a linear fashion,
- by adding new equations extracted, *e.g.*, from the relations between the observability (resp. controllability) matrices of the fully-parameterized

⁹Keep in mind that a consistent fully-parameterized state-space triplet $(\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{C})$ is assumed to be available.

state-space form and the structured one. These matrices are indeed directly related via the similarity transformation \mathbf{T} .

By doing so, the problem is directly solvable via a well-chosen combination of SVD (see [Ramos and Lopes dos Santos, 2010] for details). Unfortunately, this solution is not generic. Indeed, for each model structure, a new set of equations must be added or removed and new manipulations must be performed in order to find suitable and convenient null-space problems of smaller dimensions.

In the following of this sub-section, a solution to the general null-space problem (4.37) is introduced. More precisely, a multi-step technique is put forward which results in a solution $\hat{\tau}$ so that

- (i) the last component of $\hat{\tau}$ is equal to 1,
- (ii) the matrices \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{C} involved in $\hat{\tau}$ satisfy structural constraints known *a priori* (presence of 1 or 0 at specific places in the matrices, redundancy in the parameters, ...),
- (iii) the similarity transformation involved in $\hat{\tau}$ is invertible.

By having access to this solution $\hat{\tau}$, the similarity transformation \mathbf{T} as well as the structured state-space matrices $(\mathbf{A}(\theta), \mathbf{B}(\theta), \mathbf{C}(\theta))$ can be extracted from τ as follows

$$\hat{\mathbf{T}} = \text{reshape}(\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\tau}, n_x, n_x) \quad (4.39a)$$

$$\mathbf{A}(\hat{\theta}) = \hat{\mathbf{T}}^{-1}\text{reshape}(\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{A}}\hat{\tau}, n_x, n_x) \quad (4.39b)$$

$$\mathbf{B}(\hat{\theta}) = \hat{\mathbf{T}}^{-1}\text{reshape}(\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{B}}\hat{\tau}, n_x, n_u) \quad (4.39c)$$

$$\mathbf{C}(\hat{\theta}) = \text{reshape}(\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{C}}\hat{\tau}, n_y, n_u), \quad (4.39d)$$

where the selection matrices \mathbf{P}_{\bullet} are defined as follows

$$\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{T}} = [\mathbf{I}_{n_x^2 \times n_x^2} \quad \mathbf{0}_{n_x^2 \times n_x^2 + n_x(n_u + n_y) + 1}] \quad (4.40a)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{A}} = [\mathbf{0}_{n_x^2 \times n_x^2} \quad \mathbf{I}_{n_x^2 \times n_x^2} \quad \mathbf{0}_{n_x^2 \times n_x(n_u + n_y) + 1}] \quad (4.40b)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{B}} = [\mathbf{0}_{n_x n_u \times 2n_x^2} \quad \mathbf{I}_{n_x n_u \times n_x n_u} \quad \mathbf{0}_{n_x n_u \times n_x n_y + 1}] \quad (4.40c)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{C}} = [\mathbf{0}_{n_x n_y \times 2n_x^2 + n_x n_u} \quad \mathbf{I}_{n_x n_y \times n_x n_y} \quad \mathbf{0}_{n_x n_y \times 1}] \quad (4.40d)$$

and where $\text{reshape}(\bullet, n_1, n_2)$ returns the $n_1 \times n_2$ matrix whose elements are taken columnwise from \bullet .

4.4.1.1 General formulation

The solution proposed in this paragraph is mainly decomposed into three steps

1. the determination of the components of the null-space of Δ satisfying the constraint (i),
2. the construction of a state-space form from the estimated vector $\hat{\tau}$,
3. the optimization of the afore-estimated state-space form so that the structural constraints satisfied by $\mathbf{A}(\theta)$, $\mathbf{B}(\theta)$ and $\mathbf{C}(\theta)$ are verified (see constraint (ii)).

Because the first step of the developed algorithm consists in determining the null-space of Δ satisfying condition (i), it is quite natural to define the affine space of admissible τ vectors satisfying $\tau(end) = 1$, *i.e.*,

$$\mathcal{X} = \{\tau \in \text{null}(\Delta) : \tau(end) = 1\}. \quad (4.41)$$

In the following, $n_{\mathcal{X}} \in \mathbb{N}$ will denote the dimension of \mathcal{X} . Then, by following the same lines as those given in the previous paragraph, for all $\tau \in \mathcal{X}$, the second step of the algorithm requires the definition of functions equivalent to Eq. (4.39), *i.e.*,

$$\mathbb{T}(\tau) = \text{reshape}(\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{T}}\tau, n_x, n_x) \quad (4.42a)$$

$$\mathbb{A}(\tau) = \mathbb{T}^{-1}(\tau)\text{reshape}(\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{A}}\tau, n_x, n_x) \quad (4.42b)$$

$$\mathbb{B}(\tau) = \mathbb{T}^{-1}(\tau)\text{reshape}(\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{B}}\tau, n_x, n_u) \quad (4.42c)$$

$$\mathbb{C}(\tau) = \text{reshape}(\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{C}}\tau, n_y, n_x). \quad (4.42d)$$

The rational functions in τ , $\mathbb{A}(\tau)$ and $\mathbb{B}(\tau)$, can be defined if and only if the matrix $\mathbb{T}(\tau)$ is invertible (see constraint (iii)). Unfortunately, this matrix may not be invertible on the whole affine space \mathcal{X} . However, by defining

$$\begin{aligned} g: \mathcal{X} &\longmapsto \mathbb{R} \\ \tau &\longmapsto \det(\mathbb{T}(\tau)) \end{aligned} \quad (4.43)$$

and

$$\mathcal{S} = g^{-1}(\{0\}) \quad (4.44)$$

the functions $\mathbb{A}(\tau)$ and $\mathbb{B}(\tau)$ are well-defined on the open set $\mathcal{X} \setminus \mathcal{S}$. From a practical point of view, it is important to know whether, for $\tau \in \mathcal{X}$, the probability to get a singular matrix $\mathbb{T}(\tau)$ is weak or not. By assuming that the mapping g is a submersion [Lang, 1998], *i.e.*, g is a differentiable map whose differential is everywhere surjective, the set \mathcal{S} is a smooth sub-manifold of \mathcal{X} of dimension $n_{\mathcal{X}} - 1$. Thus, basically, if g is a submersion, the amount of singular matrices $\mathbb{T}(\tau)$ for $\tau \in \mathcal{X}$ is quite small. Furthermore,

Proposition 4.1 *if Assumption 4.1 is satisfied and if g is a submersion, then \mathcal{S} has an empty interior.*

Proof 4.1 *If g is not a submersion and if a vector $\tau_0 \in \mathcal{X}$ and a scalar $\varepsilon > 0$ exist such that $g(\tau) = 0$ with $\|\tau - \tau_0\| \leq \varepsilon$, then g equals zero over \mathcal{X} . Indeed, under the aforementioned conditions, g is a polynomial which vanishes on the set $N_\varepsilon = \{\tau \in \mathcal{X} : \|\tau - \tau_0\| \leq \varepsilon\}$ and N_ε has a non-empty interior for the topology of affine space \mathcal{X} . Thus, for all $\tau \in \mathcal{X}$, $\mathbb{T}(\tau)$ is singular and Eq. (4.29) cannot be satisfied. As a consequence, the identifiability assumption is no more verified. Hence, under the assumption of an identifiable model structure, the set \mathcal{S} has an empty interior.*

Remark 4.6 *In order to avoid some numerical problems related to the existence of the open set \mathcal{S} , the functions $\mathbb{A}(\tau)$ and $\mathbb{B}(\tau)$ can be defined by resorting to the Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse $\mathbb{T}^\dagger(\tau)$ instead of $\mathbb{T}^{-1}(\tau)$ [Horn and Johnson, 1990]. This allows the computation of $\mathbb{A}(\tau)$ and $\mathbb{B}(\tau)$ for all τ in \mathcal{X} . However, for the identification problem considered herein, whatever the technique used for the computation of $\mathbb{A}(\tau)$ and $\mathbb{B}(\tau)$, values of τ such that \mathbb{T} is nearly singular are not desirable.*

The third step of the optimization procedure consists in constraining the state-space data set $(\mathbb{A}(\tau), \mathbb{B}(\tau), \mathbb{C}(\tau))$ in order to satisfy specific structural constraints known from the parameterization $\mathbf{A}(\theta)$, $\mathbf{B}(\theta)$ and $\mathbf{C}(\theta)$. Mathematically, such structural constraints can be modelled with the help of a function f_S defined as follows

$$\begin{aligned} f_S : \mathbb{R}^{n_\Delta} &\longmapsto \mathbb{R}^+ \\ \gamma &\longmapsto f_S(\gamma) \end{aligned} \quad (4.45)$$

where, for $\tau \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\tau}$,

$$\gamma(\tau) = \begin{bmatrix} \text{vec}(\mathbb{A}(\tau)) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbb{B}(\tau)) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbb{C}(\tau)) \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\Delta} \quad (4.46)$$

such that

- $f_S : \mathbb{R}^{n_\Delta} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^+$ is a continuous function,
- if $f_S(\gamma) = 0$, then γ satisfies the afore-mentioned parameterization constraints.

Thus, τ can be identified by solving

$$\min_{\tau \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \mathcal{S}} f_S(\gamma(\tau)). \quad (4.47)$$

Because γ is a rational function of τ , it is a smooth function on the set $\mathcal{X} \setminus \mathcal{S}$. Thus, the cost function $\tau \mapsto f_S(\gamma(\tau))$ is continuous on the set $\mathcal{X} \setminus \mathcal{S}$. Furthermore, it can be proved that a solution to Eq. (4.47) exists either by assuming the coercivity of the cost function [Folland, 1995] or by constraining the search of τ inside a compact set.

Remark 4.7 *Under the assumption that the model structure is identifiable, the solution of Eq. (4.47) is unique. Herein, it has been chosen to use a numerical optimization method in order to compute this solution. Alternatively, because γ is a rational function, theoretically, Eq. (4.47) could have been solved by using computer algebra. This is however not straightforward and further studies are required to find the analytic solution efficiently.*

Up until now, no explicit expressions of the cost function f_S have been put forward. In fact, the parameterization $(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))$ can be used to build a convenient cost function f_S . Like γ , let us define, for $\boldsymbol{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta}$, the vectorized form

$$\boldsymbol{\kappa}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{bmatrix} \text{vec}(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\Delta}. \quad (4.48)$$

Then, a convenient choice for the f_S function may be

$$f_S(\gamma) = \inf_{\boldsymbol{\eta} \in \Omega} \|\boldsymbol{\eta} - \gamma\|_2^2. \quad (4.49)$$

where Ω is defined as follows

$$\Omega = \{\boldsymbol{\kappa}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) : \boldsymbol{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta}\} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_\Delta}. \quad (4.50)$$

In the definition of f_S , the standard Euclidean norm on \mathbb{R}^{n_Δ} is used. It may be replaced with any other distance on this space.

4.4.1.2 Affine parameterization case

The optimization of the cost function (4.49) is not really easy in the general case. However, when the function $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ is affine with respect to $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, a simpler expression of the cost function (4.49) can be put forward. More precisely, when this condition is satisfied, a vector $\boldsymbol{\kappa}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\Delta}$ as well as a matrix $\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\Delta \times n_\theta}$ exist such that

$$\boldsymbol{\kappa}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \boldsymbol{\kappa}_0 + \mathbf{K}\boldsymbol{\theta}. \quad (4.51)$$

By using this parameterization, the cost function (4.49) satisfies

$$f_S(\gamma) = \inf_{\boldsymbol{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta}} \|\boldsymbol{\kappa}_0 + \mathbf{K}\boldsymbol{\theta} - \gamma\|_2^2. \quad (4.52)$$

The computation of the projection of $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\Delta}$ onto the affine space Ω is straightforward by using a singular value decomposition of \mathbf{K} . Indeed, this tool leads to the solution

$$\theta^* = (\mathbf{K}^\top \mathbf{K})^\dagger \mathbf{K}^\top (\kappa_0 - \gamma) \quad (4.53)$$

where, again, $(\bullet)^\dagger$ is the Moore-Penrose pseudo inverse [Horn and Johnson, 1990] computed from the SVD of \mathbf{K} . By using explicitly this solution, the criterion $f_S(\gamma)$ becomes

$$f_S(\gamma) = \|\mathbf{M}_\mathbf{K}(\kappa_0 - \gamma)\|_2^2 \quad (4.54)$$

where the orthogonal projection $\mathbf{M}_\mathbf{K}$ is defined as follows

$$\mathbf{M}_\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{K}^\top \mathbf{K})^\dagger \mathbf{K}^\top - \mathbf{I}_{n_\Delta \times n_\Delta}. \quad (4.55)$$

This simplification leads to a much simpler optimization problem

$$\min_{\tau \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \mathcal{S}} \|\mathbf{M}_\mathbf{K}(\kappa_0 - \gamma(\tau))\|_2^2. \quad (4.56)$$

Notice unfortunately that this new criterion is still non-convex in general because γ is often not an affine but a rational function with respect to τ . Problems of local minima can arise from this non-convexity.

4.4.1.3 Parameterization of the affine space \mathcal{X}

In practice, a parameterization of the affine space \mathcal{X} can be used to solve the afore-mentioned optimization problem. This parameterization is based on a three-step procedure. First, a basis of the null-space of Δ is computed by using an SVD. By denoting by $\mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\tau \times n_Z}$ this basis, the second step consists in determining¹⁰ a vector $\beta_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{n_Z}$ such that $\mathbf{Z}\beta_0 \in \mathcal{X}$, *i.e.*, $\mathbf{Z}\beta_0$ satisfies the constraint (i). By having access to this vector β_0 , the third step aims at computing a basis of the null-space of the last row of \mathbf{Z} . By doing so, a matrix \mathbf{Z}_2 can be built so that, for all $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^{n_Z-1}$, the last component of the vector $\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}_2\alpha$ is zero. By using these three steps, the affine space \mathcal{X} can be parameterized as follows

$$\mathcal{X} = \{\mathbf{Z}(\beta_0 + \mathbf{Z}_2\alpha) : \alpha \in \mathbb{R}^{n_Z-1}\}. \quad (4.57)$$

Notice that this parameterization implies that $n_\mathcal{X} = n_Z - 1$. By using Eq. (4.57), the optimization problem (4.47) becomes

$$\min_{\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\mathcal{X}}} f_S(\gamma(\mathbf{Z}(\beta_0 + \mathbf{Z}_2\alpha))). \quad (4.58)$$

¹⁰This can be done, *e.g.*, by generating β_0 randomly, then by computing $\mathbf{Z}\beta_0$ and finally by fixing $\beta_0 = \beta_0 / ((\mathbf{Z}\beta_0)(end))$.

By extension, the optimization problem (4.56) satisfies

$$\min_{\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^{p, x}} \|\mathbf{M}_K(\boldsymbol{\kappa}_0 - \gamma(\mathbf{Z}(\boldsymbol{\beta}_0 + \mathbf{Z}_2\boldsymbol{\alpha}))\|_2^2. \quad (4.59)$$

This parameterization makes the optimization a lot easier.

4.4.2 (Un)constrained optimization techniques

A different way to solve the problem (4.29) simply consists in minimizing the error involved in the equations (4.29) [Xie and Ljung, 2002, Parrilo and Ljung, 2003]. More precisely, this problem can be solved by resorting to a least-squares formulation of Eq. (4.29), *i.e.*, the optimization of a cost function $F(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T})$ defined as follows [Xie and Ljung, 2002, Parrilo and Ljung, 2003]

$$F(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T}) = \|\mathbf{2}\mathbf{T} - \mathbf{T}\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\|_F^2 + \|\mathbf{3} - \mathbf{T}\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\|_F^2 + \|\mathbf{C}\mathbf{T} - \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\|_F^2. \quad (4.60)$$

Again, like the initial problem, this cost function is bilinear with respect to $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and \mathbf{T} . The first solution, available in [Xie and Ljung, 2002], relies on the following observation: by assuming that $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ (resp. \mathbf{T}) is known *a priori*, the cost function $F(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T})$ is linear with respect to \mathbf{T} (resp. $\boldsymbol{\theta}$). In this case, this problem is well-suited for applying least-squares methods. This point is the basis of the developments available in [Xie and Ljung, 2002]. More precisely, a two-step iterative algorithm (summed up in Algo. 1) switching between two combined least-squares minimizations with respect to \mathbf{T} and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is considered. The main advantage of this algorithm is the use of linear regressions and least-

Algorithm 1 Optimization algorithm developed in [Xie and Ljung, 2002] to minimize $F(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T})$

Choose an initial parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}_0$ (using prior information)

For $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = \boldsymbol{\theta}_0$,

$\hat{\mathbf{T}} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{T}} F(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}, \mathbf{T})$ with a least-squares algorithm

while $F(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}, \hat{\mathbf{T}}) > \epsilon$ (with ϵ chosen by the user) **do**

$\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = \arg \min_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} F(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \hat{\mathbf{T}})$ with a least-squares algorithm

$\hat{\mathbf{T}} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{T}} F(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}, \mathbf{T})$ with a least-squares algorithm

end while

squares optimizations. The key issue of such an iterative algorithm is still its initialization. Indeed, because $F(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T})$ is a non-convex criterion, a bad initial parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}_0$ (or \mathbf{T}_0) may still lead to a local optimum. A discussion concerning this problem as well as solutions for specific parameterizations are available in [Xie and Ljung, 2002]. Unfortunately, in many situations, the initialization of the iterative algorithm Algo. 1 is almost as difficult as the initialization of the initial optimization problem.

Inspired by the developments in [Xie and Ljung, 2002], Parrilo and Ljung have reformulated the optimization of $F(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T})$ as a polynomial optimization problem which avoids an iterative algorithm [Parrilo and Ljung, 2003]. This method uses specific sum of squares decompositions [Parrilo, 2000] to provide a lower bound on the optimal value. Despite its mathematical robustness, this solution is limited to small size matrices (around 20-24 unknown parameters as claimed by the authors [Parrilo and Ljung, 2003]).

In this sub-section, the cost function adopted in [Xie and Ljung, 2002] and [Parrilo and Ljung, 2003] is considered again and the underlying optimization problem is revisited. This revision is mainly based on the following observation pointed out by [Parrilo and Ljung, 2003]: the global solution to the optimization of $F(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T})$ may be unusable in practice because of a nearly singular transformation matrix \mathbf{T} at the global optimum. This situation must be avoided by taking care of the condition number of this matrix during the optimization. Thus, in the following of this sub-section, a new cost function is introduced in order to control the condition number of \mathbf{T} . By construction, the function introduced hereafter is non-smooth because of the constraint on the condition number. To bypass this difficulty, specialized algorithms are used to solve such a non-smooth optimization problem. Bundle methods are efficient techniques in the field of non-smooth optimization [Bonnans et al., 2006]. The spectral bundle method [Apkarian et al., 2008, Noll et al., 2008] is more precisely used because of its good convergence properties.

It is important to point out (again) that our objective is not to find the global optimum, but rather a good local one in order to initialize the iterative gradient-based algorithm used in the final output-error method.

4.4.2.1 General formulation and solution

In order to perform the estimation of the vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ as well as the similarity transformation matrix \mathbf{T} , *i.e.*, in order to find a local optimum of the cost function F , a quasi-Newton Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno (BFGS) method can be used [Nocedal and Wright, 2006]. To set up this method, the gradients of the cost function F with respect to $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and \mathbf{T} must be computed. This gradient computation can be performed as follows. By assuming that the structured state-space matrices depends on $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ linearly, the matrices $d\mathbf{A}$, $d\mathbf{B}$ and $d\mathbf{C}$ can be defined as follows

$$\text{vec}(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) = d\mathbf{A}\boldsymbol{\theta} \quad \text{vec}(\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) = d\mathbf{B}\boldsymbol{\theta} \quad \text{vec}(\mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) = d\mathbf{C}\boldsymbol{\theta}. \quad (4.61)$$

Then, the expression of the gradient of F with respect to θ is

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\theta} F(\theta, \mathbf{T}) = & -2\text{vec}\left(\mathbf{T}^{\top} \mathfrak{A} \mathbf{T} - \mathbf{T}^{\top} \mathbf{T} \mathbf{A}(\theta)\right) d\mathbf{A} \\ & - 2\text{vec}\left(\mathbf{T}^{\top} \mathfrak{B} - \mathbf{T}^{\top} \mathbf{T} \mathbf{B}(\theta)\right) d\mathbf{B} - 2\text{vec}\left(\mathfrak{C} \mathbf{T} - \mathbf{C}(\theta)\right) d\mathbf{C}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.62)$$

It is important to point out that Eq. (4.62) remains valid even in the non-linear case by substituting the matrices $d\mathbf{A}$, $d\mathbf{B}$ and $d\mathbf{C}$ for the derivative of \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{C} with respect to θ . The gradient of the cost function F with respect to \mathbf{T} can be derived by using the fact that $\|\bullet\|_F^2 = \text{tr}(\bullet^{\top} \bullet)$ [Horn and Johnson, 1990], *i.e.*,

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\mathbf{T}} F(\theta, \mathbf{T}) = & 2\left(\mathfrak{C}^{\top} \mathfrak{C} \mathbf{T} - \mathfrak{C}^{\top} \mathbf{C}(\theta)\right) + 2\left(\mathbf{T} \mathbf{B}(\theta) \mathbf{B}^{\top}(\theta) - \mathfrak{B} \mathbf{B}^{\top}(\theta)\right) \\ & + 2\left(\mathfrak{A}^{\top} \mathfrak{A} \mathbf{T} - \mathfrak{A}^{\top} \mathbf{T} \mathbf{A}(\theta) - \mathfrak{A} \mathbf{T} \mathbf{A}^{\top}(\theta) + \mathbf{T} \mathbf{A}(\theta) \mathbf{A}^{\top}(\theta)\right). \end{aligned} \quad (4.63)$$

To summarize, the minimization of F is used in order to get an approximated solution to the set of bilinear equations (4.2). Rather than using a global optimization method, it is aimed at focusing on local methods in order to get a good and reliable local optimum. Thanks to this local formulation, it is possible to handle structured state-space matrices with non-linear dependence on the parameters.

4.4.2.2 Constraint on the condition number

As claimed in [Parrilo and Ljung, 2003], the use of the cost function F can lead to unusable results. Indeed, its minimization can yield a singular similarity transformation matrix \mathbf{T} at the global minimum. In order to circumvent this difficulty, a constraint on the condition number of \mathbf{T} can be added into the previous optimization problem. To reach this goal, let us consider a scalar $\alpha > 0$. Then, the constrained optimization problem to solve becomes

$$\min_{\theta, \mathbf{T}} F(\theta, \mathbf{T}) \text{ subject to } \text{cond}(\mathbf{T}) \leq \alpha \quad (4.64)$$

where $\text{cond}(\mathbf{T})$ is the condition number of \mathbf{T} . Now, the constraint $\text{cond}(\mathbf{T}) \leq \alpha$ can be written as

$$\sigma_{n_x}(\mathbf{T}) \geq \frac{\sigma_1(\mathbf{T})}{\alpha} \quad (4.65)$$

where $\sigma_1(\mathbf{T})$ and $\sigma_{n_x}(\mathbf{T})$ are the highest and the lowest singular values of \mathbf{T} respectively. In order to simplify the problem, the term $\sigma_1(\mathbf{T})$ can be removed from the constraint (see Paragraph 4.4.2.3 for comments concerning this specificity). Then, the optimization problem becomes, for a value $\beta > 0$,

$$\min_{\theta, \mathbf{T}} F(\theta, \mathbf{T}) \text{ subject to } \sigma_{n_x}(\mathbf{T}) \geq \beta. \quad (4.66)$$

Rather than solving the constrained optimization problem (4.66), a penalization parameter $\mu > 0$ is introduced. More precisely, the following penalized cost function is considered

$$F_2(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T}) = F(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T}) + \mu \sigma_{n_x}(\mathbf{T})^{-2}, \quad (4.67)$$

or, similarly,

$$F_2(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T}) = F(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T}) + \mu \lambda_1 \left((\mathbf{T}^{-1})^\top \mathbf{T}^{-1} \right) \quad (4.68)$$

where $\lambda_1(\bullet)$ denotes the maximum eigenvalue function. By minimizing the maximum eigenvalue of $(\mathbf{T}^{-1})^\top \mathbf{T}^{-1}$, the smallest singular value of \mathbf{T} is maximized. This condition keeps \mathbf{T} away from singularity. Moreover, by tuning the penalization parameter, the condition number of \mathbf{T} can be adjusted easily. In practice, a small value for μ is chosen because our objective is to minimize the function F rather than the condition number of \mathbf{T} .

Although F_2 corresponds to an unconstrained optimization problem, its non-smoothness makes its optimization difficult. This characteristic comes from the maximum eigenvalue function $\lambda_1(\bullet)$ which is convex but non-smooth when the maximum eigenvalue is multiple. In order to solve this optimization problem, an algorithm able to handle non-smooth functions must be used. In this chapter, the developed algorithm resorts to the combination of

- first a non-smooth BFGS method as described in [Lewis and Overton, 2008],
- second the spectral bundle algorithm of [Apkarian et al., 2008, Noll et al., 2008] (used herein to improve the numerical results).

For both methods, a subgradient of the objective function must be provided. The function F_2 is Clarke-regular [Clarke, 1990] when the similarity transformation matrix is non-singular. Hence, subgradients can be computed by applying the chain rule. See [Lewis, 2003, Apkarian et al., 2008] for more details about the subgradient computation of the maximum eigenvalue function.

Remark 4.8 *The idea of constraining the condition number of a specific matrix in order to get a robust result (numerically speaking) can also be used in the optimization problem (4.47). Indeed, it is possible to remove the constraint $\tau \notin \mathcal{S}$ by using the following cost function*

$$f(\boldsymbol{\tau}) = \begin{cases} f_S(\boldsymbol{\gamma}(\boldsymbol{\tau})) & \text{if } \boldsymbol{\tau} \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \mathcal{S} \\ +\infty & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (4.69)$$

Unfortunately, with this cost function, it is still possible to find an optimal $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ leading to a nearly singular similarity matrix. In order to bypass this difficulty,

the idea of adding a penalization term to the cost function f_S for controlling the condition number of $\mathbb{T}(\tau)$ can be extended to. More precisely, the following cost function can be introduced

$$f_2(\tau) = f_S(\gamma(\tau)) + \mu \lambda_1 \left((\mathbb{T}^{-1}(\tau))^{\top} \mathbb{T}^{-1}(\tau) \right) \quad (4.70)$$

where $\lambda_1(\bullet)$ is the max eigenvalue function [Horn and Johnson, 1990] and μ is a penalization parameter. Because of the use of the $\lambda_1(\bullet)$, the cost function $f_2(\tau)$ becomes non-smooth. Then, solving the optimization problem induced by $f_2(\tau)$ is computationally more complex than the initial one. In practice, the cost function f_2 must be favored only if the use of Eq. (4.47) leads to a solution τ such that $\mathbb{T}(\tau)$ has a bad condition number.

The BFGS method is a quasi-Newton method, which is known to be very efficient for solving smooth unconstrained optimization problems. In the non-smooth case, it has been observed that specific quasi-Newton methods are also very good in practice, leading to a good approximation of the optimum [Lemaréchal, 1982] rapidly. The key point is that a locally Lipschitz function is differentiable almost everywhere. Thus, in [Lewis and Overton, 2008], the authors suggested using an inexact line search in order to keep the iterates away from the non-differentiable points. The strong Wolfe condition, which is commonly used in the smooth case, is replaced with the weak Wolfe condition in order to ensure the positive definiteness of the inverse Hessian update. The convergence of this inexact line search is studied under general conditions in [Lewis and Overton, 2008].

The non-smooth BFGS method is very useful in practice but a proof of convergence is still missing in the framework of non-smooth and non-convex optimization. When the non-smooth BFGS method stops at a non-smooth point, this point is used to initialize the spectral bundle method so that the numerical results are improved. The spectral bundle algorithm is based on the use of a local convex model $y \mapsto \phi(y, x_k)$ of the objective at the current iterate x_k . This model must satisfy a set of axioms [Noll et al., 2008]. When dealing with an eigenvalue optimization, this model can be derived by exploiting the intrinsic structure of the maximum eigenvalue function [Helmberg and Kiwiel, 2002, Apkarian et al., 2008, 2009]. In this case, the model can be seen as a non-smooth Taylor expansion of the objective. In practice, the model $\phi(\bullet, x_k)$ is not numerically tractable. Hence, a polyhedral working model is built iteratively from cutting planes of $\phi(\bullet, x_k)$. A new candidate point y^* for the optimization is obtained from this working model. Then,

- if this point leads to a sufficient decrease of the objective, then we set $x_{k+1} = y^*$ a new local model $\phi(\bullet, x_{k+1})$ is built,

- else, the working model is improved by updating its bundle of cutting planes.

Such a cutting planes algorithm must be stabilized [Bonnans et al., 2006], for instance, by using a proximity control parameter. In the spectral bundle method, this proximity parameter helps us to deal with the non-convexity of the cost function. The proximity parameter is in fact chosen with respect to the distance between the objective and the models.

4.4.2.3 Comments and discussion

While the developed approach handles (a modified version of) the objective function used in [Xie and Ljung, 2002] and [Parrilo and Ljung, 2003], several differences and advantages can be highlighted. For instance, in [Xie and Ljung, 2002], because the objective function is bi-convex, the authors use alternatively two convex optimizations to find a solution to the minimization of $F(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T})$. However, as shown in [Gorski et al., 2007], convergence, even local, cannot be ensured with such an approach. On the contrary, the BFGS method used in our local approach is known to be globally convergent under mild assumption. The use of a local approach (rather than a global one as in [Parrilo and Ljung, 2003]) is also an interesting feature. Indeed, by using such a local approach, it is easier

- to handle a non-linear parameterization of the structured model without changing the optimization algorithm,
- to introduce constraints on the parameters by considering in this case an algorithm dedicated to constrained optimization instead of the BFGS method.

Let us now focus on the reasons why the term $\sigma_1(\mathbf{T})$ is removed from the constrained optimization (4.64). Let us assume that a local optimum $(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T})$ can be obtained such that $F_2(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T}) < \eta$. Then, we have

$$\|\mathfrak{A}\mathbf{T} - \mathbf{T}\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\|_F^2 < \eta, \quad \|\mathfrak{B} - \mathbf{T}\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\|_F^2 < \eta, \quad \|\mathfrak{C}\mathbf{T} - \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\|_F^2 < \eta. \quad (4.71)$$

These three inequalities can be rewritten as follows

$$\|\mathbf{M}_\theta \text{vec}(\mathbf{T}) - \boldsymbol{\beta}_\theta\|_F^2 < 3\eta, \quad (4.72)$$

where

$$\mathbf{M}_\theta = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} \otimes \mathfrak{A} - \mathbf{A}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \otimes \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} \\ \mathbf{B}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \otimes \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} \\ \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} \otimes \mathfrak{C} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \boldsymbol{\beta}_\theta = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \text{vec}(\mathfrak{B}) \\ \text{vec}(\mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.73)$$

Thus, a vector $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ exists such that $\mathbf{M}_\theta \text{vec}(\mathbf{T}) - \boldsymbol{\beta}_\theta = \boldsymbol{\nu}$ and $\|\boldsymbol{\nu}\| < \sqrt{3n}$. Now, let us assume that the matrix \mathbf{M}_θ is of full rank, *i.e.*, $\text{rank}(\mathbf{M}_\theta) = n_x^2$. Then,

$$\mathbf{T} = \text{reshape}\left(\mathbf{M}_\theta^\dagger(\boldsymbol{\beta}_\theta + \boldsymbol{\nu}), n_x, n_x\right) \quad (4.74)$$

where $\mathbf{M}_\theta^\dagger$, again, denotes the Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse of matrix \mathbf{M}_θ [Horn and Johnson, 1990]. Finally, by computing the matrix 2-norm $\|\bullet\|_2$ [Horn and Johnson, 1990] of \mathbf{T} , we get

$$\|\mathbf{T}\|_2 = \sigma_1(\mathbf{T}) \leq \left\| \mathbf{M}_\theta^\dagger(\boldsymbol{\beta}_\theta + \boldsymbol{\nu}) \right\|_2 \leq \left\| \mathbf{M}_\theta^\dagger \right\|_2 \left(\|\boldsymbol{\beta}_\theta\|_2 + \sqrt{3\eta} \right). \quad (4.75)$$

Thus, the greatest singular value of matrix \mathbf{T} is bounded. If it is assumed that the values of $\left\| \mathbf{M}_\theta^\dagger \right\|_2$ and $\|\boldsymbol{\beta}_\theta\|_2$ are bounded in a neighborhood of the local optimum, we get a bound for $\sigma_1(\mathbf{T})$ on this neighborhood. As a consequence, in order to improve the condition number of \mathbf{T} , it is sufficient to maximize its smallest singular value, that is the reason why we only consider $\sigma_{n_x}(\mathbf{T})$ in cost function F_2 .

4.4.2.4 Relation with transfer functions

By looking closer at the previous results, it is worth highlighting that the cost function F can have an interesting physical meaning. This feature can be pointed out when continuous-time systems are addressed. Let us consider $\omega \in [0, \infty[$ and

$$\mathbf{E}(\omega) = \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})(i\omega\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))^{-1}\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{C}}(i\omega\mathbf{I} - \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{A}})^{-1}\boldsymbol{\mathfrak{B}}. \quad (4.76)$$

Our objective herein is to find a bound of $\|\mathbf{E}(\omega)\|_F$ by using the value of the cost function $\varepsilon = F(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T})$. A straightforward calculation shows that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E}(\omega) &= \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{C}}(i\omega\mathbf{I} - \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{A}})^{-1}(\mathbf{T}\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{B}}) \\ &\quad + (\mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{C}}\mathbf{T})(i\omega\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))^{-1}\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \\ &\quad + \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{C}}\left(\mathbf{T}(i\omega\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))^{-1} + (i\omega\mathbf{I} - \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{A}})^{-1}\mathbf{T}\right)\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}). \end{aligned} \quad (4.77)$$

Now, by using the identity $(\mathbf{A}^{-1} - \mathbf{B}^{-1})^{-1} = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{B} - \mathbf{A})^{-1}\mathbf{B}$ [Horn and Johnson, 1990], the following relation can be deduced

$$\begin{aligned} &(\mathbf{T}(i\omega\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))^{-1} + (i\omega\mathbf{I} - \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{A}})^{-1}\mathbf{T})^{-1} \\ &= (i\omega\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))(\mathbf{T}\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{A}}\mathbf{T})^{-1}(i\omega\mathbf{I} - \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{A}}). \end{aligned} \quad (4.78)$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} E(\omega) &= \mathfrak{C}(\imath\omega\mathbf{I} - \mathfrak{A})^{-1}(\mathbf{T}\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \mathfrak{B}) \\ &\quad + (\mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \mathfrak{C}\mathbf{T})(\imath\omega\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))^{-1}\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \\ &\quad + \mathfrak{C}(\imath\omega\mathbf{I} - \mathfrak{A})^{-1}(\mathbf{T}\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \mathfrak{A}\mathbf{T})(\imath\omega\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))^{-1}\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}). \end{aligned} \quad (4.79)$$

Finally, with

$$\mathbf{E}_B(\omega) = \|(\imath\omega\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))^{-1}\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\|_F \quad (4.80a)$$

$$\mathbf{E}_C(\omega) = \|\mathfrak{C}(\imath\omega\mathbf{I} - \mathfrak{A})^{-1}\|_F \quad (4.80b)$$

we get the following inequality

$$\|\mathbf{E}(\omega)\|_F \leq \sqrt{\varepsilon} [\mathbf{E}_B(\omega) + \mathbf{E}_C(\omega) + \mathbf{E}_B(\omega)\mathbf{E}_C(\omega)]. \quad (4.81)$$

This inequality shows that the distance between the transfer functions of both system representations $(\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{C})$ and $(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))$ decreases with ε . Moreover, the distance between both transfer functions is smaller for high values of ω .

4.4.3 Simulation examples

In this sub-section, two simulation examples are used to test and to validate the techniques introduced in Sub-Section 4.4.1 and in Sub-Section 4.4.2 respectively. First, the time domain technique described in Sub-Section 4.4.2 is compared with the techniques described in [Xie and Ljung, 2002, Parrilo and Ljung, 2003] which use the cost function given in Eq. (4.60). Second, the new methods discussed in this chapter are compared to each other with the help of a gray-box model of a printer belt drive system [Dorf and Bishop, 2008].

4.4.3.1 Inverted pendulum

The numerical example considered in this study was used in [Xie and Ljung, 2002] and [Parrilo and Ljung, 2003]. The system is composed of a cart with an inverted pendulum (see Fig. 4.1). The underlying control problem consists in keeping the pendulum upright via the signal u . The physical modeling is available, e.g., in [Ogata, 2009], and can be written as [Xie and

Ljung, 2002]

$$\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \theta_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & \theta_2 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{2mg}{2M+m} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{2g(M+m)}{(2M+m)l} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.82a)$$

$$\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \theta_3 \\ 0 \\ \theta_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{2}{2M+m} \\ 0 \\ -\frac{1}{(2M+m)l} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.82b)$$

$$\mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = [1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0] \quad (4.82c)$$

with

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = [y(t) \ \dot{y}(t) \ \alpha(t) \ \dot{\alpha}(t)]^\top. \quad (4.83)$$

Herein, m and M are the mass of the pendulum and the cart respectively, l is the length of the pendulum and g is the gravitation constant. The same experimental condition as in [Xie and Ljung, 2002] are considered, *i.e.*, $m = 1.2 \text{ kg}$, $M = 5.5 \text{ kg}$ and $l = 2.3 \text{ m}$.

Figure 4.1: Inverted pendulum system.

To start with, the optimization problem involving the cost function F_2 and introduced in Sub-Section 4.4.2 is initialized with the following black-box

Figure 4.2: Comparison of the magnitude Bode plots of the real system (-) and the initial model (- -).

model

$$\mathfrak{A} = \begin{bmatrix} -18.4268 & 30.1636 & -15.0469 & 3.3101 \\ -3.3101 & -5.0311 & 9.9923 & -1.6512 \\ 1.6512 & -9.9923 & 5.0311 & 3.3101 \\ -3.3101 & 15.0469 & -30.1636 & 18.4268 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.84a)$$

$$\mathfrak{B} = \begin{bmatrix} -2.5304 \\ 0.8296 \\ -0.8214 \\ 2.4391 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.84b)$$

$$\mathfrak{C} = 10^{-4} \times [8.118 \quad -8.301 \quad -8.800 \quad 8.282]. \quad (4.84c)$$

This initial continuous-time model is suggested in [Xie and Ljung, 2002] and, according to the Authors, can be obtained by using a dedicated black-box identification algorithm (see [Xie and Ljung, 2002] for details). Curiously, as illustrated by the magnitude Bode plot given in Figure 4.2, this initial model is stable whereas the system to identify is by construction unstable. Thus, as shown in Figure 4.2, the frequency response of this initial model is far from being similar to the frequency response of the system, especially for $\omega \leq 0.1 \text{ rad/s}$. Despite this shortcoming, in order to perform a fair comparison with the results available in [Xie and Ljung, 2002] and [Parrilo and Ljung, 2003], it has been chosen to keep this initial stable model.

First, because of the bad condition number of \mathbf{T} near the initial point¹¹, the cost function F_2 is used. The user-defined parameter μ is chosen equal to $1e - 18$. By using a non-smooth BFGS optimization algorithm combined with the spectral bundle technique developed in [Apkarian et al., 2008], we get

$$\hat{\theta} = [-1.287422 \quad 5.184889 \quad 0.1639943 \quad -0.06322288] \quad (4.85)$$

with a final condition number equal to $3.6e3$. By using the same procedure as the one available in [Xie and Ljung, 2002], we can compute from $\hat{\theta}$

$$\hat{M} = 5.452270486 \quad \hat{l} = 2.090192372 \quad \hat{m} = 1.291004849. \quad (4.86)$$

These values are quite similar to the real ones as well as the ones found by Xie and Ljung. Indeed, in [Xie and Ljung, 2002], from

$$\bar{\theta} = [-2.0630 \quad 5.1955 \quad 0.1639 \quad -0.0333], \quad (4.87)$$

we get $\hat{M} = 5.56635$, $\hat{l} = 2.0521$ and $\hat{m} = 1.0730$. Furthermore, it is important to notice that, contrary to the results shown in [Parrilo and Ljung, 2003], the

¹¹Thanks to the availability of the real system parameters, it is possible to compute the similarity transformation \mathbf{T} between $(\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{C})$ and $(\mathbf{A}(\theta), \mathbf{B}(\theta), \mathbf{C}(\theta))$. The condition number of \mathbf{T} is $1.1e5$ which justifies the use of F_2 instead of F .

condition number of \mathbf{T} is quite good. Thus, our developments are able to give access to reliable and accurate estimates with a good condition number of the involved similarity transformation, at least better than with techniques suggested in [Xie and Ljung, 2002, Parrilo and Ljung, 2003]. In order to quantify the estimation quality, the following error function is introduced

$$e(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{T}) = \|\mathfrak{A}\mathbf{T} - \mathbf{T}\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\|_F^2 + \|\mathfrak{B} - \mathbf{T}\mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\|_F^2 + \|\mathfrak{C}\mathbf{T} - \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\|_F^2 \quad (4.88)$$

i.e., the distance between the estimated structured model and the initial black-box model. In [Xie and Ljung, 2002], the value of this error at the optimum is equal to $4.72e - 6$. With our approach, it is $1.14e - 5$. Although the error with our algorithms is ten times greater than with the solution obtained by Xie and Ljung, the frequency behavior of both models are quite similar and really close to the real system behavior, as shown in Figure 4.3 (top magnitude Bode plots) where the frequency responses of the estimated models corresponding to $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \check{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ respectively are drawn relatively to the real one. Notice that these good results are obtained by initializing our algorithms with a parameter vector (corresponding to the initial state-space representation given in Eq. (4.84)) far from being optimal, as illustrated by the curves plotted in Figure 4.2.

The second experiment consists in initializing the vector of parameters with zeros and \mathbf{T} with the identity matrix. This initialization condition is by definition quite complicated. Under such conditions, the algorithm of Xie and Ljung does not converge. On the contrary, with a tolerance value equal to $1.e - 12$, the BFGS method leads to the following local minimum for the objective function F

$$\check{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = [0.42634 \quad 0.80347 \quad 0.16368 \quad 0.01675]. \quad (4.89)$$

The value of the cost function at this point is $\check{F} = 2.36e - 11$ and the condition number of matrix \mathbf{T} is equal to $1.181e5$. As shown in Figure 4.3 (bottom left magnitude Bode plot), the corresponding estimated model is able to depict the system behavior on a large range of frequencies. Unfortunately, while the frequency plots of the models obtained with $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \check{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ respectively are similar and while the error values are, for both initializations, of the same magnitude, the computed parameters are not convenient in this second case. Indeed, as a ratio of masses and positive constant values times -1 , the first parameter θ_1 should be a negative number, which is not the case for the local minimum obtained previously. This result is essentially due to the fact that the initial vector of parameters used in this experiment is composed of zeros. Such a practical case can appear when no reliable initial models are available. First, better results can be obtained by choosing these initial parameters from a randomly-generated drawn, *e.g.*, thanks to the MATLAB function `randn`, as

shown by the first experimental conditions which have led to $\hat{\theta}$. Second, according to the Author's experience, the solution given by a non-smooth BFGS method could be improved by introducing *a priori* information into the optimized cost function, e.g., via the introduction of lower and upper bounds on the parameters. As shown beforehand, this type of constrained cost function can be minimized by using algorithms dedicated to constrained optimization. An extension to other (equality) constraints including prior knowledge is conceivable. This problem should be studied in the near future.

Figure 4.3: Magnitude Bode plots of the difference between the real system and a structured model satisfying Eq. (4.82) with $\theta = \bar{\theta}$ (in the top right), $\theta = \hat{\theta}$ (in the top left), $\theta = \bar{\theta}$ (in the bottom right), $\theta = \tilde{\theta}$ (in the bottom left).

Finally, in order to test the influence of the constraint on the condition number of \mathbf{T} , the same numerical tolerance and the same initial point as for the second experiment are used with the non-smooth function F_2 . Now, μ equals $1e - 8$. Then, the following estimated parameters are obtained

$$\tilde{\theta} = [0.01393 \quad -0.01860 \quad 0.16369 \quad 0.07840]. \quad (4.90)$$

Furthermore, for this particular point, $\tilde{F}_2 = 2.4e - 4$, $e(\tilde{\theta}) = 0.01$ and the condition number of the similarity transformation matrix is $1.2e2$. This solution

has clearly a greater error than the one obtained previously but, as expected, the condition number is a lot smaller. While the error $e(\tilde{\theta})$ is quite large, the Bode plots of the real system and the estimated model are quite close (except for $\omega \approx 0.15 \text{ rad/s}$) (see Figure 4.3 (bottom right magnitude Bode plot)). Hence, the estimated model is still able to picture the dynamic behavior of the system. As far as the non-physical pole at $\omega \approx 0.15 \text{ rad/s}$ is concerned, it is interesting to notice that such a mis-estimation also arises when $\mu = 0$. This problem is only related to the non-convexity of the cost function.

4.4.3.2 Printer belt drive system

Figure 4.4: Printer belt system. Picture borrowed from [Dorf and Bishop, 2008, Section 3.8], page 183.

This simulation example is extracted from [Dorf and Bishop, 2008, Section 3.8]. As shown in Figure 4.4, the system under study is a printer belt drive used to move the printing end effector laterally across the printed page. For this simulation, the output¹² z of the system has been chosen as the speed of

¹²Herein, the output is denoted by z in order to differ from the notation y used for the

the printing device $\frac{dy(t)}{dt}$. The input u is the torque applied to drive the belt. As far as the state vector is concerned, the following components are suggested in [Dorf and Bishop, 2008] and kept in the following

$$x_1(t) = r\theta(t) - y(t) \quad (4.91)$$

$$x_2(t) = \frac{dy(t)}{dt} \quad (4.92)$$

$$x_3(t) = \frac{d^2\theta(t)}{dt^2} \quad (4.93)$$

where r and θ are the pulley radius and the angular position of the DC motor respectively. Based on this triplet $\{u, z, \mathbf{x}\}$ as well as the equations governing the motion of the system available in [Dorf and Bishop, 2008, Section 3.8], the following state-space system can be written

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta})u(t) \quad (4.94a)$$

$$z(t) = \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{x}(t) \quad (4.94b)$$

where

$$\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & \theta_1 \\ \theta_2 & 0 & 0 \\ \theta_3 & \theta_4 & \theta_5 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \theta_6 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{C}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.95)$$

The unknown parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta} = [\theta_1 \ \theta_2 \ \theta_3 \ \theta_4 \ \theta_5 \ \theta_6]^\top$ are related to the physical parameters governing the behavior of the system as follows

$$\theta_1 = r \quad \theta_2 = \frac{2k}{m} \quad \theta_3 = -\frac{2kr}{J} \quad (4.96a)$$

$$\theta_4 = -\frac{K_m k_1 k_2}{RJ} \quad \theta_5 = -\frac{b}{J} \quad \theta_6 = -\frac{1}{J}. \quad (4.96b)$$

The values of the parameters used in this study are gathered in Table 4.1. For this set of values, the poles and zeros as well as the step response of the system are drawn in Figure 4.5- 4.6. These plots indicate that the system has a highly under-damped behavior as well as a negative gain.

Identifiability As it was proved previously, the identifiability of the structure $(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))$ is required to ensure that the algorithms developed previously yield an accurate and unique solution. As far as the identifiability of the printer belt state-space form (4.95) is concerned, several comments can

position as depicted in Figure 4.4.

Signification	Symbol	Value
Mass	m	$0.2kg$
Light sensor	k_1	$1V/m$
Radius	r	$0.15m$
Friction	b	$0.25N.ms/rad$
Resistance	R	$2N.m/A$
Inertia	J	$0.01kg.m^2$
Controller gain	k_2	$0.1s$

Table 4.1: Parameters of the printer belt drive.

Figure 4.5: Step response of the printer belt drive.

Figure 4.6: Poles-zeros plot of the printer belt drive.

be made. An easy way to study the identifiability of a model structure consists in determining the corresponding analytic transfer function [Walter and Pronzato, 1997]. Straightforwardly, from the state-space form (4.95), we get

$$H(s) = \frac{Z(s)}{U(s)} = \frac{\alpha_1}{s^3 + \alpha_2 s^2 + \alpha_3 s + \alpha_4} \quad (4.97)$$

where the $\{\alpha_j\}_{j=1}^4$ are well-defined combinations of the components of θ

$$\alpha_1 = \theta_1 \theta_2 \theta_6 \quad (4.98a)$$

$$\alpha_2 = -\theta_5 \quad (4.98b)$$

$$\alpha_3 = \theta_2 - \theta_1 \theta_3 \quad (4.98c)$$

$$\alpha_4 = -\theta_2(\theta_5 + \theta_1 \theta_4). \quad (4.98d)$$

While the parameters $\{\alpha_j\}_{j=1}^4$ (and the corresponding transfer function) are identifiable, the parameters $\{\theta_i\}_{i=1}^6$ can not be recovered from the knowledge of the $\{\alpha_j\}_{j=1}^4$. Thus, the state-space representation given in Eq. (4.95) is not identifiable. Theoretically, because of this identifiability issue, the identification of the structured state-space form $(\mathbf{A}(\theta), \mathbf{B}(\theta), \mathbf{C}(\theta))$ should be performed by adding prior knowledge in order to ensure that the developed identification algorithm supplies a unique solution. For instance, by assuming that θ_1 and θ_2 are known, the state-space structure $(\mathcal{A}(\vartheta), \mathcal{B}(\vartheta), \mathcal{C}(\vartheta))$ defined by

$$\mathcal{A}(\vartheta) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0.15 \\ 200 & 0 & 0 \\ \theta_3 & \theta_4 & \theta_5 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathcal{B}(\vartheta) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \theta_6 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathcal{C}^\top(\vartheta) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.99)$$

where

$$\vartheta = [\theta_3 \quad \theta_4 \quad \theta_5 \quad \theta_6]^\top \quad (4.100)$$

becomes identifiable because, in this case,

$$\alpha_1 = 30\theta_6 \quad (4.101a)$$

$$\alpha_2 = -\theta_5 \quad (4.101b)$$

$$\alpha_3 = 200 - 0.15\theta_3 \quad (4.101c)$$

$$\alpha_4 = -200(\theta_5 + 0.15\theta_4) \quad (4.101d)$$

which leads to

$$\theta_1 = 0.15 \quad (4.102a)$$

$$\theta_2 = 200 \quad (4.102b)$$

$$\theta_3 = \frac{200 - \alpha_3}{0.15} \quad (4.102c)$$

$$\theta_4 = \frac{-\frac{\alpha_4}{200} + \alpha_2}{0.15} \quad (4.102d)$$

$$\theta_5 = -\alpha_2 \quad (4.102e)$$

$$\theta_6 = \frac{\alpha_1}{30}. \quad (4.102f)$$

For identifiability reasons, the model structure $(\mathcal{A}(\vartheta), \mathcal{B}(\vartheta), \mathcal{C}(\vartheta))$ should be preferred to $(\mathbf{A}(\theta), \mathbf{B}(\theta), \mathbf{C}(\theta))$. Unfortunately, dealing with the structural constraints involved by the identifiable model $(\mathcal{A}(\vartheta), \mathcal{B}(\vartheta), \mathcal{C}(\vartheta))$ can lead to more non-convex search space than when the structure $(\mathbf{A}(\theta), \mathbf{B}(\theta), \mathbf{C}(\theta))$ is handled. Furthermore, it can be a lot more difficult to converge to a unique point θ^* (required when an identifiable model is looked for) than to a manifold containing this sought unique point. That is the main reason why, in the following, the structured state-space forms $(\mathbf{A}(\theta), \mathbf{B}(\theta), \mathbf{C}(\theta))$ as well as $(\mathcal{A}(\vartheta), \mathcal{B}(\vartheta), \mathcal{C}(\vartheta))$ will be considered and compared. It is indeed interesting to study if, in practice, it is easier and more efficient to deal with

- a non-identifiable model structure associated with a non-convex search space for which a candidate solution corresponding to a line or a plan is looked for,
- an identifiable model imposing a highly non-convex feasible region as well as the determination of a unique point as its optimal solution.

As shown hereafter, the problem of constraining $(\mathbf{A}(\theta), \mathbf{B}(\theta), \mathbf{C}(\theta))$ with an equality constraint ensuring the identifiability of the final state-space mode can indeed be solved by considering a two-step approach.

Estimation results The first step of the procedure consists in estimating a fully-parameterized state-space model $(\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{C})$. To get this initial model, as shown in Figure 4.7, the printer belt drive system is fed with a pseudo random binary sequence tuned so that the entire dynamic of the system is well excited. Then, a subspace-based identification algorithm¹³ [Van Overschee

¹³Herein, the MATLAB function `n4sid` is used to get this initial discrete-time black-box model with standard tuning parameters, *i.e.*, `Model = n4sid(datae,nx,'DisturbanceModel','None','N4Weight','AUTO');`. Equivalent results have been obtained with the LTI-Toolbox [Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007].

Figure 4.7: I/O data sample.

and De Moor, 1996a, Katayama, 2005, Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007] is applied to the acquired data set in order to get a reliable fully-parameterized black-box model of the system. Because this subspace-based identification technique leads to a discrete-time model, its continuous-time counterpart is computed by using the MATLAB function `d2c`. The resulting state-space form is

$$\mathfrak{A} = \begin{bmatrix} -19.42 & 5.333 & 3.505 \\ -12.13 & -0.6035 & -11.48 \\ 16.31 & 14.9 & -4.98 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathfrak{B} = \begin{bmatrix} -1.722 \\ -0.6439 \\ 1.727 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.103a)$$

$$\mathfrak{C} = [10.85 \quad -6.926 \quad 8.238] \quad \mathfrak{D} = 0. \quad (4.103b)$$

As shown in Figure 4.8 as well as in Table 4.2, the accuracy of this initial model is validated by comparing the frequency responses as well as the poles and zeros plots of this fully-parameterized CT model and the ones of the system (4.95) simulated with the parameter values gathered in Table 4.1. These plots prove that this initial model is reliable for the following of this study.

	System	Model
s_1	$-1.2204 + 1.5279e + 01i$	$-1.2204 + 1.5279e + 01i$
s_2	$-1.2204 - 1.5279e + 01i$	$-1.2204 - 1.5279e + 01i$
s_3	$-2.2559e + 01$	$-2.2559e + 01$

Table 4.2: Poles of the printer belt drive system and its model.

Remark 4.9 *The initial model (\mathfrak{A} , \mathfrak{B} , \mathfrak{C}) has been estimated by resorting to a standard subspace-based identification algorithm. Because the goal of this simulation example is to test the algorithms developed to re-structure a black-box*

Figure 4.8: Comparison of the Bode plots of the real system (-) and the initial model (\mathfrak{A} , \mathfrak{B} , \mathfrak{C}) (- -) (top) and magnitude Bode plot of the difference between the real system and the initial model (bottom).

model into a gray-box one and not to validate a specific subspace-based identification algorithm, the n_4sid algorithm used herein is applied on noise-free data. Similar results can be obtained from noisy data by introducing an instrumental variable tuned according to the properties of the disturbances acting on the system.

Identifiable model To start with, the identifiable state-space representation $(\mathcal{A}(\vartheta), \mathcal{B}(\vartheta), \mathcal{C}(\vartheta))$ is considered, *i.e.*, the parameters

$$\vartheta^* = [-600 \quad -10 \quad -25 \quad -100]^\top \quad (4.104)$$

are looked for.

First, the null-space-based technique introduced in Sub-Section 4.4.1 is applied to re-structure the initial black-box model $(\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{C})$ into the gray-box structure $(\mathcal{A}(\vartheta), \mathcal{B}(\vartheta), \mathcal{C}(\vartheta))$. As far as the initialization is concerned, an initial value of τ required for the optimization of the cost function (4.56) is drawn randomly¹⁴ by using the MATLAB function `randn`. By using a BFGS algorithm to optimize $f_S(\tau)$, for the first draw of τ_{init} , we get, in one shot, an estimate $\hat{\tau}_n$ satisfying $f_S(\hat{\tau}_n) = 5.4e - 21$ from which the following similarity transformation

$$\mathbb{T}(\hat{\tau}_n) = \begin{bmatrix} 4.663e - 01 & 3.607e - 02 & 1.722e - 02 \\ 9.772e - 01 & -2.380e - 02 & 6.439e - 03 \\ 2.071e - 01 & 5.386e - 02 & -1.727e - 02 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.105)$$

as well as the following state-space matrices

$$\mathbb{A}(\hat{\tau}_n) = \begin{bmatrix} 4.143e - 11 & -1 & 0.15 \\ 200 & 4.166e - 11 & -9.619e - 11 \\ -600 & -10 & -25 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.106a)$$

$$\mathbb{B}(\hat{\tau}_n) = \begin{bmatrix} -5.049e - 11 \\ 1.702e - 11 \\ -100 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.106b)$$

$$\mathbb{C}(\hat{\tau}_n) = [1.101e - 12 \quad 1 \quad 2.025e - 13] \quad (4.106c)$$

can be extracted by following the set of equations (4.42). It is obvious that, if the numerical values lower than $1e - 11$ are *a posteriori* fixed equal to 0, the reconstructed state-space matrices $(\mathbb{A}(\hat{\tau}_n), \mathbb{B}(\hat{\tau}_n), \mathbb{C}(\hat{\tau}_n))$ can be considered as accurate estimates of the identifiable model structure $(\mathcal{A}(\vartheta), \mathcal{B}(\vartheta), \mathcal{C}(\vartheta))$. Notice that the similarity transformation $\mathbb{T}(\hat{\tau}_n)$ obtained by applying the null-space-based technique has a good conditioning number because $\text{cond}(\mathbb{T}(\hat{\tau}_n)) = 50.2$.

¹⁴Notice that the last component of τ_{init} is constrained to be equal to 1.

Second, the same problem is tackled by using the unconstrained optimization technique introduced in Sub-Section 4.4.2. Like for the null-space-based approach, the same starting point, *i.e.*, the same black-box model $(\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{C})$ is used. Because, for this simulation example, the similarity transformation between $(\mathcal{A}(\vartheta), \mathcal{B}(\vartheta), \mathcal{C}(\vartheta))$ and $(\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{C})$ has a moderate condition number (equal to 201.2), the cost function F is preferred to F_2 . As far as the initialization of the BFGS algorithm is concerned, the initial similarity transformation is chosen equal to the identity matrix and the initial values of ϑ are drawn randomly from a normal distribution. Despite many tries with different initial points generated randomly, no reliable results have been obtained by following this procedure. Thus, in order to slightly modify the involved cost function and to improve the optimization procedure, it is then suggested balancing the black-box model $(\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{C})$ thanks to the MATLAB function `balreal`. The corresponding balanced state-space form verifies

$$\mathfrak{A} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.599 & -15.09 & 1.468 \\ 15.09 & -1.812 & 3.004 \\ 1.468 & -3.004 & -22.59 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathfrak{B} = \begin{bmatrix} -1.403 \\ 2.277 \\ 1.794 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.107a)$$

$$\mathfrak{C} = [1.403 \ 2.277 \ -1.794] \quad \mathfrak{D} = 0. \quad (4.107b)$$

Although the similarity transformation between $(\mathcal{A}(\vartheta), \mathcal{B}(\vartheta), \mathcal{C}(\vartheta))$ and the balanced states-space form $(\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{C})$ has a greater condition number than previously¹⁵, the BFGS algorithm is now able to converge to a minimum¹⁶

$$\hat{\vartheta}_o = [-5.999e + 02 \quad -9.999 \quad -25 \quad -100]^\top \quad (4.108a)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{T}}_o = \begin{bmatrix} 1.544e - 01 & -9.952e - 02 & 2.471e - 01 \\ 1.403 & 2.277 & -1.794 \\ 1.1468 & -4.093 & -4.965e + 01 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.108b)$$

satisfying $F(\hat{\vartheta}_o, \hat{\mathbf{T}}_o) = 8.5e - 11$ for which

$$\mathcal{A}(\hat{\vartheta}_o) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0.15 \\ 200 & 0 & 0 \\ -5.999e + 02 & -9.999 & -25 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.109a)$$

$$\mathcal{B}(\hat{\vartheta}_o) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -100 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.109b)$$

$$\mathcal{C}(\hat{\vartheta}_o) = [0 \ 1 \ 0]. \quad (4.109c)$$

Notice unfortunately that, even though the estimated parameter vector $\hat{\vartheta}_o$ is composed of the sought parameter values, the optimization of the cost function $F(\vartheta, \mathbf{T})$ requires at least 2 hours of computation (on a recent computer)

¹⁵Now, $\text{cond}(\mathbf{T}) = 4237$.

¹⁶Notice that $\text{cond}(\hat{\mathbf{T}}_o) = 251.9$ which is satisfactory.

in order to converge to the (local) minimum $\{\hat{\vartheta}_o, \hat{\mathbf{T}}_o\}$. This huge computational load (which could be problematic for real-time identification) could be explained by the existence of long and tight valleys in the involved cost function.

Non-identifiable model This first study is completed by the identification of the non-identifiable structure $(\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathbf{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))$. As it was shown previously, it can be really difficult and time-consuming to converge to the unique optimal point of the (highly) non-convex optimization criterion F involved in the time-domain approach described in Sub-Section 4.4.2 if the identifiable model structure is tackled. Thus, instead of trying to focus on this unique point, it is suggested hereafter

- first estimating a manifold containing this unique point,
- second extracting the identifiable model among all the models included in the afore-estimated manifold by resorting to an analytical procedure.

Again, both re-structuration techniques introduced in Sub-Section 4.4.1 and in Sub-Section 4.4.2 respectively are compared by using, as a starting point, the state-space form given in Eq. (4.107).

First, with the technique based on the criterion F , the following local minimum

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_o = \begin{bmatrix} 5.165e + 01 & 2.079e + 02 & -1.588 \\ -9.350e - 03 & -25 & -2.792e - 01 \end{bmatrix}^\top \quad (4.110a)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{T}}_o = \begin{bmatrix} 3.688e - 02 & 8.885e - 01 & 3.679e - 01 \\ 1.085e + 01 & -6.925 & 8.238 \\ 1.038e - 01 & -3.451e - 02 & -7.101e - 02 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.110b)$$

satisfying $F(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_o, \hat{\mathbf{T}}_o) = 7.4e - 20$ is obtained. Straightforwardly, we get

$$\mathbf{A}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_o) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 5.165e + 01 \\ 2.079e + 02 & 0 & 0 \\ -1.588 & -9.350e - 03 & -25 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.111a)$$

$$\mathbf{B}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_o) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -2.792e - 01 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.111b)$$

$$\mathbf{C}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_o) = [0 \quad 1 \quad 0]. \quad (4.111c)$$

Figure 4.9: Comparison of the Bode plots of the real system (-) and the estimated model $(A(\hat{\theta}_o), B(\hat{\theta}_o), C(\hat{\theta}_o))$ (- -) (top) and magnitude Bode plot of the difference between the real system and the estimated model (bottom).

Figure 4.10: Comparison of the Bode plots of the real system (-) and the estimated model $(\mathbf{A}(\hat{\tau}_n), \mathbf{B}(\hat{\tau}_n), \mathbf{C}(\hat{\tau}_n))$ (- -) (top) and magnitude Bode plot of the difference between the real system and the estimated model (bottom).

Contrary to the previous case, it takes less than 1 minute to get this estimate. Notice also that the condition number of the corresponding similarity transformation is equal to 138.2 which is satisfactory. Second, with the null-space-based procedure, we get an estimate $\hat{\tau}_n$ satisfying, again, $f_S(\hat{\tau}_n) = 5.4e - 21$ from which the following similarity transformation

$$\mathbb{T}(\hat{\tau}_n) = \begin{bmatrix} 9.086e - 01 & -7.282e - 02 & 1.078e - 03 \\ 1.904e + 00 & -6.452e - 02 & 4.029e - 04 \\ 4.036e - 01 & 1.631e - 01 & -1.081e - 03 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.112)$$

as well as the following state-space matrices

$$\mathbb{A}(\hat{\tau}_n) = \begin{bmatrix} 4.369e - 09 & -1 & 4.818e - 03 \\ 3.897e + 02 & 3.356e - 09 & 8.226e - 09 \\ 2.069e + 04 & 2.366e + 03 & -25 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.113a)$$

$$\mathbb{B}(\hat{\tau}_n) = \begin{bmatrix} 3.321e - 08 \\ 4.799e - 09 \\ -1.598e + 03 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.113b)$$

$$\mathbb{C}(\hat{\tau}_n) = [-1.031e - 08 \quad 1 \quad 3.067e - 12] \quad (4.113c)$$

can be extracted by following the set of equations (4.42). Although the condition number of $\mathbb{T}(\hat{\tau}_n)$ is quite large ($\text{cond}(\mathbb{T}(\hat{\tau}_n)) = 4083.2$), the frequency response of the structured model $(\mathbb{A}(\hat{\tau}_n), \mathbb{B}(\hat{\tau}_n), \mathbb{C}(\hat{\tau}_n))$ is equivalent to the one of the system as shown in Figure 4.10. The same assessment can be made for the model $(\mathbf{A}(\hat{\theta}_o), \mathbf{B}(\hat{\theta}_o), \mathbf{C}(\hat{\theta}_o))$ (see Figure 4.9).

Although both estimated state-space forms have frequency responses similar to the one of the system, because of the identifiability problem underlined previously, the values of the estimated parameters are not equal to the ones of the system. In order to circumvent this problem, it is now possible to determine the unique similarity transformation \mathbf{S} such that (i) $\mathbf{S}\mathbf{A}(\hat{\theta})\mathbf{S}^{-1}$ satisfies the structure of $\mathbf{A}(\theta)$ and (ii) the constraints $\theta_1 = 0.15$ and $\theta_1 = 200$ are verified (as the system (4.95) does). A symbolic computation of \mathbf{S} can be performed by using a standard symbolic computing software. Such a solution

leads to

$$\mathbf{S}_o = \begin{bmatrix} 1.039 & -3.719e-17 & 4.406e-18 \\ 6.109e-18 & 1 & -2.7564e-17 \\ -9.923e-14 & -2.661e-01 & 3.5811e+02 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.114a)$$

$$\mathbf{S}_o \mathbf{A}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_o) \mathbf{S}_o^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 6.874e-15 & -1 & 0.15 \\ 200 & 7.433e-15 & 3.446e-19 \\ -600 & -10 & -25 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.114b)$$

$$\mathbf{S}_o \mathbf{B}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_o) = \begin{bmatrix} -1.230e-18 \\ 7.697e-18 \\ -100 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.114c)$$

$$\mathbf{C}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_o) \mathbf{S}_o^{-1} = [-5.875e-18 \quad 1 \quad 7.697e-20] \quad (4.114d)$$

and

$$\mathbf{S}_n = \begin{bmatrix} 1.948 & 1.039e-10 & 4.050e-11 \\ -1.031e-08 & 1 & 3.003e-12 \\ 5.846e-06 & -6.324 & 6.2590e-02 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.115a)$$

$$\mathbf{S}_n \mathbf{A}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_n) \mathbf{S}_n^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} -4.485e-16 & -1 & 0.15 \\ 200 & 4.256e-11 & 6.731e-12 \\ -600 & -10 & -25 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.115b)$$

$$\mathbf{S}_n \mathbf{B}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_n) = \begin{bmatrix} -5.427e-14 \\ -9.459e-16 \\ -100 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.115c)$$

$$\mathbf{C}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_n) \mathbf{S}_n^{-1} = [1.032e-15 \quad 1 \quad 1.013e-12] \quad (4.115d)$$

with $\text{cond}(\mathbf{S}_o) = 358.1$ and $\text{cond}(\mathbf{S}_n) = 654.9$ respectively. These numerical results point out the performance of the developed two-step procedure as well as the optimization algorithms described in Sub-Section 4.4.1 and in Sub-Section 4.4.2 respectively.

4.5 Conclusions

In many applications, it is necessary to identify a linear time-invariant model of a system with a model structure dictated by the laws of physics governing the system behavior. With such a constraint, a gray-box model is looked for. This problem is often solved by using a prediction-error or output-error cost function associated with a dedicated gradient-based algorithm tuned to estimate the global optimum of the minimized criterion. Well-known for their efficiency, these techniques can suffer from initialization problems. Basically,

the main practical obstacle consists in finding a reliable initial parameter vector from which it can be ensured that the developed gradient-based algorithm will converge to the optimal minimum, *i.e.*, problem of local minima are circumvented. Solutions to initialize prediction or output-error optimizations have been introduced in this chapter. These techniques give reliable solutions for the problem of the consistent initialization and local minima of standard cost functions encountered in the LTI system identification framework. More precisely, given an initial and assumed reliable black-box and fully-parameterized state-space model, two new methods extracting from this initial state-space form the unknown physical parameters of a same dimensional state-space model have been brought out. Both techniques carry out a similarity transformation between the fully-parameterized model and the physical one. On the one hand, the first method introduced herein re-formulates the resulting bilinear equations into a null-space problem, where the similarity transformation matrix and the physical parameters are contained in the solution vector belonging to the null-space of a matrix containing the parameters of the fully-parameterized model. Given that the dimension of the null-space is larger than 1, the novelty of the algorithm lies in the extraction of the physical parameters by using a non-convex optimization. By assuming that the initial fully-parameterized realization of the system is consistent and the final physically-structured state-space form is identifiable, uniqueness of the solution can be ensured. On the other hand, the cost function considered in [Xie and Ljung, 2002], then in [Parrilo and Ljung, 2003], is used and modified so that

- an algorithm dedicated to non-smooth optimization combined, if necessary, with the spectral bundle algorithm developed in [Apkarian et al., 2008], can be provided to transform the initial fully-parameterized model into the structured state-space parameterization of the system to identify,
- a specific constraint on the similarity transformation between both system representations is added to avoid singularity.

Both techniques have been discussed, then compared via specific simulation examples. These numerical results have highlighted the performance of the developed techniques. More precisely, it has been shown that

- the method involving the cost function F_2 and the afore-mentioned optimization algorithms outperforms the techniques available in the literature which deals with equivalent criterion,
- an identifiable linear time-invariant gray-box model can be extracted from an afore-estimated reliable fully-parameterized state-space form

- by resorting to the techniques introduced in Sub-Section 4.4.1 and in Sub-Section 4.4.2 respectively but, sometimes, at the price of a high computational load,
- by considering a two-step approach consisting in *(i)* extracting a non-identifiable model by estimating a manifold containing the sought unique and identifiable parameter vector and *(ii)* re-structuring the estimated non-identifiable model into an identifiable one by using an analytic computation scheme.

All these appealing results prove that interesting solutions are available for the initialization of the non-linear optimizations involved in prediction-error or output-error-based system identification.

CHAPTER 5

Identification of state-space linear parameter-varying models from local experimental data: new developments for the local approach

5.1 Motivations

As shown in Chapter 1, the basic idea of the techniques dedicated to the identification of non-linear systems consists in following the well-known and efficient "divide and conquer" strategy [Nelles, 2000], *i.e.*, breaking down the whole non-linear functioning domain of the system into many local domains where

- the local behavior of the system is more linear than the global one,
- the system can thus be approximated by a simple but reliable local model.

For instance, this approach can be applied to determine a mathematical model of a pick-and-place robot. This type of robot can be found, *e.g.*, on printed circuit board assembly lines for picking and placing chips on boards. As described and explained in [Juloski et al., 2004], this robot first grabs an electronic component from a specific place, second moves it, as fast as possible, above its final position, third pushes it down so that the component is fixed to the board before releasing it. This simple description of the system behavior points out that several different modes of operation occur during the placement process. As shown in [Juloski et al., 2004], each local behavior (each corresponding to a specific operating mode) can be modeled with the help of an ARX model, *i.e.*, an LTI model with an easy-tuning structure. Then, the global behavior of the system (which is highly non-linear because of, *e.g.*, the saturations occurring when the component is pushed down) can be reconstructed by a user-defined combination of the local models.

This idea of combining (in different ways) several local but (quasi-)linear models in order to capture the whole dynamics of a non-linear system is widely used in system identification [Murray-Smith and Johansen, 1997, Nelles, 2000, Verdult, 2002, Paoletti et al., 2007]. It can be used for different non-linear systems such as¹

- an aircraft or any vehicle for which the global functioning can be broken down into local modes which are functions, *e.g.*, of the altitude or the speed of the vehicle [Marcos and Balas, 2004],
- a heat exchanger for which a model with parameters depending on exogenous variables (the cold and hot mass flow rates) can be obtained from the law of thermodynamics [Mercère et al., 2011b],
- a soil solarization procedure [Stapleton, 2000], the behavior of which is deeply affected by the depth at which the temperature of the reaction is considered (see [Belforte et al., 2005] for details).

The main advantage of such an approach relies on the use of well-known and really efficient techniques dedicated to the estimation of the parameters of LTI models [Ljung, 1999a]. Among all the multi-model structures available in the literature, a particular attention has been paid to the linear parameter-varying (LPV) models during the last two decades (see Chapter 1 of [Tóth, 2010] for an historical presentation of LPV identification). This interest can be mainly explained by the following reasons. First, an LPV model can be seen as a combination of local models with parameters evolving as a function of measurable variables (called the scheduling variables in the following) which can be related to the different operating points of the system. By this way, the model structure is close to the standard LTI one but with a structural flexibility able to picture time-varying, even non-linear behaviors. Second, the development of LPV models is linked to control engineering where a controller must be designed in order to guarantee a suitable closed-loop performance for a given plant in different operating conditions. A well-known example of controller design technique using this basic idea is the gain scheduling approach [Shamma, 1996, Rugh and Shamma, 2000]. The gain scheduling approach can be briefly summarized as follows:

- find one or more scheduling variables which can completely parameterize the operating space of interest for the system to control,
- define a parametric family of linearized models for the plant associated with the set of operating points of interest,

¹Notice that, for the following examples, the dynamics of the system depends on (measurable) external variables. Thus, they are good candidates for LPV model identification.

- design a parametric controller which can both ensure the desired control objectives in each operating point and an acceptable behavior during (slow) transients between one operating condition and the other.

A wide body of design techniques is now available for this problem (see, e.g., [Shamma and Athans, 1990, Kukreja et al., 1995, Apkarian and Adams, 1998]), which can be solved reliably, provided that a suitable model in a parameter-dependent form has been derived.

As far as the determination of LPV models is concerned, two broad classes of methods can be put forward:

- the analytic methods consisting in converting the available non-linear physical model of the system into an LPV representation,
- the experimental methods aiming at determining LPV models of the plant under study from the available input-output data.

The first class, which probably gathers the initial solutions to the LPV modeling problem of physical systems [Shamma, 1996], mainly resorts to extensions of the familiar notions of linearization, such as the Jacobian linearization [Marcos and Balas, 2004] as described in Chapter 1 (see also [Tóth, 2010, Chapter 7] for an overview of the main analytic developments as well as [Casella and Lovera, 2008] for an interesting but shorter presentation of the main techniques). The second family of methods can be broken down into two subclasses generally called the global approach and the local approach. Historically, the first developments focused on the global procedure and assumed that one global experiment can be performed in which the control inputs as well as the scheduling variables can be both excited [Nemani et al., 1995, Lee and Poolla, 1999, Verdult and Verhaegen, 2002, Bamieh and Giarré, 2002, Verdult and Verhaegen, 2005, Hsu et al., 2008, van Wingerden and Verhaegen, 2009, Tóth et al., 2009]. By this way, all the non-linearities of the system are excited in one shot by passing through a large number of operating points. On the other hand, the recent methods are based on a multi-step procedure where

- local experiments are carried out in which the operating points (corresponding to fixed values of the scheduling variables) are held constant and the control inputs are (persistently) excited,
- local LTI models are estimated by using these sets of local input/output (I/O) measurements,
- an interpolation phase is performed in order to derive a final global parameter-dependent model.

It is obvious that this multi-step approach is a lot closer to the standard procedure used for non-linear system identification or the one dedicated to gain scheduling. Such a viewpoint has been considered, e.g., in [Steinbuch et al., 2003, van Helvoort et al., 2004, Groot Wassink et al., 2005, Pajmans et al., 2008, De Caigny et al., 2009]. For more details about these two approaches and the algorithms developed until 2008, an interesting state-of-the-art about LPV identification methods is given in [Tóth, 2008, 2010]. Both classes of methods have advantages and drawbacks. From a practical point of view, the global approach can suffer from the difficulty to satisfy the persistently excitation of the control inputs and the scheduling variables simultaneously. Hence, it is obvious that persistently exciting the altitude of a plane to carry out a global identification experiment may not be reasonable mainly for safety reasons. From a theoretical point of view, well-exciting the scheduling variables requires an optimal experimental design in order to maximize the accuracy of the identified model. To the Author's knowledge, the problem of well-exciting the scheduling variables has been little investigated for the global approach until now. The main contribution is probably [Bamieh and Giarré, 2002] where persistently exciting conditions are obtained for LPV-ARX models. Notice finally that, in the literature, dealing with global experiments for state-space LPV representations means involving (i) iterative gradient-based schemes (requiring reliable initial estimates) for the optimization of highly non-linear cost functions [Lee and Poolla, 1997] or (ii) computationally cumbersome algorithms and kernel-based adaptations when subspace-based identification techniques are used [Verdult and Verhaegen, 2005, van Wingerden, 2008, van Wingerden and Verhaegen, 2009, Houtzager, 2011]. Both approaches suffer from significant computational load which makes them difficult to use in case of large scaled systems. On the contrary, applying small variations around particular operating points, as considered by the local approach, is more conceivable in many practical cases. That is the reason why most of the following developments will focus on the local approach. The contributions introduced hereafter is indeed applied and compared by using a manipulator for robot-assisted surgery for which, as explained in Section 5.5, persistently exciting the scheduling variables is not reasonable.

Remark 5.1 *In specific frameworks, for instance in the mechatronic domain, the user may have access to local specifications about the model quality. In this case, a local approach should be favored in order to take into account this prior knowledge into the local experiment design. To the Author's knowledge, this idea has not been exploited until now and should be investigated. Notice that this basic idea can also justify the developments introduced in Section 5.4.*

As pointed out first in [Tóth et al., 2007], then in [Kulcsár and Tóth, 2011], the interpolation step involved in the local approach can lead to a global LPV

model with an inaccurate dynamic behavior even if the local LTI models are consistent. This shortcoming can be related to two main reasons highlighted in [Tóth et al., 2007, Kulcsár and Tóth, 2011, Tóth et al., 2011]:

- the conversion of an input-output LPV model into a state-space LPV model (and vice versa) cannot be performed as easily as in the LTI framework because the transformation may depend on time-shifted versions of the scheduling variables,
- for many LPV state-space forms, the similarity transformation converting the initial state-space representation into an equivalent one may, again, depend on time-shifted versions of the scheduling variables.

Thus, a number of issues deserve attention as far as the relation between the local models is concerned, as shown, *e.g.*, [Tóth, 2008]. However,

- the local approach works quite well when slow variations of the operating conditions are considered [Shoukens et al., 2003, van Helvoort et al., 2004, Hashemi et al., 2009, Paijmans et al., 2008, De Caigny et al., 2011, Mercère et al., 2011b],
- some recent extensions improving the numerical reliability of the local models can be introduced (see Section 5.3 and [Lovera and Mercère, 2007] for details),
- the prior knowledge about the non-linear equations governing the behavior of the system can be used to improve the local approach by choosing the structure of the final LPV model and adapting the identification strategy (see Section 5.4 and [Mercère et al., 2011a] for details).

These items will be introduced and tackled in the following part of this chapter. More precisely, after having defined mathematically what we mean by linear parameter-varying state-space representation in Section 5.2, a specific attention is paid to their identification from local experiments. First, Section 5.3 addresses this identification problem with the help of local balanced forms. The balanced realizations have indeed suitable numerical properties which can be efficiently used to build up the final global LPV model from the local LTI ones. Second, in Section 5.4, the problem of the identification of a global LPV model directly from local experiments, *i.e.*, without interpolation, is tackled. Based on a simulator of a 2-DOF non-linear flexible manipulator, both identification techniques are evaluated and validated in Section 5.5. Section 5.6 concludes this chapter.

5.2 Linear parameter-varying state-space models: definitions and notations

In the literature dedicated to LPV system modeling [Tóth, 2010] or control [Shamma, 1996], on the one hand, a continuous-time state-space LPV model is often defined as

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{p}(t))\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{p}(t))\mathbf{u}(t) \quad (5.1a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{p}(t))\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{p}(t))\mathbf{u}(t) \quad (5.1b)$$

where, again, $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ are the input signals, $\mathbf{y}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ are the output signals, $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ is the state vector and $t \in \mathbb{R}$. Contrary to the standard LTI state-space forms, the matrices $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ are functions of measurable time-varying signals, gathered into the vector $\mathbf{p}(t) \in \mathbb{P} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{n_p}$ and called the scheduling variables, *i.e.*,

$$\mathbf{A} : \mathbb{P} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x} \quad (5.2a)$$

$$\mathbf{B} : \mathbb{P} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_u} \quad (5.2b)$$

$$\mathbf{C} : \mathbb{P} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_x} \quad (5.2c)$$

$$\mathbf{D} : \mathbb{P} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_u}. \quad (5.2d)$$

\mathbb{P} is the so-called scheduling space [Tóth et al., 2011].

Remark 5.2 *In general, the scheduling variables are external and independent signals. Notice however that, commonly, the LPV framework encompasses the quasi-LPV modeling context where the scheduling variables \mathbf{p} are dependent on \mathbf{y} , \mathbf{u} or \mathbf{x} [Tóth, 2010].*

On the other hand, a discrete-time state-space LPV model is usually defined as

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{p}(t))\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{p}(t))\mathbf{u}(t) \quad (5.3a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{p}(t))\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{p}(t))\mathbf{u}(t) \quad (5.3b)$$

with $t \in \mathbb{Z}$. Like in the CT case, the DT matrices $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ are dependent on the scheduling variables $\mathbf{p}(t) \in \mathbb{P} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{n_p}$, *i.e.*,

$$\mathbf{A} : \mathbb{P} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x} \quad (5.4a)$$

$$\mathbf{B} : \mathbb{P} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_u} \quad (5.4b)$$

$$\mathbf{C} : \mathbb{P} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_x} \quad (5.4c)$$

$$\mathbf{D} : \mathbb{P} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_u}. \quad (5.4d)$$

Whatever the time domain, the state-space matrices are assumed to be continuous functions of the scheduling variables \mathbf{p} . First, this assumption ensures that the dynamics of the model vary smoothly with respect to \mathbf{p} [Wood, 1995]. Second, it implies boundedness of the coefficients composing these matrices for $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{P}$ [Wood et al., 1996]. In many cases [Lovera, 1997, Verdult, 2002, Tóth, 2008], it is assumed that the afore-introduced matrices $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ (resp. $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$) have affine dependence on \mathbf{p} , *i.e.*,

$$\clubsuit(\mathbf{p}) = \clubsuit_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{n_p} \clubsuit_i p_i \quad (5.5)$$

where \clubsuit_0 is a constant matrix standing for $\mathbf{A}_0, \mathbf{B}_0, \mathbf{C}_0$ and \mathbf{D}_0 (resp. $\mathbf{A}_0, \mathbf{B}_0, \mathbf{C}_0, \mathbf{D}_0$) and where

$$\mathbf{p} = \begin{bmatrix} p_1 \\ \vdots \\ p_{n_p} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_p}. \quad (5.6)$$

Other well-known parameterizations of $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ (resp. $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$) are available in the literature such as the rational or the linear fractional transformation (LFT) parameter dependence [Lovera, 1997, Verdult, 2002]. When \mathbf{p} is constant for all $t \in \mathbb{Z}$ or \mathbb{R} , the corresponding "frozen scheduling variables" representation [Wood, 1995, Tóth, 2008] is LTI. Concerning the dependency of \mathbf{p} with respect to t , it is often assumed that the matrices $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ (resp. $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$) are only dependent on the instantaneous value of the scheduling variables (see Eq. (5.1) and Eq. (5.3)). In this case, it is said that the functional dependence is static [Tóth, 2008]. This assumption will be kept hereafter. The interested reader is advised to refer to [Tóth et al., 2011] and [Tóth, 2008, Chapter 3] for definitions and well-defined LPV model representations of LPV state-space forms involving dynamic mapping between \mathbf{p} and the matrices $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ (resp. $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$).

Notice that, when the scheduling variables \mathbf{p} can be explicitly related to a list of operating points of the system, the affine representation seems to be particularly suited to the local approach because, by construction, it can be seen as a linear interpolation of local LTI models connected by operating point dependent weighting functions [Rugh and Shamma, 2000]. Furthermore, as shown in [Tóth et al., 2007, Theorem 8], any LPV system with a static dependence can be represented by an affine representation.

Remark 5.3 *As shown in [Tóth et al., 2007], the simple case of the static dependence is already problematic because, for instance, in the DT framework, for $\mathbf{z}(t) = \mathbf{T}(\mathbf{p}(t))\mathbf{x}(t)$ with $\det(\mathbf{T}(\mathbf{p}(t))) \neq 0$ and $\mathbf{T}(\mathbf{p}(t))$ bounded for all $\mathbf{p}(t) \in \mathbb{P}$*

[Tóth et al., 2007, Kulcsár and Tóth, 2011],

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{z}(t+1) = & \mathbf{T}^{-1}(\mathbf{p}(t+1))\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{p}(t))\mathbf{T}(\mathbf{p}(t))\mathbf{z}(t) \\ & + \mathbf{T}^{-1}(\mathbf{p}(t+1))\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{p}(t))\mathbf{u}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (5.7)$$

which highlights a non-causal dynamic dependence. The problem of equivalent representations has been recently studied in [Tóth et al., 2011, Kulcsár and Tóth, 2011]. Although the general problem is difficult to solve (see [Tóth et al., 2011] for details), the paper [Abbas and Werner, 2011, Kulcsár and Tóth, 2011] introduce interesting formulas making the computation of the state transformations conceivable in case of affine static LPV representations.

As said previously, the experimental estimation of the state-space matrices $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$ (resp. $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D})$) can be performed by following the procedure of the local or the global approach [Casella and Lovera, 2008]. Because the global approach requires the persistently excitation of the scheduling variables which can be difficult to satisfy for many practical applications, the global methods are often restricted to specific systems where the components of \mathbf{p} are totally controllable and excitable (and not only measurable). Practical applications for which global methods have yielded reliable LPV models are available in the literature (see, e.g., [Tanelli et al., 2008, van Wingerden, 2008, Houtzager, 2011, Tanelli et al., 2011]). Notice however that, when subspace-based identification techniques are concerned, the standard global methods can suffer from the "curse of dimensionality" [Verdult, 2002, van Wingerden, 2008], the reduction of which can be performed when the scheduling variables used for these processes have particular properties such as periodicity [Felici et al., 2007], piece-wise constancy [van Wingerden et al., 2007] or white noise characteristics [Santos et al., 2007]. In order to bypass the difficult problem of persistently exciting \mathbf{p} , the following techniques will mainly focus on the local approach. As explained, e.g., in [Tóth et al., 2008], the local approach starts with the estimation of a user-defined number of local LTI models, calculated from a set of local experiments, each of them corresponding to a constant scheduling variables vector, by using a user-defined standard algorithm for LTI models. Then, by assuming that the dependence of the state-space matrices on the scheduling variables is chosen² *a priori*, the determination of the global LPV model is performed by interpolating the local LTI models consistently. As

²The choice of the scheduling variables dependency can be made by using prior knowledge, often extracted from the physical laws satisfied by the system, or, in the black-box framework, by defining an arbitrary user-defined dependency, for instance a static affine dependency, often obtained by plotting the evolution of the parameters of the local models with respect to the scheduling variables.

shown in [Tóth et al., 2007, Tóth, 2010], this interpolation step is probably the most difficult step in the procedure. This difficulty is twofold. First, on a real system, it might be possible that $(\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{p}), \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{p}), \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{p}), \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{p}))$ (resp. $(\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{p}), \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{p}), \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{p}), \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{p}))$) are dynamic functions³ of \mathbf{p} , *i.e.*, depend on time-shifted versions of $\mathbf{p}(t)$. When the real system satisfies a dynamic scheduling dependency, a misspecification of the mapping relating the state-space matrices of the model with respect to \mathbf{p} can lead to a bad input-output dynamic behavior of the global LPV model over the entire operating regime of the identified process even if the model fits the local operating points. This difficulty is especially encountered in the black-box framework, *i.e.*, when no information about the internal structure of the real system which generated the data is available. This problem related to the dynamic scheduling dependency can also appear when the user tries to convert the studied state-space LPV model into an input-output LPV form (and vice versa as in [Giarré et al., 2006]). Indeed, as shown in [Tóth et al., 2007], such a transformation can lead to a model with a dynamic scheduling dependency, even if the dependency on \mathbf{p} of the initial state-space model is static. Second, as highlighted by Eq. (5.7) and now well-explained in [Tóth et al., 2007, Abbas and Werner, 2011, Kulcsár and Tóth, 2011, Tóth et al., 2012], all the local state-space models should be identified in a dependent way in order to ensure that the interpolation of the global LPV model satisfies Eq. (5.7). Such a constraint is really difficult to satisfy in a general black-box framework. As shown in [Verdult and Verhaegen, 2004], it can be solved for piecewise linear systems under specific experimental constraints. Unfortunately, these conditions are not satisfied for all the processes and solutions usable for any LPV state-space systems must be investigated. Because, for the local approach, it is almost impossible to find easily the dynamic scheduling dependency of the real process to identify, especially when black-box identification is concerned, convenient (but not necessarily totally accurate) solutions must be suggested. In the following Sections, two of them are introduced. The first one, dedicated to the black-box framework, is developed to solve numerical issues encountered with standard methods available in the literature [Steinbuch et al., 2003, van Helvoort et al., 2004, Groot Wassink et al., 2005, Pajjmans et al., 2008]. Notice that, unfortunately, this technique does not solve the state-space basis issue mainly because of the lack of information about the structure of the system when black-box identification is concerned. The second one, called the global approach, circumvents the challenging problem of realizing all the local models with respect to the same state variables by estimating the parameters of a global LPV model, obtained from the study of the non-linear equations governing the behavior of

³This type of parameterization can be theoretically well-described by following a behavioral approach [Polderman and Willems, 1997] as in [Tóth et al., 2011].

the plant, exclusively from local experiments. Both approaches are more precisely described below. Whatever the technique used for the identification, it is assumed that a set of constant scheduling variables for $N_{op} \in \mathbb{N}^*$ local working points is given beforehand. Furthermore, it is assumed that this set of local experiments is well-chosen, *i.e.*, all the working range of the system is covered (*i.e.*, N_{op} is large enough) and the "distance" between two constant working points is small enough. Finally, it is assumed that the variations of \mathbf{p} are slow with respect to the dynamics of the system. These assumptions, which are system dependent, are compulsory (but, unfortunately not sufficient) to perform an efficient interpolation [Khalate et al., 2009].

5.3 Identification of linear parameter-varying state-space models from local experiments: an approach using local balanced forms

In this section, the problem of the identification of a linear parameter-varying state-space model from local experiments is tackled in a black-box framework. More precisely, it is assumed that the user has little knowledge about the system (apart from the values of the operating points where the local identification experiments are carried out) and no search for parameters with a physical meaning is investigated. Basically, the user is only interested in finding an LPV model able to picture the dynamic behavior of a non-linear system operating under changing steady state conditions.

This problem has already been studied in the literature dedicated to LPV system identification from local experiments. For instance, In [Steinbuch et al., 2003, van Helvoort et al., 2004],

- input-output local models are identified using a frequency-domain approach,
- the identified models are written in state-space representation by using a canonical controllability form,
- an interpolation step for the elements of the state-space matrices completes the identification procedure.

In [Groot Wassink et al., 2005], a similar approach is adopted, followed by a conversion of the identified model into an LFT form. Finally, in [Paijmans et al., 2008] a method for the identification of affine LPV SISO models with a scalar varying parameter is proposed, based on the interpolation of the parameter-dependent gain, zeros and poles. All the above methods are clearly

based on the idea of following a two-stage procedure, which consists in deriving a set of local models and performing some kind of interpolation between them. However, a number of issues deserve attention as far as this general procedure is concerned. First, as shown in [Tóth et al., 2007, Tóth, 2008] performing the interpolation on input-output models directly might lead to significant problems if the obtained LPV model is used eventually in a state-space representation. Second, numerical issues might turn out to be critical in the interpolation problem if an ill-conditioned parameterization for the model class is chosen (e.g., numerator and denominator coefficients in a high order transfer function). Finally, when dealing with the problem of interpolating black-box local models in state-space form, the challenging problem of realizing all the models with respect to the same state variables comes into play. Indeed, interpolating such state-space models without taking this issue into account may lead to inaccurate LPV models, even if the local LTI models are consistent. To the Author's knowledge, no local method dedicated to state-space models is currently able to solve all the problems listed beforehand. Hereafter, a first step towards a numerical improvement of the existing techniques is investigated. This technique consists in

- estimating LTI discrete-time state-space models for each operating by using, e.g., a subspace-based identification technique, so enabling the straightforward treatment of MIMO as well as SISO modeling problems, in state-space form, by using both time-domain or frequency-domain data,
- balancing the identified models, if the used subspace-based identification technique does not yield a balanced form directly, in order to exploit the numerical reliability of the balanced realization for the interpolation step,
- converting, if necessary, the local DT balanced models into continuous-time state-space forms with a bilinear transformation (see Eq. (5.22) or [Garnier and Wang, 2008] for more details),
- interpolating the state-space matrices of the local models, by using the good properties of the balanced realizations.

Notice right now that, even if the proposed approach is able to deal with some of the limitations of the existing methods, the state-space basis issue is not solved, *i.e.*, the \mathbf{p} -dependent state transformation highlighted, e.g., in Remark 5.3, is not taken into account. The introduction of balanced forms is indeed mainly used to improve the interpolation step numerically by avoiding ill-conditioned local state-space forms as well by using the nice property

of "internal dominance" [Moore, 1981] inherent to the balanced realizations. Such properties are really interesting and relevant from a practical point of view.

Because the problem of the identification of LTI state-space models has been widely studied in the previous chapter, the first step of the procedure described beforehand is not addressed hereafter. Hence, it is assumed that a set of local state-space models is available. These models are assumed to be reliable and well-validated at least locally. Thus, the rest of this section is mainly dedicated to the balancing of the identified local models. The quality of this local transformation and the resulting local models are indeed crucial to ensure a good interpolation leading to an accurate LPV model.

5.3.1 Balancing of the identified local models

The construction of a balanced LTI state-space form from (time domain or frequency domain) input-output data can be performed

- directly by using a specific subspace-based identification algorithm⁴ with the property of leading to identified state space models in a balanced form [Moonen and Ramos, 1993, Van Overschee and De Moor, 1995b, McKelvey et al., 1996, Markovsky et al., 2005],
- indirectly by using a prediction error method [Ljung, 1999a] or a more standard subspace-based identification algorithm [Katayama, 2005] to get first a state-space model in any basis, second by applying standard techniques for state transformations leading to a balanced basis [Moore, 1981].

The idea of converting all the local LTI models into the same state coordinates basis is not new, even in the LPV system identification framework [Steinbuch et al., 2003, van Helvoort et al., 2004, Groot Wassink et al., 2005]. However, according to the Author's experience as well as the literature dedicated to balanced forms [Moore, 1981, Laub et al., 1987, Chou and Maciejowski, 1997], the balanced realizations are a lot more numerically reliable and suitable than any other canonical forms used until now for LPV model identification.

Remark 5.4 *Notice that the idea of using a subspace-based system identification algorithm to estimate local models in a coherent basis has been used with success for switched linear systems [Bako et al., 2009b]. More precisely, a recursive*

⁴Associated with the interesting property of dealing with SISO or MIMO systems similarly, this direct determination of a balanced form thanks to well-known subspace-based identification algorithms working with time domain and frequency domain data can explain the developments and the focus on subspace-based identification in [Lovera and Mercère, 2007].

adaptation of the propagator method introduced in Chapter 3 has been developed in the aforementioned article with the property of keeping a control on the state basis in which all the estimated local state-space matrices are computed. Unfortunately, this technique cannot be directly extended to the LPV system identification framework. Indeed, basically, an LPV system is a switched system with an infinite number of modes (and sub-models) such as a linear time-varying system. This feature makes the extension of the propagator method to the LPV system identification really difficult.

Before discussing the properties of the balanced forms interesting for local LPV system identification, let us start with a review of some basic results about balanced realizations.

Balancing (in Moore's sense [Moore, 1981]) a stable minimal state-space realization of an LTI system consists in determining a similarity transformation $\mathbf{T} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$ which brings the initial state-space form into a realization which has equal and diagonal reachability and observability Gramians. The diagonal elements of the balanced Gramians are known as Hankel singular values and are input-output invariants [Chou and Maciejowski, 1997]. In the discrete-time framework, the observability Gramian \mathfrak{W}_o for a DT state-space system $(\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{C}, \mathfrak{D})$ is defined as [Moore, 1981]

$$\mathfrak{W}_o = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\mathfrak{A}^\top)^k \mathfrak{C}^\top \mathfrak{C} \mathfrak{A}^k \quad (5.8)$$

and satisfies the following Lyapunov⁵ equation [Bauer and Deistler, 1999]

$$\mathfrak{W}_o = \mathfrak{A}^\top \mathfrak{W}_o \mathfrak{A} + \mathfrak{C}^\top \mathfrak{C}. \quad (5.9)$$

Similarly, the reachability Gramian \mathfrak{W}_r is defined as

$$\mathfrak{W}_r = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \mathfrak{A}^k \mathfrak{B} \mathfrak{B}^\top (\mathfrak{A}^\top)^k \quad (5.10)$$

and satisfies

$$\mathfrak{W}_r = \mathfrak{A} \mathfrak{W}_r \mathfrak{A}^\top + \mathfrak{B} \mathfrak{B}^\top. \quad (5.11)$$

Thus [Moore, 1981, Laub et al., 1987],

Definition 5.1 *A state-space realization is balanced if*

$$\mathfrak{W}_o = \mathfrak{W}_r = \Sigma = \text{diag}(\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_{n_x}) \quad (5.12)$$

⁵That is the reason why this balanced realization is often called Lyapunov balanced.

with $\sigma_1 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_{n_x} > 0$. Furthermore, for $i \in [1, n_x]$,

$$\sigma_i = \sqrt{\lambda_i(\mathfrak{W}_r \mathfrak{W}_o)} \quad (5.13)$$

where $\lambda_i(\bullet)$ denotes the i th eigenvalue of \bullet .

An important result is that any stable minimal system can be converted into a balanced realization [Moore, 1981]. That is the reason why, in the following, the studied (local sub-)systems will be assumed LTI, minimal and stable. The determination of the similarity transformation \mathbf{T} converting the initial state-space form into a balanced one consists of the following steps [Laub et al., 1987]:

1. compute the Gramians \mathfrak{W}_o and \mathfrak{W}_r from the initial state-space form $(\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{C}, \mathfrak{D})$,
2. apply a Cholesky factorization⁶ [Golub and Van Loan, 1996] to obtain

$$\mathfrak{W}_o = \mathbf{L}_o \mathbf{L}_o^\top \quad (5.14a)$$

$$\mathfrak{W}_r = \mathbf{L}_r \mathbf{L}_r^\top \quad (5.14b)$$

where \mathbf{L}_o and \mathbf{L}_r are the lower triangular factors of the Gramians,

3. compute the SVD [Golub and Van Loan, 1996]

$$\mathbf{L}_o^\top \mathbf{L}_r = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Sigma} \mathbf{V}^\top, \quad (5.15)$$

4. then, the balancing similarity transformations are defined as

$$\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{L}_r \mathbf{V} \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1/2} \quad (5.16a)$$

$$\mathbf{T}^{-1} = \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1/2} \mathbf{U}^\top \mathbf{L}_o^\top. \quad (5.16b)$$

This conversion leads to a state-space representation which emphasizes the contribution of each state vector component into the input-output mapping. The first step, *i.e.*, the computation of \mathfrak{W}_o and \mathfrak{W}_r requires to solve the Lyapunov equations (5.9) and (5.11) which are quadratic in \mathfrak{A} . In order to make the computation easier, it is suggested resorting to the continuous-time observability and controllability Gramians defined for a CT state-space form $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{D})$ as

$$\mathcal{W}_o = \int_0^\infty (e^{t\mathcal{A}})^\top \mathcal{C}^\top \mathcal{C} e^{t\mathcal{A}} dt \quad (5.17a)$$

$$\mathcal{W}_c = \int_0^\infty e^{t\mathcal{A}} \mathcal{B} \mathcal{B}^\top (e^{t\mathcal{A}})^\top dt \quad (5.17b)$$

⁶For a stable and minimal $(\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{C}, \mathfrak{D})$, the Gramians are positive and definite. Hence, they admit a Cholesky factorization [Datta, 2003].

which satisfy respectively

$$\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{W}_o + \mathbf{W}_o \mathbf{A} = -\mathbf{C}^\top \mathbf{C} \quad (5.18a)$$

$$\mathbf{A} \mathbf{W}_c + \mathbf{W}_c \mathbf{A}^\top = -\mathbf{B} \mathbf{B}^\top. \quad (5.18b)$$

Indeed, these Lyapunov equations are linear with respect to \mathbf{A} which simplifies the computation of the Gramians. Because these CT Gramians and Lyapunov equations are defined for CT state-space forms, their use for DT state-space systems requires to convert the DT state-space matrices (\mathfrak{A} , \mathfrak{B} , \mathfrak{C} , \mathfrak{D}) into CT counterparts (\mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C} , \mathbf{D}). This conversion can be performed via the bilinear transformation

$$s = \frac{z-1}{z+1} \Rightarrow z = \frac{1+s}{1-s} \quad (5.19)$$

which relates $\mathbf{G}(s) = \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{C}(s\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} - \mathbf{A})^{-1}\mathbf{B}$ to $\mathbf{G}(z) = \mathfrak{D} + \mathfrak{C}(z\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} - \mathfrak{A})^{-1}\mathfrak{B}$ via

$$\mathbf{G}(z) = \mathbf{G}\left(\frac{z-1}{z+1}\right). \quad (5.20)$$

Then, the following relations are true [Al-Saggaf and Franklin, 1988]

$$\mathfrak{A} = (\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} + \mathbf{A})(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} - \mathbf{A})^{-1} \quad (5.21a)$$

$$\mathfrak{B} = \sqrt{2}(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} - \mathbf{A})^{-1}\mathbf{B} \quad (5.21b)$$

$$\mathfrak{C} = \sqrt{2}\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} - \mathbf{A})^{-1} \quad (5.21c)$$

$$\mathfrak{D} = \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} - \mathbf{A})^{-1}\mathbf{B} \quad (5.21d)$$

$$\mathbf{A} = (\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} + \mathfrak{A})^{-1}(\mathfrak{A} - \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x}) \quad (5.21e)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \sqrt{2}(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} + \mathfrak{A})^{-1}\mathfrak{B} \quad (5.21f)$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \sqrt{2}\mathfrak{C}(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} + \mathfrak{A})^{-1} \quad (5.21g)$$

$$\mathbf{D} = \mathfrak{D} - \mathfrak{C}(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} + \mathfrak{A})^{-1}\mathfrak{B}. \quad (5.21h)$$

More interesting, besides converting a DT (resp. CT) state-space representation into its CT (resp. DT) state-space counterpart, the maps

$$h : \begin{matrix} \mathcal{C}_{n_x}^{n_y, n_u} \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} \mathbf{A} \\ \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{C} \\ \mathbf{D} \end{array} \right] \end{matrix} \mapsto \begin{matrix} \mathcal{D}_{n_x}^{n_y, n_u} \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} (\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} + \mathbf{A})(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} - \mathbf{A})^{-1} \\ \sqrt{2}(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} - \mathbf{A})^{-1}\mathbf{B} \\ \sqrt{2}\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} - \mathbf{A})^{-1} \\ \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} - \mathbf{A})^{-1}\mathbf{B} \end{array} \right] \end{matrix} \quad (5.22a)$$

$$h^{-1} : \begin{matrix} \mathcal{D}_{n_x}^{n_y, n_u} \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} \mathfrak{A} \\ \mathfrak{B} \\ \mathfrak{C} \\ \mathfrak{D} \end{array} \right] \end{matrix} \mapsto \begin{matrix} \mathcal{C}_{n_x}^{n_y, n_u} \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} (\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} + \mathfrak{A})^{-1}(\mathfrak{A} - \mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x}) \\ \sqrt{2}(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} + \mathfrak{A})^{-1}\mathfrak{B} \\ \sqrt{2}\mathfrak{C}(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} + \mathfrak{A})^{-1} \\ \mathfrak{D} - \mathfrak{C}(\mathbf{I}_{n_x \times n_x} + \mathfrak{A})^{-1}\mathfrak{B} \end{array} \right] \end{matrix} \quad (5.22b)$$

where

$$\mathcal{D}_{n_x}^{n_y, n_u} = \{(\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{C}, \mathfrak{D}) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_u} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_x} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_u} \mid (\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{C}, \mathfrak{D}) \text{ is a minimal and asympt. stable DT system}\} \quad (5.23a)$$

$$\mathcal{C}_{n_x}^{n_y, n_u} = \{(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{D}) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_u} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_x} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_u} \mid (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{D}) \text{ is a minimal and asympt. stable CT system}\} \quad (5.23b)$$

are bijective and preserve balancing [Ober, 1987, Prop. 4.1]. Thus, in practice, the Lyapunov equations for CT systems are mainly used to construct a canonical form, even if the final use is in a DT framework [Bauer and Deistler, 1999]. Furthermore, the following comments made for discrete-time systems can be successfully exploited for models in the continuous-time case.

5.3.2 Comments and discussion

Historically, the initial interest in balanced forms was probably due to their numerical low sensitivity with respect to round-off errors, as highlighted in [Mullis and Roberts, 1976] or in [Thiele, 1986]. In the system identification framework, this low sensitivity is mainly used to yield numerically well-conditioned models as studied, *i.e.*, in [Chou and Maciejowski, 1997, Bauer and Deistler, 1999]. Indeed, as explained in [Chou and Maciejowski, 1997], the balanced realization of a state-space representation is the one which is "furthest away" from non-minimality⁷. Furthermore, as proved in [Lutz and Hakimi, 1988], the balanced realizations minimize a particular sensitivity measure of the transfer function due to perturbation effects of the elements of the state-space matrices.

Besides these good numerical properties and the fact that, for a stable and minimal system, the balanced realizations always exist, the most interesting characteristic of balanced realizations, as far as this contribution is concerned, is associated with the uniqueness of the balancing transformation (see [Laub et al., 1987] and [Moore, 1981] for details). By construction, the Lyapunov balancing procedure introduced previously does not yield to a unique parameterization. Indeed, when the algorithm developed in [Laub et al., 1987] and summed up previously is applied⁸ on any fully-parameterized state-space form, the computed balanced form is also fully-parameterized, which invalidates the condition that the number of real-valued parameters of the resulting

⁷This idea is used, *e.g.*, for model reduction [Moore, 1981].

⁸The MATLAB function to perform the balancing is `balreal`.

state-space representation is⁹ lower or equal to $n_x(n_u + n_y) + n_u n_y$ [Chou, 1994, Lemma 3.6] for a canonical form. More precisely [Moore, 1981],

Theorem 5.1 *Let $(\mathbf{A}_b, \mathbf{B}_b, \mathbf{C}_b, \mathbf{D}_b)$ a state-space form in the subset of $\mathcal{D}_{n_x}^{n_y, n_u}$ composed of all balanced systems and define*

$$\Sigma = \text{diag}(\sigma_1 \mathbf{I}_{n(1) \times n(1)}, \sigma_2 \mathbf{I}_{n(2) \times n(2)}, \dots, \sigma_k \mathbf{I}_{n(k) \times n(k)}) \quad (5.24)$$

with $\sigma_1 > \sigma_2 > \dots > \sigma_k > 0$ and $\sum_{j=1}^k n(j) = n_x$, then $(\mathbf{A}_b, \mathbf{B}_b, \mathbf{C}_b, \mathbf{D}_b)$ is unique up to an orthogonal state-space transformation of the form

$$\mathbf{Q} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{Q}_1, \dots, \mathbf{Q}_k) \quad (5.25)$$

with orthogonal $\mathbf{Q}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n(i) \times n(i)}$ for all $i \in [1, k]$.

However, when this balancing procedure is used, it is shown in [Laub et al., 1987] that

- if the eigenvalues of the product of the reachability and observability Gramians are distinct, the similarity transformation \mathbf{T} is essentially unique, *i.e.*, is unique up to a post-multiplication by any matrix of the form $\text{diag}(\pm 1, \pm 1, \dots, \pm 1)$,
- if two or more eigenvalues are repeated, their corresponding eigenvectors can be rotated arbitrarily in the corresponding eigenspace.

As far as LPV system identification is concerned, these local features imply that, as long as the eigenvalues are distinct, if the true system exhibits a smooth dependence from the scheduling variables, then the overall parameter dependent model can be reconstructed directly from the identified local models. This conclusion must be relaxed because

- in general, the assumption of distinct eigenvalues cannot be guaranteed *a priori*,
- the case of distinct eigenvalues does not ensure uniqueness of the matrices parameters, because of the determination of the similarity transformation matrix up to the sign.

In fact, these two linked problems can be solved by resorting to the following system-dependent systematic approach.

⁹It is well-known that the set of all possible input-output behaviors of a state-space systems is a manifold of dimension $n_x(n_u + n_y) + n_u n_y$ [Clark, 1976].

- If the elements of the state-space matrices of the identified local models exhibit a smooth variation as a function of the scheduling variables, then the overall parameter-dependent model can be directly recovered by using specific interpolation techniques.
- If, on the contrary, the behavior of the elements of the state-space matrices exhibits abrupt sign changes (associated with sign changes in the columns of the balancing transformations), then, the eigenvalues of the balanced Gramians must be verified.
 - If sign changes are present but the eigenvalues are distinct, then a mild non-uniqueness is occurring, which can be corrected by adjusting the signs of the "stray" matrix elements (see Remark 5.5),
 - If, on the other hand, sign changes are associated with non unique eigenvalues, then a convenient solution could be to neglect momentarily the local model giving rise to the problem of performing the model interpolation by using $N_{op} - 1$ local models only.

Remark 5.5 *Adjusting the sign of the "stray" matrix elements consists in introducing a similarity transformation, diagonal and almost equal to the identity matrix, with -1 at the position corresponding to the required changes of sign. In [Tréguet, 2009, Chapter 2], an algorithm, summed up hereafter, and based on a smart analysis of the components of the matrices of two successive local models, is available to deal with this problem of non-uniqueness of the similarity transformation involved in the construction of a balanced form.*

Algorithm 2 Sign change detection and corresponding similarity transformation construction [Tréguet, 2009].

```

T = I $n_x \times n_x$ 
for  $c = 1 : n_x$  do
  {Avoid sign changes due to numerical imprecision}
  Find the line index, denoted  $j$ , of the largest absolute value of  $\mathbf{C}_i[:, c]$ 
  {Check if the sign of the  $c$ th column of  $\mathbf{C}_{i+1}$  has to be changed}
  if  $\text{sign}(\mathbf{C}_{i+1}[j, c]) \neq \text{sign}(\mathbf{C}_i[j, c])$  then
    T[ $c, c$ ] =  $-1$ 
  end if
end for

```

Once a set of reliable local models $\{\mathbf{A}_{b_i}, \mathbf{B}_{b_i}, \mathbf{C}_{b_i}, \mathbf{D}_{b_i}, i \in [1, N_{op}]\}$ described via balanced representations is available, the last step consists in interpolating the parameters of the local models efficiently by resorting to standard

techniques of interpolation [Sakhnovich, 1997, Mastroianni and Milovanovic, 2008]. Thanks to the use of the balanced form, it is assumed that the scheduling variables dependency of the LPV model is smooth. Specific choices of the interpolations functions and dependency (affine, LFT, ...) will result in different global LPV model. If, for instance, an affine dependency such as (5.5) is considered, the following cost function can be used

$$\arg \min_{\mathbf{M}_j, j \in [0, n_p]} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{op}} \left\| \mathbf{M}_0 + \sum_{j=1}^{n_p} p_j \mathbf{M}_j - \mathfrak{M}_i \right\|_F^2 \quad (5.26)$$

where, for $i = [1, N_{op}]$, the local models are described via the compact equation

$$\mathfrak{M}_i = \begin{bmatrix} \mathfrak{A}_{b_i} & \mathfrak{B}_{b_i} \\ \mathfrak{C}_{b_i} & \mathfrak{D}_{b_i} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.27)$$

and where, for $j = [0, n_p]$, the matrices \mathbf{M}_j defined as

$$\mathbf{M}_j = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_j & \mathbf{B}_j \\ \mathbf{C}_j & \mathbf{D}_j \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.28)$$

must be computed. This optimization can be written as a least-squares minimization problem (see, e.g., [Tréguet, 2009, Chapter 2] for an illustration). Notice that, for more complex scheduling variables dependency, similar cost functions can be introduced. Unfortunately, as shown in [De Caigny et al., 2009], some of them can lead to non-linear least-squares problems [De Caigny et al., 2009]. A good initialization is then necessary (see [De Caigny et al., 2009] for some insights concerning this problem). Whatever the interpolation procedure as well as the \mathbf{p} -dependency used to fit the LPV model to the local estimates, a good validation of the final LPV model is essential to verify that the prior choice of \mathbf{p} -dependency is good enough to approximate the dynamic behavior of the process under study.

Remark 5.6 *Although the afore-described technique solves many numerical problems and limitations of the methods suggested in [Steinbuch et al., 2003, van Helvoort et al., 2004, Groot Wassink et al., 2005, Paijmans et al., 2008, De Caigny et al., 2009], the problem of local state basis is still open. The issue with black-box identification is that no prior information is available, which renders the determination of coherent state basis coordinates quite complicated. According to the Author's experience, the use of balanced forms is a first relevant step towards the construction of accurate local techniques in a black-box framework.*

5.4 Direct identification of a global linear parameter-varying state-space model from a collection of local experimental data: the glocal method

Worthwhile, *e.g.*, for controller design, the black-box techniques can miss interesting information available from an initial study of the non-linear equations governing the behavior of the plant under study. Indeed, if the only source of information is restricted to measured data, it can be difficult to select the good scheduling variables of the LPV model or, more annoying, the correct structure of the LPV model. According to the Author's knowledge, the idea of using the non-linear dynamic equations to build a suitable LPV model structure is usually restricted to the global approach, as it was done, *e.g.*, in [Smith and Ahmed, 2000, Rugh and Shamma, 2000, Marcos and Balas, 2004, Giarré et al., 2006, Kwiatkowski et al., 2006], [van Wingerden, 2008, Chapters 3 and 4], [Hashemi et al., 2009]. For instance, in [Hashemi et al., 2009], the non-linear dynamic model of a CRS A465 robotic manipulator is used to derive a quasi-LPV model of the system. More precisely, a parameter-affine LPV model is identified by applying a global approach where typical trajectories of the scheduling variables are generated so that all of the expected operating regions of the plant are covered. On the contrary, the methods belonging to the local approach family generally resort to black-box local models and focus on the problem of a coherent interpolation of LTI models described in different state space coordinates bases [Shoukens et al., 2003, Groot Wassink et al., 2005, Lovera and Mercère, 2007, Paijmans et al., 2008]. Inspired by the discussion available in [Casella and Lovera, 2008], more precisely by the fact that shortcomings of the analytic and experimental methods could be relaxed by combining techniques and ideas originating from both points of view, it is suggested in the following

- resorting to the knowledge available from the study of the non-linear equations governing the system behavior in order to fix the structure of the global LPV model,
- estimating the parameters of this global LPV model by using data acquired locally, *i.e.*, input-output data sets corresponding to different but fixed operating points.

By doing so, this approach is interesting from a theoretical as well as a practical point of view because

- it circumvents the standard problems related to the interpolation of local models such as [Lovera and Mercère, 2007, Tóth, 2010]

- the numerical issues if an ill-conditioned parameterization for the model class is chosen (*e.g.*, use of canonical forms with coefficients with huge magnitude variations (see [Steinbuch et al., 2003] for an illustration of this problem)),
- the challenge of realizing all the models with respect to the same state variables which comes into play when dealing with the problem of interpolating black-box local state-space models,
- it does not require a persistent excitation of the scheduling variables. Indeed, persistently exciting the scheduling variables is sometimes difficult to satisfy in a number of application domains such as, *e.g.*, in the mechatronics or aeronautics domains.

Among all the advantages listed above, the use of prior knowledge in order to design the dependency of the state-space matrices with respect to the scheduling variables is probably the most interesting one.

To sum up, the parameters of the global model are estimated from a collection of the different local experiments. This basic idea of realizing global functions by local actions is inspired from Hara's work dedicated to the design of "glocal controllers" [Hara, 2010]. For this reason, the identification procedure described herein is also called "glocal" in the sequel.

For the glocal technique, all the local I/O data sets are used at the same time in order to estimate the parameters of the global LPV model. More precisely, considering the availability of δ local I/O data sets, the following cost function is used

$$V(\boldsymbol{\vartheta}) = \sum_{i=1}^{\delta} \|\mathbf{y}_i(t) - \mathbf{y}_i(t, \boldsymbol{\vartheta})\|_2^2 \quad (5.29)$$

where $\mathbf{y}(t, \boldsymbol{\vartheta})$ is the output of the LPV model, $\boldsymbol{\vartheta}$ is the parameter vector to estimate and $\mathbf{y}(t)$ is the output of the system to identify. By doing so, the parameters of the LPV model are estimated in one shot without requiring any interpolation step. Furthermore, by using such a cumulative cost function, the variance of the estimated parameters should be smaller than by calculating the parameters as the mean value of δ estimates computed from each local experimental data set.

Because the criterion $V(\boldsymbol{\vartheta})$ can be highly non-linear with respect to the parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\vartheta}$, its optimization can be quite complex. A reliable initial parameter vector is essential in order to guarantee a good convergence towards the global optimum when standard gradient-based techniques are involved. Solutions restricted to LTI state-space models have been introduced in Chapter 4. Although their extension to LPV models is conceivable (and under study recently), the first studies show that the adaptation, *e.g.*, of the

null-space approach developed in Sub-Section 4.4.1 still deserves work before being applied in the LPV framework. In order to circumvent this problem of initialization, a good solution consists in using a genetic algorithm [Goldberg, 1989]. Among all the algorithms available in the literature [Banzhaf et al., 1997], a good candidate is the differential evolution algorithm developed by Price et al. (see [Price et al., 2005] for details). As claimed by its authors, this differential evolution algorithm is "a very simple population-based stochastic function minimizer". As a genetic algorithm, the basic idea of this differential evolution algorithm is a reliable scheme able to generate efficiently the trial parameter vectors. The main improvements of this approach (w.r.t. the literature dedicated to the genetic methods [Schaefer, 2010]) are mainly its good convergence properties and its suitability for parallelization [Price et al., 2005]. Notice that the estimates obtained from this genetic algorithm can be used as initial estimates for a more standard non-linear optimization algorithm used by a prediction error or output error method.

Remark 5.7 *The efficiency of the glocal technique to approximate the behavior of the system is highly dependent on the way the global LPV model structure is selected beforehand. Like the standard identification techniques dedicated to LPV model identification, the availability of a reliable LPV form of the system to identify is the starting point and the first assumption of the glocal method. This initial step has not been (and will not be) thoroughly studied in this monograph. Only the description of a standard linearization-based approximation method has been introduced in Section 1.3. As shown in [Tóth, 2008, Chapter 7], the linearization-based techniques or the substitution ones can suffer from drawbacks in terms of remainder terms drops, selection of good linearization terms, loss of validity, ... Thus, the user of the glocal technique must be aware that, if it is not used with caution, possible transient mis-functioning of the final LPV model can occur because of the linearization-based technique used for the determination of the LPV model structure. A combination with the technique described in [Tóth, 2008, Section 7.4] can be seen as a good solution if the standard and easy-tuning techniques such as the linearization-based methods fail to give access to a final consistent LPV model.*

5.5 Simulation example

When models of robotic systems are required, a standard solution consists in resorting to a white-box model obtained by combining the laws of physics governing the behavior of the system [Shi and McPhee, 2000]. Their descriptions are usually based on the Euler-Lagrange equations and the virtual work principle [Dym and Shames, 1973]. Interesting from a theoretical point of

view, the exclusive use of the standard laws of physics makes the final model quite complex and requires an accurate knowledge of the manipulator as well as high-level skills in robotics especially when different robot structures are handled. This is all the more true when the user wants to have access to physical parameters of the system which are imperfectly known. In order to circumvent these difficulties, efforts dedicated to robot identification are more and more made in the industry [Kozłowski, 1998, Stanway et al., 1998]. However, a direct identification of a non-linear black-box model is often complicated because

- strong non-linearities (*e.g.*, inherent flexibilities) can appear in particular working conditions,
- the development of a global non-linear model structure can rely on strong assumptions such as a uniform density of the manipulator segments or the nature of the deformations if any.

Because a linear time-invariant model is often not sufficient when the system is used in a large robot workspace, LPV models are more and more introduced in robotics (see, *e.g.*, [Steinbuch et al., 2003, van Helvoort et al., 2004, Lachhab et al., 2008, Hashemi et al., 2009, Boonto and Werner, 2010]). The development of LPV model identification for the experimental modeling of robots is advocated for two main reasons. First, from an identification point of view, the introduction of such a structure allows the use of standard tools dedicated to LTI models for the estimation of models with a structural flexibility able to picture time-varying as well as non-linear dynamics. Second, the construction of a reliable LPV model is a standard initial step for many controller design techniques available in robotics [Craig, 2005].

As far as LPV system identification of robotic manipulators or mechanical systems is concerned, to the Author's knowledge, apart from [Hashemi et al., 2009], most of the developments available in the literature have considered the local approach. More precisely, in [Steinbuch et al., 2003, van Helvoort et al., 2004], the derivation of robot LPV models is performed by interpolating local LTI state-space models calculated from frequency responses measured at different operating points. Then, in [Paijmans et al., 2008, De Caigny et al., 2011], the identification of mechanical or vibro-acoustic applications is tackled by using the SMILE technique. This method is more particularly based on the interpolation of black-box canonical state-space LTI representations that are estimated for fixed operating conditions of the system. In the following of this chapter, we will not depart from this basic idea and local experimental data sets will be handled. In order to evaluate and highlight the performance of the afore-described local techniques, a specific robot manipulator is going to be used. This manipulator, the test-bed as well as the dynamic equations

governing its behavior are first introduced in Sub-Sections 5.5.1 and 5.5.2. Then, the identification techniques described in Section 5.3 and Section 5.4 are evaluated with the help of simulated data in Sub-Section 5.5.3 and in Sub-Section 5.5.4 respectively.

5.5.1 Robot manipulator description

Figure 5.1: Geometry of the flexible arm studied in this section.

In this study, the system is a horizontal flexible arm composed of two ($n_\theta = 2$) segments as depicted in Figure 5.1. Such a structure can be found, e.g., when considering the two first rotoid joints of a SCARA manipulator. Under specific functioning conditions, this type of manipulator may have important flexibilities. For instance, these flexible characteristics are satisfied by a prototype manipulator designed by SINTERS and used in [Ginhoux et al., 2005] (see Fig. 5.2). This robot is lightweight because it is designed to attain fast dynamics in order to compensate the heart tissue motion for cardiac surgery. As a result, it is observed that the bandwidth is restricted by flexible modes that can be attributed to small deformations of the segments. This flexible system, more precisely a simulator of this surgery robot, is going to be used in the following for the validation of the identification techniques introduced beforehand.

For the system depicted in Figure 5.2, both joints are torque-controlled and the joint positions θ_1 and θ_2 (see Fig. 5.1 for the definition) are measured by encoders. The aim is to control the position of the end-effector so that it can be measured by a video camera. Deformations of the two segments are considered but are not measured. Both segments have the same length

Figure 5.2: SINTERS robot with 6 degrees of freedom (DoF).

$\ell_1 = \ell_2 = 0.5$ m and respective masses of 7.5 and 5 kg. Their sections are squares of length 5 cm. The material has a Young modulus equal to 5 MPa.

A general scheme of the test-bed used hereafter is presented Figure 5.3. On the real system (available at the Image Sciences, Computer Sciences and Remote Sensing Laboratory of the University of Strasbourg), each joint is actuated by an electric motor. Incremental encoders measure the motor angular positions. The motor speed of each joint is locally controlled by a commercial drive. The joint velocity controllers are tuned in order to satisfy a good trade-off between high bandwidth and low noise on the current references. A dedicated computer is also used to communicate with the system and to control the motors via an I/O board. The end-effector could be any surgical tool. As shown in Figure 5.4, the position of the end-effector is measured thanks to a LED, a laser and optical markers. A CCD camera is used to measure the relative position between the organ and a tool held by the end-effector. A second computer is dedicated to the image acquisition and the image processing. Details and characteristics for the high-speed cameras and the real-time implementation of the data acquisition and image processing are available in [Gangloff et al., 2006, Cuvillon et al., 2012]. The measurement of the relative translation of the instrument with respect to the heart is performed by

Figure 5.3: Test-bed diagram.

measuring

- the vector between the target center of mass (blue cross in Fig. 5.4) and the laser spot (red cross in Fig. 5.4),
- the distance in the image between the LED spot (green circle in Fig. 5.4) and the target center of mass (blue cross in Fig. 5.4).

The first degree of freedom (# 1) of the arm is used for the vertical motion. The second and third ones (# 2 and # 3) are linked to the relative position of the target center of mass (blue cross in Fig. 5.4) and the laser spot (red cross in Fig. 5.4). For this validation step, the studied motion is restricted to these two last degrees of freedom (# 2 and # 3).

As said previously, the spot position measurements are made with the help of a CCD camera. In practice, first this camera must be located so that it does not disturb the surgeon and his staff and second is difficult to move during the operation mainly for safety reasons. These practical conditions highly reduce the working field of the robot. Because of these constraints, the use of a global technique requiring a persistent excitation of the inputs as well as the scheduling variables is not conceivable. On the contrary, a local approach seems to be well-tuned for the LPV model identification of such a system.

Figure 5.4: Zoom on the visual markers, camera and tools used to measure the position of the end-effector.

5.5.2 Non-linear and linearized dynamic models

Under the assumption of Euler-Bernoulli beam, the dynamic equations of a flexible arm can be derived by using the assumed-mode method where the deformation field is decomposed into a finite sum of elementary deformations [Shi and McPhee, 2000]. In the current case, small deformations are considered and only one mode is chosen for the transverse deformation field. For segment $\#k$, $k = 1, \dots, n_\theta$, the deformation field writes $\delta_k(x, t) = x^2 v_k(t)$, where x represents the abscissa along the segment and $v_k(t)$ is the state of the deformation. Therefore, the resulting deformation at the end of the segment of length ℓ_k is $\delta_k(\ell_k, t) = \ell_k^2 v_k(t)$. The dynamic model is derived from the Virtual Work Principle using the DynaFlex toolbox developed on Maple by Shi and McPhee (see [Shi and McPhee, 2002]). By denoting $\boldsymbol{\theta} = [\theta_1 \ \theta_2]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta}$ and $\mathbf{v} = [v_1 \ v_2]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n_v}$, the resulting model relies on a generalized position vector $\mathbf{q} = [\boldsymbol{\theta}^\top \ \mathbf{v}^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n_q}$, with $n_q = n_\theta + n_v$, and writes (see Fig. 5.1 for the notations)

$$\mathcal{M}(\mathbf{q}(t)) \ddot{\mathbf{q}}(t) = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{q}(t), \dot{\mathbf{q}}(t)) + \mathcal{G} \mathbf{u}(t) \quad (5.30)$$

where $\mathcal{M}(\mathbf{q})$ is the inertia matrix, $\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})$ is a generalized force vector that includes the Coriolis and centrifugal effects (see Appendix A.4 for details about the mathematical expressions of the matrix \mathcal{M} and the vector \mathcal{F}). The torque vector $\mathbf{u} = [u_1 \ u_2]^\top$ has only effects on the dynamics of the rigid positions

θ_1 and θ_2 , corresponding to

$$\mathcal{G} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n_\theta \times n_\theta} \\ \mathbf{0}_{n_v \times n_\theta} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5.31)$$

The x and y positions of the end-effector can be written from the geometric model, resulting in the non-linear measurement equation $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{q})$, *i.e.*,

$$\begin{aligned} z_1 = & (\ell_1 - \frac{2}{3}\ell_1^3 v_1^2) \cos(\theta_1) - \ell_1^2 v_1 \sin(\theta_1) \\ & + (\ell_2 - \frac{2}{3}\ell_2^3 v_2^2) \cos(\theta_{12}) - \ell_2^2 v_2 \sin(\theta_{12}) \end{aligned} \quad (5.32a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} z_2 = & (\ell_1 - \frac{2}{3}\ell_1^3 v_1^2) \sin(\theta_1) + \ell_1^2 v_1 \cos(\theta_1) \\ & + \ell_2^2 v_2 \cos(\theta_{12}) + (\ell_2 - \frac{2}{3}\ell_2^3 v_2^2) \sin(\theta_{12}) \end{aligned} \quad (5.32b)$$

where $\theta_{12} = \theta_1 + \theta_2 + 2\ell_1 v_1$.

In order to fix the structure of the global LPV model required by the technique introduced in Section 5.4, a standard Jacobian linearization can be applied to the generalized second order model given in Eq. (5.30). More precisely, for a set of working points $(\mathbf{q}_0, \dot{\mathbf{q}}_0)$, we get ¹⁰

$$\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{p})\ddot{\mathbf{q}}(t) = \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{p})\dot{\mathbf{q}}(t) + \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{p})\mathbf{q}(t) + \mathbf{G}\mathbf{u}(t) \quad (5.33)$$

where $\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{q}_0, \dot{\mathbf{q}}_0)$ is the scheduling variable vector and where

$$\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{q}_0, \dot{\mathbf{q}}_0)) = \mathcal{M}(\mathbf{q}_0) \quad \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{q}_0, \dot{\mathbf{q}}_0)) = \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{q}_0, \dot{\mathbf{q}}_0)}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{q}}} \quad (5.34a)$$

$$\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{q}_0, \dot{\mathbf{q}}_0)) = \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{q}_0, \dot{\mathbf{q}}_0)}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \quad \mathbf{G} = \mathcal{G} \quad (5.34b)$$

are the inertia, the damping, the stiffness and the control matrices of the linearized model respectively. Notice that \mathbf{G} does not depend on \mathbf{p} . In this work, we focus on the identification of a model that includes the variability of the behavior with respect to the positions θ_k , $k = 1, 2$. Then, the other phenomena can be neglected and, consequently¹¹, $\mathbf{q}_0 = [\theta_0^\top \quad \mathbf{0}_{1 \times n_v}]$ and $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_0 = \mathbf{0}_{n_q \times 1}$. By considering

$$\mathbf{x} = [\mathbf{q}^\top \quad \dot{\mathbf{q}}^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^8 \quad (5.35)$$

as the state vector, the following local linearized state equation can be deduced¹²

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{p})\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{p})\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(t) \quad (5.36)$$

¹⁰In the following, the equilibrium values are omitted in order to shorten the notations.

¹¹This choice corresponds to neglect the Coriolis effects. The validity of this assumption will be evaluated simultaneously with the identified model.

¹²In the sequel, z_\bullet , θ_\bullet , v_\bullet , q_\bullet , ..., are considered as variations around a nominal value.

with

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{p}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n_q \times n_q} & \mathbf{0}_{n_q \times n_q} \\ \mathbf{0}_{n_q \times n_q} & \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{p}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.37a)$$

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{p}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_q \times n_q} & \mathbf{I}_{n_q \times n_q} \\ \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{p}) & \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{p}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.37b)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_q \times n_u} \\ \mathbf{G} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5.37c)$$

For most of the robotic manipulators, the inertia matrix $\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{p})$ is inverted. This property is generally used in the literature (see, e.g., [Hashemi et al., 2009]) leading to the following local state-space representation

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \bar{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{p})\mathbf{x}(t) + \bar{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{p})\mathbf{u}(t) \quad (5.38)$$

with

$$\bar{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{p}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_q \times n_q} & \mathbf{I}_{n_q \times n_q} \\ \mathbf{M}^{-1}(\mathbf{p})\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{p}) & \mathbf{M}^{-1}(\mathbf{p})\mathbf{D}(\mathbf{p}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.39a)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{p}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_q \times n_u} \\ \mathbf{M}^{-1}(\mathbf{p})\mathbf{G} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5.39b)$$

This more standard representation unfortunately depends on \mathbf{p} in a more complex way than for the descriptor one. For instance, contrary to $\bar{\mathbf{B}}$, the input matrix \mathbf{B} is independent on \mathbf{p} . For both state-space forms, the state equation only depends on θ_2 ¹³ whereas the output equation depends on both θ_1 and θ_2 .

As shown in Eq. (5.32), the output equations are highly non-linear with respect to θ_1 and θ_2 . This complexity can be reduced by using efficiently the Jacobian of the rigid geometric model (see Eq. (5.32) for a definition of \mathbf{g}), i.e.,

$$\mathbf{J}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \frac{\partial \mathbf{g} \left([\boldsymbol{\theta}^\top \quad \mathbf{0}_{1 \times n_v}]^\top \right)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}}. \quad (5.40)$$

Except for the singular positions, this Jacobian is invertible and it is possible to define a new measurement vector

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{J}^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{z}. \quad (5.41)$$

The entries of this new measurement vector \mathbf{y} are the angular positions of a fictitious rigid arm which would have the same geometry and the same measurement \mathbf{z} than the flexible one (see Figure 5.5). The use of \mathbf{y} instead of \mathbf{z} allows the simplification of the measurement equation, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t) \quad (5.42)$$

¹³The system behavior is invariant by a rotation of angle θ_1 . Therefore, the matrices \mathbf{A} , $\bar{\mathbf{A}}$, \mathbf{B} and $\bar{\mathbf{B}}$ do not depend on θ_1 .

Figure 5.5: Flexible manipulator (gray) and virtual rigid manipulator (black) with the same image position of the end-effector.

where

$$\mathbf{C} = [\mathbf{C}_1 \quad \mathbf{0}_{n_\theta \times n_q}] \quad (5.43)$$

and

$$\mathbf{C}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \ell_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \ell_1 & \ell_2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5.44)$$

Thus, the structure of \mathbf{C}_1 is quite simple when the output \mathbf{y} is handled instead of \mathbf{z} . By assuming that the geometry of the rigid part of the manipulator is available, \mathbf{C} can moreover be considered as known.

By looking closer at the equations available in Appendix A.4, it is clear that the matrices \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{D} and \mathbf{K} are affine functions of $\cos(\theta_2)$ and $\sin(\theta_2)$. Then, the scheduling variable should be related to θ_2 . Notice that this angular position is easy to measure on a flexible robot because an encoder is generally located at the motor side of the joints. This availability is paramount when the experimental modeling of the LPV model is considered.

As claimed previously, the industrial manipulators are equipped with low-level joint-velocity control loops in order to reduce the effects of the frictions which occur in the gear-boxes and therefore obtain a simpler behavior (see Controller in Fig. 5.3). Due to the co-location of the torque actuation and the position measurement at the motor side, a high bandwidth of this inner loop can be obtained with a standard static output feedback. More precisely,

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = \mathbf{\Lambda} \left(\dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}^*(t) - \dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(t) \right) \quad (5.45)$$

where $\dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}^*(t) = [\dot{\theta}_1^*(t) \ \dot{\theta}_2^*(t)]^\top$ is the vector of the speed references. The state-space representations given in Eq. (5.36) and Eq. (5.38) become respectively

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{p})\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_q \times n_\theta} \\ \mathbf{G}\boldsymbol{\Lambda} \end{bmatrix} \dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}^*(t) \\ &+ \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_q \times n_q} & \mathbf{I}_{n_q \times n_q} \\ \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{p}) & \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{p}) - \mathbf{G}\boldsymbol{\Lambda} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n_\theta \times n_\theta} & \mathbf{0}_{n_\theta \times n_v} \end{bmatrix} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (5.46)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_q \times n_\theta} \\ \mathbf{M}^{-1}(\mathbf{p})\mathbf{G}\boldsymbol{\Lambda} \end{bmatrix} \dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}^*(t) \\ &+ \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_q \times n_q} & \mathbf{I}_{n_q \times n_q} \\ \mathbf{M}^{-1}(\mathbf{p})\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{p}) & \mathbf{M}^{-1}(\mathbf{p}) (\mathbf{D}(\mathbf{p}) - \mathbf{G}\boldsymbol{\Lambda} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n_\theta \times n_\theta} & \mathbf{0}_{n_\theta \times n_v} \end{bmatrix}) \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (5.47)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Lambda} = \text{diag}(\lambda_1, \lambda_2)$.

Considering the position \mathbf{y} as the output measurement has one drawback: the model is unstable due to the pure integration between speed and position. Therefore, it is generally recommended to use the velocity $\dot{\mathbf{y}} = \dot{\mathbf{y}}$ instead¹⁴. By using the state matrices introduced beforehand, the output equation rewrites

$$\dot{\mathbf{y}}(t) = \mathbf{C}\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \dot{\mathbf{C}}\mathbf{x}(t) \quad (5.48)$$

where

$$\dot{\mathbf{C}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_\theta \times n_q} & \mathbf{C}_1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5.49)$$

By analyzing the relations given in Eq. (5.47)-(5.48), it appears that this state-space form is not minimal because the two first states θ_1 and θ_2 are not influenced by the input and have no effects on the output. Hence,

$$(\mathbf{M}^{-1}(\mathbf{p})\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{p}))(:, 1 : n_\theta) = \mathbf{0}_{n_q \times n_\theta}. \quad (5.50)$$

The change of output signal allows the reduction of the model order. A minimal realization of order 6 can be extracted by considering

$$\check{\mathbf{x}} = [\mathbf{v}^\top \ \dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}^\top \ \dot{\mathbf{v}}^\top]^\top. \quad (5.51)$$

More precisely,

$$\dot{\check{\mathbf{x}}}(t) = \check{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{p})\check{\mathbf{x}}(t) + \check{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{p})\dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}^*(t) \quad (5.52a)$$

$$\check{\mathbf{y}}(t) = \check{\mathbf{C}}\check{\mathbf{x}}(t) \quad (5.52b)$$

¹⁴In practice, the velocity is estimated from the discrete-time measurement of the position.

where¹⁵

$$\check{\mathbf{A}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_v \times n_\theta} & \mathbf{0}_{n_v \times n_v} & \mathbf{I}_{n_v \times n_v} \\ (\mathbf{M}^{-1}(\mathbf{p})\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{p}))(:, n_\theta + 1 : \text{end}) & -\mathbf{M}^{-1}(\mathbf{p})\mathbf{G}\mathbf{\Lambda} & \mathbf{0}_{n_q \times n_v} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.53a)$$

$$\check{\mathbf{B}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_v \times n_\theta} \\ \mathbf{M}^{-1}(\mathbf{p})\mathbf{G}\mathbf{\Lambda} \end{bmatrix} \quad \check{\mathbf{C}} = [\mathbf{0}_{n_\theta \times n_v} \quad \mathbf{C}_1]. \quad (5.53b)$$

5.5.3 Identification results with the method based on the local balanced forms

First, the system introduced beforehand is identified by using the local technique described in Section 5.3. A SIMULINK model of the flexible robotic manipulator is available to carry out the experiments. This simulator is built from the non-linear equations governing the behavior of the flexible arm presented in Sub-Section 5.5.1 and in Sub-Section 5.5.2. As said previously, δ local I/O data sets are first generated. More precisely, for 7 constant values of θ_2 in the range $[\frac{\pi}{8} : \frac{\pi}{8} : \frac{7\pi}{8}]$, 7 noise-free I/O data sets are acquired. The inputs of the system, as shown in Figure 5.3, are angular position references $\theta^* = [\theta_1^* \quad \theta_2^*]^\top$ and are chosen as two uncorrelated pseudo-random binary sequences built so that all the dynamics of the system is well-excited. The outputs of the model are \check{y} , *i.e.*, the angular velocities of the fictitious rigid robot having the same geometry of the flexible robot. This noise-free I/O data is generated once for each value of $\theta_2 \in [\frac{\pi}{8} : \frac{\pi}{8} : \frac{7\pi}{8}]$. Then, a Monte Carlo simulation of size 100 is used for the estimation of the local models. This Monte Carlo simulation is carried out by adding up on the noise-free outputs 100 realizations of two uncorrelated zero-mean white Gaussian noises satisfying a signal-noise ratio¹⁶ equal to 30dB. The length of each local data set is equal to 30000 samples with a sampling period of 0.1 *ms*. For the identification, a down-sampling is performed with a rate equal to 10. A sample of noisy I/O data is given in Figure 5.6.

The first step of this local procedure consists in estimating, for each run of the Monte Carlo simulation, reliable local models expressed in a balanced state coordinate basis. In order to reach this goal,

- first the PI-MOESP algorithm [Verhaegen, 1994, Verhaegen and Verdult, 2007] is applied to perform the local estimation from the local I/O noisy data sets. This subspace-based identification algorithm is indeed well-known to be efficient under the noisy conditions described beforehand,

¹⁵For our system, $\mathbf{D}(\mathbf{p}) = \mathbf{0}_{n_q \times n_q}$.

¹⁶The signal-to-noise ratio is defined as follows: $SNR = 10 \log \left(\frac{\text{cov}\{\check{y}_i\}}{\text{cov}\{v\}} \right)$, $i \in [1, n_y]$ where v stands for the noise acting on the noise-free output \check{y}_i .

Figure 5.6: I/O data sample.

- second the local state-space representations are balanced with the help of the function `balreal` of MATLAB.

This two-step procedure is third completed by a discrete-to-continuous-time transformation. This step is required because

- the system under study is by construction continuous-time,
- the PI-MOESP algorithm only leads to discrete-time models,

This discrete-to-continuous-time domain conversion is performed by using the function `d2cm` available in MATLAB, more precisely by using the bilinear Tustin approximation to the derivative.

Once 100 local models are estimated for each operating point, 7 local models can be computed for each value of δ by averaging these 100 local models. These 7 average local models are then locally validated by considering two complementary tools

- two I/O fits evaluated on a new noise-free data set generated for this task,
- a comparison of the frequency responses (magnitude Bode plots) of the estimated local model and an analytic local model calculated from a linearization of the non-linear equations governing the behavior of the system.

For $i \in [1, n_y]$, the following fit measurements¹⁷ are introduced in order to quantify the model quality on validation data (*i.e.*, a data set different from

¹⁷ \check{y}_i stands for the i^{th} system output and \hat{y}_i for its estimate.

the one used for the estimation)

$$\text{FIT}_i = 100 \times \max \left(1 - \frac{\|\check{y}_i - \hat{y}_i\|}{\|\check{y}_i - \text{mean}(\check{y}_i)\|}, 0 \right) \quad (5.54a)$$

$$\text{VAF}_i = 100 \times \max \left(1 - \frac{\text{var}(\check{y}_i - \hat{y}_i)}{\text{var}(\check{y}_i)}, 0 \right) \quad (5.54b)$$

Table 5.1 (see also the time responses in Figure 5.7 for a qualitative validation for $\theta_2 = \frac{5\pi}{8}$) gathers these fit measurements for $\theta_2 \in [\frac{\pi}{8} : \frac{\pi}{8} : \frac{7\pi}{8}]$. From these values, it can be concluded that, for each operating point, the estimated local LTI models describe the actual system quite well. The reader must keep in mind that the system behavior is highly non-linear. Having fit measurements in the range [67%, 98%] is, according to the Author's experience, more than suitable. This initial conclusion is enhanced by comparing the frequency responses of these estimated LTI models with the frequency responses of local analytic models. Figure 5.8 shows the magnitude Bode plots in the least favorable case, *i.e.*, for $\theta_2 = \frac{\pi}{8}$ of

- the estimated local model (- -),
- a local analytic model of the flexible system (-) obtained by linearizing the non-linear equations given in Sub-Section 5.5.2,
- a local analytic model of an equivalent rigid system (-o).

These frequency plots show that the local model is able to approximate the system behavior in a relatively large range of frequencies (until $1e4 \text{ rad/s}$). Notice however that the local model has difficulties to picture the gain of the system when the transfers $\check{y}_1 \leftrightarrow u_2$ and $\check{y}_2 \leftrightarrow u_1$ are considered. The comparison with the rigid model indicates that the estimated models are a lot better at capturing the flexibilities of the system.

θ_2	$\frac{\pi}{8}$	$\frac{2\pi}{8}$	$\frac{3\pi}{8}$	$\frac{4\pi}{8}$	$\frac{5\pi}{8}$	$\frac{6\pi}{8}$	$\frac{7\pi}{8}$
FIT ₁ (%)	85.83	91.23	90.23	92.09	89.65	88.42	91.01
FIT ₂ (%)	67.42	98.18	85.07	97.83	88.97	89.82	97.23
VAF ₁ (%)	97.98	99.23	99.04	99.37	98.93	98.66	99.2
VAF ₂ (%)	89.39	99.96	97.77	99.9	98.78	98.96	99.9

Table 5.1: Performance metrics for the estimated LTI models on validation data.

Figure 5.7: Comparison of the time responses of the system (-) and the estimated local model (- -) for $\theta_2 = \frac{5\pi}{8}$.

Once 7 average local models are available, the resulting model parameters (elements of the estimated matrices $(\hat{\mathbf{A}}, \hat{\mathbf{B}}, \hat{\mathbf{C}}, \hat{\mathbf{D}})$) can be plotted versus the scheduling variable $p = \cos(\theta_2)$ (see Figure 5.9). This figure shows that, in this case, sign changes are clearly visible. These changes are due to the non-uniqueness in the used balancing transformation. A check of the eigenvalues of the balanced Gramians (see Figure 5.10) shows that the sign changes are due to a "mild" non-uniqueness because the eigenvalues are distinct for all considered values of p . Therefore, it is possible to proceed with model interpolation once the sign changes have been corrected. By using the algorithm described previously (see Algo. 2), this sign change problem is solved resulting in the parameters plotted in Figure 5.11. This figure shows that the estimated matrix elements exhibit a smooth and clearly recognizable dependence from the scheduling variable p .

The last step of the identification procedure consists in interpolating the coefficients of the estimated local state-space representations. The curves in Figure 5.11 lead us to choose a polynomial p -dependent form, *i.e.*,

$$\check{\mathbf{A}}(p) = \check{\mathbf{A}}_0 + \check{\mathbf{A}}_1 p + \dots + \check{\mathbf{A}}_d p^d \quad (5.55)$$

and similarly for $\check{\mathbf{B}}(p)$, $\check{\mathbf{C}}(p)$ and $\check{\mathbf{D}}(p)$. By using suitable regressors formed from the scheduling variable $p = \cos(\theta_2)$, a least-squares algorithm can be used to estimate the matrices $\check{\mathbf{A}}_i, \check{\mathbf{B}}_i, \check{\mathbf{C}}_i, \check{\mathbf{D}}_i, i \in [0, d]$, and, by extension $\check{\mathbf{A}}(p)$, $\check{\mathbf{B}}(p)$, $\check{\mathbf{C}}(p)$ and $\check{\mathbf{D}}(p)$. Notice indeed that the data used in this least-squares optimization is noise-free. This feature ensures an accurate estimation. The

Figure 5.8: Comparison of the frequency responses of the system (-), a rigid model (-o) and the estimated local model (- -) for $\theta_2 = \frac{\pi}{8}$.

Figure 5.9: Evolutions of the entries of the estimated balanced LTI state-space matrices with respect to $p = \cos(\theta_2)$ before sign change treatment.

Figure 5.10: Evolutions of the eigenvalues of the balanced Gramian matrices with respect to $p = \cos(\theta_2)$.

Figure 5.11: Evolutions of the entries of the estimated balanced LTI state-space matrices with respect to $p = \cos(\theta_2)$ after sign change treatment.

plots in Figure 5.11 show that the evolution is quite smooth and can be captured with a low-order polynomial. In order to validate the interpolation step, a second fit measurement is used

$$\overline{\text{FIT}} = 100 \times \left(1 - \frac{\|\boldsymbol{\eta} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}\|}{\|\boldsymbol{\eta} - \text{mean}(\boldsymbol{\eta})\|} \right) \quad (5.56)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ stands for a vector obtained after the vectorization of all the LTI model parameters estimated for $\theta_2 \in [\frac{\pi}{8} : \frac{\pi}{8} : \frac{7\pi}{8}]$ and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}$ the corresponding simulated vector using Eq. (5.55). The fits for the estimated models with $d = 2$ and $d = 3$ are displayed in Table 5.2. These figures show that the proposed interpolation procedure is efficient and that a low-order polynomial LPV model is a good trade-off between complexity and efficiency.

	d	$\check{\mathbf{A}}(p)$	$\check{\mathbf{B}}(p)$	$\check{\mathbf{C}}(p)$	$\check{\mathbf{D}}(p)$
$\overline{\text{FIT}}$ (%)	2	94.8	89.9	91.1	98.1
$\overline{\text{FIT}}$ (%)	3	97.5	95.7	95.5	98.9

Table 5.2: Parameter fit between the least-squares estimates and the local model parameters for different values of the degree d .

The final LPV model must be validated. For that, a new set of I/O data is generated. The system is more precisely excited so that the whole range of θ_2 is visited (see Fig. 5.12). Once again, the time responses for each output of the experimental LPV model are compared with the outputs of the non-linear simulator (see Tab. 5.3 for a quantified comparison and Fig. 5.13 for a specific sample). These fit measurements (average values of 10 different validation data sets) show that the designed LPV model is able to capture the dynamic behavior of the non-linear system. All these results prove that a local LPV model identification procedure based on local balanced state-space realizations can result in an accurate LPV model of a flexible arm robot.

	FIT (%)	VAF (%)
\check{y}_1	72.8	92.4
\check{y}_2	76.5	93.9

Table 5.3: Performance metrics (FIT and VAF) for the experimental LPV models (with $d = 3$) on validation data.

Figure 5.12: Evolution of θ_2 during the LPV models validation.

Figure 5.13: Comparison of the time responses of the system (-) and the identified LPV model (- -).

5.5.4 Identification results with the glocal method

In this sub-section, the identification of the LPV descriptor state-space model given in Eq. (5.46)-(5.48) is performed by using the glocal method described in Section 5.4. The main advantage of the descriptor model (in comparison with the more standard state-space representation given in Eq. (5.51)) is its simpler dependence on the scheduling variable p . Notice indeed that the model in Eq. (5.51) is rational in p because of $M^{-1}(p)$. A close look at the matrices composing the state-space representation given in Eq. (5.46)-(5.48) (see Appendix A.4 for details) brings out that these matrices are functions of the physical parameters $\ell_1, \ell_2, m_1, m_2, d$ and ε . In the following, the parameters to estimate are $\vartheta = [\varepsilon \ d]$. The developed technique could be applied similarly for the estimation of other physical parameters such as the mass or the length of the segments. This choice is mainly motivated by the availability of reliable measurements of ℓ_1, ℓ_2, m_1 and m_2 .

An identification setup similar to the one used in the previous sub-section is considered, *i.e.*, 7 noise-free I/O data sets are acquired for 7 constant θ_2 in the range $[\frac{\pi}{8} : \frac{\pi}{8} : \frac{7\pi}{8}]$. For each run, the input signals are chosen as two uncorrelated pseudo-random binary sequences. Then, the parameter vector $\vartheta = [\varepsilon \ d]$ is estimated by using

- the glocal technique described in Section 5.4,
- the same algorithm as the one applied for the glocal approach (*i.e.*, the differential evolution algorithm developed by K. Price *et al.* [Price et al., 2005]) but with the 7 local data set separately (so that 7 local models are estimated with a state-space structure satisfying Eq. (5.46)- (5.48) but with a fixed value of p).

The length of each local data set is again equal to 30000 samples with a sampling period of 0.1 *ms*. For the identification, a down-sampling is performed with a rate equal to 10. A Monte Carlo simulation is also carried out by adding up on the noise-free outputs 100 realizations of two uncorrelated zero-mean white Gaussian noises satisfying a signal-noise ratio equal to 20*dB*. As far as the initialization of the evolution algorithm is concerned, the initial population members (for each new generation) is allowed to vary in the range $[1 \text{ GPa}, \ 5 \text{ cm}] \times \pm 20\%$.

Figure 5.14 and Figure 5.15 illustrate this comparison with error bars. These curves are used to show the confidence intervals (black lines) of the estimated parameters (black crosses). Figure 5.14 and Figure 5.15 are each composed of three sub-plots. On the left-hand-side, the parameters estimated from the local data sets (associated with their standard deviations) versus the working points are drawn for each estimated local model. In the middle of

Figure 5.14: Estimation of $d = 0.05m$. Comparison of the mean values (black crosses) and the standard deviations (black lines) of the local results with the global one.

Figure 5.15: Estimation of $\epsilon = 1GPa$. Comparison of the mean values (black crosses) and the standard deviations (black lines) of the local results with the global one.

these figures is plotted the mean value of these 7 local estimates (with the corresponding standard deviation). On the right-hand-side, the estimated parameters and their confidence intervals obtained by applying the glocal method are given. By analyzing these figures, it is clear that

- the developed approach leads to reliable estimates of the parameters d and ε ,
- the confidence intervals of the estimated parameters is smaller with the glocal technique.

These results prove that the use of a mixed analytic/experimental local/global technique can be really effective.

In order to validate the LPV descriptor model, the time responses of the system and the model are compared in the following. For the model, the estimated parameters are chosen equal to $d = 0.05017 \text{ m}$ and $\varepsilon = 1.012e + 09 \text{ Pa}$, *i.e.*, the average values obtained with the glocal method (see Fig. 5.14 and Fig. 5.15). The system as well as the LPV model are excited so that the whole range of the scheduling variable is smoothly visited (see Fig. 5.12). The fit introduced in Eq. (5.54a) is used to quantify the quality of the model on validation data. Using 10 different sets of validation data, the average fit for the first and the second output of the system is 97.5% and 98.2% respectively. These figures prove the efficiency of the developed identification method.

5.6 Conclusions

In this chapter, the identification of LPV models from local data sets has been investigated. By local data sets, it is meant that, for each local experiment, the scheduling variables are held constant and the control inputs are excited. Such a point of view is standard in many applications where the scheduling variables cannot be excited intensively. For instance, this is the case for the robot manipulator introduced in Sub-Section 5.5.1. Indeed, in the aimed setup, a single video camera is used to provide a measurement of the position of the end-effector equipped with visual markers. In this situation, it is first recommended to zoom in on the markers in order to obtain an accurate measurement of the displacements due to the flexible modes which are of relatively small amplitude. Second, when moving the arm to another configuration, the camera must be re-positioned in order to keep the markers in the image. Thus, generating trajectories so that all the expected operating regions of the plant are covered in one shot is not conceivable. In order to get accurate LPV models from this local experimental data, two complementary local procedures have been introduced. First, a subspace-based identification

technique using suitable properties of the balanced state-space realizations has been presented and discussed. This technique

- first estimates local LTI state-space models from the available local data sets by using, *e.g.*, a subspace-based identification algorithm,
- second converts these local models into balanced realizations,
- third calculates the parameter-dependent model by interpolating the state-space matrices of the local models with a quite good efficiency and an interesting numerical robustness thanks to the unique properties of the balanced realizations.

Second, a mixed analytic/experimental local/global technique has been introduced. The idea used by this global technique consists in

- resorting to the knowledge available from the study of the non-linear equations governing the behavior of the system to fix the structure of the global LPV model,
- using the local experiment data to estimate, in one shot, the unknown parameters of the global LPV model.

Both techniques, which can be, in a way, considered as complementary, have been described into details in the previous sections and validated in terms of output fit and parameter fit for the identification of a flexible robot manipulator. These identification results have shown that

- LPV models with a low-order polynomial dependency can provide good results,
- the technique based on the local balanced state-space realizations operates a complexity reduction¹⁸ without really decreasing the approximation performance of the global model. Indeed, the structure of the identified LPV models is polynomial whereas the LPV model derived by Jacobian linearization of the non-linear equations has a rational dependence,
- using an additional modeling effort during the estimation step of the parameters of an LPV model can be worthwhile if the user is looking for parameters having a physical meaning,

¹⁸This complexity reduction is welcome for controller synthesis because most of the methods dedicated to the control of LPV systems do not stand rational dependence.

- dealing with a descriptor state-space representation instead of a standard state-space form can make the identification and the optimization procedure easier.

These results, obtained herein on simulation data, should be now validated with data acquired from the real test-bed available at the Image Sciences, Computer Sciences and Remote Sensing Laboratory of the University of Strasbourg.

APPENDIX A

Appendices

A.1 Canonical state-space matrices determination

In this section, it is proved that, for any matrix \mathbf{A} , any matrix \mathbf{C} and any vector $\boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top$ satisfying Proposition 3.1, the similarity transformation $\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C})$ gives rise to the state-space matrices \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{C} described in Eq. (3.13).

First of all, to make the notations easier, let us assume that \mathbf{K} is defined as in Eq. (3.11), *i.e.*,

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} \kappa_1 & \kappa_2 & \cdots & \kappa_{n_y} \\ 0 & 1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 1 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_y}. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Notice that this proof can be adapted directly for another choice of \mathbf{K} . Then,

$$\bar{\mathbf{y}}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{y}(t) \\ y_2(t) \\ \vdots \\ y_{n_y}(t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \bar{\mathbf{C}} = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \\ \mathbf{c}_2^\top \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{c}_{n_y}^\top \end{bmatrix}, \quad \bar{\mathbf{D}} = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{D} \\ \mathbf{d}_2^\top \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{d}_{n_y}^\top \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where y_i , \mathbf{c}_i^\top and \mathbf{d}_i^\top , $i \in [2, n_y]$ are respectively the i th output of the system and the i th rows of \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{D} . Let \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{C} be two matrices that are similar to \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{C} in the following sense

$$\mathcal{A} \Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C}) = \Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C}) \mathbf{A}, \quad (\text{A.3a})$$

$$\mathcal{C} \Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C}) = \bar{\mathbf{C}}. \quad (\text{A.3b})$$

Then, we shall show that \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{C} have the structure given in Eq. (3.13). As far as \mathcal{C} is concerned, we have

$$\mathcal{C}(1, :) \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A} \\ \vdots \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A}^{n_x-1} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{c}_1^\top \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A} \\ \vdots \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A}^{n_x-1} \end{bmatrix} = \bar{\mathbf{C}}(1, :) = \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where $\mathbf{c}_1^\top = \mathcal{C}(1, :)$. Introducing c_{1j} , $j \in [1, n_x]$, as the coefficients of \mathbf{c}_1^\top , the previous equation leads to

$$(c_{11} - 1)\boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} + c_{12}\boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A} + \cdots + c_{1n_x}\boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A}^{n_x-1} = 0. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Now, because $\text{rank}\{\boldsymbol{\Gamma}_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C})\} = n_x$, the rows of $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C})$ are linearly independent and, by extension,

$$c_{11} = 1 \text{ and } c_{1j} = 0, j \in [2, n_x]. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Using the same approach, we have

$$\mathcal{A}(j, :) \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A} \\ \vdots \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A}^{n_x-1} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{a}_j^\top \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A} \\ \vdots \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A}^{n_x-1} \end{bmatrix} = \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A}^j, \quad j \in [1, n_x] \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where $\mathbf{a}_j^\top = \mathcal{A}(j, :)$. Firstly, for $j \in [1, n_x - 1]$, we have

$$(a_{j(j+1)} - 1)\boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A}^j + \sum_{\substack{\ell=1 \\ \ell \neq j+1}}^{n_x} a_{j\ell} \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A}^{\ell-1} = 0 \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Again, because $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C})$ has full rank, it holds

$$a_{j(j+1)} = 1 \quad (\text{A.9a})$$

$$a_{j\ell} = 0, \ell \neq j+1, \forall j \in [1, n_x - 1]. \quad (\text{A.9b})$$

Then, as far as $\mathbf{a}_{n_x}^\top$ is concerned, we have

$$\mathbf{a}_{n_x}^\top \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A} \\ \vdots \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A}^{n_x-1} \end{bmatrix} = \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A}^{n_x}. \quad (\text{A.10})$$

Using the Cayley Hamilton theorem [Horn and Johnson, 1990], we know that

$$\mathbf{A}^{n_x} = -\alpha_0 \mathbf{I}_{n_x} - \alpha_1 \mathbf{A} - \dots - \alpha_{n_x-1} \mathbf{A}^{n_x-1} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

where α_ℓ , $\ell \in [0, n_x - 1]$, are the coefficients of the \mathbf{A} characteristic polynomial. Thus, Eq. (A.10) becomes

$$\sum_{\ell=1}^{n_x} (a_{n_x \ell} + \alpha_{\ell-1}) \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A}^{\ell-1} = 0. \quad (\text{A.12})$$

The full rank property of $\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}^\top \mathbf{C})$ leads to

$$a_{n_x \ell} = -\alpha_{\ell-1} \quad \forall \ell \in [1, n_x]. \quad (\text{A.13})$$

A.2 Proof of Proposition 3.2

This proof is directly adapted from the one of [Ljung, 1999a, Theorem 4.A.2]. More precisely,

If-part: Consider two values $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta}^*$ for the structure (3.13) giving the same I/O behavior. Then, introducing $\mathbf{y}(t, \boldsymbol{\theta})$ as the output of the autonomous linear part (i.e., $\mathbf{u}(t) = \mathbf{0}$, $t \geq 0$) of the system (3.1) with $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}) = (\mathcal{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathcal{B}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathcal{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathcal{D}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))$, we have

$$\mathbf{y}(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{y}(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}^*) \quad \forall t \geq 0. \quad (\text{A.14})$$

Now, let us introduce the following output stacked vector

$$\mathbf{y}_{n_x}(t, \boldsymbol{\vartheta}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y}(t, \boldsymbol{\vartheta}) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{y}(t + n_x - 1, \boldsymbol{\vartheta}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.15})$$

where $\boldsymbol{\vartheta}$ stands for $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ or $\boldsymbol{\theta}^*$. Then,

$$\mathbf{y}_{n_x}(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{y}_{n_x}(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}^*) \quad \forall t \geq 0. \quad (\text{A.16})$$

Furthermore, $\mathbf{y}_{n_x}(t, \boldsymbol{\vartheta})$ satisfies

$$\mathbf{y}_{n_x}(t, \boldsymbol{\vartheta}) = \Gamma_{n_x}(\mathcal{A}(\boldsymbol{\vartheta}), \mathcal{C}(\boldsymbol{\vartheta})) \mathbf{x}(t, \boldsymbol{\vartheta}). \quad (\text{A.17})$$

Then, by using equality (A.16), we get

$$\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathcal{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathcal{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) \mathbf{x}(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \Gamma_{n_x}(\mathcal{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^*), \mathcal{C}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^*)) \mathbf{x}(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}^*). \quad (\text{A.18})$$

By using the particular structure of the matrices of \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{C} given in Eq. (3.13), a permutation matrix $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x n_y \times n_x n_y}$ can be introduced such that

$$\mathbf{S}\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathcal{A}(\vartheta), \mathcal{C}(\vartheta)) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n_x} \\ * \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.19a})$$

$$\mathbf{S}\Gamma_{n_x}(\mathcal{A}(\theta^*), \mathcal{C}(\theta^*)) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n_x} \\ ** \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.19b})$$

Multiplying Eq. (A.18) by \mathbf{S} and then plugging the above equalities into it, we have

$$\mathbf{x}(t, \theta) = \mathbf{x}(t, \theta^*). \quad (\text{A.20})$$

Now, assuming that the structure (3.13) is controllable, θ and θ^* correspond to minimal realizations and, using [Kailath, 1980, Theorem 6.2.4], a unique invertible matrix \mathbf{T} exists such that

$$\mathbf{x}(t, \theta^*) = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{x}(t, \theta) \quad (\text{A.21})$$

and

$$\mathcal{A}(\theta^*) = \mathbf{T}\mathcal{A}(\theta)\mathbf{T}^{-1}, \quad \mathcal{B}(\theta^*) = \mathbf{T}\mathcal{B}(\theta), \quad (\text{A.22a})$$

$$\mathcal{C}(\theta^*) = \mathcal{C}(\theta)\mathbf{T}^{-1}, \quad \mathcal{D}(\theta^*) = \mathcal{D}(\theta). \quad (\text{A.22b})$$

Gathering Eq. (A.20) and (A.21) leads to $\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{I}_{n_x}$ and (see Eq. (A.22))

$$\mathcal{A}(\theta^*) = \mathcal{A}(\theta), \quad \mathcal{B}(\theta^*) = \mathcal{B}(\theta), \quad (\text{A.23a})$$

$$\mathcal{C}(\theta^*) = \mathcal{C}(\theta), \quad \mathcal{D}(\theta^*) = \mathcal{D}(\theta). \quad (\text{A.23b})$$

Thus, by extension, $\theta = \theta^*$.

Only if part: Let us assume that $(\mathbf{A}(\theta^*), \mathbf{B}(\theta^*))$ is not controllable. Then, the behavior of the system can be described with the help of a model with a lower McMillan degree and with an additional and arbitrary non-controllable part. This can be achieved via many different parameter vector θ which leads to a contradiction with the identifiability definition.

A.3 Proof of Proposition 3.3

Claim (ii) is immediate by Appendix A.1. Claim (i) is proved in two steps as follows.

First, it is a direct consequence of the definition of \mathcal{E}_κ that for any quadruple $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}) \in \mathcal{F}_\kappa$, there is an element $(\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{B}, \mathbb{C}, \mathbb{D})$ of \mathcal{E}_κ such that

$$(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}) \# (\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{B}, \mathbb{C}, \mathbb{D}). \quad (\text{A.24})$$

The second step consists in proving that any element of \mathcal{F}_κ is equivalent under $\#$ to a unique element of \mathcal{E}_κ . To reach this goal, consider a quadruple $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}) \in \mathcal{F}_\kappa$, and assume that it is equivalent to two elements $(\bar{\mathbf{A}}, \bar{\mathbf{B}}, \bar{\mathbf{C}}, \bar{\mathbf{D}})$ and $(\bar{\bar{\mathbf{A}}}, \bar{\bar{\mathbf{B}}}, \bar{\bar{\mathbf{C}}}, \bar{\bar{\mathbf{D}}})$ of \mathcal{E}_κ , that is,

$$(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}) \# (\bar{\mathbf{A}}, \bar{\mathbf{B}}, \bar{\mathbf{C}}, \bar{\mathbf{D}}) \quad (\text{A.25a})$$

$$(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}) \# (\bar{\bar{\mathbf{A}}}, \bar{\bar{\mathbf{B}}}, \bar{\bar{\mathbf{C}}}, \bar{\bar{\mathbf{D}}}). \quad (\text{A.25b})$$

Recall from Theorem 3.1 that $\#$ is an equivalence relation. Then, by exploiting the symmetry and transitivity properties of $\#$, one can write

$$(\bar{\mathbf{A}}, \bar{\mathbf{B}}, \bar{\mathbf{C}}, \bar{\mathbf{D}}) \# (\bar{\bar{\mathbf{A}}}, \bar{\bar{\mathbf{B}}}, \bar{\bar{\mathbf{C}}}, \bar{\bar{\mathbf{D}}}). \quad (\text{A.26})$$

This means that a non-singular matrix $\mathbf{\Lambda} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$ exists such that

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{\Lambda} \bar{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{\Lambda}^{-1}, \quad \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{\Lambda} \bar{\mathbf{B}}, \quad (\text{A.27a})$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \bar{\mathbf{C}} \mathbf{\Lambda}^{-1}, \quad \mathbf{D} = \bar{\mathbf{D}}. \quad (\text{A.27b})$$

It follows that

$$\mathbf{\Gamma}_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{C}) = \mathbf{\Gamma}_{n_x}(\bar{\mathbf{A}}, \bar{\mathbf{C}}) \mathbf{\Lambda}^{-1}, \quad (\text{A.28})$$

which, by straightforward algebraic calculations, implies that

$$\mathbf{\Gamma}_{n_x}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{K}\mathbf{C}) = \mathbf{\Gamma}_{n_x}(\bar{\mathbf{A}}, \mathbf{K}\bar{\mathbf{C}}) \mathbf{\Lambda}^{-1}. \quad (\text{A.29})$$

Claim (ii) ensures that $(\bar{\mathbf{A}}, \mathbf{K}\bar{\mathbf{C}})$ and $(\bar{\bar{\mathbf{A}}}, \mathbf{K}\bar{\bar{\mathbf{C}}})$ have the structure displayed in Eq. (3.13). From this specific structure, a permutation matrix $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x n_y \times n_x n_y}$ can be found such that

$$\mathbf{S} \mathbf{\Gamma}_{n_x}(\bar{\mathbf{A}}, \mathbf{K}\bar{\mathbf{C}}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n_x} \\ * \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{S} \mathbf{\Gamma}_{n_x}(\bar{\bar{\mathbf{A}}}, \mathbf{K}\bar{\bar{\mathbf{C}}}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{n_x} \\ ** \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.30})$$

This, together with Eq. (A.29), implies that $\mathbf{\Lambda} = \mathbf{I}_{n_x}$. Now, reference to the equalities (A.27) leads to

$$(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}) = (\bar{\mathbf{A}}, \bar{\mathbf{B}}, \bar{\mathbf{C}}, \bar{\mathbf{D}}) \quad (\text{A.31})$$

hence concluding the proof.

A.4 Dynamic model of the flexible two-links arm

The expressions of the matrices $\mathcal{M}(\mathbf{q})$ and $\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}, \mathbf{T})$ appearing in the dynamic model (5.30) are obtained with the DynaFlex toolbox and satisfy

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & M_{12} & M_{13} & M_{14} \\ M_{21} & M_{22} & M_{23} & M_{24} \\ M_{31} & M_{32} & M_{33} & M_{34} \\ M_{41} & M_{42} & M_{43} & M_{44} \end{bmatrix} \ddot{\mathbf{q}} = \begin{bmatrix} F_1 \\ F_2 \\ F_3 \\ F_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.32})$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{11} = & m_2 \ell_2^3 v_{11} (\sin(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2) - \cos(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2)) \\
 & + \frac{2}{3} m_2 \ell_2^3 v_{21} (\sin(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2) - \cos(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2)) \\
 & + \frac{1}{12} m_2 d_2^2 + \frac{1}{12} m_1 d_1^2 + \frac{1}{3} m_1 \ell_1^2 + \frac{4}{3} m_2 \ell_2^2 \\
 & + m_2 \ell_2^2 (\sin(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2) + \cos(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2)) \quad (\text{A.33a})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{12} = & 6m_2 \ell_2^3 v_{11} (\sin(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2) - \cos(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2)) \\
 & - 4m_2 \ell_2^3 v_{21} (\cos(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2) - \sin(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2)) \\
 & + 6m_2 \ell_2^2 (\cos(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2) + \sin(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2)) + d_2^2 + 4m_2 \ell_2^2 \quad (\text{A.33b})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{13} = & \frac{5}{3} m_2 \ell_2^3 + \frac{1}{4} m_1 \ell_1^3 + \frac{1}{6} m_2 \ell_2 d_2^2 + \frac{1}{12} m_1 \ell_1 d_1^2 \\
 & + \frac{3}{2} m_2 \ell_2^3 (\sin(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2) + \cos(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2)) \quad (\text{A.33c})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{14} = & \frac{1}{4} m_2 \ell_2^3 + \frac{1}{12} m_2 \ell_2 d_2^2 \\
 & + \frac{1}{3} m_2 \ell_2^3 (\cos(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2) + \sin(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2)) \quad (\text{A.33d})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$M_{21} = M_{12} \quad (\text{A.34a})$$

$$M_{22} = \frac{1}{12} m_2 (4\ell_2^2 + d_2^2) \quad (\text{A.34b})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{23} = & \frac{1}{6} d_2^2 + \frac{2}{3} m_2 \ell_2^3 \\
 & + \frac{1}{2} m_2 \ell_2^3 (\cos(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2) + \sin(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2)) \quad (\text{A.34c})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$M_{24} = \frac{1}{4} m_2 \ell_2^3 + \frac{1}{12} m_2 \ell_2 d_2^2 \quad (\text{A.34d})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{31} = & -\frac{4}{3} m_2 \ell_2^4 v_{11} (\cos(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2) - \sin(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2)) \\
 & - m_2 \ell_2^4 v_{21} (\cos(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2) - \sin(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2)) + \frac{5}{3} m_2 \ell_2^3 \\
 & + \frac{3}{2} m_2 \ell_2^3 (\sin(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2) + \cos(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2)) \\
 & + \frac{1}{6} m_2 \ell_2 d_2^2 + \frac{1}{12} m_1 \ell_1 d_1^2 + \frac{1}{4} m_1 \ell_1^3 \quad (\text{A.35a})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{32} = & \frac{1}{6}m_2\ell_2 \left(-2\ell_2^3v_{11} (\cos(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2) - \sin(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2)) \right. \\
& + 2\ell_2^3v_{21} (\sin(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2) - \cos(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2)) + d_2^2 \\
& \left. + 4\ell_2^2 + 3\ell_2^2 (\cos(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2) + \sin(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2)) \right) \quad (\text{A.35b})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{33} = & \frac{1}{9}m_1\ell_1^2d_1^2 + \frac{7}{3}m_2\ell_2^4 + \frac{1}{5}m_1\ell_1^4 + \frac{1}{3}m_2\ell_2^2d_2^2 \\
& + 2m_2\ell_2^4 (\cos(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2) + \sin(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2)) \quad (\text{A.35c})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{34} = & \frac{1}{6}m_2\ell_2^2 (d_2^2 + 3\ell_2^2 \\
& + 2 (\ell_2^2 \cos(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2) + \sin(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2))) \quad (\text{A.35d})
\end{aligned}$$

$$M_{41} = M_{14} \quad (\text{A.36a})$$

$$M_{42} = M_{24} \quad (\text{A.36b})$$

$$M_{43} = M_{34} \quad (\text{A.36c})$$

$$M_{44} = \frac{1}{45}m_2\ell_2^2 (9\ell_2^2 + 5d_2^2) \quad (\text{A.36d})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
F_1 = & -f_{v_1}\dot{\theta}_1 + T_1 \\
& - m_2\ell_2^3\dot{v}_{11}\dot{\theta}_1 (\sin(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2) + \cos(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2)) \\
& + \frac{2}{3}m_2\ell_2^3\dot{v}_{21}\dot{\theta}_1 (\cos(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2) - \sin(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2)) \\
& - 2m_2\ell_2^3\dot{v}_{11}\dot{\theta}_2 (\sin(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2) - \cos(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2)) \\
& + \frac{2}{3}m_2\ell_2^3\dot{v}_{21}\dot{\theta}_2 (\cos(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2) - \sin(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2)) \\
& + \frac{1}{2}\dot{\theta}_2^2m_2\ell_2^3v_{11} (\cos(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2) + \sin(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2)) \\
& + \frac{1}{2}\dot{\theta}_2^2m_2\ell_2^2 (\cos(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2) - \sin(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2)) \\
& + \frac{1}{3}\dot{\theta}_2^2m_2\ell_2^3v_{21} (\cos(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2) + \sin(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2)) \\
& + \dot{\theta}_1\dot{\theta}_2m_2\ell_2^3v_{11} (\sin(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2) \cos(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2)) \\
& + \dot{\theta}_1\dot{\theta}_2m_2\ell_2^2 (\cos(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2) - \sin(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2)) \\
& + \frac{2}{3}\dot{\theta}_1\dot{\theta}_2m_2\ell_2^3v_{21} (\sin(q_1) \sin(q_1 + q_2) + \cos(q_1) \cos(q_1 + q_2)) \quad (\text{A.37a})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
F_2 = & -f_{v_2}\dot{\theta}_2 + T_2 \\
& + m_2\ell_2^3\dot{v}_{11}\dot{\theta}_1 (\sin(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2) - \cos(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2)) \\
& - \frac{1}{2}\dot{\theta}_1^2 m_2\ell_2^3 v_{11} (\cos(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2) + \sin(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2)) \\
& - \frac{1}{2}\dot{\theta}_1^2 m_2\ell_2^2 (\cos(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2) + \sin(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2)) \\
& - \frac{1}{3}\dot{\theta}_1^2 v_{21} m_2\ell_2^3 (\cos(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2) + \sin(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2)) \quad (\text{A.37b})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
F_3 = & -\frac{1}{2}\dot{\theta}_2^2 m_2\ell_2^3 (\sin(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2) - \cos(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2)) \\
& + \frac{1}{2}\dot{\theta}_1^2 m_2\ell_2^3 (\sin(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2) - \cos(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2)) \\
& - 2m_2\ell_2^4\dot{v}_{11}\dot{\theta}_2 (\sin(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2) - \cos(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2)) \\
& + \frac{2}{3}\dot{\theta}_1\dot{\theta}_2 m_2\ell_2^4 v_{21} (\cos(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2) + \sin(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2)) \\
& + \frac{2}{3}\dot{\theta}_1\dot{\theta}_2 v_{11} m_2\ell_2^4 (\sin(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2) + \cos(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2)) \\
& - \dot{\theta}_1\dot{\theta}_2 m_2\ell_2^3 (\sin(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2) - \cos(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2)) \\
& - \frac{2}{3}m_2\ell_2^4\dot{v}_{21}\dot{\theta}_2 (\sin(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2) - \cos(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2)) \\
& - \frac{1}{3}\dot{\theta}_1^2 m_2\ell_2^4 v_{21} (\cos(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2) + \sin(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2)) \\
& - \frac{2}{3}m_2\ell_2^4\dot{v}_{21}\dot{\theta}_1 (\sin(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2) - \cos(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2)) \\
& - \frac{2}{3}\dot{\theta}_1^2 v_{11} m_2\ell_2^4 (\sin(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2) + \cos(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2)) \\
& + \frac{1}{3}\dot{\theta}_2^2 v_{11} m_2\ell_2^4 (\cos(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2) + \sin(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2)) \\
& - \frac{1}{15}\dot{\theta}_1^2 v_{11} m_1\ell_1^4 - \frac{1}{3}\varepsilon_1 d_1^4 v_{11}\ell_1 \quad (\text{A.37c})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
F_4 = & \frac{10}{15}m_2\ell_2^4\dot{v}_{11}\dot{\theta}_1 (\sin(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2) - \cos(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2)) \\
& - \frac{1}{3}\dot{\theta}_1^2 m_2\ell_2^4 v_{11} (\cos(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2) + \sin(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2)) \\
& - \frac{1}{3}\dot{\theta}_1^2 m_2\ell_2^3 (\cos(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2) - \sin(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2)) \\
& - \frac{1}{3}\dot{\theta}_1^2 v_{21} m_2\ell_2^4 (\cos(q_1)\cos(q_1+q_2) + \sin(q_1)\sin(q_1+q_2)) \\
& - \frac{1}{15}\dot{\theta}_1^2 v_{21} m_2\ell_2^4 - \frac{1}{15}\dot{\theta}_2^2 v_{21} m_2\ell_2^4 - \frac{1}{3}\dot{\theta}_1\dot{\theta}_2 v_{21} m_2\ell_2^4 - \frac{1}{3}\ell_2 d_2^4 v_{21} \quad (\text{A.37d})
\end{aligned}$$

where the involved variables are defined in Section 5.5.

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